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RISK ASSESSMENT OF BUILDINGS DUE TO
EARTHQUAKE – INDUCED GROUND SHAKING,
LIQUEFACTION AND TSUNAMI

DOCTORAL THESIS

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“Acceptance of this Doctoral Thesis by the Department of Civil Engineering of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki does not imply acceptance of the opinions of the author”
(Law 5343/1932, article 202, par. 2)

*To my dear father
Vasileios Karafagkas*

*Στον αγαπημένο μου πατέρα
Βασίλειο Καραφαγκά*

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SUMMARY

Earthquake-induced hazards, such as ground shaking, liquefaction and tsunami, are high-impact geophysical events that are often catastrophic and attract global attention, as they may cause tremendous losses to structures and pose significant threat to people. Moving toward a safer and more resilient society requires efficient risk assessment tools targeting integrated risk mitigation strategies on a regional or site-specific scale. Stemming from the general lack of methodological frameworks to assess building vulnerability and risk to the above hazards, one of the most significant challenges of the present research is the proposition and quantification of analytical methodologies to estimate the physical vulnerability and subsequently the risk of building typologies subjected to tsunami forces, liquefaction-induced differential permanent displacements as well as combined ground shaking and liquefaction considering soil-structure interaction (SSI). Vulnerability is defined through probabilistic fragility and vulnerability curves or surfaces (when it is deemed appropriate) which allow for direct implementation within a probabilistic risk assessment framework. To gain confidence on the proposed fragility functions developed in this thesis, representative fragility results are compared with corresponding literature ones and recorded building damages from real past events (tsunamis and earthquakes which caused extensive liquefaction and lateral spreading).

More specifically, an analytical methodology is proposed to derive tsunami fragility and vulnerability curves for buildings subjected to tsunami forces. Typical buildings representative of typologies found in ordinary port areas in South Europe like the port of Thessaloniki, namely low-code RC buildings and steel light frame warehouses are considered. Tsunami nonlinear static time-history analyses are performed and the structure's response in terms of material strain is estimated. Except for flexural failure, failure due to shear is also considered and the structure's demand in terms of shear forces is also estimated. Tsunami fragility and vulnerability curves are finally derived in terms of inundation depth. It is shown that the height of the buildings, its structural typology (MRF or Dual) as well as the existence of masonry infill walls influence the building's fragility due to tsunami.

Moreover, an analytical assessment methodology for the vulnerability and risk assessment of buildings with shallow flexible foundation system subjected to liquefaction-induced differential permanent ground displacements (settlements and lateral movements) is proposed, where possible initial damage to the building's structural members due to ground shaking is ignored. It is noted that the differential ground displacements become the major

cause of damage to buildings, as the absolute displacements on their own are often insufficient to describe the main damage patterns of the structures. Typical low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses are considered. Nonlinear static time-history analysis is carried out considering different gradually increasing differential displacement patterns applied directly at the building supports (footings). Different damage mechanisms are also examined including a flexural damage of the building members and a shear failure of the columns. Fragility and vulnerability curves are finally derived as a function of liquefaction-induced differential displacement. The building height is proved to be a great influential feature on the vulnerability of the building exposed to liquefaction-induced differential displacements.

A further challenge of the present thesis is to investigate the complex issue of combined damages due to ground shaking and soil liquefaction to individual buildings considering SSI. An analytical methodology is proposed for the vulnerability and risk assessment of buildings on liquefiable soils subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, based on a fully coupled numerical approach considering SSI. The direct one-step approach where the soil and the structure are modelled and analysed as a single system is implemented. Typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights with flexible foundation system and three typical soil profiles susceptible to liquefaction at level ground conditions and slope conditions are considered. Two-dimensional incremental dynamic analysis (IDA) of the nonlinear SSI systems is conducted for the estimation of the fragility function parameters. A second set of IDA is also performed considering slope with a 5% grade to better examine the contribution of liquefaction-induced lateral spreading. Coupled fragility and vulnerability curves and surfaces are finally assessed. The total height of the building is found to considerably influence its vulnerability to the earthquake-induced ground shaking and liquefaction. A major contribution of the present research is also the proposition of predictive relationships between the maximum differential permanent ground displacements and the maximum permanent ground displacements (PGD) vector at surface bellow buildings with shallow flexible foundation on soils at level ground or slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction.

Finally, a scenario seismic risk assessment in terms of economic losses due to the combined effect of ground shaking and liquefaction is applied to the buildings of Thessaloniki port, one of the largest Greek seaports, in an effort to estimate the risk and increase its resilience. Through this application the applicability of the proposed methodological frameworks and the effectiveness of the respective fragility curves and surfaces is verified. The proposed fragility functions can be used within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the vulnerability and risk of these type of buildings exposed to earthquake-induced tsunami or liquefaction differential displacements or ground shaking and liquefaction hazard, along European-Mediterranean and other regions of similar facilities worldwide. Stakeholders can use the developed fragility functions to evaluate the risk to their structures and take appropriate decisions to reduce their risk.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Statement of the problem

The occurrence of earthquake-induced hazards (e.g. ground shaking, liquefaction and tsunami) may be dramatic for structures and poses significant threat to people. These natural hazards are rapid-onset, high-impact geophysical events that are often catastrophic and attract global attention (e.g. the 1999 Kocaeli earthquake in Turkey, the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami, the 2011 Christchurch earthquake in New Zealand, the 2011 Great East Japan earthquake and tsunami, etc.), as they may cause tremendous direct and indirect losses in terms of fatalities and infrastructure. Critical infrastructure is the backbone of modern society and provides many essential goods and services. Among critical infrastructure, ports play a crucial role in world economy since around 90% of world trade is carried by the international shipping industry, while world seaborne trade was estimated at 10.7 billion tons in 2017 ([UNCTAD 2018](#)). Therefore, resilience of ports are interrelated with the international, national and regional development. However, ports are usually located in areas prone to geo- hazards such as ground shaking and induced phenomena like tsunamis and liquefaction.

The recent strong seismic events have demonstrated the high vulnerability of port buildings. It is observed that most damage to port buildings is often associated with significant deformation of soft or liquefiable soil deposits. In case of tsunami hazard, in addition to direct damages due to waves, non-anchored equipment or pieces of cargo may be carried away by the tsunami waves, becoming debris that may collide with other structures and cause significant damage. Typical examples are the 2011 (M_w9.0) Great East Japan earthquake and tsunami in Japan, which caused severe damage to port infrastructure resulting primarily in economic losses due to business (service) interruption and repair costs ([Fraser et al. 2013](#)) and the 1999 (M_w7.6) Kocaeli earthquake in Turkey, that caused heavy damage and significant economic loss to a large number of port structures, indicating that port facilities are particularly susceptible to liquefaction-induced ground deformations ([Erdik 2000](#)).

Tsunamis have got increased interest since the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami, one of the greatest disasters of recent decades, with extremely severe impact to buildings and a death toll of at least 230.000. It is expected that future tsunamis may have even higher impact due to the increasing number of people, buildings and infrastructures that are being exposed to natural hazards as the pressures for urban development extend into areas of higher tsunami risk (Jelínek and Krausmann 2008). However, only a limited number of tools to estimate the potential impacts of tsunami are available until now.

In addition, earthquake-induced liquefaction has cost society hundreds of millions of U.S. dollars, as it was early observed by Seed and Idriss 1982. Detailed observations and records of the damage that may be caused by ground failure (i.e. liquefaction) have early been made after the two major damaging earthquakes in 1964, the Alaska earthquake and Niigata earthquake in Japan, which first highlighted the devastating effects of ground failure. It should also be noted that the tsunami, triggered by movement of the sea floor associated with the fault rupture, totally destroyed the port of Niigata. Earthquake-induced liquefaction constitutes "one of the most important, interesting, complex and controversial topics in geotechnical engineering", as noted by Kramer (1996) and aspects such as how liquefaction impacts the built environment in terms of damage and losses are not well represented by the present modelling capabilities. Also, full nonlinear dynamic analyses of the soil were not a usual practice, restricted by the computation cost of such operations. Nonetheless, for realistic estimations of damage due to future earthquakes, liquefaction potential is a major challenge in earthquake engineering and risk assessment.

Moving toward a safer and more resilient society requires reliable assessment of the vulnerability and associated risks for port buildings, targeting integrated risk mitigation strategies. Vulnerability is commonly expressed through fragility curves, which express the probable damage to an element at risk given a level of hazard (characterised as within the associated hazard assessment). Seismic risk assessment of an exposed element due to a hazardous event requires consideration of the element's vulnerability in order to be able to translate the expected building damage into the expected losses (e.g. in terms of fatalities or economic losses) during an earthquake scenario. This concept allows the assessed level of hazard to be translated to an estimated level of risk. By predicting the losses due to a natural hazard, many entities including emergency planners, lifeline operators and stakeholders, can gain invaluable information as to where the worst losses are expected and where recovery efforts should be concentrated. In this context, an estimation of the economic losses (e.g. in terms of repair cost to replacement cost ratio) can also be useful where national or international financial assistance is likely to be required.

An important aspect for disaster risk reduction is the better understanding of the hazards causing a significant threat as well as the vulnerabilities of the society and built environment. Although the focus in research until recently was on the hazard assessment, the last two decades vulnerability assessment has also emerged as an important research field. However, although there are several studies providing fragility curves due to ground shaking, vulnerability assessment methodologies for buildings and infrastructures due to other earthquake-induced hazards (i.e. tsunami and liquefaction) have been developed only recently and they are principally based on empirical data and/or expert judgment, as field reconnaissance of the damage caused by earthquake-induced hazards has been standard practice for many years. Therefore, there are limitations in their general application as they are highly specific to a particular seismotectonic, geomorphological and built environment.

1.2 Objectives and scope of the research

This thesis aims to propose a comprehensive vulnerability assessment methodology resulting to the derivation of analytical tsunami fragility and vulnerability curves for some typical buildings representative of typologies found in ordinary port areas in South Europe like the port of Thessaloniki, i.e. low-code reinforced concrete (RC) buildings and steel light frame warehouses. Another main objective of this thesis is also the proposal and quantification of an analytical methodology to assess the seismic vulnerability and finally the risk of these typical port buildings i.e. (low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses) due to the earthquake-induced liquefaction of the underlying soil, using reliable methods and techniques. Fragility and vulnerability curves for typical low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses subjected to liquefaction-induced differential permanent displacements are proposed, where possible initial damage to the building's structural members (e.g. in terms of stiffness and strength degradation) due to ground shaking is ignored. To enhance the reliability and robustness of the proposed fragility curves, they are compared with the available ones from the literature as well as with field observations.

In addition, although progress has been made on the influence of ground shaking or soil liquefaction on the structural response of buildings, studies coupling both phenomena are very limited. Soil-Structure Interaction (SSI) may also play a significant role on the seismic performance of coastal buildings, modifying their dynamic characteristics as well as the seismic response at foundation level. However, numerical modelling techniques for estimating the influence of both ground shaking and soil liquefaction considering SSI effects on the structural response of buildings, has not received much attention and hence requires further investigation. To bridge this gap, an analytical methodology for

the vulnerability and risk assessment of typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights (low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise) with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at level ground or slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction based on a fully coupled numerical approach considering SSI is also proposed. Vulnerability is expressed in terms of coupled lognormally distributed fragility curves, coupled vulnerability curves to assess the expected direct losses in normalised cost terms as well as in terms of coupled fragility surfaces. The liquefiable soil response and subsequently the SSI models are validated through observed trends that are also identified in the literature, while the proposed fragility curves and surfaces are compared with analytical ones and field data from the literature to verify their reliability.

Finally, a scenario-based risk assessment in terms of economic losses (repair cost to replacement cost) due to the combined effect of the two natural hazards (ground shaking and liquefaction) is applied to the buildings of Thessaloniki port, one of the largest Greek seaports. This assessment is conducted in an effort to identify as accurately as possible the site-specific response of Thessaloniki port area and subsequently estimate the risk and increase its resilience as well as validate the applicability and effectiveness of the proposed methodological frameworks and the respective fragility functions.

1.3 Outline of the Thesis

This thesis is organised into eight chapters with the following contents:

In the present chapter (**Chapter 1**) the statement of the problem as well as the main goals and scope of this thesis are presented.

In **Chapter 2** an overview on the definition, the assessment and the fundamental concepts of natural hazards triggered by earthquakes (i.e. ground shaking, liquefaction and tsunami) is presented. In addition, field data are used from past earthquake-induced events (i.e. tsunami, ground shaking and liquefaction) to investigate the observed building performance and provide the principal lessons learned including the main causes of damage as well as the potential failure mechanisms for buildings.

Chapter 3 provides a review of the principles of seismic risk assessment. This includes a brief discussion of the components of seismic risk assessment, a short review of the past and current research on seismic risk assessment as well as an outline of the parameters and available methods to derive fragility functions, which are used in the seismic risk assessment of buildings at urban and regional scale. The aim of this chapter is to contribute to the knowledge and better understanding of the main factors governing the current practice in seismic vulnerability and risk assessment.

In **Chapter 4** fragility and vulnerability curves for some typical buildings representative of typologies found in ordinary port areas in South Europe like the port of Thessaloniki, i.e. low-code reinforced concrete (RC) buildings and steel light frame warehouses subjected to tsunami hazard are developed. The reference port buildings that have been selected in the context of this thesis to assess their vulnerability due to tsunami hazard are presented in full detail. The material properties, structural detailing, as well as modelling issues and associated assumptions are also addressed. A numerical investigation is performed for the various structure typologies considering different combinations of tsunami loads based on FEMA P646 (2008) recommendations for gradually increasing tsunami inundation depths. Lognormally distributed tsunami fragility curves, which describe the probability of exceeding a certain level of structural damage of the building, are proposed, as a function of the tsunami inundation depth. To minimize the uncertainties related to the definition of damage limit states, tsunami nonlinear static analyses are performed, and appropriate tsunami capacity curves are derived for the considered structures. Structural limit states are defined on tsunami capacity curves in terms of threshold values of material strain. For the complete damage state, shear failure is also considered, since the collapse of structures may be caused by the occurrence of either a flexural or shear failure in structural components. Once the fragility curves for the considered building typologies are derived, a vulnerability curve is developed for each building typology, which include also the possibility of shear failure. The vulnerability curve provides a unique damage or vulnerability index for each level of tsunami inundation depth, which is a convenient measure to quantify the structural losses (in normalised cost terms) and finally to assess the risk at building or community level when properly aggregated. The derived fragility curves are then compared with available empirical fragility curves and results from other numerical studies from the literature to verify the validity of the proposed methodology.

Chapter 5 focuses on the proposal and quantification of an analytical methodology to assess the seismic vulnerability and finally the risk of typical low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses with shallow flexible foundations subjected to liquefaction-induced differential permanent displacements, ignoring possible initial damages (e.g. in terms of stiffness and strength degradation) due to ground shaking. Vulnerability is expressed in terms of lognormally distributed fragility curves and vulnerability curves (to assess the expected direct losses in normalised cost terms), as a function of the liquefaction induced differential displacements. Nonlinear static analyses are carried out for each considered structural typology assuming different gradually increasing differential displacement patterns applied as quasi-static loads directly at its supports (footings). Different damage mechanisms are examined including a flexural

damage of the building members and a shear failure of the columns. Afterwards, to enhance the reliability and robustness of the proposed fragility curves, they are compared with corresponding literature curves as well as field observations from past events which caused catastrophic ground failures, including liquefaction, lateral spreads and differential settlements.

The focus of **Chapter 6** is the proposition of an analytical methodology for the vulnerability and risk assessment of typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights (low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise) with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at level ground or slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction based on a fully coupled numerical approach taking into account the soil-structure interaction. Vulnerability is expressed in terms of lognormally distributed fragility curves and vulnerability curves (to assess the expected direct losses in normalised cost terms), as a function of rock outcropping peak ground acceleration (PGA_{rock}) or peak ground velocity (PGV_{rock}). In addition, vulnerability is also expressed in terms of coupled fragility surfaces as functions of both peak ground acceleration at free field surface (PGA_{ff}) and permanent ground displacement (PGD) at surface below the structure as well as functions of both peak ground velocity (PGV) and maximum PGD vector at surface below the structure. Moreover, predictive relationships are established through regression analysis between the maximum differential permanent ground displacements (settlement or vector) and the maximum PGD vector at surface for buildings with shallow flexible foundations due to ground shaking and soil liquefaction. In this chapter the important issue of the interaction of ground shaking and ground failure (i.e. soil liquefaction) for individual buildings is investigated. The direct one-step approach where the soil and the structure are modelled and analysed as a single system is implemented considering soil nonlinearity introduced by soil liquefaction. Three typical soil profiles susceptible to liquefaction are investigated. Two-dimensional incremental dynamic analysis (IDA) of the nonlinear SSI systems is conducted for the estimation of the fragility function parameters. Furthermore, a second set of incremental dynamic analyses is performed considering slope with a 5% grade to better examine the contribution of liquefaction-induced lateral spreading. Thereafter, to enhance the reliability and robustness of the proposed fragility curves and surfaces for the typical low-code RC frame buildings considering soil liquefaction, they are compared with some representative analytical fragility curves and field data from the literature.

Chapter 7 aims at verifying the applicability and effectiveness of the proposed methodological frameworks and the respective fragility curves and surfaces through their application to a scenario-based risk assessment due to the combined effect of ground shaking and liquefaction of the buildings of Thessaloniki port, one of the largest Greek

seaports. The risk assessment is performed taking into account the potential physical damages and corresponding losses of the critical port buildings for two different seismic hazard scenarios based on parametric nonlinear site-response analyses for representative soil profiles susceptible to liquefaction. The potential damages and losses to port warehouses are assessed separately for the effect of ground shaking and liquefaction and combined at a later stage using appropriate fragility models for ground shaking from the literature and the fragility curves developed in **Chapter 5** for liquefaction, while the potential damages and losses to port RC frame buildings are assessed for the combined effect of ground shaking and liquefaction using the fragility surfaces developed in **Chapter 6**. A structural damage index d_m weighted with respect to the built area is evaluated to quantify the economic losses as the ratio of the cost of repair to the cost of replacement.

Chapter 8 summarizes the main findings and contributions of this thesis providing also recommendations for future research.

1.4 Originality of the Thesis

A comprehensive vulnerability assessment methodology resulting to the derivation of analytical fragility and vulnerability curves for typical port RC buildings and steel light frame warehouses exposed to tsunami hazard is proposed. Such curves allow for an efficient quantitative estimation of vulnerability within a probabilistic risk assessment framework from site specific to local/regional scales. In addition, fragility and vulnerability curves for typical port low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses subjected to liquefaction-induced differential permanent displacements are proposed, ignoring possible initial damages due to ground shaking. Furthermore, an unusually extensive set of numerical computations is performed to estimate the response and subsequently the vulnerability of typical RC frame building typologies for different liquefiable soil profiles at level ground or slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction. The consideration of slope conditions provides insight into the influential role of the liquefaction-induced lateral spreading on the building's response. Moreover, predictive relationships are established between the maximum differential permanent ground displacements (settlement or vector) and the maximum PGD vector at surface for buildings with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at level ground or slope conditions due to ground shaking and soil liquefaction. Finally, a major contribution of the present thesis is the development of fragility curves and surfaces due to the combined effect of ground shaking and liquefaction for typical low-code RC frame buildings at level ground or slope conditions considering soil-structure interaction.

All the proposed fragility functions can be used within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the vulnerability and subsequently the risk of typical low-code RC buildings and typical steel light frame warehouses exposed to earthquake-induced tsunami or liquefaction or ground shaking and liquefaction hazards along European-Mediterranean and other regions of similar facilities worldwide. Stakeholders can make use of the proposed fragility curves and surfaces within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to evaluate efficiently the risk to their own structures and take appropriate measures to reduce their risk and increase their resilience.

Chapter 2

Fundamental concepts of seismic ground shaking, liquefaction and tsunami

2.1 Introduction

A number of naturally occurring events, such as earthquakes, are capable of causing deaths, injuries and property damage. Hazards associated with earthquakes are commonly referred to as seismic hazards ([Kramer 1996](#)). These hazards cause tremendous damage around the world each year. Ground shaking is widely recognised as the primary cause of damage to structures. However, experience gained from recent strong seismic events has demonstrated the high vulnerability of buildings to earthquake-related hazards associated not only to the ground shaking itself but also to the induced phenomena, namely tsunami and liquefaction, resulting to severe physical damages and important economic and societal losses. This chapter describes the fundamental concepts of the earthquake-triggered tsunami, ground shaking and liquefaction hazards. Their definition and principal assessment methods are also provided. Past incidents are analysed to shed light on the vulnerability of buildings to the selected natural hazards and better understand the main causes of damage, the potential failure mechanisms and system weaknesses of buildings, as well as the potential consequences and contributing factors.

2.2 Ground shaking

Ground shaking is the result of seismic waves radiating away from the source and traveling rapidly through the earth's crust due to fault rupture and may last from seconds to minutes. The strength and duration of ground shaking at a particular site depends on the size and location of the earthquake and on the characteristics of the site. Ground shaking can cause tremendous damage especially at sites near the source of a large earthquake. [Kramer \(1996\)](#) supports that ground shaking can be considered to be the most important of all seismic hazards, as the other hazards are caused by ground

shaking and because where ground shaking levels are low, these other seismic hazards may be low or non-existent.

Soil type can also have a significant effect on the intensity of ground shaking at a particular site. Although seismic waves travel through rock over the majority of their trip from the source of an earthquake to the ground surface, the final portion of that trip is often through soil and the characteristics of the soil can considerably influence the nature of shaking at the ground surface. Soil deposits tend to act as "filters" to seismic waves by attenuating ground motion at certain frequencies and amplifying it at others. Since soil conditions often vary dramatically over short distances, levels of ground shaking can vary significantly within a small area. The severity of the local effects depends on the complex combination of the earthquake magnitude, the distance from the epicentre, and the local geological and geomorphological conditions, which may amplify or reduce wave propagation. Specific local geological and geomorphological features can induce high levels of shaking on the ground surface even from low-intensity earthquakes. This effect is called site or local amplification. Thus, the intensity of ground shaking depends on the conditions of the local geology (e.g. solid bedrock is far less subject to intense shaking than loose sediment), the size of the earthquake, as well as the distance from the epicentre (as it drops off the intensity of the shaking decreases). The last one depends on the type of material underlying the area. There are however some exceptions, such as the 1985 earthquake of moment magnitude M_w 8.1 in Mexico city that had its epicentre 350.0 km away to the south on the coast. However, damage to the city was extensive as Mexico city is built on a former lake made up of soft unconsolidated sediment.

Ground motion parameters are essential for describing the important characteristics of strong ground motion in quantitative form. Several parameters have been proposed to characterise the amplitude, frequency content and duration of strong ground motions. The most commonly used measure of the amplitude of a particular ground motion is the Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA). Nevertheless, it provides no information on the frequency content or duration of the ground motion. Thus, it may be supplemented by additional information to characterise a ground motion accurately. Peak Ground Velocity (PGV) is another useful parameter for the characterization of ground motion amplitude. Since the velocity is less sensitive to the higher-frequency components of the ground motion, the PGV is more likely than the PGA to characterise ground motion amplitude accurately at intermediate frequencies, while Peak Ground Displacement is generally associated with the lower-frequency components of an earthquake motion. For structures that are sensitive to loading in intermediate frequency range (e.g. tall or flexible buildings, bridges etc.), the PGV may provide a much more accurate indication of the damage potential. Average Spectral Acceleration ($S_{a,avg}$), Sustained Maximum

Acceleration (SMA) and Velocity (SMV), Effective Design Acceleration (EDA), Predominant period, Root-Mean-Square (RMS) of acceleration, velocity and displacement, Arias Intensity (I_a), Characteristic Intensity (I_c), Cumulative Absolute Velocity (CAV), Housner Intensity (HI), Acceleration (ASI) and Velocity (VSI) Spectrum Intensity are a number of other ground motion parameters. Some describe only one of these characteristics, while others may reflect two or three. However, due to the complexity of earthquake ground motions, identification of a single parameter that accurately describes all important ground motion characteristics is regarded as impossible (Jennings 1985; Joyner and Boore 1988).

Ground motion estimates are usually generated in the form of GIS-based contour maps and location-specific seismic demands stored in relational databases. The spatial distribution of ground motion can be determined using deterministic ground motion analysis or probabilistic ground motion maps (NIBS 2004). Deterministic seismic ground motion demands can be calculated for specified scenario earthquakes. For a given event magnitude, attenuation relationships are used to calculate ground shaking demand for rock sites, which is then amplified by factors based on local soil conditions (NIBS 2004). Ground Motion Prediction Equations (GMPEs), also referred to as attenuation relationships, are used to describe the change in earthquake ground motion with magnitude and distance. GMPEs are based on the geographic location and on the type of fault. Since PGA is the most commonly used ground motion parameter, many PGA attenuation relationships have been developed (e.g. Cambell 1981; Akkar and Bommer 2010; Boore et al. 2014). Recently, attenuation relationships for predicting PGV and spectral acceleration are also proposed (e.g. Akkar and Bommer 2010; Boore et al. 2014).

2.3 Liquefaction

Soil liquefaction is the phenomenon in which loose saturated cohesionless soil deposits (sands and silts) under undrained conditions suddenly lose their strength or stiffness and appear to flow as fluids that contributes to large permanent displacements of the ground. The term "*liquefaction*" originally coined by Mogami and Kubo (1953). Because liquefaction only occurs in saturated soils, it is quite often observed in ports.

The liquefaction phenomenon of soils can be described as the reduction of shear strength due to pore pressure build-up in the soil profile. The shear strength of cohesionless soil, τ , mainly depends on the internal friction angle and the effective stress acting on the soil profile (GDP-9 2007) and can be expressed as:

$$\tau = \sigma' \tan \varphi \quad (2.1)$$

$$\sigma' = \sigma - u \quad (2.2)$$

where τ is the shear strength
 σ' is the effective normal stress
 σ is the total normal stress
 u is the pore pressure
and ϕ is the internal friction angle

When saturated cohesionless soils are subjected to strong ground shaking, primarily triggered by the shear waves upward propagation from bedrock, they tend to contract. As water drainage cannot take place due to the short duration of the earthquake loading, the soil volume contraction cannot occur immediately, and excess pore pressure progressively builds up. The state referred to as "*initial liquefaction*" is when the pore pressure becomes equal to the total stress, reducing the effective stress to zero, where cohesionless soils completely lose their stiffness and shear strength, at least temporarily.

The stress-strain behaviour of liquefying sands strongly depends on their relative density. At the onset of initial liquefaction, loose deposits of sands undergo continued deformation at constant low residual stress or with no residual resistance due to the build-up and maintenance of high pore-water pressures, which reduce the effective confining pressure to a very low value. This corresponds to the "*flow liquefaction*" condition. On the other hand, dense sands require greater intensity cyclic stresses or more repetitions of cyclic stresses to develop the "*initial liquefaction*" state. However, as the cyclic stress applications continue, the amount of deformation required to produce a stable condition may increase, but it never becomes larger than a certain limit, either due to the remaining resistance of the soil to deformation or due to the soil dilation, the pore-pressure decrease and the soil stabilization under applied loads. This corresponds to the "*initial liquefaction with limited strain potential*" or else "*cyclic mobility*" condition. In the field, flow liquefaction occurs less frequently compared to cyclic mobility which can occur under a broader range of soil and site conditions (Kramer 1996).

2.3.1 Failure types

Liquefaction is considered one of the most important, interesting and controversial topics in geotechnical earthquake engineering. As it is a complicated phenomenon, it actually encompasses several related phenomena, capable to cause large deformations of the ground. Such deformation of the ground is called ground failure and may be manifested in several types according to NRC (1985), namely flow failures, lateral spreading, ground oscillation, loss of bearing capacity, sand boils, buoyant rise of buried structures, failure of retaining walls and ground settlement.

Flow liquefaction produces the most devastating liquefaction-related ground failures, namely flow failures, which involve very large movements of a soil mass. They usually develop in loose saturated sands or silts on slopes greater than three degrees. Flow failure occurs when the shear strength of the soil drops below the level required to maintain stability under static conditions (static shear stress). Such failure can produce very large deformations. Flow failures are characterised by their sudden nature, the speed with which they develop and the large distance over which the liquefied material moves (Kramer 1996).

Lateral spreading is the most common type of ground failure triggered by liquefaction (Varnes 1978) resulting from the lateral displacement of a gently sloping ground (most commonly between 0.3 and 3 degrees). The soil undergoes lateral incrementing displacements depending on the strength degree of the stress pulses and the number of the pulses that exceed the strength capacity of the soil. Horizontal displacements on lateral spreads commonly range up to several meters and are able to extend up to several tens of meters where slopes are particularly favourable and ground shaking durations are long. Lateral spreads commonly disrupt foundations of buildings located on or across the failure.

Ground oscillation occurs when the ground is too flat to allow lateral displacement where liquefaction of a soil deposit at depth leads to back and forth movements of intact blocks of surface soil. The jostling of soil block causes an oscillation often seen as ground waves. Ground oscillation is capable to inflict serious damage if it occurs in a built-up area.

Loss of bearing capacity, causing foundations failures, occurs when the soil supporting a structure liquefies and loses strength, leading to large deformations and/or tilting of structures. Loss of soil bearing capacity may also occur when liquefaction that has been developed in a sand layer a few meters below a footing then propagates upward through overlying sand layers and subsequently weakens the soil supporting the structure.

Sand boils are formed due to the presence of high ground water pressures generated at shallow depth by the compaction of granular soils during seismic shaking. They are not strictly a form of ground failure because alone they do not cause ground deformation, but they constitute diagnostic evidence of elevated pore water pressure at depth and an indication that liquefaction has occurred. They usually result in subsidence and relatively minor damage.

Buoyant rise of buried structures, such as tanks or pipelines, may occur during an earthquake when the surrounding soil liquefies. Damage caused by buoyant rise of structures is rarely destructive but can have important consequences to lifelines and

community services. In addition, failure of retaining walls may occur due to increased lateral loads from liquefied backfill soil or loss of support from liquefied foundation soils.

Finally, ground settlement is commonly associated with and enhanced by liquefaction. The pore pressure build-up, and then its gradual expansion after the end of the earthquake causes densification of the soil, resulting in the total volume decrease, which eventually manifests as a settlement of the soil surface.

2.3.2 Liquefaction susceptibility factors

The evaluation of liquefaction susceptibility of a soil is the first step to assess the liquefaction hazard. Historical, geological, compositional and soil state criteria are basically used to determine the susceptibility of a soil to liquefaction.

Liquefaction is often observed at sites that had been liquefied in past earthquakes. Thus, a first indicator of liquefaction susceptibility in future earthquakes is the observed field evidence. The repeatability of liquefaction occurrence can be used as a preliminary tool for assessing liquefaction hazard ([Papathanassiou et al. 2005a](#)). [Youd \(1991\)](#) discussed past instances where historical evidence of liquefaction has been used to map liquefaction susceptibility. In addition, [Ambraseys \(1988\)](#) estimated a limiting epicentral and fault distance beyond which liquefaction would not be triggered by different earthquake magnitudes, using a worldwide set of liquefaction data. More recently, [Papathanassiou et al. \(2005a\)](#) published similar research for Greece. In general, predictive relationships of maximum expected fault distance to earthquake magnitude are helpful for the estimation of regional liquefaction hazard.

The geologic conditions are also a good indicator of liquefaction susceptibility. The age of the soil deposit, the environment in which it was deposited, and its hydrological environment contribute to its liquefaction susceptibility ([Youd and Hoose 1977](#)). [Youd and Perkins \(1978\)](#) provided a qualitative estimate of liquefaction susceptibility of various sediment types noting that liquefaction resistance increases with time since deposition and older soil deposits are generally less susceptible to liquefaction than newer deposits. Thus, soils deposited in the Holocene period are more susceptible than those of Pleistocene age. Moreover, geologic processes set soils into uniform grain size distributions and deposit them in loose state with high liquefaction susceptibility. Thus, fluvial, colluvial and aeolian deposits when saturated are susceptible to liquefaction. It is noted that liquefaction occurs only in saturated soils and the depth of groundwater table affects susceptibility to liquefaction. According to [Idriss and Boulanger \(2008\)](#), surface evidence of liquefaction has most commonly been associated with liquefaction occurring at depths of less than about 15.0 m, probably due to the fact that the shallower deposits

are typically the youngest and therefore most susceptible to liquefaction. Man-made loose fills with no or little compaction are also susceptible to liquefaction.

Since liquefaction is associated with the development of excess pore pressure, the compositional characteristics that imply volume-change behaviour, including particle size, shape and gradation, increase liquefaction susceptibility (Kramer 1996). Uniformly graded soils and soils with rounded particle shapes are most susceptible to liquefaction. Figure 2.1 illustrates the Japanese Criteria for liquefaction susceptibility (Iai et al. 1989). As may be observed, they are solely based on grain size distribution and are still in use (Green and Ziotopoulou 2015).

Figure 2.1. Ranges of grain size accumulation curves for liquefiable (a) soils of uniform grading and (b) well graded soils (Iai et al. 1989)

For many years, only sands were thought to be susceptible to liquefaction. However, liquefaction can occur over a broader range of soil types, such as gravels and non-plastic silts, as it has been observed (Ishihara 1984; 1985) in the field and the laboratory, indicating that plasticity characteristics rather than grain size alone affect the liquefaction susceptibility. Furthermore, cohesive soil deposits, such as clays and plastic silts, are able to exhibit "strain-softening behaviour" similar to that of liquefiable soils, as they can also develop significant strains and ground deformations during earthquake loading. The so-called Chinese Criteria, which were based primarily on case history data from fine-grained soils at various sites in China during strong earthquakes, as reported by Wang (1979), are widely used as a means for identifying clayey soils that are susceptible to significant strength loss (Seed and Idriss 1982; Kramer and Elgamal 2001):

Clay fraction (finer than 0.005 mm)	$\leq 15\%$
Liquid limit (LL)	$< 35\%$
Natural water content	≥ 0.90 LL
Liquidity index	≤ 0.75

In addition, Andrews & Martin (2000) proposed modifications to the Chinese Criteria limits concluding that (a) soils are susceptible to liquefaction if they have clay content $<10\%$ finer than 0.002mm and $LL < 32$, (b) soils are not susceptible to liquefaction if they have clay content $\geq 10\%$ finer than 0.002mm and $LL \geq 32$, and (c) further study is required for soils that meet one, but not both, of these criteria.

Seed et al. (2003) proposed the liquefaction susceptibility criteria shown in Figure 2.2, based on post-earthquake field data in conjunction with subsequent laboratory tests. It should be noted that they distinguish the term "classic" cyclically-induced liquefaction, which refers to significant loss of strength and stiffness due to cyclic pore pressure generation from the phenomenon of "strain-softening" or "sensitivity", which is defined as the loss of strength due to monotonic shearing and/or remoulding as a result of larger, monotonic (unidirectional) shear displacements. Therefore, soils within Zone A are considered potentially susceptible to "classic" cyclically-induced liquefaction, soils within Zone B may be liquefiable, while soils in Zone C (not within Zones A or B) are generally no susceptible to "classic" cyclic liquefaction but should be checked for potential "sensitivity".

It is also noted that Boulanger and Idriss (2006) classify soils as "sand-like" and "clay-like" based on PI, with a transition zone between these two categories as illustrated in Figure 2.3. For "sand-like" soils, they state that the liquefaction potential can be evaluated using the simplified liquefaction evaluation procedure, while for "clay-like" soils laboratory tests should be used.

Figure 2.2. Plasticity chart showing the liquefaction susceptibility criteria (Seed et al. 2003)

Figure 2.3. Schematic illustration of the transition from sand-like to clay-like behaviour for fine-grained soils with increasing PI, and the recommended guideline for assigned cyclic resistance ratio "CRR" (Boulanger and Idriss 2006)

Finally, liquefaction susceptibility is strongly influenced by the initial state of the soil at the time of the earthquake, which is defined by its density and effective stress. Castro (1969) was the first one who observed that (a) soils with low density under high effective stress consistently exhibit highly contractive behaviour (with flow liquefaction) under monotonic loading, (b) soils with high density under low effective stress consistently exhibit dilative behaviour under monotonic loading and (c) soils of intermediate density and/or intermediate effective stresses exhibit limited liquefaction. Building upon the critical void-ratio concept identified by Casagrande (1936) and by plotting the steady-state effective confining pressure as a function of void ratio, "e", Castro defined a steady-

state line (SSL) that marked the boundary between (contractive) states susceptible to flow liquefaction and (dilative) states not susceptible to flow liquefaction (Figure 2.4).

Figure 2.4. Schematic illustration of the steady-state line (SSL) as a boundary between initial states that are and are not susceptible to flow liquefaction

2.3.3 Evaluation of liquefaction potential

Over the years several reliable approaches for the evaluation of earthquake-induced liquefaction potential have been proposed, all based on the principles mentioned in the previous section. The “Cyclic Stress Approach” is the most well-documented and commonly used procedure for the evaluation of liquefaction potential. In this approach, cyclic shear stresses characterize both the loading imposed on the soil by the earthquake (seismic demand) and the resistance of the soil to liquefaction (capacity).

In particular, the seismic demand on a soil layer is typically characterised in terms of the cyclic stress ratio (CSR) which is defined as the ratio of the equivalent cyclic shear stress, τ_{cyc} , to the initial vertical effective stress, σ'_{vo} :

$$CSR = \frac{\tau_{cyc}}{\sigma'_{vo}} \quad (2.3)$$

The equivalent cyclic shear stress is generally taken as being equal to 65% of the peak cyclic shear stress, τ_{max} . Seed and Idriss (1971), in a procedure commonly referred to as the “Simplified method” which constitutes now the state-of-the-practice approach for evaluating liquefaction potential at a specific site, estimated the peak cyclic shear stress from the peak ground surface acceleration and a depth reduction factor, r_d , which represents the average rate at which peak shear stress attenuates with depth. Thus, the equation for calculation of the cyclic stress ratio, was formulated as:

$$CSR = \frac{\tau_{av}}{\sigma'_{vo}} = 0.65 \frac{\tau_{max}}{\sigma'_{vo}} = 0.65 \frac{\alpha_{max}}{g} \frac{\sigma_v}{\sigma'_{vo}} r_d \quad (2.4)$$

where τ_{av} is the average horizontal shear stress acting on soil layer during shaking generated by given earthquake

a_{max} is the peak horizontal acceleration at the ground surface generated by the earthquake

g is the acceleration of gravity

σ_{vo} is the total vertical overburden stress

σ'_{vo} is the effective vertical overburden stress

r_d is the stress reduction coefficient, which accounts for flexibility of the soil

For routine practice and noncritical projects, the following may be used to estimate average values of r_d (Liao and Whitman 1986; Robertson and Wride 1998):

r_d		Depth z (m)
$1.0 - 0.00765z$	→	$z \leq 9.15\text{m}$
$1.174 - 0.0267z$	→	$9.15 < z \leq 23\text{m}$
$0.744 - 0.008z$	→	$23 < z \leq 30\text{m}$
0.5	→	$z > 30\text{m}$

where z is the depth below ground surface in meters

The capacity of the soil to resist liquefaction is typically expressed in terms of the cyclic resistance ratio (CRR), which is defined as the cyclic stress ratio that just causes initial liquefaction and is determined as a function of two parameters, namely the penetration resistance and earthquake magnitude. For the evaluation of CRR, several in situ tests have gained common usage including the standard penetration test (SPT) and the cone penetration test (CPT) to characterize the soil. Shear-wave velocity (V_s) measurements and the Becker penetration test (BPT) are also used in specific cases. Most common it is to relate CRR to corrected SPT resistance, $(N_1)_{60}$. Youd et al. (2001) proposed a graphical relationship between $CRR_{7.5}$ and $(N_1)_{60}$ appropriate only for M_w 7.5 earthquakes (Figure 2.5). For other earthquake magnitudes, M , correction factors termed "magnitude scaling factors (MSFs)" have been proposed by various researchers as shown in Figure 2.6 and CRR_M is calculated as:

$$CRR_M = CRR_{7.5} \cdot MSF \quad (2.5)$$

In addition, several other factors influence SPT resistance, so Youd et al. (2001) proposed the following equation incorporating these corrections:

$$(N_1)_{60} = N_m \cdot C_n \cdot C_e \cdot C_b \cdot C_r \cdot C_s \quad (2.6)$$

where N_m is the measured standard penetration resistance

C_n is a factor to normalize N_m to a common reference effective overburden stress

C_e is the correction for hammer energy ratio (ER)

- C_b is the correction factor for borehole diameter
- C_r is the correction factor for rod length
- C_s is the correction for samplers with or without liners

Figure 2.5. Relationship between $CRR_{7.5}$ and $(N_1)_{60}$ for M_w 7.5 earthquakes (Youd et al. 2001)

Figure 2.6. Magnitude scaling factors derived by various researchers (Youd et al. 2001)

CRR can also be determined by correlation to the results of CPT in situ tests. Robertson and Wride (1998) proposed a method to estimate grain characteristics directly from the CPT and incorporated it into one of the methods for evaluating CRR (NCEER 97). According to this method, although cone penetration resistance is often just corrected for overburden stress (resulting in the term q_{c1}), truly normalized (i.e., dimensionless) cone penetration resistance corrected for overburden stress (q_{c1N}) can be given by equation:

$$q_{c1N} = \left(\frac{q_c}{P_{a2}} \right) C_Q = \frac{q_{c1}}{P_{a2}} \quad (2.7)$$

where q_c is field cone penetration resistance measured at the tip; C_Q is a normalizing factor for cone penetration resistance equal to $(P_a/\sigma'_{vo})^n$ and P_a is 100kPa or approximately one atmosphere of pressure in the same units used for σ'_{vo} . A maximum value of $C_Q = 2$ is generally applied to CPT data at shallow depths. The value of the exponent, n , is dependent on grain characteristics of the soil and ranges from 0.5 for clean sands to 1.0 for clays. An intermediate value of n between 0.5 and 1.0 would be appropriate for silts and silty sands. It is possible to estimate grain characteristics directly from CPT results using the soil behaviour type chart shown in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7. Normalized CPT soil behaviour type chart, as proposed by Robertson (1990). Soil types: 1, sensitive, fine grained; 2, peats; 3, silty clay to clay; 4, clayey silt to silty clay; 5, silty sand to sandy silt; 6, clean sand to silty sand; 7, gravelly sand to dense sand; 8, very stiff sand to clayey sand (heavily overconsolidated OCR or cemented); 9, very stiff, fine grained (heavily overconsolidated or cemented). OCR, overconsolidation ratio; ϕ' , friction angle

The radius of each circle, referred to as the soil behaviour type index, I_c , is calculated from the following equation:

$$I_c = [(3.47 - Q)^2 + (\log F + 1.22)^2]^{0.5} \quad (2.8)$$

where

$$Q = \left(\frac{q_{c-\sigma_{vo}}}{P_{a2}} \right) \left(\frac{P_a}{\sigma'_{vo}} \right)^n \quad \text{and} \quad F = \left(\frac{f_s}{q_{c-\sigma_{vo}}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (2.9)$$

If the calculated I_c , computed with an exponent $n=1.0$, is less than 2.6, the soil is most likely granular in nature and Q and C_Q should be recalculated using an exponent $n=0.5$ and q_{c1N} substituted for Q . I_c should then be recalculated and if it is found again less than 2.6, the soil can be classed as non-plastic and granular, and this I_c can be used to estimate liquefaction resistance. If the recalculated I_c is greater than 2.6, the soil is likely to be very silty and possibly plastic. In this instance, q_{c1N} and then I_c should be recalculated using an intermediate exponent of 0.7. This intermediate I_c is finally used to calculate liquefaction resistance.

The proposed equation to correct the normalized CPT penetration resistance (q_{c1N}), of sand with fines to an equivalent clean sand value (q_{c1N})_{CS}, is a function of both the measured penetration resistance, q_{c1N} , and the grain characteristics of the soil, as follows: (q_{c1N})_{CS} = $K_c \times q_{c1N}$, where the CPT correction factor for grain characteristics K_c is defined by the following equations:

For $I_c \leq 1.64$, $K_c = 1.0$

$$\text{For } I_c > 1.64, K_c = -0.403 I_c^4 + 5.581 I_c^3 - 21.63 I_c^2 + 33.75 I_c - 17.88 \quad (2.10)$$

A final value of I_c greater than 2.6 indicates that the soils are most likely too clay rich or plastic to liquefy ($K_{C_{Descr}}=NLIQ$). With an appropriate I_c and K_c , the following simplified equations can be used to calculate $CRR_{7.5}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If } (q_{c1N})_{CS} < 50 & \quad CRR_{7.5} = 0.833[(q_{c1N})_{CS} / 1000] + 0.05 \\ \text{If } 50 \leq (q_{c1N})_{CS} < 160 & \quad CRR_{7.5} = 93[(q_{c1N})_{CS} / 1000]^3 + 0.08 \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

To adjust CRR to magnitudes smaller or larger than 7.5, the calculated $CRR_{7.5}$ is multiplied by an appropriate magnitude scaling factor (MSF). Idriss scaling factors (NCEER 1997) are defined by the following equation:

$$MSF = \frac{10^{2.24}}{M^{2.56}} \quad (2.12)$$

In general, it should be noted that the state-of-the-practice for the procedures on evaluation of liquefaction resistance is analytically presented in the summary of the NCEER 1997 workshop on liquefaction by [Youd et al. \(2001\)](#). Updated recommended procedures for evaluating liquefaction potential are also presented by [Idriss and Boulanger \(2006\)](#).

The liquefaction potential in a particular earthquake is usually expressed in terms of a factor of safety (FS) against liquefaction. Generally, the factor of safety is defined as a ratio of capacity to demand. The factor of safety in the case of liquefaction can be expressed as:

$$FS = \frac{CRR_M}{CSR} \quad (2.13)$$

FS values less than one indicate that liquefaction is likely to occur, according to the simplified procedure (NCEER 97) described above.

In Europe, liquefaction potential is also estimated according to Eurocode 8 (EC8)- Part 5 (CEN 2004b). In this approach, the seismic shear stress τ_e , may be estimated from the simplified expression:

$$\tau_e = 0.65 \cdot \alpha \cdot S \cdot \sigma_{vo} \quad (2.14)$$

where α is the ratio of the design ground acceleration on type A ground, a_g , to the acceleration of gravity g

S is the soil parameter according to EC8 - Part 1 (CEN 2004a)

σ_{vo} is the is the total overburden pressure

For the SPT, the measured values of the blowcount N_{SPT} , expressed in blows/30 cm, N_{30} , are normalised for overburden effects and for the energy ratio according to the following expression:

$$(N_1)_{60} = N_{30} \cdot \left(\frac{100}{\sigma'_{vo}}\right)^{1/2} \cdot \frac{ER}{60} \quad (2.15)$$

where ER is one hundred times the energy ratio specific to the testing equipment. For depths of less than 3.0 m, the measured N_{SPT} values should be reduced by 25%. Then $CRR_{7.5}$ is evaluated using the charts of Figure 2.8. Subsequently, in order to evaluate CRR for earthquake magnitudes different from $M_s = 7.5$, where M_s is the surface-wave magnitude, $CRR_{7.5}$ should be multiplied by a factor CM indicated in Table 2.1.

It should be noted that the liquefaction hazard may be neglected when $\alpha \cdot S < 0,15$ and at least one of the following conditions is fulfilled:

- the sands have a clay content greater than 20% with plasticity index $PI > 10$;
- the sands have a silt content greater than 35% and $(N_1)_{60} > 20$ at the same time;
- the sands are clean, with $(N_1)_{60} > 30$.

Finally, according to EC8 - Part 5 (CEN 2004b), a soil should be considered susceptible to liquefaction when the safety factor against liquefaction is less than 1.25. However, it should be noted that the safety factor against liquefaction, either it is calculated according to NCEER 97 or according to EC8, does not distinguish between flow liquefaction and cyclic mobility, and this information is insufficient to predict the post-liquefaction behaviour of structures and finally make an integrated damage and risk assessment.

Figure 2.8. Relationship between $CRR_{7.5}$ ($=\tau_e/\sigma'_{vo}$) and $(N_1)_{60}$ values for (A) clean and (B) silty sands for M_w 7.5 earthquakes, where curve 1: 35 % fines, curve 2: 15% fines and curve 3: < 5% fines (CEN 2004b)

Table 2.1. Values of factor CM (CEN 2004b)

M_s	CM
5.5	2.86
6.0	2.20
6.5	1.69
7.0	1.30
8.0	0.67

Furthermore, Liquefaction Potential Index (LPI), initially proposed by Iwasaki et al. (1982), is used as an assessing tool of liquefaction potential. LPI is an index which considers the thickness of the liquefiable layer, the thickness of the non-liquefiable layer and the value of the factor of safety against liquefaction. It is computed using the following equation:

$$LPI = \int_0^z F(z)W(z)dz \tag{2.16}$$

where z is the depth below the ground surface (in meters) and is calculated as $w(z)=10-0.5z$; $F(z)$ is a function of the factor of safety against liquefaction, f_s , where $F(z)=1-f_s$ when $f_s < 1$ and if $f_s > 1$ then $F(z)=0$. Equation 2.10 gives the values of LPI ranging from 0 to 100. The LPI is related to the factor of safety (f_s) however, only the

soils with $f_s < 1$ that satisfy at the same time the liquefaction susceptibility criteria contribute to the severity of liquefaction (Juang and Li 2007).

According to this index, liquefaction potential has been characterized as high where LPI ranges between 5 and 15 and low at sites where $0 < \text{LPI} < 5$. The liquefaction potential is extremely low where LPI is equal to 0, while the liquefaction potential is extremely high at sites where $\text{LPI} > 15$. Modifications to LPI were subsequently made by several authors (e.g. Sonmez 2003; Lee et al. 2004; Sonmez and Gokceoglu 2005;). The advantage of LPI is that it quantifies the likely of liquefaction of the site, by providing a unique value for the entire soil column instead of several factors of safety per layer (Papathanassiou 2008). Thus, for liquefaction hazard maps the values of LPI are used.

Papathanassiou (2008) investigated the impact of the liquefaction susceptibility criteria proposed by Seed et al. (2003) to the existing LPI-based classifications of severity of liquefaction-induced failures. He calculated the factor of safety against liquefaction and the LPI of borings with SPT, conducted at liquefied and non-liquefied sites in Taiwan, in Turkey and in Greece, based on the recommendations suggested by Youd et al. (2001) and Iwasaki et al. (1982), respectively. He finally proposed a LPI-based probabilistic approach for the evaluation of liquefaction-surface evidences and, by considering a cut-off value of 50% probability, he defined a threshold value of LPI equal to 14 for discriminating the cases of liquefaction surface manifestation from the non-liquefaction ones.

2.4 Tsunami

The term "tsunami" is a Japanese word (津波), composed of the two characters "tsu" meaning "harbour" and "nami" meaning "wave". Tsunamis are long-period sea waves that can be triggered by a single source of given size or intensity (undersea shallow-focus earthquake, underwater or aerial landslide or volcanic eruption). Nevertheless, the vast majority of tsunamis are induced by a seismic event. Tsunamis are categorised by the location of the triggering event and the time it takes the waves to reach a given site. A far-source generated tsunami is one that originates from a source that is far away from the site of interest and takes two hours or longer after the triggering event to arrive, while a near-source generated tsunami is one that originates from a source that is close to the site of interest and can arrive within thirty minutes (FEMA 2008). Generally, sites experiencing near-source generated tsunamis are also affected by the triggering event (e.g. ground shaking caused by a near-source earthquake).

For a locally-generated tsunami, the first leading wave is often a receding water level followed by an elevation wave. This may not be the case if the coastline subsides by co-seismic displacement. For far-source generated tsunamis, the leading wave is often an

elevation wave. This trend may be related to the pattern of sea floor displacement resulting from a subduction-type earthquake. Whether or not coastline uplift or subsidence occurs or what part of the seafloor displacement profile is submerged depends on the position of the interplate rupture area relative to the coastline (Geist 1999). Figure 2.9 depicts schematic diagrams of the vertical displacement resulting from subduction-type fault dislocation. In the case shown in Figure 2.9a, coastline subsidence exacerbates the effect of tsunami inundation from an interplate event, while in Figure 2.9b where co-seismic coastal uplift occurs only part of the vertical displacement field is transferred to the tsunami. When the rupture zone is located far offshore, no coastal movement occurs, and a deep-water tsunami is generated that is subsequently amplified during propagation across the continental margin (Figure 2.9c).

Tsunami wave height, in the deep ocean, typically ranges from a few centimetres to tens of centimetres. As the tsunami wave approaches the continental shelf and coastline and the water depth decreases, wave height increases by a process known as “wave shoaling”. In particular, the tsunami's energy flux, which is dependent on both wave velocity and wave height, remains nearly constant. Hence, wave velocity and wavelength decrease with decreasing water depth results in an increase in wave amplitude as kinetic energy is converted to potential energy. Because of this shoaling effect, by the time tsunami waves hit coastline they can be tens of metres high, depending on the source, energy, propagation path and local conditions (e.g. tides, coastal bathymetry, resonant wave periods) and can cause widespread damages to ports and coastal structures. The magnitude and location of the earthquake or triggering event, the configuration of the continental shelf and shoreline as well as the upland topography determines the tsunami impact at a site and damage potential (FEMA 2005).

The probability of tsunami hazard is related to the location and faulting characteristics of the earthquake as well as the topography and near-shore bathymetry of the coastline. Historical tsunami data are an important first step for assessing the preliminary tsunami hazard of a region. Geologic data can be used to extend the record significantly for earthquakes and tsunamis (e.g. Dominey-Howes 2002). Also, numerical models provide estimates of maximum possible tsunami heights (e.g. Bernard and González 1994), tsunami arrival times, currents, and forces on structures (Mofjeld et al. 1999). According to Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC UNESCO 2009), there are three steps to modelling a tsunami, namely, source modelling (where parameters describing the tsunami source are used to calculate the size and shape of the initial tsunami wave), tsunami propagation modelling (taking the initial wave and propagating that wave to the coast) and tsunami inundation modelling (modelling the tsunami as it inundates the

coast). Maps can then be produced showing areas likely to be inundated by tsunamis with various return periods (e.g. [Bernard et al. 1994](#)).

Figure 2.9. Schematic diagrams of the vertical displacement resulting from thrust fault dislocation: (a) rupture zone adjacent to coastline with coastal subsidence, (b) rupture zone located farther landward than (a) with coastal uplift and (c) rupture zone located far offshore ([Geist 1999](#))

There are two approaches that may be employed to express the potential for tsunami impact, namely, scenario-based Deterministic Tsunami Hazard Assessment (DTHA) which uses single-valued events (worst credible and/or most likely tsunami events, according to some presumed geological framework), and Probabilistic Tsunami Hazard Assessment (PTHA) which allows the use of multi-valued events and models (often based on more than one geological framework), incorporating the magnitude and frequencies of all events that could impact a site. [Wijetunge \(2014\)](#), among others, conducted a DTHA for the southwest coast of Sri Lanka. PTHA was inspired from probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA), first introduced by [Cornell \(1968\)](#), and developed to estimate coastal tsunami heights from future earthquakes. A PTHA requires historical tsunami data, quantitative probabilistic models of local and far-field tsunami sources (earthquake, landslide, volcano), high resolution digital elevation models (topography, bathymetry, tidal information), and numerous inundation and propagation models for the potential tsunami sources. The result of PTHA is probabilistic tsunami inundation maps. One of the first studies in probabilistic tsunami hazard assessment is that of [Rikitake and Aida \(1988\)](#), who estimated the probability of exceedance of wave height at coastal locations in Japan, accounting for both local and distant earthquake sources. [Power et al. \(2007\)](#) developed a PTHA method for estimating probabilistic tsunami heights from distant earthquakes, using a Monte-Carlo technique. [Annaka et al. \(2007\)](#) proposed a logic-tree approach for PTHA to construct tsunami hazard curves (tsunami height - probability of exceedance at a particular site relationship). [González et al. \(2009\)](#) developed probabilistic inundation maps based on the principles of flood risk assessment for the town of Seaside, Oregon. Finally, a combination of both approaches may be used (e.g. [Papadopoulos and Dermentzopoulos 1998](#)).

2.5 Recorded seismic damages to buildings during past events and lessons learned

The seismic response of buildings is of great importance as it is directly related to the damage and losses caused by earthquakes and the associated hazards, such as ground shaking, liquefaction and tsunami. Field reconnaissance of past and recent earthquakes, such as 1964 Alaska, 1964 Niigata in Japan, 1978 Thessaloniki in Greece, 1989 Loma Prieta in California, 1992 Erzincan in Turkey, 1994 Northridge in California, 1995 Hanshin/Kobe in Japan, 1999 Chi-Chi in Taiwan, 1999 Düzce and 1999 Kocaeli in Turkey, 1999 Athens and 2003 Lefkada in Greece, 2004 Sumatra and 2005 Nias in Indonesia (Indian Ocean), 2008 Wenchuan in China, 2009 L'Aquila in Italy, 2010 Haiti, 2010 Maule in Chile, 2010 Darfield and 2011 Christchurch in New Zealand, 2011 Tohoku-Oki in East Japan, 2012 Emilia-Romagna in Northern Italy, 2016 Central Italy, 2017 Bodrum-Kos in

Greece (Seed and Idriss 1967; Penelis et al. 1988; Bray and Stewart 2000; Love et al. 2004; Chung et al. 1996; Lee and Loh 2000; Erdik 2001; Papathanassiou et al. 2005b; Elnashai et al. 2010; Green et al. 2011, Cubrinovski 2013; Goda et al. 2013; Lai et al. 2015; Luzi et al. 2017; Papathanassiou et al. 2019; etc.) and several others highlighted the vulnerability of buildings against these hazards. Subsequently, the major characteristics of the damage and performance of various buildings under different geotechnical environment observed during major earthquakes worldwide are presented.

2.5.1 Damage due to ground shaking

Ground shaking caused by an earthquake poses significant threat to the built environment. Evidence from past earthquakes has demonstrated that ground shaking constitutes the principal cause of damage to structures. For example, although the devastating 1999 Chi-Chi earthquake of magnitude M_w 7.7 in Taiwan induced extensive geotechnical hazards including soil liquefaction, ground shaking dominated the structures damage. As a direct result of this earthquake, more than 10000 buildings collapsed and at least 7000 suffered damage (Lee and Loh 2000). From the reconnaissance report it is observed that a great number of the above was the direct result of the strong ground shaking combined with common deficiencies in design and construction. Similarly, in Adapazari although significant building damage occurred in areas of significant ground failure, the structural damage was primarily due to strong ground shaking and poor structural design and construction (Sancio et al. 2004). Special attention should be given to the cumulative damage in structures subjected to repeated shaking. The two separate earthquakes of M_w 6.5 in May and M_w 6.0 in September demonstrated the cumulative effects on the stiffness and strength and therefore the response of unrepaired buildings subjected to a subsequent earthquake, including collapse of heavily damaged structures (Love et al. 2004).

Moderate or severe ground motions can result to physical collapse or serious structural and/or non-structural damage of commercial, industrial, residential and public buildings as well as lifeline systems. The seismic performance of a structure depends on the superstructure and foundation system, while the extent of damage is determined by the magnitude of ground shaking at a particular location. In addition, soft soil deposits are widely recognised to affect site amplification of ground motion. This is the reason why soil amplification factors as well as topographic amplification factors have been incorporated in the modern seismic design codes. Nonetheless, during the 1999 M_w 7.4 Kocaeli earthquake, buildings suffered severe damages at soft sites at Adaparazi and Avcilar, although Avcilar is about 80.0 km west of the epicentre. Similarly, topographic amplification of ground motion was also evident during the 2011 M_w 6.1 Christchurch

earthquake (Lo and Wang 2012). Goda et al. (2013) also observed that the damage to buildings after the 2011 M_w 9.0 Great East Japan earthquake was concentrated in areas with soft soil conditions, while (Elnashai et al. 2010) supported that the significant damage of several engineered buildings in Concepción city, after the 2010 M_w 8.8 Maule earthquake in Chile, was mainly attributed to its soft soil conditions, as it is a sedimentary valley with sand deposits of approximately 80.0m depths, resulting in relatively high accelerations at long periods. It is noted that especially high-rise RC buildings in the city suffered significant damage due to the effect of soil conditions.

Strong ground motion observation data can be used as quantitative input to investigate the damage patterns and buildings performance. The "Learning from Earthquakes (LFE) Program", which has been conducted by the Earthquake Engineering Research Institute (EERI) since 1973 (<https://www.eeri.org/lfe>), the Earthquake Engineering Field Investigation Team (EEFIT), formed in 1982 as a joint venture between industry and universities (<https://www.istructe.org/eefit>), as well as the New Zealand National Society for Earthquake Engineering founded in 1968 (<http://www.nzsee.org.nz/projects/past-earthquakes/>), among others, provide earthquake reports including the nature of earthquake-induced ground motion, the structures behaviour to this ground motion, and the ability of structures to withstand certain types of damage, which constitute valuable resources of field reconnaissance. Some significant earthquake-induced ground motions and their impact to the built environment are presented below.

Field survey from the 1995 M_w 6.9 Great Hanshin or Kobe earthquake showed that the collapse ratio of mid-rise pre-1981 RC and steel frame buildings was unexpectedly high. In central Kobe as much as 15% of pre-1981 RC buildings collapsed (Chandler and Pomonis 1997), while no evidence of collapse in any of the newer (post-1981) engineered RC structures was evident (Chung et al. 1996). The extent of damage to RC buildings in Kobe can be compared with that after the 1985 M_w 8.0 Mexico earthquake, the 1986 M_w 6.0 Kalamata earthquake in Southern Greece and the Erzincan earthquake in Eastern Turkey, as the RC buildings in Kalamata and Erzincan are often non-ductile, irregular frames with unreinforced masonry infills, designed for base shear of 6.0 to 8.0%, similar to those in Mexico city, although smaller in size. Kobe as well as 1994 M_w 6.7 Northridge earthquakes also confirmed the poor performance of buildings with soft first stories. The Northridge earthquake also revealed the vulnerability of moment-resisting steel frames and light wood frame residential construction, previously thought to be highly earthquake resistant (Mahin 1998).

The 1999 M_w 7.4 Kocaeli and M_w 7.2 Duzce earthquakes caused substantial damage to residential and commercial RC buildings, as the buildings predominant structural system

in Turkey consists of RC frames with a symmetric floor plan and unreinforced masonry infills, designed according to low seismic provisions. According to [Erdik \(2001\)](#), the damage caused to RC buildings was due to the poor building material quality, soft stories, strong beams with weak columns resulting to the early failure of columns, poor detailing as well as short columns leading to shear failures. In contrast to non-ductile RC frames, steel buildings performed much better to both earthquakes. The same year, the 1999 M_w 7.7 Chi-Chi earthquake in Taiwan caused serious damage or collapse of many high-rise RC moment resisting frame (MRF) buildings. [Naeim et al. \(2000\)](#) supported that the failures occurred to buildings that were designed and constructed ignoring the well-established seismic design and construction principles. [Lee and Loh \(2000\)](#) also claimed that a large percentage of collapsed buildings were non-engineered RC MRF structures that clearly exhibited a lack of ductile detailing as well as that many school buildings suffered considerable damages due to the existence of short columns, as small windows above partial height infill shortened the effective length of the columns (Figure 2.10). Shear failure also occurred in several buildings in Chi-Chi due to their poor transverse reinforcement detailing and soft-storey failure in others with strong-beam weak-column systems as shown in Figure 2.10.

More recently, the 2010 M_w 8.8 Maule earthquake in Chile led to significant damage only to a limited number of RC buildings, mainly due to structural deficiencies such as irregularities in plan and elevation, soft-stories and short-column effects, while the majority of the RC building structures performed well, as reported by [Elnashai et al. \(2010\)](#). Some buildings with RC walls were also damaged due to insufficient confinement in the bearing walls, since proper confinement in walls were not required until recently in the Chilean Building Code. It is noted that Maule Region suffered the heaviest damage from the earthquake due to its proximity to the rupture area. In addition, during the 2011 M_w 6.3 Christchurch earthquake the building damage reported by [Aydan and Ulusay \(2012\)](#) was much heavier compared with that during the 2010 M_w 7.0 Darfield. The higher strong ground motions observed during the 2011 earthquake, despite the magnitude of the earthquake, may be related to the depth, distance and faulting characteristics. The worst-affected buildings were the older unreinforced masonry buildings. The out-of-plane failure of walls, parapet, anchorage and chimney failures were the main causes of damage to unreinforced masonry buildings. Non-structural damage due to partitions cracking, fall or toppling of ceiling tiles and lights was also observed in all types of buildings.

In addition, the most powerful earthquake ever recorded in Japan and one of the most notable earthquakes in the world, the 2011 M_w 9.0 Tohoku or Great East Japan earthquake and subsequent giant tsunami caused tremendous damage and disruption to

structures, several casualties and huge economic loss. [Goda et al. \(2013\)](#) identified that key factors for severe ground shaking damage were from structural capacity viewpoint the insufficient lateral reinforcement and detailing in structural columns, while from seismic demand viewpoint, the rich spectral content of ground shaking in the intermediate vibration period range. In Sendai, it was generally observed that many of the damaged or collapsed buildings were RC structures constructed prior to 1981, when major improvements in seismic provisions were incorporated to the Japanese seismic design code.

Figure 2.10. Damage due to short columns (left) and building failure due to first soft-storey (right) in Chi-Chi, Taiwan ([Lee and Loh 2000](#))

In Greece, the 2003 M_w 6.2 Lefkada earthquake was one of the strongest earthquakes occurred in the last few decades with recorded peak ground acceleration (PGA) of 0.42g. However, the damages to the built environment were surprisingly limited. According to [Pitilakis and Roumelioti \(2013\)](#), this was attributed to the fact that Lefkada is a Greek island which belongs to the highest seismicity zone in Greece having a design ground acceleration of 0.36g as well as the combination of community awareness due to the long seismic history of the area and good building practices. Nonetheless, a single four-storey, irregular in plane, RC building on pile foundation suffered rather significant but repairable damage due to its low design acceleration (0.16g!) according to old Greek seismic code provisions of 1959. The damage typology is relatively standard for this type of structures, namely flexural failure of the columns at the ground floor, short column failure and diagonal cracking extending to the body of the masonry infills. Moreover, a three-storey RC building with short columns on the ground floor at the front and thick brick infill walls at the back, poorly designed with inadequate stirrups at the columns, totally collapsed, as shown in Figure 2.11, while other damage to RC buildings reported by [Margaris et al. \(2003\)](#) was due to flexure-shear failure of poorly designed columns in buildings with soft stories at ground level, non-symmetrical distribution of infill walls, failure of short columns that were originally not designed to act as such, failures at beam-column joints

due to unpredicted local action of the infill walls, shear failure of RC shear walls due to inadequate web reinforcement, flexural cracking at RC beam ends (although this type of failure has a beneficial contribution to the overall building stability since the formation of plastic hinges at columns is avoided) and masonry infills cracking (diagonal shear cracks, detachment of the wall from the surrounding frames, out-of-plane collapses). The large impact recorded damages were of geotechnical character observed in the shore area of the capital of the island (Papathanassiou et al. 2005b) and are discussed in the next section.

Figure 2.11. Two-storey RC building collapse caused by the 2003 Lefkada earthquake (Pitilakis and Roumelioti 2013)

In addition, the 2017 M_w 6.6 Bodrum-Kos, Aegean Sea earthquake induced minor damages to contemporary residential houses and buildings, that were constructed following the regulations of the Greek Seismic Code, at the island of Kos in Greece and severe damages on Venetian and Ottoman-era constructions causing two fatalities. Secondary effects in the eastern part of the Kos island, including liquefaction-related phenomena and tsunami were also reported by Papathanassiou et al. (2019) and Yalçiner et al. (2017) and are analysed in more detail in the next sections.

2.5.2 Damage due to liquefaction and lateral spreading

Experience gained from recent strong seismic events has demonstrated the high vulnerability of buildings and infrastructure to earthquake-induced liquefaction displacements resulting to severe physical damages and important economic and societal losses. However, compared to ground-shaking and tsunami hazards, liquefaction is less likely to cause conventional collapse of buildings or fatalities. A common indication of liquefaction is the formation of sand boils or mud spouts at the ground surface by seepage of water through ground cracks or by the development of quick sand-like conditions over substantial areas. Figure 2.12 shows a sand boil from the 1989 M_w 6.9 Loma Prieta in California, after the liquefaction-induced boiling has ceased. Idriss and

Boulanger (2008) argued that the damage from liquefaction is seldom due to the sand boils themselves, but rather due to the loss of strength and stiffness in the soils that have liquefied and the associated ground deformations that ensue.

Figure 2.12. Sand boil after liquefaction-induced boiling from the 1989 Loma Prieta, California earthquake has ceased

The 1964 M_w 7.5 Niigata earthquake, together with the 1964 M_w 9.2 Alaska earthquake, which first highlighted the damaging potential of ground failure, brought liquefaction phenomena and their devastating effects to the attention of the engineering and seismological community. After soil liquefaction occurs, the soil loses its shear resistance and may result in loss of bearing capacity and submerge of the overlying heavy structures, uplift of light structures, lateral spreading if there is ground inclination as well as increase of lateral pressure on structures. In Alaska, the earthquake that caused significant liquefaction led to the collapse of a poorly detailed non-redundant shear wall structure, in contrast to the redundant shear wall buildings that performed well even if designed for low seismic loading. After this earthquake, a study of performance of non-structural building components was conducted for the first time drawing the attention of engineering community for proper seismic detailing of these building elements. In addition, during the 1964 Niigata earthquake bearing capacity failures and severe tilting of the Kawagishi-cho apartment buildings occurred due to the shear strength and stiffness loss of liquefied sands near the Shinano river bank, as shown in Figure 2.13. It is noted that despite the extreme tilting, the buildings themselves suffered remarkably limited structural damage.

The observations of building performance due to liquefaction in recent earthquakes improve the understanding of the performance of the built environment. It is seen that liquefaction-induced building displacements are the main reason for buildings failures on liquefiable sites. Liquefaction-induced building displacements after an earthquake are often estimated using procedures developed to evaluate post-earthquake reconsolidation

settlement in the free-field. However, these procedures ignore the partial drainage that occurs during strong shaking and the important deviatoric strain mechanisms that have proved by [Dashti et al. \(2010\)](#) to be really important for the estimation of liquefaction-induced building displacements. The primary liquefaction-induced displacement mechanisms have been categorised by [Dashti and Bray \(2013\)](#) as either volumetric-induced or shear-induced. The volumetric-induced displacement mechanisms are the localised volumetric strains during partially drained cyclic loading (Figure 2.14a), the downward displacement due to sedimentation after liquefaction and the consolidation-induced volumetric strains as excess pore water pressures dissipate and the soil's effective stress increases, while the shear-induced displacement mechanisms are the partial bearing failure as a result of foundation soil strength loss resulting in punching settlements or tilting of the structure (Figure 2.14b) and the cumulative ratcheting foundation displacement due to SSI-induced cyclic loading near the edges of the foundation (Figure 2.14c).

Figure 2.13. Bearing failure of foundations of the Kawagishi-cho apartment buildings after the 1964 Niigata earthquake

Reconnaissance investigations following the earthquakes in Alaska (1964), California (1989 Loma Prieta), Japan (1964 Niigata; 1995 Kobe; 2011 Tohoku), Taiwan (1999 Chi-Chi), Turkey (1999 Düzce and Kocaeli), Haiti (2010), New Zealand (2010 Darfield and 2011 Christchurch), Greece (2003 Lefkada; 2017 Bodrum-Kos) have contributed to much improved scientific understanding of liquefaction-induced damages to engineered buildings and constitute the basis for the evaluation procedures of liquefaction potential, post-liquefaction ground deformations and their effect on buildings response. Past experience has also demonstrated that by far the most widespread source of seismic damage to port structures, ranging from piles beneath jetties, pipelines, quay walls, docks and cranes to warehouses, administrative buildings, as well as industrial manufacturing and storage activities, is the liquefaction of loose, saturated soils that often prevail at coastal areas ([Pitilakis et al. 2014a](#)). Even moderate levels of earthquake

intensity can cause liquefaction, potentially leading to induced soil settlements and lateral spreading that may produce serious damages to port structures and hence result to significant economic and societal losses (PIANC 2001). The 2012 M_w 5.9 Emilia-Romagna earthquake in Northern Italy also confirms that even a moderate severity earthquake may induce liquefaction at epicentral distances smaller than 40.0 km as thoroughly discussed by Galli (2000). Indeed, although this earthquake was of rather moderate magnitude, an area up to 17.0 km from the epicentre with severe damage and collapse of several warehouses was affected. Lai et al. (2015) reported widespread liquefaction phenomena, such as sand boils and ground failures.

Figure 2.14. Primary liquefaction-induced displacement mechanisms: (a) volumetric strains caused by water flow in response to transient gradients; (b) partial bearing capacity failure due to soil softening; and (c) SSI-induced building ratcheting during earthquake loading (Dashti and Bray 2013)

Evidence of past earthquakes highlighted the seismic risk to port buildings. Port administrative buildings are subject to ground shaking damage, as well impacts caused by loss of bearing or lateral movement of foundation soils. Extensive damage due to ground motion, or soil liquefaction and lateral spreading can lead to prolonged closure

times with potentially serious impacts on the regional economy when customers start diverting their business to alternative ports. Damage to port structures can be severe, as in many cases in the analysis and design of a structure, neither all the important material seismic response behaviours, such as soil liquefaction, nor a realistic seismic loading on the structure might have been considered. Even if seismic design provisions changed to account for these phenomena, in some cases a more consistent soil-structure interaction analysis may be needed (Tanaka and Inatomi 1996).

In Kobe field observations after the 1995 earthquake indicated that port infrastructure and engineered buildings are particularly susceptible to extensive liquefaction, lateral spreading, and differential ground settlements, while deep pile foundations performed well when designed to current standards (Chung et al. 1996). In particular, the port of Kobe, one of the largest container cargo ports in the world, suffered major damages due to extensive ground failure, including liquefaction and lateral displacement. Quay walls over a large proportion of the port, container berths, gantry cranes, warehouses, administrative buildings, all bridges to Rokko and Port Islands, as well as utility lines underwent significant damage that essentially shut it down and required over two years to fully repair (Chang 2000). Several concrete caisson quay walls moved 2.0-5.0m into the sea, possibly caused by inertia of the heavy concrete caissons, large dynamic lateral pressures created by liquefaction of the backfill materials and the reduction of bearing capacity of replaced sands under the caissons. Chandler and Pomonis (1997) also noticed that the great majority of damage to RC industrial facilities in Kobe resulted from differential displacements imposed by soil movement as well as the poor (non-ductile) RC details, while steel buildings generally remained serviceable, although long term damage may have occurred to welded connections. In addition, the buildings with shallow foundations were found to be particularly affected by liquefaction. An example is a three-storey office building which seemed to be on shallow foundations at the Port Island (Kobe Port). The building itself did not suffer structural damage, but the structure tilted as a block by about 2.5 degrees toward the sea side due to lateral spreading and also slightly sheared as seen from observation of unfitted windows (Chandler and Pomonis 1997). On the contrary, it should be noted that the improved ground sites sustained less deformation and subsequently damage compared with the adjacent ground.

The M_w 7.0 2010 Haiti earthquake also led to severe damage to the Port International de Port-au-Prince due to the extensive ground failures occurred in the calcareous sand artificial fills at the seaport, including liquefaction, lateral spreading, differential settlements and total collapse of the pile-supported wharf and pier. Green et al. (2011) reported that steel warehouses founded on strip footings around their perimeters sustained severe damage due to differential settlements, a grain silo yard north of the

North Wharf suffered approximately 1.2m of cumulative lateral spreading displacement, a storage yard north of the grain silo area suffered approximately 2.4m of lateral spreading displacement, as well as that lateral displacements likely 15.0m or more, over 2.6m, and almost 1.0m were observed at the southern, western, and northern perimeter of the North Wharf, respectively.

In contrast to the previous earthquakes, in Adapazari after the 1999 M_w 7.4 Kocaeli earthquake (Turkey), many buildings founded on very stiff and strong thick mat foundations were affected by the cyclic softening or liquefaction of shallow and relatively thin layers of loose, saturated silt and silty sand. Buildings in Adapazari were primarily three to six-storey RC frame buildings with elastic fundamental periods ranging between 0.3 and 0.4sec (Bray and Sancio 2009). The significant levels of building settlement commonly observed there could not be estimated using the available empirical relationships, because the thickness of the governing liquefiable soil layer was typically only a few meters thick (less than 2–3-m), as well as due to the fact that a building's foundation contact pressure and height to width (H/B) ratio were found to greatly influence the amount of building settlement and tilt, respectively (Sancio et al. 2004). In particular, building settlements were remarkably greater for taller, heavier buildings than for shorter, lighter ones, possibly due to the shear-induced deformation and localised volumetric strain under the building foundations. Tall buildings erected on relatively narrow foundation widths were found to be prone to tilt excessively or topple (Bray and Dashti 2014). This type of foundation behaviour in Adapazari City due to the presence of Holocene alluvium during the 1999 Kocaeli earthquake was also observed during the 1985 M_w 7.4 Mexico City earthquake due to the presence of sensitive clay in Mexico City (Seed et al. 1988). In general, buildings in Adapazari settled into the surrounding ground, tilted due to significant differential foundation displacements, slid laterally on liquefied/softened ground or totally collapsed (e.g. Bray and Stewart 2000; Sancio et al. 2004; Bray et al. 2004). In the cases where the building could not topple as a rigid body, it failed in a pan-cake mode as a result of beam-column failure due to the significant degree of tilting. On the other hand, no damage was observed on a few multi-storey buildings with pile foundations in Adapazari. Bray and Dashti (2014) supported that the most common mechanism of building settlement in Adapazari after the Kocaeli earthquake was believed to be the soil rapid spreading directly under the building outwards due to a temporary loss of bearing capacity and SSI ratcheting of buildings into the softened ground.

After the 1999 M_w 7.7 Chi-Chi earthquake in Taiwan, soil liquefaction was also one of the main causes for heavy damages to the structures. Several geotechnical failures with an impact on the seismic performance of buildings were observed, such as settlement

due to liquefaction as shown in Figure 2.15 to a building in Chi-Chi, Taiwan (Lee and Loh 2000).

Figure 2.15. Damage due to settlement caused by liquefaction in Chi-Chi, Taiwan (Lee and Loh 2000)

One of the major characteristics of both the 2010 M_w 7.0 Darfield earthquake as well as the 2011 M_w 6.3 Christchurch earthquake is liquefaction and associated lateral spreading, which generally affected the same areas. The liquefaction-induced settlements, lateral spreading, and large sand boils were widespread. Similarly to Adapazarı after the 1999 earthquake, light structures were uplifted while heavy structures sank into the ground. Residential buildings and lifelines on liquefied sites suffered extensive damage due to the liquefaction-induced ground settlements and lateral spreading. The effect of lateral spreading of liquefied ground was damaging even to RC structures. Lateral spreading involves large lateral ground movements as well as substantial differential displacements in the direction of spreading, resulting in large extensional deformations. Spreading-induced lateral and vertical ground displacements were spatially non-uniform, causing localised deformation, stretching, tensile cracking and shearing of the ground. (Cubrinovski et al. 2012; Cubrinovski 2013). Lateral spreading refers to the accumulation of permanent lateral displacement in soils subjected to ground shaking in the presence of static driving stresses. It is noted that lateral spreading typically occurs in sloping ground or level ground close to waterways (e.g. river banks, in the backfills behind quay walls, etc.). Even a very gentle slope in the ground (of just few degrees) creates a bias in the cyclic loads acting on the soil mass during an earthquake which drives the soil to move in the down-slope direction. When the underlying soil liquefies, the liquefied soil mass naturally moves down-slope and continues this movement until equilibrium is re-established (i.e. resisting forces reach the level of driving forces). Cubrinovski et al. (2012) reported maximum (relative)

magnitudes of permanent lateral ground displacements due to spreading of liquefied soils of the order 2.0-3.5m. The observed spatial distribution of spreading displacements was similar to that observed in the 1995 Kobe earthquake (Ishihara et al. 1997) and recommended by the empirical model of Tokimatsu and Asaka (1998).

Soil liquefaction also adversely affected the performance of many high-rise buildings in the Christchurch business district resulting in total and differential settlements, lateral displacements of foundations, tilt of buildings, and bearing failures (Cubrinovski et al. 2011; Aydan and Ulusay 2012; Cubrinovski et al. 2014). Liquefaction of shallow soils just beneath the foundations of buildings has been identified as the direct cause for excessive differential settlements of high-rise buildings on shallow foundations (Cubrinovski et al. 2014). According to Cubrinovski (2013), the total settlement exceeded 40.0-50.0cm, in the worst cases. Differential settlement resulted in permanent tilt of houses and often caused foundation and structural damage. Four different foundation types have been largely used in the Christchurch region for residential buildings, namely concrete slab on grade, timber floor with perimeter footing, piled foundations and more recently rib-raft or waffle slab with inverted beams. Both concrete slab and particularly older perimeter foundations suffered substantial liquefaction-induced damage because of inadequate stiffness, strength and liquefaction considerations in their design. The damage to the foundations was clearly related to and increased with the liquefaction severity (Cubrinovski 2013).

After the 2011 M_w 9.0 Great East Japan earthquake, ground settlements were predominant caused by the compaction of loose soils due to the strong ground shaking. Goda et al. (2013) observed significant settlements measuring 100.0mm or more which, however, did not affect the structural integrity of the buildings which were sited on deep foundations. Bhattacharya et al. (2011) and Yasuda et al. (2012) also reported many liquefaction-related failures to the built environment in the Tokyo bay area especially in the zones of reclaimed land, fill areas or sites having young alluvium. The residential buildings in Japan which were commonly built with strip footing foundations or mat foundations sustained substantial settlements and severe tilting. It is seen that the long duration effects of ground motion contributed significantly to the liquefaction-induced damage. Moreover, liquefaction susceptibility and the damage caused by liquefaction seemed to be dependent on the age and type of fill material as well as the type of ground improvement carried out.

In Greece, extensive liquefaction, ground settlements and lateral spreading occurred after the 2003 M_w 6.2 Lefkada earthquake causing failures in port and marine facilities and important but reparable damages attributed to excessive soil pressures and liquefaction at several small fishing ports. Quay walls were displaced seawards, backfill

region was settled, while mud was ejected, sometimes in the basement of modern RC buildings, indicating the emergence of liquefaction phenomena. These phenomena were related to the local ground conditions (recent formations of coastal, alluvial, and fluvial deposits) and the high water table depth (almost 0.7m below the ground surface). Liquefaction susceptibility along the shore is literally very high, as the N_{SPT} at the top 10.0m is lower than 10blows/ft and the soil is predominantly composed of saturated loose silty-sand below (Pitilakis and Roumelioti 2013, Margaris et al. 2003). Some buildings along the shoreline with strong pile foundations avoided the problems that raised from liquefaction. In addition, at the seafront in Lefkada town several buildings sustained a uniform foundation settlement, but as no differential settlements were involved, there was no imminent danger to the structural safety of the buildings. On the other hand, in some buildings near the coastal area where a differential settlement between adjacent buildings of 5.0-10.0cm was observed, there were not severe structural damages due to their relatively small mass, their “flexible” wooden frame, and, in the cases of RC buildings, their foundation type (mat foundation, tie or foundation beams) as reported by Margaris et al. (2003).

Liquefaction-induced lateral spreading triggered by the 2017 M_w 6.6 Bodrum-Kos, Aegean Sea earthquake caused severe structural damages at the city of Kos waterfront. In particular, Papathanassiou et al. (2019) documented that the new port of Kos and the custom buildings were strongly affected leading to the loss of their functionality. A subsidence of up to 35.0cm at the main pier and tilting of 6 degrees of the lighthouse, as well as cracks parallels to the seashore in the old harbour of the city behind the quay wall with horizontal displacement up to 10.0 cm and vertical offset up to 35.0 cm were also reported. The mechanism of the failure, similar to the one described by Cubrinovski et al. (2012), was first the retaining structure’s displacement towards the sea due to the ground shaking followed by lateral spreading in the backfills. Liquefaction manifestations were also reported in cape Louros (10.0 km epicentral distance), an area covered by Holocene age coastal deposits. Papathanassiou et al. (2019) also pointed out that similar phenomena with the ones reported in the waterfront area of the city of Kos are frequently documented on structures located on relevant areas worldwide.

2.5.3 Damage due to tsunamis

Recently, an unusually large number of damaging tsunamis, e.g. the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami, the 2006 Java tsunami, the 2006 Kuril Islands tsunami, the 2007 Solomon Islands tsunami, 2009 South Pacific tsunami, the 2010 Chilean Tsunami in Dichato, the 2010 Sumatra tsunami, the 2011 Great East Japan tsunami and the 2018 Java and Sumatra tsunami, among others (https://www.tsunami.gov/recent_tsunamis/)

has raised awareness of the tremendous forces and impact of tsunami on coastal structures, critical infrastructure and communities, with social and economic consequences. It should be noted that a considerable number of tsunamis have also been observed on the coasts of Greece and the surrounding areas. The oldest recorded and most known tsunamis in Greece are the one caused by the volcanic eruption in Santorini dated about to 1600 BCE and assumed to have caused severe damage to cities around it; most notably the Minoan civilization on Crete, and the other one occurred in 479 BCE, which destroyed a Persian army that was attacking the town of Potidaea in Greece. Further information on tsunamis in Greece can be found in [Smid \(1970\)](#) and [Papadopoulos and Chalkis \(1984\)](#).

Before the 2004 Indian Ocean earthquake and subsequent tsunami, the estimation of tsunami risk was severely limited due to the lack of quantitative field data from damaging tsunamis. Since 2004, several earthquake-induced tsunamis, capable of causing a substantial amount of damage and devastation, increased the research interest of scientific community in assessing possible tsunami damage. However, the fact that these tsunamis were generated by earthquakes of different magnitudes and source mechanisms leading to different types of forces acting on coastal infrastructure complicates the understanding of how tsunamis impact the structures. Structural damage from tsunamis may be attributed to the direct hydrostatic and hydrodynamic forces from tsunami wave height (inundation depth), the impact forces from water-borne debris, scour and slope/foundation failure and wind forces induced by wave motion.

Some of the most pronounced factors affecting the vulnerability of buildings subjected to tsunamis are the hazard level, the triggering mechanism (earthquake, volcanic eruption, submerged or aerial landslide), the tsunami wave height (inundation depth) and period, the coastal topography and the strength and stiffness characteristics of the exposed elements. According to [Tinti et al. \(2011\)](#), in most of the existing methods the direct damage to a building is defined only as a function of the flow depth, that is the height of the tsunami wave arriving at the building, considering that buildings should be differentiated according to their structural capacity. In other words, damage level to buildings depends on building type and inundation depth. As observed from historical tsunamis and damage caused to buildings, the damage extent due to tsunamis presents a large dispersion from slight non-structural to total collapse or even washed away condition, depending on the building characteristics and the tsunami's parameters.

The 26 December 2004 M_w 9.3 megathrust earthquake off the northwest coast of Sumatra in the Indian Ocean generated a catastrophic tsunami that ranged in general from 2.0 to 5.0m, reaching a maximum of 31.0m in Sumatra. In the near-field northwest and north Sumatra, tsunami compounded ground shaking damage, while in the far-field

the predominant cause of destruction was tsunami waves. Performance of buildings during the 2004 Indian Ocean Tsunami indicated that tsunami-generated wave and debris impact forces can have significant effects on structural behaviour. Engineered buildings were able to survive tsunami forces, especially if designed for them, while non-engineered buildings, including RC frames with masonry infills, confined masonry and timber framed buildings were at high risk depending on the characteristics of tsunami hydraulic and debris impact forces. [Saatçioğlu \(2009\)](#) also noted that designing buildings for seismic loads may not ensure safety under large magnitude tsunami events. In Sri Lanka and Thailand the degree of damage to buildings along the coast had a considerable variation. [Rossetto et al. \(2007\)](#) confirmed that this variation is partly due to structural resistance to lateral forces and partly due to differences in tsunami forces resulting from local variations in shoreline topography, bathymetry, coastal vegetation and the presence of coral formations. The four main causes of damage to buildings identified in the region were tsunami lateral water flow, tsunami wave loading, ground scour and debris impact, with the first two being the reason for the majority of structural damage.

The extent of damage in Sri Lanka and Thailand was also influenced by the construction type. Although low-rise timber framed buildings were able to withstand the moderate wind conditions commonly existing in the coastal areas, they seemed to be extremely vulnerable to tsunamis. Moreover, low-rise unreinforced masonry residential buildings, typically non-engineered, were those that suffered severe damage or totally collapsed. Structural failure was first attributed to the collapse of walls parallel to the sea, followed by the side walls and roof. Low-rise RC framed buildings, although usually non-engineered, fared better than the unreinforced masonry ones. However, most of them suffered damage to their infill walls and windows and a few suffered partial failure, mostly due to the presence of poor beam-column joint detailing. Finally, mid-rise (three to five stories) masonry infilled RC framed buildings, which compose the majority of buildings in southern Thailand, despite not being designed for earthquake loading ([Lukkunaprasit and Ruangsassamee 2005](#)), but only to resist the lateral loads imposed by wind, showed good structural performance. It should also be noted that although the well-built RC structures withstood the tsunami, they seemed to provide inadequate life-safety to their inhabitants, as the collapse of masonry infills and windows allowed water to flood the buildings thus reducing the possibility of escape for the building occupants ([Rossetto et al. 2007](#)).

The 2006 M_w 8.3 Kuril Islands tsunami hit the port of Crescent City in Del Norte County, California, with the largest surge amplitude being equal to 1.76m peak to trough. This event highlighted the vulnerability of ports subjected to a relatively modest tsunami. Strong current velocities caused damages in the Crescent City port, almost all

of them were to the floating docks of the port. [Barberopoulou et al. \(2008\)](#) alleged that moderate tsunamis such as the 2006 Kuril Islands tsunami are frequent and are able to cause substantial damage to ports through the generation of strong currents. Another tsunami caused after the 2010 M_w 8.8 Maule earthquake in Chile seriously affected the Talcahuano Bay. [Elnashai et al. \(2010\)](#) reported that a number of several buildings at the shorefront were damaged due to hydrodynamic loading of the waves carrying debris, as shown in Figure 2.16 (top) and the buildings of the Talcahuano port, which were mostly steel frame, were also damaged and rendered non-functional as shown in Figure 2.16 (bottom).

Field observations after the 2006 Java tsunami caused after an earthquake of M_w 7.7 also confirmed that the degree of damage observed was diverse, being primarily dependant on water depth and the building typology. [Reese et al. \(2007\)](#) reported that tsunami wave depths were typically 2.0 to 4.0m seriously damaging residential buildings. Again it was observed that older brick residential buildings suffered severe damage compared to newer ones with RC beams and columns and multi-storey hotels with heavier RC columns. In addition, the earthquake-induced 2009 South Pacific tsunami is another recent reminder of the destructive potential of tsunamis to coastal communities. [Reese et al. \(2011\)](#) observed that residential timber buildings were more fragile than masonry buildings, while RC buildings were less fragile than masonry buildings.

Figure 2.16. Effects of the tsunami ([Elnashai et al. 2010](#)). Damaged buildings at the shorefront in Talcahuano due to hydrodynamic loading (top) and of the Talcahuano port (bottom)

The tsunami triggered by the 2011 M_w 9.0 Great East Japan earthquake affected an extremely wide area and caused extensive damage along the Tohoku coastline, damaging coastal structures and hundreds of thousands of buildings. The inundation height and spatial extent of the Tohoku tsunami was unprecedented and far exceeded the design values. At Sendai Port, the inundation height varied between 4.0 and 7.0m maximum, affecting all port infrastructure (quay walls, ships, terminals, administrative buildings, warehouses including stock, and industry located in the port) and causing structural and non-structural damage. Breakwaters and seawalls easily overtopped, overturned, or broken up by the tsunami-induced hydrostatic and hydrodynamic forces and scour on a large scale, but did provide some degree of protection despite this damage, barriers were severely damaged, some RC buildings were totally destroyed, while inundation maps in several areas were severely underestimated (Fraser et al. 2013; Mori and Takahashi 2012). In addition to the tsunami hydraulic impact on structures, damage due to collision with the debris was also observed. Ships that broke their moorings due to tsunami wave height and began drifting were a major source of damage. Thus, for disaster prevention purposes it is very important to predict the drifting motion of a large ship driven by tsunami current (Suga et al. 2013). RC shear wall structures were confirmed as able to withstand tsunami loading and Fraser et al. (2013) suggested they should form the primary construction type for critical infrastructure in high tsunami hazard areas. The influence of structural material and number of stories on building damage due to tsunami has been highlighted in a number of studies, such as Ruangrassamee et al. (2006), Dominey-Howes and Papatoma (2007), Reese et al. (2007, 2011), Koshimura et al. (2009), Leone et al. (2011), Valencia et al. (2011) and Suppasri et al. (2011), (2013) and (2015). They agreed that RC and steel buildings showed better resistant performance over wood or masonry ones as well as that mid and high-rise buildings (higher than two stories) were confirmed to be much stronger than low-rise buildings (one to two stories).

Recently in Greece, after the 2003 M_w 6.2 Lefkada earthquake, a very small tsunami, no more than 0.5m, hit in Vlychos Baysouth of Nydri and caused minor damage to boats and coastline construction as reported by Margaris et al. (2003). Furthermore, a tsunami wave after the 2017 M_w 6.6 Bodrum-Kos, Aegean Sea earthquake, with a maximum run-up height measured equal to 1.9m at Bodrum area, was reported by Yalçiner et al. (2017), indicating that the generation of tsunami related phenomena is likely in the Aegean Sea. The tsunami effects were observed at the south coast of Bodrum peninsula and at the northeast coast of Kos Island. In particular, according to Yalçiner et al. (2017) the tsunami-related main effects were localised in Gumbet Bay, Bodrum Peninsula, Turkey, while no damage occurred in the next bay (Bitez bay at West and Bodrum

marina at East of Gumbet bay). Most of the damage due to tsunami occurred in the port, where several boats were relocated or damaged by hitting each other or against the port infrastructure. In the island of Kos, the port rendered temporarily useless due to damage in the dock, while less damage was present in the old port of Kos, as the tsunami height reported in the coast outside the city and in the old port of the city was less than 1.0m (Yalçiner et al. 2017). In general, it should be noted that all port infrastructure is at risk from tsunami impact, even if it is of moderate intensity (inundation depth), due to their heightened exposure compared to other structures.

2.5.4 Lessons learned from past earthquake-induced hazards

Recent seismic events have highlighted the potential for disastrous natural-hazard impact on buildings and critical infrastructure, with severe consequences, which in several cases exceeded the local or national scale, ranging from health and environmental impacts to major economic losses due to structural damage and business interruption. The analysis of past earthquake-induced hazards has contributed enormously to the improved scientific understanding of them and their impact across different building typologies and underlined some common lessons learned, crucial to reduce the impact of future events. Besides, most building code changes and improvements have been the result of field observations of earthquake damage.

Naeim and Lew (2000) summarised the key earthquake engineering principles, learned from recent earthquakes, but which continue to be ignored many times leading to many fatalities, injuries and significant damage every year. The major lessons learned causing devastation of the built environment are related to two geotechnical failures (improper land-use and inadequate zoning regulations, and improper construction on liquefiable soil) as well as other eight structural failures all related to the design and construction of buildings to resist ground shaking (soft-storey building configurations, poor material quality, poor structural detailing, ignoring torsional response, weak-column/strong-floor configurations, lack of adequate loading, ignoring the influence of 'non-lateral resisting components' on building response, lack of adequate correlation between the building as analysed and designed and the building as built).

It is essential buildings be designed against ground shaking and show ductile behaviour even under extreme dynamic loading conditions. Unreinforced masonry and non-ductile RC buildings were the main structure typologies that suffered heavy damage during significant earthquakes, such as 2008 Wenchuan, 2010 Haiti, 2010 Chile, 2011 Christchurch, 2011 Tohoku, among others. Steps should be followed to ensure that only ductile detailing be used in all new buildings, especially in moderate and severe seismic zones regardless of the lateral forces used for design, as well as in the repair of damaged

ones. Moreover, “soft-storey” mechanisms as well as “short columns” should be checked and avoided in new buildings, while irregularities in plan and elevation should require special care in design. In the construction phase also special attention should be paid, as poor construction practice and lack of quality control can lead to severe damage or collapse. Another issue that deserves special attention in seismic design and post-earthquake response and reconstruction is the cumulative and progressive weakening of buildings that experience successive earthquakes that can lead to eventual collapse.

Widespread liquefaction, lateral spreading or ground failure was found to be another key contributor to poor building performance. Where liquefaction can be an issue, when the soil is found to be susceptible to liquefaction, implementing appropriate countermeasures against ground liquefaction and lateral spreading can effectively increase the seismic performance of buildings resting on it. However, when remediation measures cannot be implemented for economic reasons, mat foundations are recommended to be used for buildings on liquefiable soils to avoid differential displacements which are the main cause of structural damage of buildings on liquefiable areas. Especially for buildings on areas with steep topography and slopes appropriate safety measures are essential against lateral spreading. Even if seismic design code changed to account for ground failure or liquefaction phenomena, a more consistent soil-structure interaction analysis may be needed.

Regarding tsunami hazard, timber and unreinforced masonry buildings were generally found to be vulnerable against high tsunami waves and construction of such structures should be refrained in tsunami-prone areas. On the contrary RC and steel buildings should be preferred, as they showed better resistant performance to tsunami forces. Moreover, the design of vertical evacuation buildings with breakaway walls or open construction in the lower levels is recommended to allow water to pass through with minimal resistance. Field observations also confirmed that RC shear wall structures are able to withstand tsunami. However, for the design of vertical evacuation structures, shear walls should be oriented parallel to the anticipated direction of tsunami flow to reduce associated tsunami forces. Special attention should also be paid to an adequate tsunami warning system. It is noticed that the heavy tsunami casualties during the 2004 Indian Ocean event was attributed to the absence of a warning system, while the higher than normal casualties during the 2011 Great East Japan event was due to the unusually high tsunami run-up height in the region and the relatively short time window available for evacuation of people from the low-lying areas.

The concurrent and/or secondary hazards of an earthquake, such as ground shaking, liquefaction, tsunami, should always be considered in the areas of high levels of these hazards. Especially for major earthquakes, there is a high risk of multiple and

simultaneous impacts at a single infrastructure or to several infrastructure over a potentially large area, that can cause structural damage or affect non-structural components. The severity of some of the analysed seismic events was unexpected, indicating an underestimation of the risk that resulted in siting in natural-hazard prone areas, insufficient design and a lack of preparedness. In order to refrain potential disasters, the vulnerability of key critical infrastructure to natural hazards should be determined. Risk analysis coupled with a cost-benefit analysis is required to better understand system weaknesses and to prioritise prevention and mitigation measures. Smart and low-cost instrumentation for buildings monitoring is also desirable for both earthquake resistant design and evaluation of local site effects in the context of sustainable building development.

Regarding the maritime sector, although awareness of the risks is increasing the last decades, the port emergency planning to natural hazards is still insufficient. Therefore, reliable, advanced and standardised tools for vulnerability and risk assessment of port infrastructure are an urgent need of paramount importance. These tools will enable port stakeholders to efficiently allocate the available resources toward more resilient ports, including maintenance, repair, risk reduction measures and contingency planning.

Finally, particularly critical buildings, such as schools, emergency-response facilities, port infrastructure, should be designed and maintained at higher seismic standard, as well as located or retrofitted to meet the requirement of maintaining their function after an earthquake. Although the existing seismic design approach, developed to allow for ductility of buildings to resist large earthquakes economically and provide safety against collapse, has been effective in terms of protecting people, it may not be sufficient for modern, complex and resilient societies. After recent large earthquakes, it has been observed that many properly designed and constructed buildings, which did not collapse, were no longer functional and were later flattened rather than being repaired. If most buildings in large cities are designed under this design approach, they would be badly damaged in future large earthquakes, and the cities would have difficulties in recovery activities and could experience catastrophic loss of function. Considering such situations, [Takagi and Wada \(2017\)](#) proposed that the seismic design philosophy for building and infrastructure be changed from life-safety to post-earthquake business continuity for modern, sustainable and resilient societies, and buildings be designed to be quickly restored to full operation with minimal disruption and cost after a large earthquake.

Chapter 3

Principles of seismic risk assessment

3.1 Introduction

This chapter provides a review of the principles of seismic risk assessment. It includes a brief description of the components of seismic risk assessment as well as a short review of the past and current research on this field. An outline of the parameters and available methods to derive fragility functions is also provided, as they are used for the seismic risk assessment of buildings at urban and regional scale. The aim of this chapter is to contribute to the knowledge and better understanding of the main factors governing the current practice in seismic vulnerability and risk assessment.

3.2 Risk for a single element

Nowadays, modern societies become more complex and more sophisticated. However, they are still vulnerable, although the seismic provisions have been considerably improved. Thus, an integrated seismic risk assessment and loss estimation are of fundamental importance not only for predicting the economic impact of future earthquakes, but also for decision-making on reduction or mitigation of earthquake-induced risk, as they define accurately the physical seismic risk and the socio-economic vulnerability and resilience. Physical seismic risk can be defined as the probability of expected damages and losses to structures and people (fatalities and casualties, damage of buildings, economic activity disrupted) resulting from seismic hazards. Conceptually, seismic risk can be defined as the convolution of seismic hazard, vulnerability and exposure with the following basic formulation:

$$\text{Seismic Risk} = \text{Seismic Hazard} \otimes \text{Vulnerability} \otimes \text{Exposure} \quad (3.1)$$

Seismic Hazard can be defined as the probability of occurrence of a specified level of ground shaking within a specified period of time and within a given area. A more general definition includes not only ground shaking but also earthquake-related surface faulting, liquefaction, landslides, tectonic deformation, and tsunamis. Vulnerability can be defined

as the degree of loss to a given element or set of elements at risk exposed to a specified hazard of given characteristics. The vulnerability can be calculated in a probabilistic or a deterministic way for a single structure or groups of structures. Exposure in the equation above expresses the value (or cost) of the element at risk. Resilience is the capacity of a society and economy to cope with earthquake events.

Seismic hazard and vulnerability are defined conceptually in an independent manner for methodological reasons and for a better comprehension of risk. Thus, in order to reduce the risk, one or two of the components of risk should be altered. However, in many cases seismic hazard is not possible to be modified and there is nothing left but modify the conditions of vulnerability of the exposed elements at risk. This is the reason why literature in the field of vulnerability and vulnerability reduction as a measure of prevention mitigation has received significant attention, although what is really intended by this is risk reduction ([Cardona 2004](#)).

In the last few decades, the field of seismic risk assessment and loss estimation has remarkably developed. A loss model aims to estimate the seismic hazard at the site of interest and to convolve this hazard with the vulnerability of the exposed building stock, predicting finally the damage ratios, which relate the cost of repair to the cost of replacement of the buildings. Thus, it is acknowledged that a significant component of a loss model is a methodology to assess the vulnerability of the built environment ([Calvi et al. 2006](#)). Figure 3.1 shows the components of seismic risk assessment and a range of options for the vulnerability assessment procedure according to [Calvi et al. \(2006\)](#). They claimed that the various vulnerability assessment methods proposed in the past for use in loss estimation can be divided into two main categories, empirical or analytical, both of which can be used in hybrid methods. There are two main types of empirical methods for the seismic vulnerability assessment of buildings that are based on the damage observed after earthquakes, damage probability matrices (DPM) and vulnerability functions. [Whitman et al. \(1973\)](#) first proposed the use of DPM for the probabilistic prediction of damage to buildings from earthquakes, which express in a discrete form the conditional probability $P [D = j | i]$ to obtain a damage level j due to a ground shaking of intensity i . Vulnerability functions are relations expressing in a continuous form the damage as a function of parameters that describe the intensity of the earthquake and the vulnerability index ([Benedetti and Petrini 1984](#)). In addition, the Capacity Spectrum Method (CSM), first introduced by [Freeman et al. \(1975\)](#) as a rapid evaluation procedure in a pilot project for assessing seismic vulnerability of buildings, as well as a fully displacement-based vulnerability assessment framework, initially proposed by [Calvi \(1999\)](#) that used displacements as the fundamental indicator of damage and a spectral representation of the earthquake demand, can also be used within a risk assessment study.

Figure 3.1. The components of seismic risk assessment and choices for the vulnerability assessment procedure (modified after Calvi et al. 2006)

Developments of the methodology proposed by Calvi (1999) for RC buildings were made by Pinho et al. (2002) and Crowley et al. (2004; 2006), leading to the Displacement-Based Earthquake Loss Assessment (DBELA) procedure, while for masonry buildings, a parallel extensive development was carried out by Restrepo-Vélez and

Magenes (2004), Restrepo-Vélez (2005), and Modena et al. (2005) leading to the Mechanical Based Procedure for the Seismic Risk Estimation of Unreinforced Masonry Buildings (MeBaSe). Existing methodologies used for the seismic risk analyses of buildings and urban areas are also discussed by Barbat et al. (2010).

The necessity of reliable models capable of estimating losses in future earthquake-induced hazards has been widely recognised by emergency planners and insurance industries. The development of such a sophisticated loss model for a given region is not only of interest for predicting the economic impact of future earthquakes but can also be of importance for risk mitigation. A loss model can be used to mitigate risk through the reduction of the vulnerability of structures, that can be achieved through the calibration of seismic codes for the design of new buildings as well as through retrofitting schemes examined conducting cost/benefit studies for different types of structures. It should be noted that, usually, in loss assessment methodologies strong ground shaking is the only hazard considered. Calvi et al. (2006) suggested earthquake loss models ideally include all the possible earthquake-induced hazards, i.e. amplified ground shaking, liquefaction, surface fault rupture, landslides and tsunamis.

3.2.1 Earthquake losses: direct and indirect

An integrated loss estimation requires comprehensive analysis of the effect of the geophysical event on the built environment and subsequently on the economy, including estimates of the direct and indirect damage and social/economic loss. Direct damage comprises structural (i.e. damage to the load bearing structural elements of a building) and non-structural damage (i.e. to non-load bearing components, building contents, etc.) and is usually classified into descriptive damage states ranging from “none” to “complete”, while indirect damage is a secondary effect of the damage to buildings. Direct economic loss is typically measured by the cost of repair or replacement of damaged buildings and direct losses due to disruption of businesses and can be calculated only from the building damage. In addition, loss of life is obviously the most significant direct social loss, primarily related to collapse of buildings. Over 75% of earthquake-related fatalities are caused by building collapse, while if secondary disasters are excluded, building collapse causes almost 90% of earthquake-related deaths (Coburn and Spence 2002).

Indirect economic loss is due to the effects of the disruption of the damaged buildings on the undamaged enterprises to conduct business. Indirect economic loss as well as other social losses including casualties, short- and long-term homelessness and disruption to schooling and employment are extremely difficult to quantify, as they are

dependent on many variables, such the time of the event occurrence, the income of the affected households, etc.

3.2.2 Earthquake loss estimation methods for buildings

Following the 1971 M_w 6.6 San Fernando earthquake in United States (Lew et al. 1971), where many old (pre-1933) buildings were either severely damaged or totally collapsed, many research efforts were launched to better comprehend the causes of the seismic failures and identify ways to mitigate potential damages and losses. Much of the early work on regional earthquake loss estimation was conducted in the western USA, particularly California. The first earthquake loss estimation was carried out by Algermissen et al. (1972) with a study by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Agency for San Francisco. Between 1972 and the early 1990s, an extensive array of loss estimation methods was developed but there were relatively little in the way of practical application (Reitherman 1985). In 1985, ATC-13 (ATC 1985), one of the most influential publications, set a new standard through its methodology for the evaluation of earthquake damage caused by ground shaking and collateral hazards. However, the main drawback of this methodology was the lack of field observational data to correlate evaluated losses. Thus, ATC-13 relied almost entirely upon expert judgement.

The development of fragility functions for seismic risk assessment also started in the early 1990s. Since 1994, efforts led by the U.S. Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) and the National Institute of Building Services (NIBS) were focused on the derivation of a comprehensive methodology, implemented in GIS, which resulted in HAZUS (NIBS 2004). HAZUS is the first comprehensive methodology that describes the models for estimating potential losses of buildings from earthquake hazards at an urban scale. Its first edition was released in 1997, while the current version (Hazus-MH) estimates losses due to earthquakes, floods, hurricanes and more recently tsunamis. In the first editions, the majority of the fragility functions were relied on the methodology and data that were presented in ATC-13 (ATC 1985) following an expert judgment approach, while studies have been later considered for buildings and the fragility curves in HAZUS were finally partly empirically based and partly developed from expert opinion (Porter 2003).

In Europe, the first initiative to establish a methodology for the seismic risk assessment of buildings include the RISK-UE (2001-2004) project followed by LESSLOSS (2004-2007) project, both funded by European Commission framework programs for Research and Technological Development. In the framework of these projects, fragility curves for buildings were proposed by establishing a new taxonomy appropriate for the European context. In addition, several research efforts were made at a national level in

Europe, aiming to propose adequate generic fragility curves for buildings, such as the [SRM-LIFE \(2003-2007\)](#) project in Greece and the [RELUIS\(2003-2013\)](#) project in Italy. Finally, a large number of other research efforts were performed worldwide, developing fragility functions and vulnerability assessment methods for different physical assets.

Among the latest developments is [SYNER-G \(2009-2013\)](#) project, funded by European Commission in the frame of 7th Framework Programme (FP7). In the framework of the project, an integrated methodology and tools were developed for the systemic seismic vulnerability and risk analysis of complex systems, such as buildings, lifelines, transportation and utility networks, gas and electric power systems, critical facilities, and infrastructure exposed to earthquake hazard. SYNER-G methodology encompassed in an integrated way all aspects in the chain, from hazard to the physical vulnerability and loss assessment of components and systems and to the socio-economic impacts of earthquakes, accounting for all relevant uncertainties within an efficient quantitative simulation scheme, modelling interactions between the multiple components and systems, as they may increase considerably the global vulnerability and risk of the whole system. Within the project, some studies, that can be found in [Pitilakis et al. \(2014b\)](#), were carried out in selected sites (urban scale) and systems to validate the methodology and the proposed fragility functions ([Pitilakis et al. 2014a](#)).

3.3 Seismic Hazard

The definition of the seismic hazard is definitely the primary input in a risk analysis framework. Seismic hazard refers to an uncertain relationship between the intensity of a seismic event and the frequency or probability of a specific location experiencing at least that intensity of seismic event and can be quantified in several ways. One is through a hazard curve, which is the result of a process disseminated with epistemic uncertainties, such as the subdivision in homogeneous seismic sources, their activity in terms of magnitudes and frequencies, their spatial dimension, the attenuation relations functional form, etc. ([Pitilakis et al. 2014a](#)). A hazard curve is commonly depicted as a function of the event intensity at a site and the exceedance probability in a specified period of time or exceedance rate in events per unit time.

For the estimation of seismic hazard, the theorem of total probability can be applied to combine the uncertain ground shaking at the site caused by a specific fault rupture and the occurrence frequency or probability of that rupture. The uncertain ground shaking given a fault rupture can be quantified using an attenuation relationship or a ground-motion prediction equation (GMPE). The ground shaking intensity depends on the earthquake source, the travel effects of the wave and the local site conditions. The effects of the wave travel path include the distance from the earthquake source to the

site of interest as well as the geology through which the seismic waves propagate, including soil amplification, liquefaction and landslides. Especially local soil conditions may considerably influence the ground shaking level on ground surface. Therefore, the estimation of hazard is usually conducted for rock-site conditions and the incorporation of site effects is achieved through appropriate soil amplification factors. Detailed soil maps for the regions of interest are also necessary to account for local site conditions.

It is worth noting that for the sites that are susceptible to ground failure, the definition of seismic hazard is preferred to be scenario-based rather than based on probabilistic seismic hazard assessment, as local site conditions are usually uncertain (especially V_{s30} , liquefaction potential, landslide potential), except for the sites where data from boreholes exist. However, even in such cases, ground water depth can fluctuate seasonally affecting liquefaction susceptibility. Earthquake magnitude, its duration and the source-to-site distance are fundamentally important variables required for the estimation of liquefaction potential and the resulting ground deformations. Therefore, despite the additional computational expense it entails, a scenario-based approach, which explicitly defines the magnitude and distances, is essential (Bird et al 2006).

In general, a hazard model aims to provide tools for sampling events in terms of location (epicentre) and possibly extension, magnitude and faulting style according to the seismicity of the study region and for predicting maps of seismic intensities, conditional on magnitude, epicentre, etc. that describe the variability and spatial correlation of intensities at different sites (Pitilakis et al. 2013).

3.4 Vulnerability

As seen above, a critical component of the chain of seismic risk assessment of a structure is the definition and evaluation of its vulnerability. Vulnerability models are required in loss estimation methods in order to define the range of behaviour expected for a given building classification subject to a specific level of hazard. The seismic vulnerability of a structure is described in all engineering-relevant approaches using fragility and/or vulnerability functions.

Fragility functions provide the probability of exceeding different limit states (e.g. physical damage or injury levels) given a level of ground shaking, while vulnerability functions describe the probability of losses (e.g. social or economic) given a level of ground shaking. The former relates the level of ground shaking with the probability of exceeding the limit states, whereas the latter relates the level of ground motion with the damage index, ID (e.g. ratio repair cost to replacement cost).

Figure 3.2 illustrates four fragility curves for four different damage states. The conditional probabilities $P[ds=i | IM]$ for a structure experiencing a particular damage state ds_i can be estimated based on the probabilities of exceedance $P[ds \geq i | IM]$.

Figure 3.2. Example of fragility curves

For example, using the fragility curves shown in Figure 3.2, the probabilities that a structure experiences the different damage states can be calculated as:

$$P_0(=\text{no damage})=1.0-P(ds \geq \text{slight damage})$$

$$P_1(=\text{slight damage})= P(ds \geq \text{slight damage}) - P(ds \geq \text{moderate damage})$$

$$P_2(=\text{moderate damage})= P(ds \geq \text{moderate damage}) - P(ds \geq \text{extensive damage})$$

$$P_3(=\text{extensive damage})= P(ds \geq \text{extensive damage}) - P(ds \geq \text{complete damage})$$

$$P_4(=\text{complete damage})= P(ds \geq \text{complete damage})$$

The total sum of these probabilities is equal to 1.

A vulnerability function can be derived from fragility functions using consequence functions, which describe the probability of loss, conditional on the damage state (Pitilakis et al. 2014a). In Figure 3.3 a graphical representation of an example vulnerability curve is presented.

Figure 3.3. Example of a vulnerability curve

3.4.1 Methodologies for the definition of vulnerability

The methodologies that are available in the literature for the definition of vulnerability of buildings exposed to earthquake-induced hazards can be classified into four generic categories; empirical, expert elicitation, analytical and hybrid, based on the input damage data (Pitilakis et al. 2014a), whether they come from damage statistics from past earthquakes (Spence et al. 1992; Sabetta et al. 1998; Rossetto and Elnashai 2003), expert judgement (ATC 1985), analysis of appropriate mechanical models (Dymiotis et al. 1999), or combinations of these (Kappos et al. 2006), respectively. Each approach has associated strengths and weaknesses.

In empirical procedures, various effects such as SSI, site effects, the earthquake source and path characteristics as well as the variability in the structural capacity of a group of buildings and the mechanisms which govern the failure modes, are intrinsically accounted through the use of real observations of damage. However, this may be simultaneously a drawback, as the empirical curves are derived for a given area and remain specific to a particular seismo-tectonic, geotechnical and built-environment. In addition, the most common problem is the unavailability of sufficient and reliable statistical data for several intensities. The infrequency of large magnitude earthquake events near densely populated areas, leads to a relative abundance of statistical data in the intensity range from 6.0 to 8.0 and a lack of data for higher intensities. The use of these data results to large uncertainties and difficulties for the selection of an appropriate cumulative distribution, since the curve fit error is remarkable and the curve shape not as anticipated. Moreover, data including observed damage due to multiple earthquakes

or damage as a consequence of phenomena other than ground shaking (e.g. ground failure, landslides, flooding, etc.) introduce errors that cannot be removed via manipulation of the damage statistics and a large data scatter may ensue even in cases where a single event and limited survey area are considered (e.g. Orsini 1999). Rossetto et al. (2015) provided an extensive review of the state-of-art in the construction of empirical vulnerability and fragility functions for buildings worldwide, highlighting the large variation in the empirical fragility assessment approaches that are available in the literature, which result from differences in the observed damage database used, the chosen functional forms to fit to the data, the selected ground motion intensity measure as well as the statistical modelling technique used.

Expert elicitation procedures entirely rely on the judgment of appointed experts with experience in the field of earthquake engineering who are asked to provide an estimate of the probable damage distribution of a given element at risk when subjected to earthquake-induced hazards of different intensities. Expert judgement constitutes the predominant source used by most current rehabilitation codes in the United States of America, such as ATC (1985) and ATC (1996), for the generation of damage probability matrices and vulnerability curves. Also, HAZUS (NIBS 2004) provides fragility curves due to ground failure for extensive/complete building damage in terms of permanent ground displacement, principally based on expert judgment, while a recent effort to revive the use of expert judgment-based methods has been carried out within the Global Earthquake Model (www.globalquakemodel.org). These techniques are not affected by the absence of extensive damage data or the reliability of the analytical structural model, are versatile and relatively fast to derive, and include all the factors affecting the seismic response of different structures, since the experts are able to provide damage estimates for any structural typology. These methods are really useful in areas that there are no damage data from past events or low level of engineering expertise. However, their main drawback is the difficulty to extrapolate their results in other countries with different engineering and construction practice. Moreover, the reliability of expert judgment-based methods is questionable due to their dependence on the individual experience and number of the experts consulted. To properly reduce the potential bias, attention to clear definitions, assumptions, and expert qualifications is required (Porter et al. 2007).

Analytical methods are essentially based on the estimation of the damage distributions through numerical modelling (e.g. Ptilakis et al. 2014c; Karapetrou et al. 2015; Fotopoulou et al. 2018; Karafagka et al. 2018a; 2018b) of a structure's response subjected to an earthquake-induced hazard. They offer a higher level of detail and result in a reduced bias and increased reliability of the vulnerability estimations for different structures compared to the previous ones. Especially nowadays, with the recent

developments of reliable numerical analysis tools, which include a number of response features, such as shear-flexure-axial interaction, SSI effect, interactive confinement on concrete members and reinforcing bar buckling, as well as with the expansion of computational power, analytical approaches become even more attractive for the estimation of vulnerability of a structure in terms of ease and efficiency. For numerical modelling of buildings, there are two widely used methods to capture the nonlinear structural behaviour, namely plastic hinge modelling (i.e. concentrated inelasticity) and fibre element modelling (i.e. distributed plasticity). The Capacity Spectrum Method (CSM) and the general Dynamic Analysis constitute the two most popular analytical methodologies used for the vulnerability assessment of buildings. More recently, the Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) has also risen to offer comprehensive evaluation of the seismic performance and vulnerability of structures.

In particular, the CSM can be used to approximate the performance level of a building subjected to ground shaking, as it provides simple and reasonably accurate means of predicting inelastic building displacement response for damage estimation purposes. The method compares the capacity of a building with the demands of the ground motion on the building. Capacity is defined as a function of yield strength, stiffness, and ductility. The later force resisting capacity of the building is represented by a force-displacement curve, which is obtained based on non-linear static (pushover) analysis. An example building capacity curve is shown in Figure 3.4. The use of capacity curves to assess the vulnerability of an element at risk (i.e. RC building) is described in detail in the HAZUS methodology (NIBS 2004). Design, yield, and ultimate capacity points define the shape of each building capacity curve. Design capacity represents the nominal building strength required by current model seismic code provisions or an estimate of the nominal strength for buildings not designed for earthquake loads. Yield capacity represents the true lateral strength of the building considering redundancies in design, conservatism in code requirements and true (rather than nominal) strength of materials, while ultimate capacity represents the maximum strength of the building when the global structural system has reached a fully plastic state. It is noted that ultimate capacity implicitly accounts for loss of strength due to shear failure of brittle elements. Typically, buildings are assumed capable of deforming beyond their ultimate point without loss of stability, but their structural system provides no additional resistance to seismic lateral forces (NIBS 2004). The demands of the ground motion are represented by response spectra curves at various levels of viscous damping. When these two curves (capacity curve and demand spectrum) are plotted on the same set of coordinates, the displacement at which the demand curve (modified for inelastic behaviour) and capacity curves intersect,

referred to as the “performance point”, provides an estimate of the response and performance levels of the building.

Figure 3.4. Example of a building Capacity Curve

Regarding dynamic analyses, they are often used to define vulnerability for individual elements (e.g. specific buildings) allowing the aleatory variability associated with the earthquake ground motion to be modelled. They are able to reproduce most accurately in most cases the seismic response of typical civil engineering structures. In particular, the seismic demand on structural models is estimated based on numerous nonlinear dynamic analyses with a series of acceleration time-histories. Probabilistic Seismic Demand Analysis (PSDA) and Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) are the two methods often used to formulate the demand model. The former method attempts to represent seismicity through a wide selection of ground motions, while the latter one achieves the same by stepwise increment of a few ground motion records.

It should be noted that the selection of appropriate ground motion records is of paramount importance for the reliable evaluation of the seismic response, as the quantity and the distribution of intensity measures in the sample of records significantly affect the fragility parameters (both the standard deviation and the median). Usually, the studied building typology is restricted to a given geographical area, which allows adequate time-histories based on specified intervals of magnitude, source-to-site distance and possibly other scenario characteristics, such as focal depth and mechanism to be selected (e.g. Bommer and Acevedo 2004). For this purpose, strong ground motion records from European and international databases and special software such as REXEL (Iervolino et al. 2010) and REXEL-DISP (Smerzini et al. 2012) can be used. In the record selection and analysis processes it is important to consider records with possible special features, such as near-source directivity pulses. Such records must be appropriately accounted for, since the results can be significantly different than those for records further from the

source. Moreover, for the cases where SSI is taken into account and both soil and structure are modelled in a coupled system, the input motion is normally introduced at bedrock and therefore it should refer to rock conditions, as the SSI model directly captures site effects.

Incremental dynamic analysis (IDA) is a promising computer-intensive parametric analysis method, that has recently emerged in several different forms, which involves the performing of a series of nonlinear dynamic analyses under a suite of multiple scaled ground motion records, whose intensities should be ideally selected to cover the entire range of response, from elasticity to global dynamic instability (Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2002). IDA curves of the structural response provide a relationship between a damage measure quantity (i.e. engineering demand parameter, *EDP*), e.g. peak roof drift ratio θ_{roof} or θ_{max} , and the ground motion intensity level measured by an intensity measure, *IM*, e.g. peak ground acceleration, *PGA*, or the 5%-damped first-mode spectral acceleration, $S_a(T_1, 5\%)$. They can be generated by interpolating the resulting EDP-IM discrete points. As an example, indicative plots of fifteen continuous IDA curves derived by interpolation of the $S_a(T_1, 5\%)$ - θ_{max} pairs for each individual record and the associated Collapse Prevention (CP) limit-state capacities for a nine-storey RC MRF building are presented in Figure 3.5. The reliability of the procedure relies primarily on the proper formation of the nonlinear structural model, the compilation of a suite of records, as well as on the selection of efficient EDPs and IMs. In addition, the selection of the scaling levels for each record as well as the post processing of the IDA analysis results need special attention. The records scaling may provide good estimates of the distribution of EDP given IM provided that their statistical relationship is effectively independent of magnitude *M* and source-to-site distance *R* in the range of interest. In spite of the relatively large computational efforts involved, the fragility curves developed by means of dynamic analyses or IDA are able to reproduce most accurately in most cases the seismic response of typical civil engineering structures (Pitilakis et al 2014a).

Figure 3.5. IDA curves for the individual records and the estimation of the associated limit-state capacities for CP limit state

In general, inelastic analysis, either static (pushover) or dynamic (time-history) is the most appropriate approach to investigate the deformation capacity and estimate the seismic vulnerability of a structure. Nevertheless, dynamic analysis requires several assumptions regarding the selection of an appropriate suite of ground motions and is also time-consuming due to the high number of numerical calculations involved. As a general remark, the analytical method that is followed for the definition of vulnerability is related to the nature of each element at risk, the availability of resources and the reliability of the analytical tools.

Finally, hybrid vulnerability approaches attempt to compensate for the scarcity of observational data, subjectivity of judgmental data and modelling deficiencies of analytical methods by combining data from different sources. Examples of hybrid-based curves typically involve the modification of analytical or judgement-based formulation with observational data. For example, [Singhal and Kiremedjian \(1998\)](#) presented a method for combining analytical fragility curves with observed building damage data from earthquakes using Bayesian statistical analysis. [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#) proposed fragility curves for RC and unreinforced masonry buildings developing a method starting from available damage statistics (appropriate for the area and structural typology under consideration) and estimating damage at the intensities for which no data were available using nonlinear analysis of typical structures. More recently, [Jaiswal and Wald \(2010\)](#) within the PAGER project attempted hybridization between empirical, expert elicitation and analytical methods to develop a global building inventory for earthquake loss assessment.

3.4.2 Fragility Functions

Fragility of an element at risk constitutes one of the key elements of seismic risk assessment and is usually expressed through fragility curves for each structure typology. In the evaluation of structural performance, it is convenient to describe the structure's performance in terms of demand and capacity. The demand can be defined in terms of different response parameters in the structural system, such as drift, strain, shear, ductility, bending moment, displacement, velocity, acceleration, energy dissipation etc., caused by the applied hazard, while the capacity of the structural system is the maximum forces or response that the system can withstand without member or system failure. Fragility assessment is made for a particular characterization of the earthquake-induced hazard, which represents the demand of the hazard on the building. Therefore, the definition of two intermediate variables is required, one describing the ground motion intensity measure (IM), which should correlate the hazard with the damage to the

building, and the other describing the structural demand, also known as engineering demand parameter (EDP).

In these terms, fragility simply defines the conditional probability, $P[..]$, of the seismic demand, D , placed upon the structure exceeding its capacity, C , for a given level of hazard intensity (IM), as shown in the following equation:

$$\text{Fragility} = P[D \geq C \mid \text{IM}] \quad (3.2)$$

Fragility curves relate the hazard intensity to the probability of reaching or exceeding a level of damage (e.g. minor, moderate, extensive, collapse) for an element at risk. Different mathematical approaches for developing fragility curves have been proposed in the literature (e.g. ATC 1985; Shinozuka et al. 2000; Cornell et al. 2002; NIBS 2004; Nielson and DesRoches 2007; Porter et al. 2007; D'Ayala et al. 2015; etc.). The determination of an appropriate statistical distribution is of paramount importance to deal with various sources of uncertainty. A two-parameter lognormal distribution function is usually adopted due to its simple parametric form (Shinozuka et al. 2000) to represent a fragility curve for a predefined damage/limit state, as in the following equation:

$$P[d_s \geq ds_i \mid \text{IM}] = \Phi \left[\frac{1}{\beta_{\text{tot}}} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{\text{IM}}{\text{IM}_{mi}} \right) \right] \quad (3.3)$$

where $P[..]$ denotes the probability of being at or exceeding a particular damage state ds_i for a given hazard intensity level defined by the hazard intensity measure IM (e.g. *inundation depth* for tsunami hazard, *peak ground acceleration (PGA)* for ground shaking, *differential displacements* for liquefaction hazard, etc.), Φ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function, IM_{mi} is the median threshold value of the hazard intensity measure IM required to cause the i th damage state and β_{tot} is the total standard deviation. Thus, the definition of two parameters is required, namely IM_{mi} and β_{tot} , in order to develop fragility curves.

In the framework of SYNER-G project (<http://www.vce.at/SYNER-G/>), the Fragility Function Manager (FFM) tool has been developed to store, visualize and manage a large number of fragility function sets not only for buildings but also for bridges and other elements at risk. A detailed description of the FFM tool and its features can be found in Ptilakis et al. (2014a). Each fragility function is accompanied by metadata to allow the user to compare and select the functions of interest. For buildings, the general metadata provided for each study includes the reference, the region of applicability, the typology of the building considered, the SYNER-G taxonomy, the methodology used to develop the fragility functions, the intensity measure type, the damage scale, as well as other notes and comments on the analysed study. With FFM tool users are able to easily obtain standardised sets of the available fragility functions that contain all the parameters required for their use in seismic risk assessment.

The main methodological parameters that are involved in the derivation of fragility functions are taxonomy/typology/classification, performance levels and damage states, as well as intensity measures. It is noted that many of the epistemic uncertainties are related to the ontology and definition of these parameters.

3.4.2.1 Taxonomy, Typology, Classification

Buildings with similar structural characteristics, that are in similar geotechnical conditions are expected to perform in the same way when they are exposed to an earthquake-induced hazard. Within this context, damage is directly related to the structural properties of the elements at risk. RC buildings, masonry buildings, steel buildings, monuments, harbour facilities, have their own specific set of typologies and different taxonomy. Thus, the development of an efficient taxonomy able to adequately group different types of existing buildings from different countries in Europe and worldwide is of major importance in the vulnerability assessment procedure. Especially for buildings, geometry, material properties, age, seismic design level, soil conditions, and foundation details are fundamental typology descriptors/parameters.

Prominent building typologies in literature can be found in ATC-13 (ATC 1985); EMS-98 (Grunthal 1998); ATC-14 (ATC 1987); FEMA P-154 (FEMA 2015), and other funded efforts by Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA); HAZUS (NIBS 2004), RISK-UE 2004 project (Mouroux et al. 2004); PAGER project (Jaiswal and Wald 2008; Jaiswal et al. 2010) and the most recent developed SYNER-G project (<http://www.vce.at/SYNER-G/>) for typical European structures. In SYNER-G a great effort was paid to develop a unique, coherent and comprehensive taxonomy, proposed to be the reference from now on in Europe, from which European typologies for the most important elements at risk are defined (Hancilar and Taucer 2013). Particularly for buildings, SYNER-G identified different main categories to describe a building, such as the Force Resisting Mechanism (FRM), FRM Material (FRMM), Plan (P), Elevation (E), Cladding (C), Detailing (D), Floor System (FS), Roof System (RS), Height Level (HL) and Code Level (CL). The SYNER-G infrastructure taxonomy with all the systems, components and their sub-components considered in the infrastructure are reported in Ptilakis et al. (2014a).

3.4.2.2 Intensity measures

The selection of an appropriate IM that characterises the earthquake-induced hazard and best correlates with the building response is of major importance for the derivation of fragility curves. Knowledge and use of an efficient IM will reduce variability and improve accuracy of the predicted measure of performance. Optimum IMs are defined in terms of efficiency, sufficiency, practicality, effectiveness, robustness and hazard computability (Cornell et al. 2002; Mackie and Stojadinovic 2003; 2005; Mehanny 2009).

Another metric to assess optimal IMs termed proficiency was proposed by [Padgett et al. \(2008\)](#), which has the advantage of measuring the composite effect of efficiency and practicality.

Efficiency is the most widely used quantitative measure in characterizing an ideal IM. An efficient IM reduces the amount of variation in the estimated demand for a given IM value ([Giovenale et al. 2004](#)). Sufficiency describes the extent to which the IM is statistically independent of ground motion characteristics, such as magnitude and epicentral distance ([Padgett et al. 2008](#)). A sufficient IM renders the structural demand measure conditionally independent of the earthquake scenario. Sufficiency may be quantified via statistical analysis of the response of a structure for a given set of records. Practicality refers to whether or not there is any direct correlation between an IM and the demand placed on the structure ([Padgett et al. 2008](#)). A practical IM has some direct correlation to known engineering quantities and makes engineering sense. A further criterion for evaluating practicality is whether the IM is readily described by available attenuation relationships or other sources of hazard data ([Mackie and Stojadinovic 2005](#); [Mehanny 2009](#)). The effectiveness of an IM is determined by its ability to evaluate, in a closed form ([Mackie and Stojadinovic 2003](#)), the mean annual frequency of a given decision variable (or more concisely EDP) exceeding a given limiting prescribed value ([Mehanny 2009](#)). Robustness describes the efficiency trends of an IM-EDP pair across different structures, and therefore different fundamental period ranges ([Mackie and Stojadinovic 2005](#); [Mehanny 2009](#)). Hazard computability of the IM refers to the level of effort required in order to determine the hazard curve in terms of the proposed IM ([Padgett et al. 2008](#)).

IMs are grouped into two general classes, namely the empirical IMs (such as European macroseismic scale, *EMS*) and instrumental IMs (such as *PGA*, *PGV*, *PGD*). The selection of an appropriate IM is also related to the method followed for the derivation of fragility curves, the typology of the element at risk and the adopted hazard. Empirical fragility functions are often expressed in terms of the macroseismic intensity defined according to the different Macroseismic Scales, i.e. *EMS*, Mercalli-Cancani-Sieberg intensity scale, *MCS*, and Modified Mercalli intensity, *MMI*, which are used to identify the observed effects of ground shaking over a limited area. Contrariwise, analytical or hybrid fragility functions are related to instrumental IMs, which are related to parameters of the ground motion (*PGA*, *PGV*, *PGD*) or of the structural response (spectral acceleration S_a or spectral displacement S_d , for a given value of the period of excitation T). As an example, for the vulnerability assessment of buildings subjected to ground failure (i.e. liquefaction), permanent ground deformation (*PGD*) is considered to be a proper IM,

while in the cases that the vulnerability of buildings subjected to tsunami forces is examined, inundation depth is considered as an appropriate IM.

3.4.2.3 Damage measures and damage states

Fragility assessment of buildings exposed to an earthquake-induced hazard involves multiple damage states (DS), which are a discrete qualitative description of the average level of damage in structural and non-structural components of the building for different intensity levels. The most common way to define the extent and severity of damage to structural and non-structural components of a building is a classification in terms of the following damage states: No damage; slight/minor; moderate; extensive; complete. This qualitative approach requires an agreement on the meaning and the content of each damage state. DS can also be related to specific performance levels of a building, namely Operational Performance (OP), Immediate occupancy (IO), Life safety (LS) and Collapse Prevention (CP).

In general, the performance levels of a building can be defined through damage thresholds called limit states (LS). A limit state defines the boundary between two different damage states. For example, if two *Limit States* are defined to describe the performance of a building, there will be three *Damage States*, as shown in Figure 3.6. DS imply a relationship between the response of the structure and its capacity to resist this response. For instance, the displacement capacity can be related to damage states that are identifiable through limit states. Thus, the fulfilment of a certain performance is guaranteed if the seismic displacement demand is not beyond the corresponding LS threshold.

Figure 3.6. Limit states and damage states (Crowley et al. 2011)

Various damage criteria have been proposed in the literature, depending on the element at risk (typology, state of maintenance, functionality, etc.) and the procedure used for the derivation of fragility curves. Generally, methods for deriving fragility curves model the damage on a discrete damage scale. In empirical methods, the scale is used in reconnaissance efforts to produce post-earthquake damage statistics and is rather subjective, whereas in analytical approaches the scale is related to mechanical properties of the buildings, such as displacement capacity, that are described by appropriate indices.

The number of damage states and subsequently the number of limit states depend on the damage scale used. The Homogenised Reinforced Concrete, HRC (Rossetto and Elnashai 2003), HAZUS 1999 (FEMA 1999), Vision 2000 (SEAOC 1995), EMS98 (Grunthal 1998), ATC-13 (ATC 1985) constitute some of the most frequently used damage scales. Table 3.1 presents a summary and qualitative comparison of some of the damage scales applicable for general RC structures.

Table 3.1. Comparison of existing damage scales with the HRC damage scale for general RC structures (adapted from Rossetto and Elnashai 2003)

HRC	HAZUS 1999	Vision 2000	EMS98	ATC-13
None	No damage			
Slight	Slight damage	Fully operational	Grade 1	Slight
Light		Operational	Grade 2	Light
Moderate	Moderate damage		Life Safe	Grade 3
Extensive	Extensive damage	Near Collapse	Grade 4	Heavy
Partial Collapse		Collapse		Major
Collapse	Collapse			

For the fragility assessment of buildings exposed to earthquake-induced hazards for different damage states, it is necessary first to establish a damage measure (or damage indicator) in terms of engineering demand parameter (EDP) that can adequately describe building's expected performance and is easily measurable from analytical results, monitored structural response or structural surveys. The latter is important for maintaining the link between engineering design and in-the-field survey measurements (Hill and Rossetto 2008). It is also noted that the damage states should be defined with limiting values of measurable response parameters (EDPs), capable of representing both global and local damage and the EDP values defining the damage state thresholds should

be derived from large quantities of high quality experimental or observed data (Sinha and Shiradhonkar 2012; Hill and Rossetto 2008).

In general, damage in buildings is related to irrecoverable (inelastic) deformations. Thus, any EDP should preferably refer to a certain deformation quantity, such as strain (compressive/tensile) and curvature, chord rotations (at member ends), horizontal storey displacements and relative displacements between adjacent storeys (inter-storey drifts). The last two quantities characterise global damage, while strains, curvatures or rotations are used for the characterization of local damage. In addition, forces (e.g. base shears, storey shears, member resistances) are occasionally used as EDPs, while the energy absorbed or dissipated during inelastic reversed cyclic loading of a RC member or structure may be another one meaningful damage measure (Kappos 1997). A review of the literature proposed damage measures and the associated damage states is following.

FEMA 356 (FEMA 2000) adopts global drift as the EDP. Indicatively, Table 3.2 presents for some building typologies typical drift values associated with various *Structural Performance Levels* according to FEMA 356 (FEMA 2000). It is noted that these drift values are indicative of the range of drift that typical structures containing the indicated structural elements may undergo when responding within the various *Structural Performance Levels*. The values indicated are intended to be qualitative descriptions of the approximate behaviour of structures meeting the indicated levels. This response parameter (global drift) considers global response but can overlook a local 'soft-storey' failure. Thus, it is not ideal for linking to damage.

Table 3.2. Structural Performance Levels for different buildings and limit state values in terms of drift according to FEMA 356 (FEMA2000)

	IO	LS	CP
Concrete Frames	1% transient Negligible permanent	2% transient 1% permanent	4% transient or permanent
Concrete Walls	0.5% transient negligible permanent	1% transient 0.5% permanent	2% transient or permanent
Steel Moment Frames	0.7% transient; negligible permanent	2.5% transient; 1% permanent	5% transient or permanent

On the contrary, Crowley et al. (2004) use a local (material strain-based) EDP for structural damage. In particular, they estimated the damage to the structural (load-bearing) system of a building using four damage bands. A qualitative description of each damage band for RC frames is given in Table 3.3 along with quantitative suggestions for the definition of the mechanical material properties for each limit state based on the work of Priestley (1997) and Calvi (1999). The first structural limit state is defined as steel bar

yielding, whereas the second and third structural limit states are attained when the sectional steel and concrete strains reach the limits suggested in Table 3.3. It is noted that two alternative ranges of strain limits are proposed for the limit states *Extensive* and *Collapse* due to the dependence of the ultimate sectional strains that can be reached on the level of confinement of the structural members. However, this response parameter (material strain) also needs caution as it may overlook global response.

Table 3.3. Description of RC frame structural discrete damage bands (Crowley et al. 2004)

Structural damage band	Description		
None to slight	Linear elastic response, flexural or shear type hairline cracks (<1.0 mm) in some members, no yielding in any critical section; hence limit state to damage band is structural yield point		
Moderate	Member flexural strengths achieved, limited ductility developed, crack widths reach 1.0 mm, initiation of concrete spalling, limits to strains may be assumed as: $\epsilon_c = 0.004-0.005$ $\epsilon_s = 0.010-0.015$		
Extensive	Significant repair required to building, wide flexural or shear cracks, buckling of longitudinal reinforcement may occur, limits to strains may be assumed as: <table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; border: none;">Inadequately confined members: $\epsilon_c = 0.005-0.010$ $\epsilon_s = 0.015-0.030$</td> <td style="width: 50%; border: none;">Adequately confined members: $\epsilon_c = 0.010-0.020$ $\epsilon_s = 0.040-0.060$</td> </tr> </table>	Inadequately confined members: $\epsilon_c = 0.005-0.010$ $\epsilon_s = 0.015-0.030$	Adequately confined members: $\epsilon_c = 0.010-0.020$ $\epsilon_s = 0.040-0.060$
Inadequately confined members: $\epsilon_c = 0.005-0.010$ $\epsilon_s = 0.015-0.030$	Adequately confined members: $\epsilon_c = 0.010-0.020$ $\epsilon_s = 0.040-0.060$		
Complete	Repair of building not feasible either physically or economically, demolition after earthquake required, could be due to shear failure of vertical elements or excess displacement		

In addition, Bird et al. (2005; 2006) proposed different damage states for buildings on flexible (i.e. unrestrained) shallow foundations exposed to liquefaction-induced ground deformations, which will undergo structural deformations, and those on stiff shallow foundations, which will respond as rigid bodies to deformations at foundation level. In the former case where building response comprises structural damage, damage states can be classified using the same schemes (Table 3.3) used for structural damage due to ground shaking. In that case, limit states were also specified in terms of material strain, with the first one defined as steel bar yielding whereas for the rest two, possible mean values for post-yield limit state strains for steel (ϵ_s) and concrete (ϵ_c) material were proposed (Table 3.4) for both poorly confined (poor) and well confined (good) buildings.

In the latter case, for buildings on stiff shallow foundations empirical solutions were used to describe the damage states, classifying the damage level in terms of functionality and reparability. Table 3.5 presents the proposed by Bird et al. (2006) rotational and settlement limits for grouping the rigid body response of buildings exposed to

liquefaction-induced ground deformations into similar ranges that coincide with structural damage definitions. It is also noted that for consistency with the structural damage levels described in Table 3.3, Bird et al. (2006) recommend both rotational and settlement limits be related to the repair cost ratio, although determining the cost of foundation repairs is significantly more complex than structural repairs. However, these limits have a high associated uncertainty due to the lack of available data regarding repair methods and costs for settled and rotated buildings.

Table 3.4. Mean post-yield limit state strains for steel (ϵ_s) and concrete (ϵ_c) for poorly confined (poor) and well confined (good) buildings (Bird et al. 2005)

Limit state	Poor Buildings		Good Buildings	
	ϵ_s	ϵ_c	ϵ_s	ϵ_c
2	0.0125	0.0045	0.0125	0.0045
3	0.0225	0.0075	0.0500	0.0150

Table 3.5. Suggested limit states for rigid body settlement and rotation due to earthquake-induced ground deformations beneath RC frame buildings (Bird et al. 2006)

Damage state	Structural damage (see Table 3.3 for full description)	Additional description (rigid body deformation)	Settlement (Δ) only	Rotation (θ) only
Slight	Hairline cracks only	Repairs may be necessary for aesthetic reasons	$\Delta \leq 0.1\text{m}$	$\theta \leq 0.6^\circ$ 1/100
Moderate	Some cracks in load-bearing elements	Repairable damage, serviceability and/or functionality affected	$0.1\text{m} < \Delta \leq 0.3\text{m}$	$0.6^\circ < \theta \leq 2.3^\circ$ 1/100 to 1/25
Extensive	Wide cracks and buckling of longitudinal reinforcement	Uninhabitable, but repairable	$0.3\text{m} < \Delta \leq 1.0\text{m}$	$2.3^\circ < \theta \leq 4.6^\circ$ 1/25 to 1/12.5
Complete	Repair not feasible, shear failures or excessive displacement	Demolition cheaper than repair. Structural integrity affected, possible instability	$\geq 1.0\text{m}$	$\theta \geq 4.6^\circ \geq 1/12.5$

A better and most commonly used damage measure for the derivation of fragility functions for RC buildings is inter-storey drift (ISD), which correlates to its damage description via a substantial amount of experimental data, as demonstrated by Rossetto and Elnashai (2003). Inter-storey drift is also used with the HAZUS (NIBS 2004) and RISK-UE (Milutinovic and Trendafiloski 2003) damage scales but is not used exclusively for correlation with the damage descriptions. In addition, many other studies (Rossetto and Elnashai 2003; Ghobarah 2004; etc.) have adopted ISD limits for damage assessment of RC buildings. However, the damage scales used in the different studies

are quite heterogeneous. Correspondences between the different scales are well detailed in [Hill and Rossetto \(2008\)](#).

Ductility alone is not capable of describing adequately failure due to damage concentration on the floor levels. Thus, the use of maximum ISD ratio in these cases is more appropriate as it is found to better correlate with structural damage and levels of inelastic behaviour. The displacements or drift of a structure are functions of various factors like stiffness, strength, the ability of the structural system to deform (ductility), as well as the applied load. For instance, it was found experimentally that increase in the axial load increases the shear resistance of the structural member and reduces the lateral drift ([Ghobarah 2004](#)). The relationship between performance objectives in terms of drift limits and damage is best illustrated by the typical capacity curve shown in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7. Typical structural performance and associated damage states ([Ghobarah 2004](#))

[Ghobarah \(2004\)](#) defined different sets of maximum ISD limits associated with various damage levels for some RC structural systems, namely MRFs (ductile, nonductile, with infills), ductile flexural walls and squat shear walls, that are presented in Table 3.6.

The defined performance levels were based on experimental data, field observations and measurements and analytical procedures, including time-history analysis, dynamic and static pushover analyses of various designs of RC MRFs and walls. Although ISD may have advantages over some of the other EDPs, however it may not be able to capture certain brittle failure modes, such as column shear failure, which may occur in European RC buildings not designed in accordance with modern codes.

Table 3.6. Drift ratio (%) limits associated with various damage levels (Ghobarah 2004)

State of damage	Ductile MRF	Nonductile MRF	MRF with infills	Ductile walls	Squat walls
No damage	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.2	<0.1
Repairable damage a) Light	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.2
Repairable damage b) Moderate	<1.0	<0.5	<0.4	<0.8	<0.4
Irreparable damage (>yield point)	>1.0	>0.5	>0.4	>0.8	>0.4
Severe damage - Life safe - Partial collapse	1.8	0.8	0.7	1.5	0.7
Collapse	>3.0	>1.0	>0.8	>2.5	>0.8

All the aforementioned EDPs involve a certain structural quantity. Nevertheless, when referring to damage, it is really useful in many situations involving seismic risk assessment to express it in economic terms, typically as the cost required to restore a structural member or a structure to its initial (pre-earthquake) state (Kappos 1997). Therefore, damage may also be quantified by using any of the available in literature damage indices defined as functions whose values can be related to particular structural damage states (Ghobarah et al. 1999). Damage indices are damage functions that have been formulated using response parameters of the structure, obtained through analytical evaluation of structural response (Williams and Sexsmith 1995; Sinha and Shiradhonkar 2012). They are widely used to predict potential damage in the field of vulnerability assessment, performance evaluation and decision related to retrofitting of structures. They can also be used for performance-based engineering approaches.

Williams and Sexsmith (1995), Ghobarah et al. (1999) and Rodriguez and Padilla (2009) have carried out comprehensive reviews of available damage indices. Kappos (1997), has provided elaborative classification of damage indices, assorted as local damage indices and global damage indices based on their use in quantifying damage in individual members or entire building, respectively. Cosenza and Manfredi (2000), has also provided classification of the damage indices based on the type of analytical model used in calculating the damage index (*DI*). The damage indices based on member-type

model are assorted as deformation-based damage indices, energy-based damage indices and combined damage indices. They also evaluated the correlation between damage indices and damage states for assessing the condition of the structure and for decision making regarding retrofitting and repairing of the damaged structure.

More recently, several damage indices have been proposed. Indicatively, [Erduran and Yakut \(2004\)](#) proposed a damage index corresponding to different damage states. The damage criterion used in this study mainly depends on the ductility index which is the ratio of the given drift divided by the yield drift, hence the yield drift. [Colombo and Negro \(2005\)](#) proposed a general damage index defined as the ratio of the initial and the reduced resistance capacity of a structure, evaluated by using an evolution equation for the yield strength in which the structural damageability is included, which requires the definition of several parameters related to ductility and energy dissipation. The ability of this index to model different damage situations is demonstrated. Moreover, [Kim et al. \(2005\)](#) proposed a damage index based on results of finite element analyses (FEA), in which material models were modified to consider fatigue damage based on results of numerical tests. Finally, [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#) provided the best estimate values for the loss index ranges associated with each damage state for RC structures, presented in Table 3.7, derived from their previous experience in RC structures.

Table 3.7. Damage states and loss indices for RC structures ([Kappos et al. 2006](#))

Damage state	Damage state label	Range of loss index (%)	Central index (%)
DS0	None	0	0
DS1	Slight	>0-1	0.5
DS2	Moderate	1-10	5
DS3	Substantial to heavy	10-30	20
DS4	Very heavy	30-60	45
DS5	Collapse	60-100	80

3.4.2.4 Treatment of Uncertainties

The methodological chain of seismic risk assessment, from seismic hazard assessment to evaluation of potential losses, encompasses numerous uncertainties, both aleatory and epistemic ([Riga et al. 2017](#)). Aleatory uncertainty is related to the intrinsic randomness of a phenomenon and reflects its stochastic nature, and thus cannot be reduced with the collection of additional data. Epistemic uncertainty is related to the lack of proper

knowledge, regarding the system considered and the models used to simulate the complex nature of the structure's response, and thus can theoretically be reduced with improving the method, the available data and generally the state of knowledge. In general, uncertainty that is explicitly recognised by a stochastic model is aleatory, while uncertainty on the model itself and its parameters is epistemic. Therefore, the aleatory/epistemic split of the total uncertainty is model-dependent (Wen et al. 2003). Although the distinction between aleatory and epistemic uncertainties in risk and reliability analysis is determined by our modelling choices, this distinction is useful for identifying sources of uncertainty which can be reduced in near-term and for decision-making, since it then becomes clear as to which reducible uncertainties have been left unreduced by our decisions (DerKiureghian and Ditlevsen 2009).

In general, the various uncertainties of the fragility parameters is considered through the standard deviation, β_{tot} , which describes the total variability associated with each fragility curve. A higher β_{tot} value leads to greater uncertainty. Three primary sources of uncertainty are usually taken into account (NIBS 2004), namely, the definition of the damage state values, β_{DS} , the response and resistance (capacity) of the structure, β_C , and the earthquake input motion (demand), β_D .

Uncertainty in the definition of the several damage states is due to the fact that the thresholds of the damage indices or parameters used to define damage states are not known. Uncertainty in the structural capacity reflects the variability of structure properties as well as the fact that the modelling procedures are not perfect. Uncertainty in demand reflects the fact that the IM is not exactly sufficient, so different records of ground motion with equal IM may have different effects on the same structure (Selva et al. 2013). The total variability is finally modelled by the combination of the three contributors, assuming that they are stochastically independent and lognormally distributed random variables, using the following equation:

$$\beta_{tot} = \sqrt{\beta_{DS}^2 + \beta_C^2 + \beta_D^2} \quad (3.4)$$

HAZUS (NIBS 2004) advocates $\beta_{DS}=0.40$ for all structural damage states and building types, while for the variability in the capacity recommends $\beta_C=0.25$ and $\beta_C=0.30$ for code compliant buildings and for pre-code buildings, respectively.

3.4.3 Vulnerability Functions

Vulnerability functions translate the physical damage into loss (in terms of repair costs, life-safety impacts, functionality, environmental degradation, quality of life, historical value or other measures), given a level of intensity measure, IM , and are expressed through conditional probabilistic distributions of damage index per level of the

IM. They are referred to several ways, such as damage functions, loss functions, vulnerability curves, or others. At this point, it should be noted that vulnerability is not fragility, as vulnerability measures loss, while fragility measures probability. For instance, a seismic vulnerability function relates uncertain loss to a measure of seismic excitation, such as PGA, and usually applies to a particular element at risk (Porter 2018).

More specifically, a vulnerability curve is generated based on the estimation of the damage (or vulnerability) index. The damage index, d_m , should be a convenient measure to quantify the structural losses and finally to assess the risk for a single element. As noted above, it may be quantified in cost terms as the ratio of cost of repair to cost of replacement taking values from 0: no damage (cost of repair equals 0) to 1: complete damage (cost of repair equals the cost of replacement). Once the probabilities of exceeding the specified damage states are estimated, the damage index, d_m , is evaluated for each IM level according to the following mathematical expression:

$$d_m = \sum_{ds} CDF \cdot P[ds_i = i | IM] \quad (3.5)$$

where d_m is the damage index corresponding to each IM level, $P[ds=i | IM]$ are the discrete damage probabilities for each damage state and CDF represents the central damage factor, which is the ratio of the average building cost of repair to the cost of replacement at each damage state.

3.5 Exposure

Within a risk assessment framework, the term *Exposure* is used for the definition of the elements at risk (people or assets exposed to loss). The *elements at risk* definition includes locations, values exposed to loss, as well as the characteristics necessary to estimate vulnerability. Table 3.8 adapted from Proag (2014) explains the various levels of exposure of elements at risk (people and assets) to the different hazards. Proag (2014) claims that the exposure to hazard, is largely involuntary, mainly due to the location of elements at risk in hazardous areas.

In general, the elements at risk are categorised as populations, communities, built environment, natural environment, economic activities and services, which are under the threat of hazard in a given area (Alexander 2000). They can be determined by using, respectively, physical parameters and demographic datasets. In Ptilakis et al. (2014a) the elements at risk within the built environment are examined and classified in four main categories: buildings, utility networks, transportation infrastructures and critical facilities. It should be noted that the development of a homogenous taxonomy for all engineering element at risk exposed to seismic hazard and the recommendation of adequate fragility functions for each one, considering also the European context, is a

significant contribution to the reduction of seismic risk in Europe and worldwide (Pitilakis et al. 2014a).

Table 3.8. Various levels of exposure to different hazards (Proag 2014)

Hazard	Exposure
Physical	<p>Physical vulnerability relates to buildings, infrastructure and agriculture. Although the focus is on physical assets, it also includes the potential loss of crops and other infrastructure necessary to livelihood.</p> <p>Vulnerability analysis should examine the risk faced by critical facilities, which are vital to the functioning of societies in disaster situations, such as hospitals and dispensaries, emergency services, transport, communication systems, essential services, etc.</p>
Social	<p>Vulnerable groups include women, mentally and physically handicapped persons, children, and elderly persons, the poor people, refugees, and livestock.</p>
Economic	<p>Economic vulnerability assesses the risk of hazard-causing losses to economic assets and processes. These fall into two groups:</p> <p><i>Direct.</i> Damage to or destruction of physical and social infrastructure and its repair or replacement cost, as well as crop damage</p> <p><i>Indirect.</i> Loss to production, employment, vital services, income disparities</p>

Chapter 4

Tsunami fragility curves for seaport RC buildings and steel light frame warehouses

4.1 Introduction

Harbours are crucial assets for the sustainment and development of human activities. The recent devastating tsunami events as well as the increasing number of people, structures and economic activities being exposed to tsunami hazards revealed the need for the estimation of the effects of tsunami wave on seaport structures. However, only a limited number of tools to estimate the potential impacts of tsunami are available until now. The present chapter aspires to propose different sets of fragility functions for some representative typologies of seaport structures found in ordinary port areas in Greece and in South Europe, like the port of Thessaloniki. Part of this research has recently been published in *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* scientific journal ([Karafagka et al. 2018a](#)). Probabilistic tsunami fragility curves, which describe the probability of exceeding a certain level of damage of the building, are proposed, as a function of the tsunami inundation depth. Vulnerability curves as a function of the inundation depth are also derived to be able to assess the expected direct losses in normalised cost terms.

Low-code moment resisting frame (MRF) and dual reinforced concrete (RC) buildings of various heights, and a typical warehouse subjected to tsunami hazard are considered in the analysis. A numerical investigation is performed considering different combinations of tsunami loads based on FEMA P646 ([FEMA 2008](#)) recommendations for gradually increasing tsunami inundation depths and for the various structure typologies. To minimize the uncertainties related to the definition of damage limit states, tsunami nonlinear static analyses are performed, and appropriate tsunami capacity curves are derived for the considered structures. Structural limit states are defined on tsunami capacity curves in terms of threshold values of material strain. For the complete damage state, shear failure is also considered, since the collapse of structures may be caused by the occurrence of either a flexural or shear failure in structural components. Fragility

curves are calculated for the different damage states using nonlinear regression analysis. They could be used within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the vulnerability of low-code RC buildings and typical warehouses exposed to tsunami hazard along European-Mediterranean and other regions of similar facilities worldwide.

4.2 Literature review

Tsunamis are long-period water waves that can be triggered by undersea shallow-focus earthquakes, underwater or aerial landslides or volcanic eruptions (Tinti et al. 2011). The vast majority of the observed tsunamis are induced by seismic events. Occurrence of tsunamis can cause tremendous direct and indirect losses in terms of fatalities and infrastructure damage (Jelínek and Krausmann 2008). Tsunamis are generally “relatively low probability – high consequence” events and hence the prediction of the damages is highly uncertain presenting large dispersion from slight non-structural damages to the exposed structures to total collapse or even washed away. The knowledge of the tsunamigenic sources with their probability of occurrence, size and their probable impact or consequences to all exposed elements at risk (structural, non-structural, human, economic etc.) are therefore essential to reduce uncertainty. Tsunami risk assessment has got increased interest the last few years due to the occurrence of recent tsunami events with extremely severe impact to buildings, infrastructures, population and economy (e.g. the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami, the 2006 Java tsunami, the 2007 Solomon Islands tsunami, the 2009 South Pacific tsunami, the 2010 Chilean Tsunami in Dichato, and the 2011 Great East Japan tsunami). It is expected that future tsunamis can have even higher impact due to the increasing number of people, buildings and infrastructures that are being exposed to natural hazards as the pressures for urban development extend into areas of higher tsunami risk (Jelínek and Krausmann 2008). However, only a limited number of tools to estimate the potential impacts of tsunami are available until now.

Some of the early tsunami risk assessment efforts were developed before the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami (Hatori 1984; Shuto 1993; Papadopoulos & Imamura 2001). Since then, the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami and the subsequent important tsunamis events triggered a considerable number of studies (Synolakis et al. 2008; Keen et al. 2017) related to tsunami hazard and risk assessment of seaport structures. Concerning the tsunami hazard, Tinti et al. (2011) illustrated the basic concepts and methods to produce tsunami scenarios in view of providing tools to assess tsunami hazard and potential damage. Probabilistic approaches to tsunami hazard are becoming a standard (e.g. Geist and Lynett 2014) and they are consistently being applied at the global (<http://www.preventionweb.net/english/hyogo/gar/>, <http://www.globaltsunamimodel.org>)

regional (<http://www.tsumaps-neam.eu/>) and local scale (Lorito et al. 2015), including also a full treatment of aleatory and epistemic uncertainty (Selva et al. 2016). Considering the impact, Dalrymple and Kriebe (2005); Stansfield (2005); Ghobarah et al. (2006) focused their studies on qualitative damage analysis, while Rossetto et al. (2007) and Kaplan et al. (2009) categorised building damage using field survey data from the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami in Thailand. More recently, Rossetto (2016) presented an outline of an interesting experimental and analytical research program investigating tsunami actions on buildings and their effects.

To this regard, and before presenting the research conducted in this chapter of the thesis, a short description of the available fragility curves is deemed necessary keeping in mind that the research on this subject is still at its childhood. Inspired by the seismic risk assessment of buildings, the tsunami vulnerability of structures is generally assessed using also fragility and damage functions. Tsunami fragility functions define appropriate statistical relationships between damage probability and tsunami loading characteristics (i.e. the intensity measures) such as inundation depth, velocity and hydrodynamic force. To this respect, fragility and damage functions can be empirical, semi-empirical or analytical.

4.2.1 Empirical fragility curves

In the frame of empirical relationships, the vast majority are based on post-event field observations, which are specific to the event site. A brief review of the available empirical (site-specific) fragility curves of buildings subjected to tsunamis is following.

Peiris (2006) developed vulnerability functions in terms of inundation depth for unreinforced masonry residential buildings, using field observation data from the tsunami damage in the coastal areas of Sri Lanka due to 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami, published by the Department of Census and Statistics (DCS). DCS data included the number of structures exceeding three damage states (complete, partial-unusable and partial-usable) under six inundation depth levels. Also, Dias et al. (2009) carried out probabilistic modelling to obtain a synthetic vulnerability curve for tsunami loading on detached single-storey unreinforced masonry buildings in terms of inundation depth for the complete damage state only, using the field survey data from Sri Lanka due to 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami (published by the DCS) and Monte Carlo simulation. In addition, Koshimura et al. (2009) developed tsunami fragility curves for building damage using numerical modelling of tsunami inundation and Geographic Information System (GIS) analysis of post-tsunami survey data of the 2004 Sumatra-Andaman earthquake-induced tsunami, obtained from Banda Aceh, Indonesia. The major building types in the tsunami-affected area, taken into consideration in the study, were low-rise wooden house, timber

construction, and non-engineered RC construction. The fragility functions they proposed are expressed as the damage probabilities of structures or death ratio with regard to the hydrodynamic features of tsunami inundation flow, such as inundation depth, current velocity and hydrodynamic force. [Murao and Nakazato \(2010\)](#) developed tsunami vulnerability functions for building damage in Sri Lanka, conducting field surveys to collect building damage and inundation data after the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami. They classified the buildings into two structural types, namely solid buildings (mainly RC) and non-solid buildings (masonry and timber-frame).

Additionally, [Leone et al. \(2011\)](#) implemented an original method of damage spatial and quantitative analysis based on field surveys of the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami, photo interpretations and GIS. This analysis was complemented by fragility curves for brick not-reinforced individual buildings that give the statistical relationships between mean damage intensities and inundation depths. [Valencia et al. \(2011\)](#) developed tsunami damage functions for different typologies of buildings along European-Mediterranean coasts, based on data collected by several authors in Banda Aceh (Indonesia) after the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami. They proposed fragility curves for four building types, namely light constructions on wood or timber without any design, brick not reinforced masonry, brick with reinforced column and masonry filling, and concrete not reinforced buildings. They found that a brick with reinforced column and masonry filling building in Banda Aceh, Indonesia, would sustain only light damage at an inundation depth of $< 3.0\text{m}$, moderate damage at inundation depths $> 3.0\text{m}$ and the total destruction at depths $> 7.0\text{m}$. Similar observations using mean damage levels can be found in the study of [Leone et al. \(2011\)](#). In addition, [Suppasri et al. \(2011\)](#) developed tsunami fragility curves from the tsunami features (inundation depth, current velocity, and hydrodynamic force) for different types of building materials, using visual inspection of high-resolution satellite images of damaged buildings, based on the remaining roofs, taken before and after tsunami events, as well as a tsunami inundation numerical model of the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami in Thailand. [Foytong and Ruangrassamee \(2016\)](#) also developed empirical tsunami fragility curves for RC buildings of one-storey or more, using data of observed building damage due to the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami.

Moreover, [Reese et al. \(2011\)](#) developed empirical tsunami fragility functions from observational and quantitative data on building damage obtained from the 2009 South Pacific tsunami and also attempted to quantify the effects of debris and shielding on fragility functions. It was observed that residential timber structures were more fragile (i.e. have a higher likelihood of damage for a given inundation depth) than masonry residential buildings, while residential RC buildings were observed to be less fragile than residential masonry ones for severe and collapse damage states. They also concluded

that non-structural damage states are independent of the building typology. In addition, [Gokon et al. \(2014\)](#) developed tsunami fragility functions in terms of inundation depth, flow velocity and hydrodynamic force to evaluate structural vulnerability in the areas affected by the 2009 American Samoa tsunami. They achieved this by integrating tsunami numerical modelling with the spatial distribution of building damage using GIS. Also, [Mas et al. \(2012\)](#) developed fragility curves in terms of inundation depth to estimate the structural damage against tsunami hazard in the town of Dichato, using surveyed data of inundation depth and visual inspection of satellite images of the 2010 Chilean Tsunami in Dichato. They presented a practical method suitable when there are limitations on available data for numerical simulation or damage evaluation from surveys.

Furthermore, [Amakuni and Terazono \(2011\)](#) proposed vulnerability functions in terms of inundation depth, flow velocity and hydrodynamic force to estimate the damages of wooden buildings caused by the 2011 Great East Japan tsunami in Miyagi Prefecture, Japan, using numerical modelling and GIS. [Suppasri et al. \(2013; 2015\)](#) developed empirical tsunami fragility functions, using a set of building damage data from the 2011 Great East Japan tsunami, with details on damage level, structural material, number of stories per building and location noting their importance. [Charvet et al. \(2014a; 2014b\)](#) proposed empirical fragility curves of buildings using improved statistical models. An extensive database of building damage following the 2011 Great East Japan tsunami was used. In addition, [Charvet et al. \(2015\)](#) proposed a multivariate fragility formulation in order to take into account not only inundation depth, but also inundation velocity and debris impact. It should also be mentioned that [Macabuag et al. \(2016\)](#) proposed a rigorous methodology using advanced statistical methods for the selection of optimum tsunami intensity measures (TIM) for fragility function derivation for any given dataset. The method was demonstrated by the authors using a unique, detailed, disaggregated damage dataset from the 2011 Great East Japan tsunami. Finally, [De Risi et al. \(2017a\)](#) developed empirical tsunami fragility curves, using filed survey data from the 2011 Great East Japan tsunami, based on a Bayesian framework by considering three fragility modelling approaches, namely lognormal method, binomial logistic method and multinomial logistic method in order to account for uncertainty of input tsunami hazard data in a systematic and comprehensive manner. Further, [De Risi et al. \(2017b\)](#) investigated the influence of flow velocity in multivariate empirical fragility models through rigorous statistical analysis.

A review of the existing empirical tsunami fragility functions as well as the key issues in the literature can be found in [Nanayakkara and Dias \(2013\)](#) as well as [Charvet et al. \(2017\)](#). Table 4.1 and Table 4.2 summarise the existing empirical tsunami fragility functions. All these fragility (or damage) functions for buildings and infrastructures

exposed to tsunami hazard are principally based on empirical data (hazard-damage relationships from previous tsunami events) and/or expert judgment, and as such there are limitations in their general application as they are highly specific to a particular seismo-tectonic, geomorphological and built environment.

Table 4.1. Existing empirical fragility functions for Tsunami damage

Reference	Tsunami event	Area	Methodology	IM	Main building typology
<i>Peiris (2006)</i>	2004 Indian Ocean	Sri Lanka	Field Survey data	Inundation depth	Single story unreinforced masonry
<i>Dias et al. (2009)</i>	2004 Indian Ocean	Sri Lanka	Field Survey data, Probabilistic modelling	Inundation depth	Single story unreinforced masonry
<i>Koshimura et al. (2009)</i>	2004 Indian Ocean	Banda Aceh, Indonesia	GIS, Numerical modelling, Field Survey Data	Inundation depth, flow velocity, hydrodynamic force	Low-rise wooden houses, timber construction, and non-engineered RC construction
<i>Murao and Nakazato (2010)</i>	2004 Indian Ocean	South coast of Sri Lanka	Field Survey data	Inundation depth	RC, masonry and timber-frame
<i>Leone et al. (2011)</i>	2004 Indian Ocean	Banda Aceh, Indonesia	GIS, Field Survey Data	Inundation depth	Brick not-reinforced individual buildings
<i>Valencia et al. 2011</i>	2004 Indian Ocean	European-Mediterranean coasts	Field Survey data from Banda Aceh (Indonesia)	Inundation depth	light constructions, brick not-reinforced, masonry with reinforced columns, and concrete not reinforced
<i>Suppasri et al. 2011</i>	2004 Indian Ocean	Phang Nga and Phuket, Thailand	GIS, Numerical Modelling, and Field Survey Data (for RC structures)	Inundation depth, flow velocity, hydrodynamic force	mixed type, RC and wooden
<i>Foytong and Ruangrassamee (2016)</i>	2004 Indian Ocean	Ranong, Phung-Nga, Phuket, Krabi, Trung and Satun, Thailand	Field Survey data	Inundation depth	RC
<i>Reese et al. 2011</i>	2009 South Pacific	Samoa and American Samoa	Field Survey data	Inundation depth, debris	Masonry, RC and timber residential
<i>Gokon et al. (2014)</i>	2009 South Pacific	Tutuila island, American Samoa	GIS, Numerical modelling	Inundation depth, flow velocity, hydrodynamic force	House damage (structural destruction)

Table 4.2. Existing empirical fragility functions for Tsunami damage (continued)

Reference	Tsunami event	Area	Methodology	IM	Main building typology
<i>Mas et al. 2012</i>	2010 Chile	Dichato, Chile	GIS, Numerical modelling	Inundation depth	Masonry and wooden, wooden and corrugated metal
<i>Amakuni and Terazono (2011)</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Miyagi, Japan	GIS, Numerical modelling	Inundation depth, flow velocity, hydrodynamic force	wooden
<i>Suppasri et al. 2013</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Hokkaido, Aomori, Iwate, Miyagi, Fukushima, Ibaraki and Chiba, Japan	Field Survey data	Inundation depth	RC, steel, wooden, and masonry
<i>Suppasri et al. 2015</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Ishinomaki, Japan	Field Survey data	Inundation depth	RC, steel, wooden, and masonry
<i>Charvet et al. 2014a</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Prefectures bordering the East coast of Japan	Field Survey data, Generalised linear Model (GLM)	Inundation depth	RC, steel and wooden
<i>Charvet et al. 2014b</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Ishinomaki, Japan	Field Survey data, Generalised linear Model (GLM)	Inundation depth	RC, steel, wooden, and masonry
<i>Charvet et al. 2015</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Kesennuma, Japan	Field Survey data, GLM	Inundation depth, flow velocity, debris	RC, steel, wooden, and masonry
<i>Macabuag et al. 2016</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Ishinomaki, Onagawa and Kesennuma, Japan	Field Survey data, Numerical modelling	Inundation depth, flow velocity, momentum flux, hydrodynamic force, Froude number, equivalent quasi-steady force	Engineered (RC and steel) and non-engineered (wooden and masonry)
<i>De Risi et al. (2017a)</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Iwate, Miyagi and Fukushima, Japan	Field Survey data, GLM	Inundation depth	Wooden
<i>De Risi et al. (2017b)</i>	2011 Great East Japan	Miyagi, Japan	Field Survey data, GLM	Inundation depth, flow velocity	RC, steel, wooden, and masonry

4.2.2 Analytical fragility curves

Analytical tsunami fragility curves are based on damage data derived from numerical analyses and are able to quantify risk even in the absence of field survey damage data.

The development of analytical tsunami fragility functions is more limited, while half of them are referring to the collapse state. Table 4.3 summarises the existing analytical tsunami fragility functions.

Table 4.3. Existing analytical fragility functions for Tsunami damage

Reference	Structural model	Tsunami forces considered	Damage states	IM	Analysis	Notes
<i>Park et al. (2012)</i>	Two-storey, light frame, wood (SDoF)	Hydrostatic, hydrodynamic and impulsive forces (FEMA 2008)	Collapse	Inundation depth	THA	Investigation of the effect of earthquake and tsunami on a case-study building
<i>Kircher and Bouabid (2014)</i>	Wooden, RC	Hydrodynamic, impulsive and debris forces (FEMA 2012)	Moderate, Extensive, Complete	Inundation depth, momentum flux	Pushover	Comparison of tsunami load with HAZUS seismic capacity curves
<i>Nanayakkara and Dias (2016)</i>	Masonry, RC	Tsunami bore forces (hydrodynamic component)	Collapse	Inundation depth	Check if $F_{Demand} > F_{capacity}$	Monte Carlo simulation for masonry and RC buildings.
<i>Attary et al. (2016)</i>	Three-storey steel moment frame	Hydrodynamic and impulsive forces	Slight, Moderate, Extensive, Complete	Inundation depth, momentum flux, KMMF	Pushover	Monte Carlo simulation varying tsunami and material properties
<i>Petrone et al. (2017)</i>	RC MRF	Quasi-steady forces	Collapse	Inundation depth, equivalent quasi-steady force	CHPO, VHPO, THA	Comparison of multiple capacity estimation methods and pressure distributions with dynamic analyses based on inundation simulations of 2011 Japan tsunami
<i>Alam et al. (2018)</i>	RC moment frame	Hydrodynamic forces	Slight, Moderate, Extensive, Complete	Inundation depth, momentum flux	Pushover	FOSM reliability method and nonlinear FE structural models, accounting for material and geometric sources of uncertainty
<i>Karafagka et al. (2018a)</i>	RC MRFs, RC Duals and steel light frame warehouses	Hydrostatic, buoyant, hydrodynamic, impulsive and debris impact forces (FEMA 2008)	Slight, Moderate, Extensive, Complete	Inundation depth	THA	Flexural and shear failure in the structural members is considered. Damage limit states in terms of steel strain are proposed

In particular, [Park et al. \(2012\)](#) developed a numerical approach to estimate the collapse fragility for successive earthquake and tsunami loading to buildings. They generated two different types of fragility curves, using tsunami forces only or considering successive earthquake and tsunami loading, in order to quantify the influence and better understand how this type of successive loading affects fragility. The tsunami loading was evaluated using three of the eight different types of wave forces proposed in FEMA P646 ([FEMA 2008](#)), namely hydrostatic, hydrodynamic and impulsive forces. A two-story, light frame, wood structure was used as a case study, modelled as an equivalent single-degree of freedom (SDOF) and multiple non-linear time-history analyses (THA) were conducted.

In addition, [Kircher and Bouabid \(2014\)](#) developed example analytical tsunami building damage and loss functions for incorporation into the new proposed Tsunamis Model of the HAZUS Loss Estimation Technology. They considered damage due to both tsunami inundation depth and tsunami flow (Momentum Flux) hazards. Non-structural systems and contents damage is based solely on tsunami inundation depth. Structural damage is estimated by equating hydrodynamic loads incorporating the effects of impulsive and debris loads, calculated according to [FEMA \(2012\)](#), with the lateral force (pushover) strength of model building types as defined by the properties of capacity curves of the HAZUS Earthquake Model. They supported that fewer damage states (i.e. moderate, extensive and complete) are required to adequately address tsunami losses, since slight damage is difficult to distinguish from no damage.

Moreover, [Nanayakkara and Dias \(2016\)](#) developed a probabilistic model using Monte Carlo simulations to produce synthetic fragility functions for masonry and RC structures (typical buildings in coastal areas of Sri Lanka) subjected to tsunami loading, using inundation depth as the intensity measure and considering only the complete collapse state, as it was the easiest to define. The failure of masonry buildings is considered to occur when the force causing sliding exceeds the force-resisting capacity of the building (which is based on the shear capacity of masonry at plinth level), while the failure of RC buildings is taken to occur when a collapse mechanism is formed due to the formation of plastic hinges in the RC frame. For RC buildings, local failure of masonry infill walls either due to flexural failure or shear failure between wall and concrete was also considered.

[Attary et al. \(2016\)](#) also proposed a methodology to generate physics-based tsunami fragility functions, which is based on Monte Carlo Simulation for consideration of material uncertainties and includes epistemic uncertainties in the tsunami force calculation. Inundation depth and momentum flux, as well as the new proposed IM that represents overturning moment of a structure for tsunami fragility, namely kinematic moment of momentum flux (KMMF), which is the square of the product of inundation depth and flow

velocity (h^2u^2), are used as IMs. The maximum ISD is used as the EDP for the damage assessment. Nonlinear pushover analyses were performed to estimate the response of a three-storey steel moment frame to tsunami forces (realistic combinations of tsunami inundation depth and flow velocity) and finally derive the proposed fragility curves.

Furthermore, [Petroni et al. \(2017\)](#) developed a theoretical framework to evaluate fragility curves for tsunami actions focusing on the identification of the collapse limit state (attained for either a global or a local shear failure), using different nonlinear static analyses, namely constant-height pushover (CHPO) and variable-height pushover (VHPO) and dynamic analyses based on simulated 2011 Japan tsunami waves. Finally, [Alam et al. \(2018\)](#) proposed a probabilistic framework for developing simulation-based tsunami fragility functions for structures using nonlinear finite-element (FE) structural models and the first-order second-moment (FOSM) reliability method, which accounts for material and geometric sources of uncertainty in the development of tsunami fragility functions. They also further extended previous research considering shear and flexural failure of structural members. Fragility functions were developed for a RC moment frame representative of a school building designed to current seismic codes.

Some other numerical approaches for the vulnerability assessment of buildings subjected to tsunami forces, but without resulting to fragility curves, are also following. More specifically, [Nayak et al. \(2014\)](#) assessed the tsunami vulnerability of low-rise structures by comparing tsunami force with design seismic base shear and suggested that depending upon the location and type of structural elements, appropriate combinations of tsunami-induced force components (hydrostatic, hydrodynamic, surge, buoyant and debris impact force) should be used in calculating the total tsunami force. [Macabuag et al. \(2014\)](#) proposed a method for deriving analytical tsunami fragility functions for an RC frame structure using iterative structural analyses and design standard tsunami loadings and also proposed the material strain be used as engineering demand parameter. [Foytong et al. \(2015\)](#) investigated numerically the response of a RC building under increasing tsunami loading, considering shear and flexural failure in the collapse state.

Herein, analytical fragility functions under tsunami forces are developed for different damage limit states for some typical buildings representative of typologies found in ordinary port areas like the port of Thessaloniki, i.e. low-code RC buildings and steel light frame warehouses. The work has been conducted in the frame of a European research project entitled STREST (www.strest-eu.org). A comprehensive set of numerical analyses is performed considering different combinations of statically applied tsunami loads according to FEMA P646 ([FEMA 2008](#)) recommendations for gradually increasing tsunami inundation depths. Lognormally distributed fragility curves are derived and compared

with available empirical fragility curves (i.e. Suppasri et al. 2013; 2015; Foytong and Ruangrassamee 2016) and results from other numerical studies (i.e. Foytong et al. 2015).

4.3 Conception and description of the methodological framework

Inspired from the methods used for the development of seismic fragility curves for ordinary buildings, a methodology is proposed herein to construct fragility curves and assess the vulnerability of buildings subjected to tsunami forces. It is based on a comprehensive set of nonlinear numerical computations and adequate statistical analysis. The framework of the proposed methodology for the derivation of tsunami fragility and vulnerability curves is schematically illustrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1. Flowchart of the proposed methodology for the derivation of tsunami fragility and vulnerability curves

Several building typologies (i.e. low-code RC buildings and a typical steel light frame warehouse) are considered. Nonlinear constitutive models are used to simulate the behaviour of materials since cracking and irreversible deformations are normally expected to govern the structure's response. All models used in the analysis assume fixed-base conditions. Other co-seismic effects like scouring, liquefaction or compliant

foundation are not taken into account. In this phase of the study, which is a single-risk assessment, far-source generated tsunami is considered, where the epicentre of the earthquake is assumed to be at long distances from the structure; moreover it is assumed that the structure has not sustained any initial damage prior to the tsunami due to ground shaking.

Tsunami loading is determined based on FEMA P646 ([FEMA 2008](#)) recommendations and proper engineering judgment. In particular, each structure is subjected to buoyant, hydrostatic and hydrodynamic forces combined with forces due to debris, all of which constitute tsunami load effects. The considered combinations of tsunami forces differ for the various building typologies whereas the amplitude of the resultant force increases with increasing tsunami inundation depth. The computed forces are then directly applied as input time-variant static loads to an appropriate nonlinear structural model for gradually increasing inundation depths. Static time-history analysis is conducted and the structure's response in terms of material strain (i.e. the engineering demand parameter, EDP) for the different statically applied tsunami loads is estimated. At this point it is noted that the term "static time-history analysis" refers to an analysis where the applied loads, either forces (as in this case) or displacement (as in the next chapter) or a combination of both, vary independently in the pseudo-time domain, according to a prescribed load pattern. The applied load P_i in a nodal position i is given by $P_i = \lambda_i(t)P_i^0$, i.e. a function of the time-dependent load factor $\lambda_i(t)$ and the nominal load P_i^0 . This type of analysis is typically used to model static testing of structures under various force or displacement patterns ([SeismoSoft 2015](#)).

It is noted that a local damage index, such as material strain, is better correlated with structural damage due to tsunami forces compared to a global damage index (e.g. inter-storey drift). Subsequently, appropriate damage limit states are defined to account for the flexural structural failure in terms of threshold values of the material strain of the structure, based on nonlinear static analyses for the various typical structures of the port, engineering judgment and the literature (e.g. [Crowley et al. 2004](#); [Fotopoulou and Pitilakis 2013a](#); [Pitilakis 2015](#)). Four damage states are proposed in this study associated with slight, moderate, extensive and complete structural damage of the structure. Except for flexural failure, failure due to shear (the attainment of shear capacity in a structural member) is also considered and the structure's demand in terms of shear forces (i.e. EDP) is estimated. One damage state is defined in the latter case describing the complete shear failure of the structures.

The vulnerability is assessed first through probabilistic fragility curves, which describe the probability of exceeding each limit state, considering various sources of uncertainty with respect to the structural capacity and the demand defined in terms of material strain

and shear forces. A key point in the derivation of fragility curves is the selection of the intensity measure (IM) that adequately correlates with damage. According to FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008) numerical predictions of flow velocities are less accurate than predictions of inundation depths, depending very much on the grid size for numerical simulations in the run-up zone, which must be very fine in order to obtain sufficient accuracy in velocity predictions. It is noted that as flow velocity is difficult to determine from field observational data in sufficient accuracy and resolution (Reese et al. 2007), it is always calculated numerically for fragility function derivation. In addition, most existing empirical fragility functions are derived in terms of inundation depth as it is the parameter most easily measured in the field. Based on the above, inundation depth is selected as the most adequate IM for this analysis. For the development of fragility curves, an appropriate relationship between the numerically calculated material strain or shear force (i.e. the EDP) and the gradually increasing inundation depths (i.e. the IM) is established through nonlinear regression analysis. Lognormally distributed fragility curves are then derived as a function of inundation depth for the different damage limit states for the various structure typologies considered. Once the fragility curves for the considered building typologies subjected to tsunami forces are derived, a vulnerability curve can be constructed which includes also the possibility of shear failure. The vulnerability curve provides a unique damage or vulnerability index for each level of tsunami inundation depth. The damage index is a convenient measure to quantify the structural losses. It may be quantified in cost terms as the ratio of cost of repair to cost of replacement taking values from 0: no damage (cost of repair equals 0) to 1: complete damage (cost of repair equals the cost of replacement).

4.4 Reference port buildings

4.4.1 Typologies considered

Port critical buildings in Greece mainly consist of low- and pre- code RC buildings constructed before and after the introduction of the 1959 Greek seismic code ('Royal Decree' of 1959) respectively, and steel light frame warehouses. These buildings compared to other inland buildings designed according to current modern codes (high-code) would present a worse seismic behaviour, as issues such as the ductility and capacity as well as the dynamic features of the structures were ignored in their design.

The SYNER-G (www.syner-g.eu) taxonomy (Pitilakis et al. 2014a), from which European typologies for the most important elements at risk are defined, is used to describe the different RC building typologies. The studied RC buildings are classified according to their structural system (i.e. moment resisting frame MRF, dual), their height

(i.e. low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise), the existence or not of infill walls (i.e. bare frames, infilled) as well as the seismic design level (i.e. the 1959 Greek seismic code corresponding to low level of seismic design). In particular, four building typologies with shallow foundations and low level of seismic design according to the 1959 Greek seismic code ('Royal Decree' of 1959) and with a variation of number of storeys have been chosen for the study (Kappos et al. 2006). The first building typology is a two-storey three-bay frame model that is representative of low-rise (1-3 stories) MRF RC buildings. The second one is a four-storey three-bay frame structure that represents mid-rise (4-7 stories) MRF RC buildings, while the third one is a nine-storey three-bay frame model that is considered typical of high-rise (8+ stories) MRF RC buildings. Finally, the fourth one is a two-storey three-bay three-frame structure that represents low-rise Dual RC buildings (Kappos et al. 2006). In all cases the height of the 1st storey is 4.5m and that of the upper storeys is 3.0m. All these typologies are studied considering models with and without masonry infills (eight structures in total).

As it is well known, in many parts of the world, including Southern Europe, it is common practice to use unreinforced masonry infill walls without specific measures for proper connection to the surrounding RC frame, e.g. dowels or steel shapes (Kappos et al. 2003). For this reason, it was also decided to check the effect of the presence of infill walls on the response of the buildings. Regarding warehouses, they are large space steel buildings (with or without masonry infills) that represent key components of a port system (NIBS 2004). Table 4.4 summarizes the main characteristics, while Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3 illustrate representative cross-sections and the floor plans respectively of the studied RC building typologies (Kappos et al. 2006) and the typical warehouse (as provided by the Port authorities of the Port of Thessaloniki).

Table 4.4. Main characteristics of the studied building typologies

Building typology (low-code)	Total mass (tn)	Fundamental period T(sec)	f_c (Mpa)	f_y (Mpa)
Two-storey MRF bare-frame RC	65.7	0.43	14.0	400.0
Two-storey MRF infilled RC	114.9	0.18	14.0	400.0
Four-storey MRF bare-frame RC	135.0	0.58	14.0	400.0
Four-storey MRF infilled RC	233.1	0.31	14.0	400.0
Nine-storey MRF bare-frame RC	334.0	0.89	14.0	400.0
Nine-storey MRF infilled RC	550.7	0.55	14.0	400.0
Two-storey Dual bare-frame RC	131.8	0.12	14.0	400.0
Two-storey Dual infilled RC	137.6	0.11	14.0	400.0
Warehouse	5.1	0.30	-	235.0

Figure 4.3. Plan view of the a) MRF and b) Dual RC buildings and the c) warehouse

4.4.2 Numerical modelling

Two-dimensional numerical simulations of the buildings are conducted using the fibre-based finite element (FE) code Seismostruct v7.0 (SeismoSoft 2015), which is widely and successfully used in structural earthquake engineering. The RC structures are realistically reproduced in Seismostruct using non-linear constitutive models. The models are verified through eigenvalue analysis by comparing the modal periods calculated with Seismostruct v7.0 (SeismoSoft 2015) to OpenSees (Mazzoni et al. 2009) and SAP2000 (Computers and Structures Inc. 2004); deviations less than 3% are observed in all analyses (Karapetrou et al. 2015).

Inelastic force-based formulations are implemented for the nonlinear beam-column frame element modelling. Distributed material inelasticity is applied based on the fibre approach to represent the cross-sectional behaviour (Neuenhofer and Filippou 1997). Each fibre is associated with a uniaxial stress-strain relationship and the sectional stress-strain state of the beam-column elements is obtained through the integration of the nonlinear uniaxial stress-strain response of the individual fibres into which the section is subdivided. In the present analysis, the frame sections are discretised into 300 fibres. Table 4.5 summarizes the main parameters adopted for each material, while Figure 4.4 illustrates the stress-strain models for concrete and steel material as well as the double strut model with its strut and shear curves for masonry infill walls.

The concrete fibres are modelled based on the uniaxial nonlinear model proposed by Mander (1988), assuming a constant confining pressure for the confined concrete core fibres throughout the entire stress-strain range (Figure 4.4a). Five model calibrating parameters are defined to fully describe the mechanical characteristics of the material: the compressive strength (f_c), the tensile strength (f_t), the modulus of elasticity (E_c), the strain at peak stress (ϵ_c) and the specific weight (γ_c). The compressive strength of the concrete and modulus of elasticity are set equal to $f_c=14.0$ MPa and $E_c= 1.7586 \cdot 10^4$ MPa respectively. The strain at peak stress ϵ_c that is the strain corresponding to the point of peak compressive stress (f_c) is taken equal to $\epsilon_c=0.002$. A zero tensile strength of the concrete material ($f_t = 0$ MPa) is assumed.

For the reinforcement, a uniaxial bilinear stress-strain model with kinematic strain hardening is utilised (Figure 4.4b). Five model calibrating parameters are again defined including the modulus of elasticity (E_s), the yield strength (f_y), the strain hardening parameter (μ), the fracture/buckling strain (ϵ_{ult}) and the specific weight (γ_s). The modulus of elasticity and the yield strength are taken equal to $E_s = 2.0 \cdot 10^5$ MPa and $f_y=400.0$ MPa respectively. The strain hardening parameter (μ) defined as the ratio between the post-yield stiffness and the initial elastic stiffness of the material is assumed equal to $\mu=0.01$. Finally, the strain at which fracture or buckling occurs (ϵ_{ult}) is taken equal to 0.1.

The total mass is applied as uniformly distributed along the beams (as distributed loads) and columns (by assigning the specific weight of steel and concrete material). For the simulation of dual frames, appropriate constraints (i.e. rigid links) are considered to account for the stiffness of the walls. In addition, in models with more than one frame, Equal DOF constraints are used to take into consideration the equal degrees-of-freedom between the frames.

Table 4.5. Summary of the main parameters adopted for each material

Parameter	Description	Material	Adopted value
f_c (MPa)	Compressive strength	Concrete	14.0
f_t (MPa)	Tensile strength	Concrete	0
E_c (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity	Concrete	$1.7586 \cdot 10^4$
ε_c	Strain at peak stress	Concrete	0.002
γ_c (kN/m ³)	Specific weight	Concrete	24.0
E_s (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity	Reinforcement	$2.0 \cdot 10^5$
f_y (MPa)	Yield strength	Reinforcement	400.0
μ	Strain hardening parameter	Reinforcement	0.01
ε_{ult}	Fracture/buckling strain	Reinforcement	0.1
γ_s (kN/m ³)	Specific weight	Reinforcement	78.0
E_s (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity	Steel	$2.1 \cdot 10^5$
f_y (MPa)	Steel yield strength	Steel	235.0
μ	Steel strain hardening parameter	Steel	0.01
E_m	Initial Young modulus	Infill walls	$1.5 \cdot 10^3$
f_m (MPa)	Compressive strength	Infill walls	1.5
$f_{t(m)}$ (MPa)	Tensile strength	Infill walls	0
τ_0 (MPa)	Shear bond strength	Infill walls	0.3
$\mu(m)$	Friction coefficient	Infill walls	0.7
T_{max} (MPa)	Maximum shear resistance	Infill walls	1.0
α_s	Reduction shear factor	Infill walls	1.5
t (m)	Panel thickness	Infill walls	0.15
(%)	Out-of-plane failure drift	Infill walls	5.0
A1	Strut area A_1	Infill walls	varies
A2	Strut area A_2	Infill walls	10% A_1
h_z (%)	Equivalent contact length	Infill walls	varies
x_{oi} (%)	Horizontal offset	Infill walls	calculated from frame geometry
y_{oi} (%)	Vertical offset	Infill walls	calculated from frame geometry
$Y_{s(m)}$	Proportion of stiffness assigned to shear	Infill walls	20.0
γ_m (kN/m ³)	Specific weight	Infill walls	5.0

Figure 4.4. Stress-strain models for concrete (a) and steel (b) material and the (c) double strut model with its (d) strut and (e) shear curves for masonry infill walls (SeismoSoft, SeismoStruct 2015)

The nonlinear response of the masonry panel element in the case of the infilled frame models is simulated based on the double strut model (Figure 4.4c) proposed by Crisafulli (1997). Each panel is represented by strut members that carry the axial loads across two opposite diagonal corners and the shear from the top to the bottom of the panel. This

latter strut acts only across the diagonal in compression; hence its activation depends on the deformation of the panel. The axial load struts use the masonry strut hysteresis model (Figure 4.4d), while the shear strut uses a dedicated bilinear hysteresis rule (Figure 4.4e), both developed and initially programmed by Crisafulli (1997) and implemented in SeismoStruct by Blandon (2005). Four internal nodes are employed to account for the actual points of contact between the frame and the infill panel (i.e. to account for the width and height of the columns and beams respectively), whilst four dummy nodes are introduced with the objective of accounting for the contact length between the frame and the infill panel (Figure 4.4c). All the internal forces are transformed to the exterior four nodes where the element is connected to the frame. The main parameters to represent masonry infills behaviour are: the strut curve parameters, the shear curve parameters, the infill panel thickness (t), the out-of-plane failure drift, the strut areas (A_1 and A_2), the equivalent contact length (h_z), the horizontal and vertical offsets (x_{oi} and y_{oi}), the proportion of stiffness assigned to shear ($\gamma_{s(m)}$) and finally the specific weight (γ_m). A more detailed description of the above parameters can be found in Crisafulli (1997).

In particular, the initial young modulus (E_m) and the compressive strength ($f_{m\theta}$) are taken equal to $f_{m\theta}=1.5\text{MPa}$ (Calvi et al. 2004) and $E_m=1000f_{m\theta}=1500.0\text{MPa}$ (Crisafulli 1997), a zero tensile strength of the masonry material ($f_{t(m)}=0\text{MPa}$) is assumed as well as other fourteen parameters are defined using the default values suggested/calibrated by Blandon (2005) and Smyrou et al. (2011) to characterise the masonry infill strut curve. In addition, four calibrating parameters need to be defined in order to fully characterise the shear curve namely the shear bond strength (τ_0), the friction coefficient ($\mu_{(m)}$), the maximum shear strength (τ_{\max}) and the reduction shear factor (α_s). The shear bond strength, the friction coefficient and the maximum shear strength are taken equal to $\tau_0=0.3\text{Mpa}$, $\mu_{(m)}=0.7$ and $\tau_{\max}=1.0\text{Mpa}$ respectively, while the reduction shear factor which represents the ratio between the maximum shear stress and the average stress in the panel is taken equal to $\alpha_s=1.5$. Also, a 5% out-of-plane failure drift and a $\gamma_{s(m)}=20\%$ proportion of stiffness assigned to shear are assumed. The equivalent contact length (h_z) is calculated as the average of 1/3 to 1/2 of the actual contact length (z), which is defined according to Stafford-Smith (1966). The strut area $A_1 (=t \cdot b_w)$ is defined as the product of the panel thickness (t) and the equivalent width of the strut (b_w), which is estimated according to Mainstone and Weeks (1970), and the strut area A_2 is estimated as 10% of A_1 , while the horizontal and vertical offsets (x_{oi} and y_{oi}) are calculated from the geometry of the frames. Finally, the infill panel thickness and the specific weight are adopted equal to $t=0.15\text{m}$ and $\gamma_m=5.0\text{ kN/m}^3$.

Regarding the warehouse modelling, the uniaxial bilinear model with kinematic strain-hardening is employed for the steel material (modulus of elasticity $E_s = 2.1 \cdot 10^5$ MPa; yield strength $f_y = 235.0$ MPa; strain hardening parameter $\mu = 0.01$). Columns are modelled using force-based inelastic frame elements (infrmFB) with 4 integration sections, while trusses are modelled through truss elements (truss). The number of fibres used in section equilibrium computations in both cases is set to 300. The masses are applied as distributed along columns and beams (by assigning the specific weight of steel material) plus concentrated vertical loads on joints due to the existence of trusses on the normal direction.

4.5 Tsunami loading pattern

4.5.1 Determination of tsunami forces

Currently available structural design standards and guidelines on loads induced by tsunami, e.g. FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008); MLIT 2570 (MLIT 2011); ASCE 7 (Chock 2015), as well as the HAZUS tsunami loss estimation methodology (FEMA 2017), commonly split the tsunami loads into different components. According to FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008), tsunami load effects include hydrostatic forces, buoyant forces, hydrodynamic forces, impulsive forces, debris impact forces and uplift forces in addition to debris damming forces and additional gravity loads from retained water on elevated floors. Due to the complexity of the tsunami hazard, in addition to the lack of either experimental or analytical expressions for realistic tsunami loading assessment taking into account all the aforementioned load effects, no firm policy has been established yet defining a methodology for specifying tsunami forces equations for rehabilitation purposes.

FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008) maintains that maximum tsunami loading must be considered uncertain, as large damaging tsunamis are rare events and existing knowledge is based on limited historic information. Thus, conservative assumptions should be made, to account for the various uncertainties involved. For this reason, in this study, appropriate combinations of these forces calculated according to FEMA P646 prescriptions (FEMA 2008) are applied as static loads to the selected structures to assess their vulnerability to tsunami hazard. A brief description of these forces as well as the main assumptions made in this study follows below.

Hydrostatic forces occur when standing or slowly moving water encounters a structure or structural component. They always act perpendicular to the surface of the component of interest (Figure 4.5). These forces may not be relevant to a structure with a finite (i.e. relatively short) breadth, around which the water can quickly flow and fill in on all sides.

They are implemented on walls enclosing watertight areas of a structure. The horizontal hydrostatic force on a wall panel is computed using equation (FEMA 2008):

$$F_h = \frac{1}{2} \rho_s g b h_{max}^2 \quad (4.1)$$

where ρ_s is the fluid density including sediment, b is the breadth (width) of the wall and h_{max} is the maximum water height above the base of the wall at the structure location (inundation depth).

Figure 4.5. Hydrostatic force distribution and location of resultant (FEMA 2008)

In this study, considering that tsunami flows consist of a mixture of sediment and seawater and based on an assumption of vertically averaged sediment-volume concentration of 10% in seawater, the fluid density of tsunami flow is taken as 1.2 times the density of freshwater, or $\rho_s = 1,200 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (FEMA 2008). Also, the breadth (width) of the wall is taken equal to the width of the effective zone of the perpendicular wall (see Figure 4.3). In particular, the breadth of the wall is taken equal to 3.0 m for the internal frames of the MRF bare-frame and infilled models and 4.5 m for the internal frames of the dual bare and infilled models, while for the external frames of the infilled MRF and Dual models half of the previously mentioned values are taken. It is noted that hydrostatic forces are only applicable at the infilled models, considering watertight walls, assuming that tsunami flow cannot enter the building.

Buoyant or vertical hydrostatic forces act vertically through the centroid of the displaced volume on a structure or structural component subjected to partial or total submergence (Figure 4.6). For a watertight structure, the total buoyant force is given by the following equation (FEMA 2008):

$$F_b = \rho_s g V \quad (4.2)$$

where ρ_s is the fluid density including sediment (1200.0 kg/m^3) and V is the volume of water displaced by the building. It is noted that watertight floor is considered in all models and thus buoyant forces are applied.

Figure 4.6. Buoyant forces on an overall building with watertight lower levels (FEMA 2008)

Hydrodynamic Forces occur when steady water flows around a structure. Also known as drag forces, they are a combination of the lateral forces caused by the pressure forces from the moving mass of water and the friction forces generated as the water flows around the structure or component (Figure 4.7). Hydrodynamic forces can be computed using the following equation (FEMA 2008; Yeh 2007):

$$F_d = \frac{1}{2} \rho_s C_d B (hu^2)_{max} \quad (4.3)$$

where ρ_s is the fluid density including sediment (1200.0 kg/m^3), C_d is the drag coefficient, conservatively taken equal to 2.0 as recommended by FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008), B is the breadth of the structure in the plane normal to the direction of flow, h is flow depth and u is flow velocity at the location of the structure.

Figure 4.7. Hydrodynamic force distribution and location of resultant (FEMA 2008)

The hydrodynamic forces are based on the parameter $(hu^2)_{max}$, which is the maximum momentum flux per unit mass occurring at the site at any time during the tsunami. It can be obtained by running a detailed numerical simulation model or acquiring existing simulation data. The value $(hu^2)_{max}$ is estimated using the following equation (FEMA 2008; Yeh 2007):

$$(hu^2)_{max} = gR^2 \left(0.125 - 0.235 \frac{z}{R} + 0.11 \left(\frac{z}{R} \right)^2 \right) \quad (4.4)$$

where R is the design run-up elevation and z is the ground elevation at the base of the structure. Considering the significant variability in local tsunami run-up heights, based on local bathymetry and topographic effects, and the uncertainty in numerical simulations of tsunami inundation, the design run-up elevation, R , is taken as 1.3 times the predicted maximum run-up elevation, R^* , to envelope the potential variability (FEMA 2008). The inundation depth (h) is equal to maximum run-up elevation subtracting the ground elevation (R^*-z). FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008) recommends numerically predicted values of $(hu^2)_{max}$ not be taken less than 80% of the values computed using Equation 4.4, because of uncertainties in modelling tsunami inundation. A mean value of elevation z (representing the topography) equal to 0.5m is considered (Pitilakis et al. 2016). Regarding the inundation depth (representing the hazard) gradually increasing values are considered to assess the structural response and finally derive the corresponding fragility curves.

Impulsive forces are very short duration loads caused by the leading edge of a surge of water impacting a structure. The impulsive forces are conservatively taken as 1.5 times the hydrodynamic force, as shown in the following equation (FEMA 2008):

$$F_s = 1.5 F_d \quad (4.5)$$

Once the leading edge of the surge has passed a structural component, it will no longer experience the impulsive force, but rather a sustained hydrodynamic drag force, F_d . Thus, impulsive forces will act on members at the leading edge of the surge, while hydrodynamic forces will act on all previously submerged members behind the leading edge (Figure 4.8). The worst case lateral load will likely occur when the leading edge of the surge reaches the last components in the building frame (FEMA 2008), as considered in this study.

$F_{S,c1}$: Impulsive forces on columns and beams at leading edge of bore
 $F_{d,c1}$: Drag forces on columns and beams behind leading edge of bore
 c_1 and c_2 : Columns at first and second levels, b_2 : Beams at second level

Figure 4.8. Hydrodynamic impulsive and drag forces on components of a building subjected to inundation by a tsunami bore (FEMA 2008)

The *impact force waterborne debris* (e.g. floating driftwood, lumber, boats, shipping containers, automobiles, buildings) can be a dominant cause of building damage (Figure 4.9). Herein, the worst case lateral load is considered. In particular, when the leading edge of the surge fully impacts the most closed off section of the building, debris impact forces act on the structure. The debris impact force can be estimated using equation (FEMA 2008; Yeh 2007):

$$F_i = C_m u_{max} \sqrt{km} \tag{4.6}$$

where C_m is the added mass coefficient (recommended value equal to 2.0), u_{max} is the maximum flow velocity carrying the debris at the site and m and k are the mass and the effective stiffness of the debris respectively. Approximate values of m and k for common waterborne debris are proposed by FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008) as presented in Table 4.6.

Figure 4.9. Waterborne debris impact force (FEMA 2008)

Table 4.6. Mass and Stiffness Properties of Common Waterborne Debris (FEMA 2008)

Location of Source	Mass (m) in kg	Effective stiffness (k) in N/m
Lumber of Wood Log	450	2.4×10^6
40-ft Standard Shipping Container	3800 (empty)	6.5×10^8
20-ft Standard Shipping Container	2200 (empty)	1.5×10^9
20-ft Heavy Slipping Container	2400 (empty)	1.7×10^9

In this study, lumber of wood log with the mass and the effective stiffness of the debris equal to 450.0 kg and $2.4 \cdot 10^6$ N/m respectively is considered as the waterborne debris. The maximum flow velocity at the site can be estimated using equation (FEMA 2008; Yeh 2007):

$$u_{max} = \sqrt{2gR \left(1 - \frac{z}{R}\right)} \tag{4.7}$$

where g is the acceleration due to gravity, R is the design run-up height and z is the ground elevation at the structure (the datum must be at the sea level). Following FEMA P646 (Appendix C) (FEMA 2008), for an assumed draft, d , of the log equal to 0.25m, the

ratio of the draft d to the maximum run-up height R is computed, and the FEMA (2008) proposed chart (of maximum flow velocity as a function of depth " d " at the ground elevation " z ", and maximum run-up elevation " R ") shown in Figure 4.10, is used to estimate the maximum flow velocity.

Figure 4.10. Maximum flow velocity of depth, d , at the ground elevation, z , and maximum runup elevation, R . The bottom curve represents the lower limit of maximum flow velocity (FEMA 2008)

Uplift forces are due to buoyancy and hydrodynamic forces and are applied to floor levels of a building that are submerged by tsunami inundation (Figure 4.11). The total uplift force on the floor system can be estimated using equation (FEMA 2008):

$$F_u = \frac{1}{2} C_u \rho_s A_f u_v^2 \quad (4.8)$$

where C_u is a coefficient (taken as 3.0), ρ_s is the fluid density including sediment (1200 kg/m³), A_f is the area of the floor panel or floor framing component, and u_v is the estimated vertical velocity or water rise rate as $u_v = u \tan \alpha$, where u is the horizontal flow velocity corresponding to a water depth, h_s , equal to the elevation of the soffit of the floor system, and α is the average slope of grade at the site (assumed equal to 1/5).

In this study uplift forces are only applicable to the mid- and high- rise MRFs as in the case of the low-rise MRF and dual frames the collapse comes before the inundation depth reaches the second floor.

Figure 4.11. A definition sketch for upward buoyant force exerted on an elevated floor (FEMA 2008)

Appropriate combinations of tsunami-induced force components (hydrostatic, hydrodynamic, surge, buoyant, uplift and debris impact force) are used in calculating the total tsunami forces acting on the structural models depending on their typology as recommended by FEMA and the available literature (Park et al. 2012; Nayak et al. 2014). More specifically, for the bare-frame models it is assumed that tsunami flow can enter the building, while for the infilled models tsunami flow cannot enter the building and cannot completely destroy the existing masonry infills.

As an example, Table 4.7 presents a summary of the computed tsunami-induced forces, which are applied to the nine-storey MRF bare-frame RC building for an inundation depth equal to 5.0 m (higher than the height of the first floor, so uplift forces are applicable) and the parameters needed to estimate them. After specifying the inundation depth, the other parameters are calculated according to the equations presented above. Similar tables are produced for every single tsunami inundation depth considered in order to calculate the tsunami-induced forces that would be applied to each model. The computed forces are then directly applied as input time-variant static loads to the nonlinear structural models. The tsunami inundation depth is gradually increased (and the different values mentioned above) until building collapse occurred.

4.5.2 Numerical analysis

Nonlinear static time-history analyses are performed for all models while static analyses are carried out before the onset of tsunami nonlinear analysis to account for the gravity forces. Tsunami forces calculated according to FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008) are statically imposed on the structures at the location of each load's resultant depending on the inundation depth (h). In particular, the hydrodynamic (F_d) and impulsive (F_s) forces are applied at $h/2$ from the base of the structure, the debris impact force (F_i) is applied

at h from the base of the structure while the hydrostatic forces (F_h) are applied at $h/3$ from the base of the structure. Buoyant forces (F_b) are applied at the base of the RC buildings. As noted previously the uplift forces (F_u) are applicable only in the cases where the inundation depth exceeds the height of the first floor (i.e. for the four-storey and nine-storey MRFs). The amplitude of the tsunami forces increases with increasing inundation depth.

Table 4.7. Computed tsunami-induced forces applied to the nine-storey MRF bare-frame RC building and the parameters needed to estimate them

Tsunami-induced force components			Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values	
Hydrostatic force F_h (kN)			-	Run-up height R (m)	4.23	k (N/m)	$2.4 \cdot 10^6$
Buoyant force F_b (kN)	External bay	879.37	Design run-up height R^* (m)	5.50	m (kg)	450	
			Elevation z (m)	0.50	draft d (m)	0.25	
	Internal bays	586.25	Inundation depth h (m)	5.00	d/R	0.045	
			Fluid density ρ_s (KN/m³)	1200	z/R	0.091	
Hydrodynamic force F_d (kN)			111.64	Length L (m)	16.0	u_v	2.49
				Width b (m)	3.0	$\tan\alpha$	0.20
Impulsive force F_s (kN)			167.46	Floor panel area A_f (m²)	48.0	Coefficient C_u	3.0
Debris impact force F_i (kN)			430.10	Drag coefficient C_d	2.0	h_s	3.9
Uplift force F_u (kN)	External bay	188.17	Maximum momentum flux $(hu^2)_{max}$ (m³/sec²)	31.01	h_s/R	0.92	
	Internal bays	125.45	Added mass coefficient C_m	2.0	z/R	0.09	
			u_{max} (m/s)	6.54			

Different combinations of tsunami forces are considered according to FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008) prescriptions as well as the assumptions presented in the previous section. All loads are applied in proportion to each other assuming linearly increasing time-variant loads with a constant time step up to the (maximum) calculated values. The analyses are performed for different levels of inundation depth (at least 20 levels), varying from very small values (e.g. $h=0.5\text{m}$), which result to negligible structural damage to large ones (e.g. $h=10.0\text{m}$) which may lead to significant structural damages and potential collapse. All the combinations of tsunami loading for the different analysed building types are presented in Figure 4.12 to Figure 4.15.

Figure 4.12. Tsunami loading conditions for the two-storey MRF (a) bare-frame, (b) infilled RC building and the two-storey Dual (c) bare-frame and (d) infilled RC building (where F_h , F_b , F_d , F_s , and F_i are the hydrostatic, buoyant, hydrodynamic, impulsive and debris impact tsunami-induced force components respectively)

Figure 4.13. Tsunami loading conditions for the four-storey MRF (a) bare-frame where d is lower than the height of the first floor, (b) bare-frame, where d is higher than the height of the first floor (uplift forces are applicable) and the (c) infilled RC building (where F_h , F_b , F_d , F_s , F_i and F_u are the hydrostatic, buoyant, hydrodynamic, impulsive, debris impact and uplift tsunami-induced force components respectively)

Figure 4.14. Tsunami loading conditions for the nine-storey MRF (a) bare-frame where d is lower than the height of the first floor, (b) bare-frame where d is higher than the height of the first floor (uplift forces are applicable) and the (c) infilled RC building (where F_h , F_b , F_d , F_s , F_i and F_u are the hydrostatic, buoyant, hydrodynamic, impulsive, debris impact and uplift tsunami-induced force components respectively)

Figure 4.15. Numerical simulation of tsunami loading for the warehouse (where F_d , F_i and F_s are the hydrodynamic, debris impact and impulsive tsunami-induced force components respectively)

4.6 Fragility curves

4.6.1 Definition of damage limit states

The definition of realistic damage limit states is of paramount importance for the construction of fragility curves. The selection of appropriate EDP to correlate with the selected IM (inundation depth) is a real challenge, as a general framework for EDP has not yet been established in literature. When a building response to tsunami comprises structural damage, damage states can be classified using the same schemes used for structural damage triggered by an earthquake. However, the use of a global damage index such as the inter-storey drift is not appropriate to be used as a tsunami EDP because the expected deformed shape and damage mechanism of the structure impacted by a tsunami is quite different from that of the same structure subjected to ground shaking (e.g. [Macabuag et al. 2014](#)).

Thus, a local damage index in terms of building's material strain should be used as it allows an improved correlation with structural deformation and damage. In the first phase of this study, the occurrence of shear failure in the elements is neglected, assuming that the lateral resistance is controlled by the flexural failure in the beams or columns. Four limit states (LS1, LS2, LS3 and LS4) are defined (minor, moderate, extensive and complete damage) based on nonlinear static analyses (tsunami time-history analyses) for the various structure typologies and engineering judgment (e.g. [NIBS 2004](#); [Crowley et al. 2004](#); [Fotopoulou and Ptilakis 2013a](#)). According to [NIBS \(2004\)](#), "Steel Light Frames" structures are mostly single-storey structures combining rod-braced frames in one direction and moment frames in the other. Due to the repetitive nature of the structural systems, the type of damage to structural members is expected to be rather uniform throughout the structure. Consequently, warehouses are considered as "Steel Light Frames" structures. The qualitative description of each damage state for RC frames and warehouses adopted in this research work is provided in Table 4.8 and Table 4.9, respectively.

Table 4.8. Structural damage state description for RC frame buildings ([Crowley et al. 2004](#))

Limit state	Structural damage	Description
LS1	None to slight	Linear elastic response, flexural or shear type hairline cracks (<1.0 mm) in some members, no yielding in any critical section
LS2	Moderate	Member flexural strengths achieved, limited ductility developed, crack widths reach 1.0 mm, initiation of concrete spalling
LS3	Extensive	Significant repair required to building, wide flexural or shear cracks, buckling of longitudinal reinforcement may occur
LS4	Complete	Repair of building not feasible either physically or economically, demolition required, could be due to shear failure of vertical elements or excessive displacement

Table 4.9. Structural damage state descriptions for warehouses, *Steel Light Frames* (NIBS 2004)

Limit state	Structural damage	Description
LS1	None to slight	Few steel rod braces have yielded which may be indicated by minor sagging of rod braces. Minor cracking at welded connections or minor deformations at bolted connections of moment frames may be observed
LS2	Moderate	Most steel braces have yielded exhibiting observable significantly sagging rod braces; few brace connections may be broken. Some weld cracking may be observed in the moment frame connections
LS3	Extensive	Significant permanent lateral deformation of the structure due to broken brace rods, stretched anchor bolts and permanent deformations at moment frame members. Some screw or welded attachments of roof and wall siding to steel framing may be broken. Some purlin and girt connections may be broken
LS4	Complete	Structure is collapsed or in imminent danger of collapse due to broken rod bracing, failed anchor bolts or failed structural members or connections. Approximately 3% of the total area of the buildings with complete damage is expected to collapse

In order to minimize the uncertainties associated with the selection of the appropriate damage limit states, nonlinear static analyses are performed for the different structures to define structure-specific limit state values (in terms of strains) for each damage state. The limit state values finally adopted are presented in Table 4.10. Figure 4.16 and Figure 4.17 illustrate the definition of limit states on the corresponding tsunami capacity curves derived from the tsunami nonlinear static analyses for the various structure typologies. It is noted that the tsunami capacity curves are not extracted from a single nonlinear static analysis as for a seismic capacity curve (derived from a pushover analysis) but from the total number of the tsunami nonlinear static time-history analyses. This is done considering that the location and amplitude of the applied tsunami forces changes as a function of the inundation depth.

It is seen that for all analysis cases, steel strain (ϵ_s) gives more critical results. Hence, hereafter, the proposed damage limit states are defined in terms of steel bar strain. In particular, for the MRF models with bare frames the first limit state is specified as steel bar yielding while for the infilled ones the infills cracking is assigned as the first limit state and steel bar yielding as the second one. For the rest limit states, mean values of post-yield limit strains for steel reinforcement are suggested. It should be noted that tsunami capacity curves of the four-storey and nine-storey MRF infilled models do not reach the complete damage state set for the infilled MRF RC buildings, so the definition of complete limit state should be treated with caution. Moreover, it is observed that the capacity curve of the nine-story MRF infilled frame increases again after the maximum steel strain of 0.01. This could be due to the presence of the infill walls possibly combined with P-delta effects, that are generally more pronounced for the high-rise

building (Fenwick et al. 1992), which make the behaviour of the structure unpredictable at high deformation levels. Considering that, for the sake of simplicity, the aim here is not to propose a range of limit strain values depending on the height of the building, but a single limit strain value depending on the typology of it (bare or infilled MRF), it was decided to adopt the same (mean) limit state value for the complete damage state for all MRF infilled RC buildings.

For the dual models, the steel strain limits considered in MRF models cannot be used to characterize the extensive and complete damage of the dual systems, as they lead to lower levels of maximum steel strain on the tsunami capacity curve. Thus, increased values of steel bar strain limits are adopted. It should be noted that the behaviour of the dual models when considering or not infills does not change considerably. This is to be expected considering that the contribution of the infills to the total stiffness of the model is small compared to that of the shear-wall. Based on the above considerations, the same limit strain values are specified for both bare and infilled dual structures. The same procedure is followed for the definition of the limit state values for the warehouse (steel light frame structures).

Table 4.10. Definition of limit states for the different structure typologies considered

Limit states	Steel strain (ϵ_s)			
	MRF bare frames	MRF with infills	Dual with/without infills	Warehouse
Limit state 1	0.002	0.0007	0.002	0.00112
Limit state 2	0.0125	0.002	0.0125	0.0125
Limit state 3	0.025	0.010	0.04	0.03
Limit state 4	0.045	0.020	0.08	0.055

Figure 4.16. Limit states definition on tsunami capacity curves for the warehouse

Figure 4.17. Limit states definition on tsunami capacity curves for the different RC building typologies

Failure due to shear is also considered to the RC building typologies in the second phase of the study, since the collapse of structures may be caused by the occurrence of shear failure. Shear failure is identified as the attainment of shear capacity in a member calculated according to Annex A of Eurocode 8- Part 3 (CEN 2005). In particular, the demand on the buildings columns, in terms of shear forces, is evaluated using the results of the nonlinear static time-history analysis and compared to the shear capacity of the columns.

One damage state is defined for the considered MRF and dual bare-frame and infilled RC building typologies, describing the complete shear failure of the structures. Complete shear failure is assumed when at least 50% of the columns in a storey reach their shear capacity (Kappos et al. 2006; Celarec and Dolsek 2013).

In particular, for the selected structures, the first shear failure is always observed at the 1st storey (left) column (Col 1-1), where tsunami loads are applied. An example of the shear capacity check conducted for the two-storey MRF bare-frame RC building is presented in Table 4.11.

Table 4.11. Shear capacity check of the two-storey MRF bare-frame RC building subjected to tsunami forces

Inundation depth (m)	Shear force in 1 st storey columns (kN)			
	Col 1-1 (left column)	Col 1-2 (middle column)	Col 1-3 (middle column)	Col 1-4 (right column)
1.00	46.96	8.65	4.04	14.60
1.20	53.76	11.82	7.44	17.95
1.40	61.60	15.53	11.83	21.73
1.60	65.93	19.62	16.89	26.21
1.80	71.51	24.50	22.88	31.60
2.00	76.00	30.22	29.46	37.85
2.20	76.24	36.81	36.55	45.27
2.30	76.46	40.25	40.20	49.27
2.40	76.70	44.10	44.21	53.80
2.50	77.41	48.43	48.71	58.84
2.55	81.70	54.22	55.45	62.68

*The values in bold indicate that the shear capacity is reached.

4.6.2 Generation of fragility curves

Fragility curves describe the probability of exceeding predefined levels of damage under a tsunami event of a given intensity. The results of the nonlinear numerical

analysis (inundation depth - steel strain values) are used to derive fragility curves expressed as two-parameter lognormal distribution functions. Log-normal distributions have been used extensively to introduce dispersion for other natural hazards (Park et al. 2012). The following equation gives the cumulative probability of exceeding a DS conditioned on a measure of the tsunami intensity IM:

$$P[DS_i/IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM) - \ln(\overline{IM}_i)}{\beta}\right) \quad (4.9)$$

where, Φ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function, IM is the intensity measure of the tsunami expressed in terms of inundation depth (in units of m), \overline{IM}_i and β are the median values (in units of m) and log-standard deviations respectively of the building fragilities for each damage state i and DS_i is the damage state.

The median values of inundation depth corresponding to the prescribed damage states are determined based on a regression analysis of the nonlinear static analysis results (inundation depth - steel strain pairs) for each structural model. More specifically, a second order polynomial fit of the logarithms of the inundation depth - steel strain data, which minimizes the regression residuals, is adopted in all cases. Figure 4.18 shows indicatively the derived inundation depth - steel strain relationship for the four-storey MRF bare-frame RC building.

Figure 4.18. Inundation depth - steel strain relationship for the four-storey MRF bare-frame RC building

The various uncertainties are taken into account through the log-standard deviation parameter β , which describes the total dispersion related to each fragility curve. The primary sources of uncertainty, which contribute to the total variability for any given damage state, are those associated with the capacity (β_c) of each structural type and the demand (β_D). The log-standard deviation value in the definition of the capacity is assumed to be equal to 0.3 for low-code buildings (NIBS 2004). The uncertainty in the

demand is considered by calculating the dispersion of the logarithms of inundation depth - steel strain simulated data with respect to the regression fit (Fotopoulou and Pitilakis 2013a; Cornell et al. 2002).

It is noted that for each building there is a specific response at each inundation depth and therefore the dispersion on the demand is due to the different responses at increasing inundation depths and not due to the different responses at the same inundation depth. Under the assumption that these two log-standard deviation components are statistically independent, the total log-standard deviation is estimated as the root of the sum of the squares of the component dispersions (see equation 4.10).

$$\beta = \sqrt{\beta_C^2 + \beta_D^2} \quad (4.10)$$

The herein computed log-standard deviation β values of the curves vary from 0.33 to 0.57 for all structural models. Figure 4.19 and Figure 4.20 illustrate the computed sets of fragility curves for the warehouse and the RC building typologies respectively with their lognormally distributed fragility parameters (median m and log-standard deviation β) in terms of inundation depth.

For the cases where at least 50% of the columns in a storey reach their shear capacity, new fragility curves for the complete damage state due to shear are derived. Figure 4.21 presents the comparison between the new fragility curves for the complete damage state due to shear failure (SF) with the corresponding ones due to flexural failure (FF). In these cases, it is shown that shear failure is the prevailing failure mechanism of the structure.

Figure 4.19. Fragility curves for the warehouse

Figure 4.20. Fragility curves for the different RC building typologies

Figure 4.21. Fragility curves for the complete damage state due to flexural (FF) or shear (SF) failure

4.6.3 Generation of vulnerability curves

Once the probabilities of exceeding the specified damage states are estimated, a damage (or vulnerability) index d_m is evaluated for each tsunami inundation depth according to the following expression:

$$d_{mj} = \sum_{i=1}^4 P_{ij} \cdot d_i \tag{4.11}$$

where d_{mj} is the damage index (taking values from 0: no damage to 1: complete damage) corresponding to tsunami intensity level j , P_{ij} is the discrete damage probability

for each damage state and d_i stands for the damage index at each of the considered damage states.

For the RC buildings, the central value of the damage index for each damage state (i.e. d_i) is assumed equal to 0.05, 0.20, 0.45 and 0.80 for the LS₁, LS₂, LS₃ and LS₄ respectively according to Kappos et al. (2006). A vulnerability curve is then constructed for each structural typology which provides a unique damage or vulnerability index d_m for each level of tsunami inundation depth. Figure 4.22 illustrates the derived vulnerability curves for the RC building typologies subjected to tsunami forces, which include also the possibility of shear failure. It is noted that with the given curves, losses in the RC structural members of the buildings are accounted for.

Figure 4.22. Vulnerability curves for the low-code bare-frame (left) and infilled (right) RC buildings subjected to tsunami forces

Due to the fact that the cost of the RC structural system (including the infills) totals less than the cost of a (new) building (which also includes non-structural members), the computed damage indices could then be multiplied with an empirically derived reductive coefficient to derive the final global damage index. According to Kappos et al. (2006) for the low, mid and high-rise residential RC MRF buildings this coefficient varies from 0.33 to 0.38 (values that have been calibrated against cost of damage data from Greece). Thus, it is implicitly shown that the total cost of non-structural damage, e.g. damage to ceilings, mechanical and electrical equipment that is an integral part of the structure, piping and elevators, partitions, exterior walls, ornamentation, glass (NIBS 2004), may be higher compared to the cost of repairs required to the RC structural system itself. If an average replacement cost is assumed for the considered low-code RC buildings then the final global damage index multiplied with these values returns the total cost of repairs in each building due to structural and non-structural damage.

For the steel light frame warehouse, the central value of the damage index for each damage state (i.e. d_i) is assumed equal to 0.10, 0.40, 0.75 and 1.00 for the LS₁, LS₂, LS₃ and LS₄ respectively according to [Blong \(2003\)](#). Figure 4.23 illustrates the derived vulnerability curve for the steel light frame warehouse subjected to tsunami forces.

Figure 4.23. Vulnerability curve for the steel light frame warehouse subjected to tsunami forces

Similarly with RC buildings, as the cost of the steel structural system totals less than the cost of a new building, which also includes non-structural members, the damage indices are multiplied with a reductive coefficient equal to 0.5 to derive the final damage index.

4.6.4 Discussion

A general observation is that the high-rise RC buildings present lower vulnerability compared to the low-rise ones, which is in accordance with the empirical observation ([Suppasri et al. 2013](#)), where buildings taller than two stories were found much stronger than the buildings of one or two stories under the same inundation depth. It is also shown that the low-rise and mid-rise buildings with infills are more vulnerable compared to the corresponding models with bare frames. This trend also holds true for the high-rise MRF for the exceedance of none to slight and moderate damage. This observation may be due to the presence of infill walls where we assume that tsunami flow cannot enter the building and cannot completely destroy the existing masonry infills. Thus, in this case hydrostatic forces are also applicable to the structures which may increase their deformation demand and finally their vulnerability. Additionally, this is in accordance with the FEMA guideline, which recommends the design of vertical evacuation buildings with breakaway walls or open construction in the lower levels to allow water to pass through with minimal resistance.

In contrast, when extensive or complete damage of the high-rise MRF structures is anticipated, the bare-frame is expected to sustain larger damages in comparison with the corresponding infilled one. This could be due to the fact that, for the high-rise building, the infills of the upper floors are less affected by the tsunami waves making the remaining resistance of the infilled building higher compared to the bare-frame for extensive and complete damage states. Moreover, it is seen that the low-rise dual models are more vulnerable compared to the corresponding MRFs. The latter could be related to the concentration of large tsunami forces in shear walls. This is the reason why FEMA recommends for the design of vertical evacuation structures, shear walls be oriented parallel to the anticipated direction of tsunami flow to reduce associated tsunami forces.

Regarding the fragility curves for the warehouse they are generally similar to the ones of the low-rise and mid-rise MRF RC buildings. Similar observations are in [Macabuag et al. \(2016\)](#) who using a detailed damage dataset from the 2011 Great East Japan earthquake and tsunami (total 67.125 buildings) also observed that the damage state distributions of buildings of RC and steel construction materials (typically considered as engineered construction materials) are very similar to each other. It is also observed that the difference between the damage states is not so large indicating that once yielding occurs; the structure very rapidly attains the post-yield limit states.

An important observation is that the shear failure is the prevailing failure mechanism of the structure for all the MRF RC buildings with bare frames, regardless of their height. Moreover, the infilled high-rise MRF and low-rise dual models also collapse due to shear (Figure 4.21). Those results indicate that the consideration of masonry infills may have a significant impact on the response and finally on the failure mechanism of the structures (i.e. flexural or shear).

4.6.5 Comparison with empirical fragility curves obtained from field data

The numerical tsunami fragility curves proposed in this study for a number of generic structures are first compared with the few available empirical ones [Suppasri et al. \(2013; 2015\)](#) obtained using field survey data from the 2011 Great East Japan tsunami for RC and steel structures. Unfortunately the typology of RC and steel buildings in Japan and Greece (Europe as well) is not that same and consequently the definition of damage states is also different.

In particular, [Suppasri et al. \(2013; 2015\)](#) classified building damage into six levels (i.e. Level 1: minor damage - no significant structural or non-structural damage; Level 2: moderate damage - Slight damage to non-structural components; Level 3: major damage - heavy damage to some walls but no damages in columns; Level 4: complete

damage - heavy damage to several walls and some columns; Level 5: collapsed - destructive damage to walls and several columns; and Level 6: washed away). However if we make the comparison for the numerical complete damage state (i.e. structure is collapsed or in imminent danger of collapse, see also Table 4.8 and Table 4.9) with the empirical collapse damage state (Level 5: collapsed - destructive damage to walls and several columns), where their definition is comparable, it is observed that the median of the proposed fragility curve for complete damage state of the warehouse stands between the empirical ones for the upper and mean curves derived for the collapse damage level (Figure 4.24a), which anyway present a great scatter. The same also holds in general true for the MRF RC buildings, with the high-rise and low-rise MRFs being closer to the empirical mean and upper collapse limit state respectively, while the mid-rise MRFs standing between the upper and mean curves (Figure 4.24b).

Figure 4.24. Comparison of the numerical tsunami fragility curves for the complete damage state of the warehouse and the MRF RC buildings with the empirical ones of Suppasri et al. (2013) for the upper and lower curves of collapsed (a) steel and (b) RC structures, respectively

It should also be noted that Nanayakkara and Dias (2016) comment that the corresponding median inundation depths from the study of Suppasri et al. (2013) are relatively higher than those observed in previous tsunami events. They also suggest the data from Suppasri et al. (2013) be treated separately as they include a significant amount of buildings designed to withstand extreme forces (i.e. specially designed structures).

Suppasri et al. (2015) also classified the buildings with respect to six building function categories (residential houses, shared accommodation, commercial facilities, industrial plants, public facilities, and agriculture-forestry-aquaculture facilities). Because of the different damage definition, Table 4.12 shows the proposed correspondence between the numerical and empirical damage levels. The comparison of the proposed tsunami fragility

curves for the four-storey MRF RC buildings with the empirical ones of [Suppasri et al. \(2015\)](#) for RC buildings (either commercial or public facilities) is rather good (Figure 4.25), especially for the moderate damage state which corresponds to the empirical complete damage state, enhancing the reliability of the proposed numerical curves. It is noted that the numerical moderate damage state (i.e. Member flexural strengths achieved, limited ductility developed, see also Table 4.8) is considered to correspond to the empirical complete damage state (Level 4: heavy damage to several walls and some columns), as the empirical major damage state (Level 3: heavy damage to some walls but no damages in columns) does not include damages in columns.

Table 4.12. Proposed correspondence between the numerical and empirical damage levels

Numerical damage state	Empirical damage state Suppasri et al. (2015)	Empirical damage state Foytong and Ruangrassamee (2016)
Slight	Major	-
Moderate	Complete	DL2: primary members damage
Extensive	-	-
Complete	Collapse	DL3: collapse

Figure 4.25. Comparison of the numerical tsunami fragility curves for the four-storey MRF infilled building with the empirical ones of [Suppasri et al. \(2015\)](#) for RC commercial (left) and public (right) buildings

Although the definition of damage states is also different, it was deemed appropriate to conduct another comparison of the numerical tsunami fragility curves for the MRF two-storey bare-frame and the infilled building with the empirical ones ([Foytong and Ruangrassamee 2016](#)) for 1-storey RC buildings (Figure 4.26) obtained using the data of observed building damage due to the 2004 Indian Ocean tsunami in Thailand. [Foytong and Ruangrassamee \(2016\)](#) classified building damage into four damage levels (i.e. Level 0: no damage; Level 1: damage in secondary members only - damage only in non-structural components; Level 2: damage in primary members - damage in structural

components, cracks on a beam or a column, but the building is still repairable and it can sustain its gravitational load; Level 3: collapse – the building cannot sustain its gravitational load and its repair is not feasible). If we compare the MRF two-storey infilled RC building, as it is closest to the typology of the 1-storey RC buildings considered in [Foytong and Ruangrassamee \(2016\)](#), for the moderate damage state, where the definition of damage states (numerical moderate - empirical DL2; Figure 4.26 - blue lines) is comparable (Table 4.12), a generally good agreement between the curves is observed. In particular, it is observed that the median of the proposed fragility curve for moderate damage state of the MRF two-storey infilled RC building is equal to 1.57m (beta=0.37), while for the empirical DL2 equal to 1.464 (beta=0.757). The basic difference among them is the higher slope of the empirical curve (representing the higher standard deviation). In these comparisons (i.e. Figure 4.25 and Figure 4.26), the colours of the proposed and empirical fragility curves are selected with respect to the corresponding damage states (Table 4.12).

The differences can be attributed to various reasons mainly methodological but also to the fact that the empirical fragility curves, carefully selected to represent as closely as possible the studied building typologies, were constructed based on hazard-damage relationships from previous tsunami events and expert judgment and they are highly specific to a particular tsunami and structural characteristics. In addition, the herein derived numerical fragility curves refer to low-code RC buildings in contrast to the empirical ones that include RC buildings of different levels of design codes. Moreover, the empirical curves were derived based on damage data from various RC building typologies while in our case representative MRF and dual typologies are studied. Thus, the empirical curves are characterised by a higher level of uncertainty indicated by their higher slope as well as the great scatter of the curves (see Figure 4.24).

Figure 4.26. Comparison of the numerical tsunami fragility curves for the MRF two-storey bare-frame and the infilled building with the empirical ones of [Foytong and Ruangrassamee \(2016\)](#) for 1-storey RC buildings

The numerical tsunami fragility curves for the RC MRF two-storey building are finally compared with the results of a relevant numerical study conducted by [Foytong et al. \(2015\)](#). The median values of inundation depth proposed in our study are close to the key-point results (where the behaviour of the structure changes) derived by [Foytong et al. \(2015\)](#), also enhancing the reliability of the proposed curves.

4.7 Concluding remarks

Analytical tsunami fragility functions were developed for various types of low-code RC buildings and a typical steel light frame warehouse representative of typical port structures in South Europe. An extensive numerical investigation was performed considering different combinations of statically applied tsunami loads for gradually increasing tsunami inundation depths. Structural limit states were defined in terms of threshold values of material strain and shear capacity based on nonlinear static analyses results. For the complete damage state, flexural or shear failure of the structure was considered. Fragility and vulnerability curves were finally derived as a function of inundation depth for the various structure typologies considered.

It has been shown that the high-rise RC buildings present lower vulnerability compared to the low-rise ones. For example for an inundation depth equal to 2.0m, the expected structural damage indices d_m for the low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise bare-frame RC buildings are calculated (according to Figure 4.22) as 0.25, 0.1 and 0.02 respectively. If these values would be multiplied with an empirically derived reductive coefficient (i.e. 0.33 for low-rise and mid-rise RC frame buildings and 0.38 for high-rise RC buildings), the final global damage index, which takes into account both structural and non-structural losses, is calculated equal to 0.0825, 0.033 and 0.0076 for the low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise bare-frame RC buildings respectively. In other words, the total cost of repairs for the low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise bare-frame RC buildings would be equal to 8.25%, 3.3% and 0.76% of the replacement cost respectively.

In addition, the low-rise and mid-rise building models with infills were found more vulnerable compared to the bare-frame structures. This trend also holds true for the high-rise MRF for the exceedance of none to slight and moderate damage. In contrast, when extensive or complete damage of the high-rise MRF structures is anticipated, the bare-frame is expected to sustain larger damages in comparison with the corresponding infilled one (Figure 4.20). Moreover, the low-rise dual models are more vulnerable compared to the MRFs (that is obvious from the derived vulnerability curves in Figure 4.22), which is related to the concentration of large tsunami forces to shear walls. Regarding the fragility curves for the warehouse they are generally similar to the ones of the low-rise and mid-rise MRF RC buildings, and the difference between the damage

states is not so large indicating that once yielding occurs, the structure very rapidly attains the post-yield limit states.

It has also been shown that the shear failure is the prevailing failure mechanism for all low-code MRF RC buildings with bare frames, regardless of their height as well as for the infilled high-rise MRF and low-rise dual models. The consideration of masonry infills may have a significant impact on the response and finally on the failure mechanism of the structures (i.e. flexural or shear).

Comparisons made between the numerical tsunami fragility curves and the few available empirical ones (Suppasri et al. 2013; 2015; Foytong and Ruangrassamee 2016) for RC and steel structures for particular damage states are generally satisfactory considering the important uncertainties and scatter of the empirical data. It is noted that the differences can be attributed to the fact that the empirical fragility curves, carefully selected to represent as closely as possible the studied building typologies, were constructed based on hazard-damage relationships from tsunami events and expert judgment and they are highly specific to a particular tsunami and structural characteristics.

The proposed fragility curves could be used within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the vulnerability of low-code RC buildings and typical steel light frame warehouses exposed to tsunami hazard. Knowing the expected tsunami height from an appropriate tsunami hazard analysis and the characteristics of the exposed structures (geometrical features, material strength etc.), one could select and make use of the appropriate set of fragility curves to assess the vulnerability of each structure. The fragility curves for the low-code RC buildings could be applicable to typical RC buildings designed according to the pre-1980 codes in Greece and Southern Europe, considered as "low-code" structures, as the building typologies used in this study are commonly found in these countries (Kappos et al. 2003). Moreover, the suggested curves for the representative warehouse could be applicable to typical port steel light frame warehouses worldwide, as this is a common typology in ports around the world (NIBS 2004; Green et al. 2011). The proposed herein numerical as well as the existing empirical fragility curves could be applicable in other countries around the world only if suitable modifications are made taking into account the differences in their geographical arrangement, building codes and construction practices (Suppasri et al. 2016). Stakeholders could make use of the developed fragility curves to evaluate the risk to their own structures and take appropriate decisions to reduce their risk.

Future work should address tsunami vulnerability assessment taking into account time series of tsunami forces (as a function of inundation depth and flow velocity) or additional structural configurations, different combination of tsunami forces as well as

other parameters involved, which have not been considered in this analysis, like scouring effects, soil-structure-interaction (SSI), even aging effects on the material properties and the potential structural damages caused from prior ground shaking. Investigation of foundation failure during tsunami flow or the effect of soil liquefaction ([Latcharote et al. 2017](#)) could also be included in future research. Finally, comparison of the results with experimental tests would further enforce the validity of the proposed fragility curves.

Chapter 5

Vulnerability assessment due to liquefaction-induced differential displacements

5.1 Introduction

While liquefaction has been widely recognised as being one of the principal earthquake hazards resulting to significant economic and societal losses, research in the vulnerability assessment and quantitative evaluation of the expected physical damages to building structures is rather limited. In this respect, the present chapter aims to propose an analytical vulnerability assessment methodology for typical low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses with shallow flexible foundations subjected to liquefaction-induced differential permanent displacements, ignoring possible initial damages (e.g. in terms of stiffness and strength degradation) due to ground shaking. Part of this research has recently been published in Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering scientific journal ([Fotopoulou et al. 2018](#)) as well as in the proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering ([Karafagka et al. 2018b](#)). The proposed methodology results to the development of log-normally distributed fragility curves, which describe the probability of exceeding a certain level of damage of the structure, for different structural damage states, as a function of the liquefaction induced differential displacements. Vulnerability curves are also constructed so as to assess the expected direct losses in normalised cost terms.

To this aim, nonlinear static analyses are carried out for each considered structural typology assuming different gradually increasing differential displacement patterns applied as quasi-static loads directly at its supports (footings). Different damage mechanisms are examined including a flexural damage of the building members and a shear failure of the columns. In order to enhance the reliability and robustness of the proposed fragility curves, they are compared with corresponding literature curves as well

as field observations from past events which caused catastrophic ground failures, including liquefaction, lateral spreads and differential settlements.

5.2 Literature review of methods to assess damage due to ground displacements

Experience gained from recent strong seismic events has demonstrated the high vulnerability of critical buildings to liquefaction-induced displacements resulting to severe physical damages and important economic and societal losses. By far, the most widespread source of seismic damage to port structures and infrastructure is the liquefaction of loose, saturated soils that often prevail at coastal areas ([Pitilakis et al. 2014a](#)). Even moderate levels of earthquake intensity can cause liquefaction, potentially leading to induced soil settlements and lateral spreading, that may result to severe physical damages to critical buildings and important economic and societal losses ([PIANC 2001](#)).

[Lai et al. \(2015\)](#) observed widespread liquefaction phenomena (lateral spreading and after-effects) on structures and infrastructure caused by the main shock that hit the Emilia-Romagna Region (2012) in Northern Italy. [Bray and Dashti \(2014\)](#) have documented the performance of buildings at ground failure sites during recent earthquakes in Turkey (Kocaeli 1999), Chile (Maule 2010), New Zealand (Christchurch 2011) and Japan (Tohoku 2011) indicating that a considerable number of buildings on shallow foundations have settled differentially and slid laterally as a result of liquefaction causing extensive and substantial damage beyond economic repair. As an example, [Cubrinovski \(2013\)](#) reported that liquefaction caused by the 2010-2011 Canterbury earthquake sequence in New Zealand seriously damaged 20000 residential buildings in Christchurch (representing approximately one third of the total buildings), out of which about 8000 houses were considered uneconomic to repair. A more detailed investigation on the observed building performance and damage due to liquefaction can be found in Chapter 2.

Within an earthquake risk assessment framework, the evaluation of liquefaction demand in terms of permanent ground displacements is far from straightforward ([Bird et al. 2006](#)). A number of methodologies are available for the prediction of absolute settlements and lateral movements due to liquefaction, most of which rely principally on empirical data (e.g. [Tokimatsu and Seed 1987](#); [Ishihara and Yoshimine 1992](#); [Bartlett and Youd \(1995\)](#); [Bardet et al. 1999](#); [Youd et al. 2002](#); [Zhang and Zhao 2005](#) among others). In particular, based on a review of previous studies, [Tokimatsu and Seed \(1987\)](#) summarised the available information concerning the settlements of sands during earthquakes and attempted to deploy a methodology for predicting the post-liquefaction

settlements of the ground. [Ishihara and Yoshimine \(1992\)](#) also proposed a methodology for estimating the ground settlements, based on the factor of safety against liquefaction correlated to the post-liquefaction volumetric strain, and applied it to interpret observed settlements of sandy grounds at several sites devastated by liquefaction in 1964 Niigata earthquake. In addition [Bartlett and Youd \(1995\)](#), [Bardet et al. \(1999\)](#) and subsequently [Youd et al. \(2002\)](#) applied multiple linear regression techniques to a database of documented case histories of lateral-spread displacements in order to develop an empirically based method for Prediction of Lateral Spread Displacement. Afterwards, [Zhang and Zhao \(2005\)](#) proposed a new model for estimating liquefaction-induced lateral displacement, incorporating the parameters of existing spectral acceleration attenuation models.

However, none of these methods have proved to be more reliable compared to the others. They are generally accepted to be accurate only to within a factor of 2.0 or 3.0 (e.g. [Youd et al. 2002](#)) and their ability to predict displacements tends to reduce for small-to-moderate (0.3-0.75 m) deformations. Recently, physical tests and nonlinear dynamic soil-structure-interaction (SSI) effective stress analyses have provided valuable insights into the liquefaction-induced movements of buildings with shallow foundations proving that simplified empirical procedures are often inappropriate for estimating liquefaction-induced building settlements ([Bray and Dashti 2014](#); [Bray et al. 2017](#); [Ziotopoulou and Montgomery 2017](#); [Karimi et al. 2017](#)). In addition, [Bray and Macedo \(2017\)](#) proposed a procedure for estimating liquefaction-induced building settlements, that captures the important shear-induced ground deformation mechanisms and provides an assessment consistent with the results of over 1300 nonlinear dynamic SSI effective stress analyses and data from field case histories.

While methodologies for the assessment of liquefaction potential and the resulting ground and foundation deformation due to liquefaction have been the focus of research for many years, when it comes to determining the impact these deformations will have on existing structures and the subsequent liquefaction-induced structural damages, the published literature is generally inadequate. Methods for predicting structural damages due to liquefaction-induced ground displacements can be divided into three main categories: empirical/expert judgement methods (e.g. [NIBS 2004](#); [Juang et al. 2005](#); [Cázares et al. 2012](#)), mechanics-based methods ([Bird et al. 2005](#); [2006](#)) and methods based on numerical modelling (e.g. [Ichii 2003](#); [Brandenberg et al. 2011a](#)).

Regarding the first category, they aim at relating the deformation observed from field surveys to the damage. HAZUS ([NIBS 2004](#)) multi-hazard loss estimation methodology provides expert judgement fragility curves for buildings due to ground failure that relate the free-field permanent ground displacement (PGD) to the probability of exceeding a

certain damage state. Different fragility curves that distinguish between ground failure due to lateral spreading and ground failure due to ground settlement, and between shallow and deep foundations were proposed considering one combined Extensive/Complete damage state. Juang et al. (2005) presented an empirical methodology for estimating the severity of liquefaction-induced ground damage at or near foundations of existing buildings. This method is based on field observations from recent earthquakes, and while empirical and approximate in nature, it is shown that it can explain observations of ground damage at or near buildings in limited case histories. Cázares et al. (2012) proposed vulnerability functions, defined by permanent vertical ground displacement, for buildings due to liquefaction, obtained as a result of a combination of those defined as empirical with those obtained through statistics of damage from a database of buildings affected by liquefaction during earthquakes.

As far as the second category is concerned, Bird et al. (2005; 2006) made a significant contribution in this field by proposing analytical solutions to assess the expected damage of existing RC frame buildings due to liquefaction-induced differential ground deformation (including differential vertical and/or horizontal displacements). They proposed equations in order to represent the deformational capacity of the critical column in a single frame, by applying principles of displacement-based assessment, semi-empirical and semi-mechanical formulations, while the column deformational demand related to ground motions can be obtained from simple geometry. In this approach, the structure response is idealised in four cases considering differential vertical settlements and lateral movements associated with horizontal and vertical components. Only representative cases of regular RC frame buildings with shallow, relatively flexible foundations were considered in this approach while the foundation deformation pattern was assumed to be equal to the free-field deformation. The results of this study contributed to gain insight into the damage mechanisms due to ground failure and the displacement demand of the floor columns. In particular, it is found that the displacement demand of RC frame structures is concentrated to the ground floor columns, as the upper stories generally rotate as a rigid body. Also, it is shown that for a single-bay case, deformations take place in the column rather than in the beam.

In order to estimate the liquefaction-induced damages, more sophisticated methods based on numerical modelling can also be used. Two trends are generally used in the literature to estimate the liquefaction-induced damages using numerical analysis. The first is a "coupled approach", where the damages due to combined ground shaking and soil liquefaction effects are estimated in a single step (e.g. Ichii 2003; 2004). For instance, Ichii (2003; 2004), proposed fragility-curves for gravity-type quay walls, based on a parametric study with an effective stress-based finite element method (FEM). In

particular, the direct one-step approach (coupled approach), where the soil and the structure were modelled and analysed as a single system, was used considering soil liquefaction. This approach is generally recommended for site specific applications where the degree of accuracy in the input data is high as it involves extensive computational effort. The second is an “*uncoupled approach*”, where the soil and the structure are studied separately, and the soil displacements are imposed to a finite element model of the structure (e.g. [Brandenberg et al. 2011a](#)). For example, [Brandenberg et al. \(2011a\)](#), implementing the uncoupled approach, developed fragility functions for bridges due to liquefaction-induced lateral spreading displacements. The uncoupled approach yields to the evaluation of the structural damages due to liquefaction-induced permanent displacements ignoring possible initial damages due to ground shaking.

Numerical modelling techniques for estimating liquefaction-induced damages have also been applied for bridge systems (e.g. [Bowers 2007](#); [Kwon et al. 2009](#); [Aygün et al. 2011](#); [Brandenberg et al. 2011a](#)), quay walls ([Ichii 2003](#); [2004](#)) and other simplified soil-structure systems ([Koutsourelakis et al. 2002](#); [Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi 2008](#)). However their application to typical building structures has not received much attention and hence requires further investigation.

Under these considerations, the objective of this chapter is to propose a numerical methodology for the vulnerability assessment of typical low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses subjected to differential permanent ground displacements due to liquefaction (settlements and lateral spreading) based on the uncoupled numerical approach.

5.3 Methodological framework

The schematic framework of the proposed methodology for the vulnerability assessment of buildings subjected to liquefaction-induced differential displacements is illustrated in Figure 5.1. It involves a comprehensive set of nonlinear parametric numerical computations and adequate statistical analysis. The conceptual features of the proposed methodological framework are outlined in the following paragraphs.

In the proposed vulnerability assessment methodology, the focus is on the differential component of liquefaction-induced ground deformation, which commonly occurs due to the heterogeneity in soil stiffness and stratigraphy both laterally and with depth. The differential settlements and differential lateral movements become the major cause of damage to buildings ([Bird et al. 2005](#); [2006](#)), as the absolute (uniform) displacements on their own are often insufficient to describe the main damage patterns of the structures. Thus, one may start with the quantification of the absolute free-field ground deformations using one of the available empirical or numerical methodologies and

continue with the evaluation of the corresponding differential movements beneath the foundation of a building.

Figure 5.1. Flowchart of the proposed methodology for the vulnerability and risk assessment of buildings subjected to liquefaction-induced differential displacements

The estimation of the differential ground movements entails an even greater uncertainty than the estimation of absolute movements. This is principally due to the soil heterogeneity and the lack of sufficiently detailed geotechnical data. Thus, unless an extensive geotechnical investigation at the building area is to be performed, the distribution of differential displacements over the footprint of the building in terms of a percentage of the absolute ones should be reasonably assumed based on existing knowhow and experience (e.g. [California Geological Survey 2008](#)).

The classification for the general building stock adopted in many earthquake engineering studies for the assessment of structural damage due to ground shaking includes the structural system, building materials, number of floors and code design level (e.g. [NIBS 2004](#); [Kappos and Panagopoulos 2010](#); [Pitilakis et al. 2014a](#)).

For assessing building response to liquefaction-induced differential displacement, the foundation system is also of importance. Different foundation configurations can be considered including shallow flexible foundations, shallow stiff/rigid foundations and deep foundations.

The structural response and damage to the differential ground deformation induced due to soil liquefaction depends primarily on the foundation type. A structure supported by a deep foundation (e.g. piles) compared to a shallow foundation is expected to perform much better and hence it would have a lower vulnerability (e.g. [NIBS 2004](#); [Bird and Bommer 2004](#)). For shallow foundations, a structure resting on a rigid foundation (e.g. a continuous raft foundation) is less vulnerable than a flexible one (e.g. isolated footings with inadequate connections).

In this study, the focus is on buildings with flexible foundation system (i.e. isolated footings for the RC buildings and strip footing for the steel-frame warehouse), which allow columns moving differentially and hence permitting the computation of structural deformation demand and fragility using a numerical and/or analytical approach. In this case, it is furthermore assumed that failure takes place on the building's structural elements and the load bearing capacity of the foundation is adequately designed to resist the liquefaction induced deformation. For structures with rigid foundations, a rigid-body movement without significant internal deformation of the building is expected (e.g. [Cubrinovski et al. 2012](#)). Thus, in this case the anticipated damage or failure is mainly attributed to loss of functionality and an empirical solution is required for its estimation (e.g. [Bird et al. 2005](#); [2006](#)).

Nonlinear static time-history analyses of the considered building typologies are performed using an appropriate finite element code to assess the structure's response and fragility due to the liquefaction-induced differential displacement. Different combinations of differential displacements are imposed as quasi-static loads at the structure's supports considering only the vertical component of the differential displacement (i.e. to represent settlements in level ground) or taking also into account the horizontal differential displacement with a vertical component (i.e. to represent lateral spreading in gently sloping ground). In the latter case, two different scenarios are analysed: (i) the horizontal component is assumed equal to the vertical one and (ii) the horizontal component is assumed equal to twice the vertical one. For each of the previous differential displacement profiles the maximum differential displacement is assumed to be applied either at the middle or edge column at the foundation level while a triangular distribution of the differential displacement is considered in all cases.

Different failure mechanisms of the considered RC structural models are examined including a global flexural failure of the RC frame buildings and a local shear failure

(attainment of shear capacity) of the columns. In the former case the EDP is expressed in terms of maximum values of steel and concrete material strain. Four damage states are defined describing slight, moderate, extensive and complete structural damage of the buildings based on the existing literature (Crowley et al. 2004; Bird et al. 2005; 2006; Fotopoulou and Pitilakis 2017) and expert judgement. In the latter case, the computed shear forces in the columns are used as EDP. One damage state is considered in this case describing complete shear failure defined as being attained when at least 50% of all columns in a storey have reached their shear strength (Kappos et al. 2006; Celarec and Dolsek 2013).

The vulnerability is assessed through probabilistic fragility functions, which describe the probability of exceeding each limit state under a range of liquefaction-induced differential displacements. Log-normally distributed fragility curves for the selected buildings subjected to settlements and lateral spreading differential deformation are constructed for the different damage states using nonlinear regression analysis, considering the most adverse failure mechanism (due to flexure or shear). The differential displacement is used as IM that adequately correlates with structural deformation and damage. Various sources of uncertainty are taken into account in the analysis with respect to the structural capacity and the damage states (defined empirically) and the demand (defined analytically).

Once the fragility curves of the considered building typologies subjected to liquefaction-induced displacements are available, a vulnerability curve can be constructed, which provides a unique damage or vulnerability index d_m for each level of differential displacement. The damage index is a convenient measure to quantify the structural losses and finally to assess the risk at building or community level when properly aggregated. It may be quantified in cost terms as the ratio of cost of repair to cost of replacement taking values from 0: no damage (cost of repair equals 0) to 1: complete damage (cost of repair equals the cost of replacement).

Finally, it is worth noting that in the proposed method the vulnerability is assessed only for the effect of the liquefaction-induced differential displacement while possible initial damage to the building's structural members (e.g. in terms of stiffness and strength degradation) due to ground shaking is ignored.

5.4 Numerical analysis

5.4.1. Selection of the structural building typologies

To illustrate the proposed vulnerability assessment methodology three MRF RC buildings of various heights and a steel light frame warehouse have been selected as

reference structures. They have been designed with a low seismic code according to the 1959 Greek seismic regulations ('Royal Decree' of 1959) (Kappos et al. 2006) in which the ductility and the dynamic features of the structures are neglected. The first building is a two-storey three-bay frame structure that represents low-rise (1-3 stories) MRF RC buildings. The second one is a four-storey three-bay frame structure that is considered representative of mid-rise (4-7 stories) MRF RC buildings while the third one is a nine-storey three-bay frame model that is considered typical of high-rise (8+ stories) MRF RC buildings. It is reasonably assumed that the selected poorly designed buildings are likely to have poorly designed foundations. Thus, a flexible foundation system (i.e. isolated footings) is considered allowing columns move differentially. In this case, the various modes of differential deformation can produce structural damage (e.g. in terms of cracks) to the building members (Bird et al. 2005; 2006) and the applied differential displacement (settlement or lateral spreading) may be reasonably assumed equal to the forced displacements at the bottom of the columns. In Table 4.4 the main characteristics of the models studied in this chapter can be found, namely the mass, fundamental period, compressive concrete strength f_c and yield strength of steel reinforcement f_y , while Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3 illustrate representative cross-sections and the floor plans respectively of the studied RC building typologies (Kappos et al. 2006) and the typical warehouse (as provided by the Port authorities of the Port of Thessaloniki). The reinforcement layout for the analysed RC structural models is also shown in Figure 4.2.

5.4.2. Structural modelling

The numerical analyses of the selected structures are conducted using the finite element package SeismoStruct (SeismoSoft 2015), which has been widely employed in several structural earthquake engineering applications either for research or professional engineering purposes (e.g. Causevic and Mitrovic 2011). The code is capable of predicting the large displacement behaviour of space frames subjected to static or dynamic loads allowing both geometric nonlinearities and material inelasticity to be captured. Distributed inelasticity elements are used that may fully account for the spread of inelasticity along the element length and across the section depth. The so-called "fibre approach" is used to represent the cross-section inelastic behaviour (Neuenhofer and Filippou 1997) where each fibre is associated with a uniaxial stress-strain relationship; the sectional stress-strain state of beam-column elements is then obtained through the integration of the nonlinear uniaxial stress-strain response of the individual fibres (typically 100-150) in which the section has been subdivided. In the present study, the frame sections have been discretised into 300 fibres.

The nonlinear beam-column frame elements can be implemented using either the classical displacement-based (DB) formulation (e.g. [Mari and Scordelis 1984](#)) or the more recent force-based (FB) formulation (e.g. [Spacone et al. 1996](#)). In the DB finite element formulation using nonlinear models, a refined discretisation of the structural elements (typically 4-5 sub-elements with two integration points each per sub-element) is required in order to accept the assumption of a linear curvature field inside each of the sub-domains. On the contrary, the FB formulation can be regarded as being always "exact" with the only approximation being introduced by the discrete number of the controlling points along the element that are used for the numerical integration.

In the present analysis, for the RC frame buildings, which may involve highly nonlinear structural response, strain localization effects due to softening behaviour ([Coleman and Spacone 2001](#); [Calabrese 2008](#); [Calabrese et al. 2010](#)) are expected to govern the response, which becomes sensitive to the length of the sub-elements in the DB formulation or the effective length of the integration point in the FB formulation. Considering that softening behaviour generally appears more dramatically in FB than in DB elements ([Calabrese 2008](#)), the use of DB elements with an appropriate adjustment of the sub-elements' length is preferred. More specifically, the beam-column frame elements have been subdivided into five segments with the first and last sub-element's length being equal to twice the assumed plastic hinge dimension ([Calabrese 2008](#); [Calabrese et al. 2010](#)). The latter is estimated based on an empirical relationship ([Paulay and Priestley 1992](#)). Considering that the maximum inelastic deformation has generally shown to be concentrated at the end sub-elements of the beam-column structural members, the subdivision of the remaining part of the element is of less importance, provided that the element has a softening response as in this case.

The uniaxial nonlinear constant confinement model that follows the constitutive relationship proposed by [Mander et al. \(1988\)](#) and the cyclic rules proposed by [Martinez-Rueda and Elnashai \(1997\)](#) is employed for the concrete material. Five model calibrating parameters are defined to fully describe the mechanical characteristics of the material: the compressive strength (f_c), the tensile strength (f_t), the modulus of elasticity (E_c), the strain at peak stress (ϵ_c) and the specific weight (γ). The compressive strength of the concrete and modulus of elasticity are set equal to $f_c=14.0$ MPa and $E_c= 1.7586 \cdot 10^4$ MPa respectively. The strain at peak stress ϵ_c that is the strain corresponding to the point of peak compressive stress (f_c) is taken equal to $\epsilon_c=0.002$. A zero tensile strength of the concrete material ($f_t = 0$ MPa) is assumed. For the steel reinforcement, a uniaxial bilinear stress-strain model with kinematic strain hardening is utilised. Five model calibrating parameters are again defined including the modulus of elasticity (E), the yield strength (f_y), the strain hardening parameter (μ), the fracture/buckling strain (ϵ_{ult}) and the

specific weight (γ). The modulus of elasticity and the yield strength are taken equal to $E=2.000 \cdot 10^5$ MPa and $f_y=400.0$ MPa respectively. The strain hardening parameter (μ) defined as the ratio between the post-yield stiffness and the initial elastic stiffness of the material is assumed equal to $\mu=0.010$. Finally, the strain at which fracture or buckling occurs (ϵ_{ult}) is taken equal to 0.1. The total mass (see Table 4.4) is applied as uniformly distributed along the beams (as distributed loads) and columns (by assigning the specific weight of steel and concrete material).

Regarding the warehouse modelling, the uniaxial bilinear model with kinematic strain-hardening is employed for the steel material (where $E_s = 2.1 \cdot 10^5$ MPa; $f_y = 235.0$ MPa and $\mu = 0.01$). Columns are modelled using FB inelastic frame elements with 5 integration sections, as there is no softening behaviour of steel members, while trusses are modelled through truss elements (truss). Inelastic FB formulations are also implemented for the nonlinear RC connecting beam frame element modelling. The number of fibres used in section equilibrium computations in both cases as set to 300. The masses are applied as distributed along columns and beams (by assigning the specific weight of steel material) plus concentrated vertical loads on joints due to the existence of trusses on the normal direction (Figure 5.2).

Two dimensional (2D) nonlinear static time-history analyses of the studied building typologies are performed to account for the response to the seismically induced liquefaction differential displacement. Various sets of quasi-static displacement-controlled type loads are imposed directly at its supports (foundations), to simulate the differential displacement demand of the structure impact by liquefaction. More specifically, for each structure, a series of approximately 100 nonlinear static analyses is carried out for gradually increasing level of displacement (to cover the whole range from elasticity to structural collapse) imposed at the foundation level considering six different differential displacement profiles:

- i) Settlements with the maximum differential displacement applied at the edge column
- ii) Settlements with the maximum differential displacement applied at the middle column
- iii) Lateral spreading with the horizontal component of the differential displacement (h) being equal to the vertical (v) one ($h=v$) and the maximum differential displacement vector applied at the edge column
- iv) Lateral spreading with the horizontal component of the differential displacement (h) being equal to the vertical (v) one ($h=v$) and the maximum differential displacement vector applied at the middle column

- v) Lateral spreading with the horizontal component of the differential displacement (h) being equal to twice the vertical (v) one ($h=2v$) and the maximum differential displacement vector applied at the edge column
- vi) Lateral spreading with the horizontal component of the differential displacement (h) being equal to twice the vertical (v) one ($h=2v$) and the maximum differential displacement vector applied at the middle column

The differential displacement demand at the foundation level is assumed to follow a triangular distribution in all analysed cases. Figure 5.2 presents indicatively the imposed displacement loading pattern considered for the nonlinear static analysis of the two-storey RC MRF structural model and the warehouse. In particular Figure 5.2a and Figure 5.2b present the imposed differential displacement profiles (i) and (ii) respectively for the nonlinear static analysis of the two-storey RC MRF structural model, while Figure 5.2c and Figure 5.2d show the applied differential settlement and lateral spreading displacement vector respectively for the warehouse.

Figure 5.2. Applied differential settlements with the maximum differential displacement applied at the a) edge or b) middle column for the two-storey RC MRF, and applied c) differential settlement or d) lateral spreading displacement vector for the warehouse

5.4.3. Representative results of the nonlinear analysis of the buildings

Results of the nonlinear static analyses with progressively increased differential liquefaction displacements are presented in Figure 5.3 indicatively for the four-storey RC frame building subjected to gradually increasing settlements with the maximum

differential settlement applied either at the edge or the middle column. More precisely, Figure 5.3 illustrates representative relationships for the four-storey RC MRF building between the maximum applied differential settlement and the maximum structural flexural response (or EDP) in terms of maximum material strain calculated from the nonlinear static analysis. In particular, strain values subjected to the highest bending moment that are generally expected to localise at the end sub-elements of the DB beam/column structural members are computed. It has been observed that for all analysis cases, steel strain (ϵ_s) gives more critical results compared to the concrete strain (ϵ_c). Hence, hereafter, the EDP is defined in terms of steel bar strain. Moreover, it is observed that the maximum steel strain generally increases proportionally with the differential displacement (i.e. the IM) with this increase presenting a much more linear trend in the case where the maximum differential settlement is applied at the middle column.

Figure 5.3. Representative results of the nonlinear static analysis for the four-storey RC frame building subjected to settlements with the maximum differential settlement applied at the edge (left) and middle (right) column

Large differences in the maximum applied differential settlements and the maximum computed strain values are expected depending on whether the maximum differential settlement is applied at the edge or the middle column. In particular, in the former case, the building is subjected to significantly higher maximum differential settlements until structural collapse (reaching approximately 2.0m) compared to the latter (up to 0.65m). In addition, it is observed that for the same level of maximum differential settlement (e.g. 0.5m) imposed at the edge or the middle column, the expected response of the structure might change dramatically, implying that depending on the differential displacement profile, the structure may either be in the elastic range or suffer significant damages.

These observations are principally due to the different deformation modes and failure mechanisms taking place in each case (Figure 5.4). For instance, for the four-storey RC frame building subjected to differential settlements with the maximum differential settlement applied at the right edge column, deformation is initially expected to be concentrated at the bottom of the left ground floor column rather than to the beams, with the higher storeys rotating as rigid bodies. This failure mechanism, where the formation of plastic hinges takes place at the base of the building, is due to the fact that the columns are free to rotate laterally and therefore act as cantilevers in simple bending. This mechanism has also been observed in Bird et al. (2005) for the case of a two-storey MRF building. On the other hand, when the maximum differential settlement is applied at a middle column of the structure, as there is a restraint to keep the columns vertical, a failure mechanism involving deformation and damage of the beams and consequently damage of the columns occurs, resulting to much higher deformation levels. In the following, taking into account this important observation on the failure mechanisms as well as the significant differences in the structural response depending on the considered displacement profile and recognizing the difficulty to predict where the maximum differential displacement is expected to occur, fragility curves will be derived for the most adverse cases where the maximum differential displacement is applied at the middle column.

Figure 5.4. Failure mechanisms for the four-storey RC frame building subjected to settlements with the maximum differential settlement equal to 1.35 m applied at the edge (left) column and equal to 0.15 m applied at the middle (right) column (the green colour indicates steel bar yielding members, while the red one post-yield damaged members)

In addition to the flexural response of the RC beam/column elements derived in terms of maximum material strain, the shear forces in the RC columns are also extracted from the nonlinear static analyses and compared to the shear capacity of the RC column

calculated according to EC8-3 (CEN 2005). In this way, the possibility of local failure due to shear is also examined taking into account that for the considered low-code RC MRF structures that have not been designed to withstand seismic loads, shear failure might occur prior to the attainment of the flexural failure (Mwafy and Elnashai 2008). An example of the shear capacity check conducted for the 1st storey of the nine-storey RC frame building subjected to lateral spreading with the horizontal component of the differential displacement (h) being equal to the vertical (v) one ($h=v$) and the maximum differential displacement applied at the middle column is presented in Table 5.1. It is shown that the shear strength is first reached at the right column (top sub-element) for differential displacement vector equal to 0.068 m and subsequently at the left column (top sub-element) for differential displacement vector equal to 0.305 m.

Table 5.1. Shear capacity check of the nine-storey frame RC building subjected to lateral spreading with $h=v$ and the maximum differential displacement applied at the middle column

Differential displacement vector (m)	Shear force in 1 st storey columns (kN)			
	Col 1-1 part5 (left column-top)	Col 1-2 part5 (middle column-top)	Col 1-3 part5 (middle column-top)	Col 1-4 part5 (right column- top)
0.009	3.557	17.033	19.894	40.488
0.025	5.092	54.423	32.403	81.739
0.042	5.404	83.508	31.505	109.610
0.059	11.488	106.535	36.826	131.873
0.068	16.847	115.629	42.702	141.484
0.085	25.675	130.347	54.868	159.540
0.127	50.070	153.864	76.954	180.748
0.170	79.158	170.260	86.085	177.188
0.212	105.693	181.998	91.463	167.772
0.255	126.513	185.810	93.312	152.610
0.297	138.077	178.436	93.541	133.901
0.305	139.605	176.397	93.589	130.382

*The values in bold indicate that the shear capacity is reached.

5.5 Fragility curves

5.5.1. Definition of limit states

The definition of realistic damage limit states is of paramount importance for the evaluation of fragility curve parameters. Different damage mechanisms of the structures are examined to account for the flexural damage of the structural members and the potential shear failure of the columns.

As far as the flexural damage mechanism is concerned, four damage limit states (LS1, LS2, LS3, LS4) are defined describing the exceedance of slight, moderate, extensive and complete structural damage of the building in terms of limit values of steel and concrete material strains based on the available literature (e.g. Crowley et al. 2004; Bird et al. 2005; Negulescu and Foerster 2010; Fotopoulou and Pitilakis 2013a; 2013b) for the RC MRFs and on the nonlinear static analyses and engineering judgment for the warehouse (Karafagka et al. 2018a). According to NIBS (2004), "Steel Light Frames" structures are mostly single storey structures combining rod-braced frames in one direction and moment frames in the other. Due to the repetitive nature of the structural systems, the type of damage to structural members is expected to be rather uniform throughout the structure. Consequently, warehouses are considered as "Steel Light Frames" structures. A qualitative description of the selected damage states for the RC and the steel light frames is provided in (Table 4.8) Crowley et al. (2004) and (Table 4.9) NIBS (2004) respectively. The limit state values finally adopted are presented in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2. Definition of limit states for the different structure typologies considered

Limit states	Steel strain (ϵ_s)	
	<i>MRF bare frames</i>	<i>Warehouse</i>
Limit state 1	0.002	0.00112
Limit state 2	0.0125	0.0125
Limit state 3	0.025	0.03
Limit state 4	0.045	0.055

In order to minimize the uncertainties associated with the selection of the appropriate damage state limits for the warehouse, nonlinear static analyses are performed to define structure-specific limit state values for each damage state. Figure 5.5 illustrates the definition of limit states on the corresponding liquefaction capacity curves derived from the nonlinear static analyses for the warehouse subjected to differential settlements and lateral spreading due to liquefaction. In particular, the first limit state is specified as steel bar yielding while mean values of post-yield limit strains for steel are suggested for the rest limit states. It is noted that the liquefaction capacity curves are not extracted from a single nonlinear static analysis as for a seismic capacity curve (derived from a pushover analysis) but from the total number of the nonlinear static analyses conducted.

As shear failure of RC columns is also likely to occur, one damage state is assigned describing the complete shear failure of the RC MRF structures. Complete shear failure is defined as being attained when at least 50% of the columns in a storey reach their shear capacity (Kappos et al. 2006; Celarec and Dolsek 2013). In particular, the demand on

the buildings columns, in terms of shear forces, is evaluated using the results of the nonlinear static time-history analysis and compared to the shear capacity of the columns. The shear capacity in the columns has been calculated according to the procedure proposed in Eurocode 8- part 3 (CEN 2005). For instance, as shown in Table 5.1, the shear failure in two out of the four columns in the 1st storey of the nine-storey MRF will anticipate the complete shear failure of the structure.

Figure 5.5. Definition of limit states on liquefaction capacity curves for the warehouse subjected to (left) differential settlements and (right) to lateral spreading due to liquefaction

5.5.2. Generation of fragility curves

Fragility analysis is a well-established tool in earthquake engineering that explicitly accounts for uncertainties in demand and capacity and damage states (Kaynia 2013). As mentioned in Chapter 3, it results to the development of fragility curves which represent graphical relationships of the conditional probability of exceeding predefined damage states (DS) for given levels of intensity, expressed in this chapter in terms of liquefaction-induced differential displacement. The results of the nonlinear static time-history analysis (differential displacement – maximum material strain and differential displacement – shear forces) are used to derive fragility curves expressed as two-parameter lognormal distribution functions according to Equation 5.1:

$$P[DS_i/IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM) - \ln(\overline{IM}_i)}{\beta}\right) \quad (5.1)$$

where, Φ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function, IM is the intensity measure given in terms of liquefaction-induced differential displacement, \overline{IM} and β are the median and log-standard deviation values respectively of the IM. Therefore, for the development of fragility curves according to Equation 5.1, two parameters, namely \overline{IM} and β , need to be defined. The median values of differential displacement corresponding to the predefined damage states are determined based on a statistical analysis of the nonlinear static analysis results (differential displacement - maximum strain pairs). In

particular, a quadratic fit of the logarithms of the differential displacement- maximum strain simulated data, which minimizes the regression residuals, is adopted. Figure 5.6 presents a representative plot (in log-log scale) of damage evolution in terms of maximum strain as a function of differential displacement for the four-storey RC frame building subjected to differential settlements with the maximum differential displacement applied at the middle column. The corresponding limit values of maximum steel strain defined for each damage state are also shown.

Figure 5.6. Differential displacement vector- steel strain relationship for the four-storey RC frame building subjected to differential settlements with the maximum differential displacement applied at the middle column

The log-standard deviation parameter β describes the total dispersion related to each fragility curve. A higher β value leads to a flatter fragility curve and hence to greater uncertainty. It contains three components of uncertainty associated with the definition of the limit state value β_{LS} , the capacity of each structural type β_c , and the demand β_D (NIBS 2004). The uncertainty in the definition of limit states is defined empirically as $\beta_{LS} = 0.4$ for the considered low-code RC frame buildings based on the existing literature (NIBS 2004), while it is not taken into account for the considered warehouse as the limit states are defined through numerical analysis. The log-standard deviation value in the definition of the capacity is assumed to be equal to $\beta_c = 0.3$ for the considered low code buildings (NIBS 2004). The third component uncertainty associated with the demand β_D is taken into consideration from the statistical analysis of the numerical results by calculating the dispersion of the logarithms of differential displacement - maximum strain simulated data with respect to the regression fit. As shown in Figure 5.6, the uncertainty in the demand generally presents very low values typically varying from 0.020 to 0.050. The total log-standard deviation parameter β is finally computed as the root of the sum

of the squares of the component dispersions (equation 5.2) under the assumption that these three variability components are statistically independent (NIBS 2004).

$$\beta = \sqrt{\beta_{LS}^2 + \beta_C^2 + \beta_D^2} \quad (5.2)$$

Figure 5.7 illustrates the derived sets of fragility curves for the two-storey, four-storey, nine-storey low-code MRF RC buildings and the warehouse subjected to differential displacements (settlements and lateral spreading) due to liquefaction, while Table 5.3 summarises the corresponding fragility parameters, i.e. median m and log-standard deviation β , in terms of differential displacements. It is noted that for the cases where the structures are subjected to lateral spreading with the maximum differential displacement vector applied at the middle column, the minimum of the two median differential displacements estimated for the horizontal component of the differential displacement being equal to and twice the vertical one is considered for each damage state. Thus, taking also into account the difficulty of actually knowing the proportion of the horizontal component with respect to the vertical one and to be on the safe side, instead of two different sets of curves, an upper bound set of fragility curves is finally developed for each building for the lateral spreading case.

As shown in Table 5.3 the final dispersion of the four- and nine- storey RC frame buildings is 0.5, which is principally due to the uncertainty in the capacity and limit state, while only the two-storey RC frame building seems to be influenced by an increase in dispersion due to the demand. The latter is due to the rather high variability of the computed strains at low differential displacement levels (lower than 0.015m) which influences the goodness of the regression fit resulting to increased demand uncertainty and consequently to increased β value. Regarding the warehouse, the final dispersion is 0.41, a quite lower value compared to the others, as the uncertainty associated with the definition of the limit state value β_{LS} is not taken into account since the limit states are defined through numerical analysis.

A general observation for the studied typical low-code MRF RC buildings is that the total height of the structure may considerably influence its vulnerability to the liquefaction-induced differential displacements, with the studied high-rise building being more vulnerable compared to the low- and mid-rise ones. This last observation is more pronounced for the lateral spreading cases. Moreover, regarding the warehouse, it is shown that it is by far less vulnerable than the RC frame structures.

It has also been observed that for the studied low-code RC frame buildings their vulnerability is generally increased when they are subjected only to settlements compared to the case where the applied differential displacement has also a horizontal component due to lateral spreading with the increase being more noticeable for the

complete damage state. This could be due to the fact that in the latter case damage is generally more distributed at the building members while in the former case damage is mainly concentrated at beams and columns at the one side of the buildings resulting to higher deformation demand and hence higher vulnerability.

Table 5.3. Parameters of fragility functions for the studied building typologies subjected to liquefaction-induced differential displacements

Building typology	Differential displacement profile	Median liquefaction-induced differential displacement (m)				Dispersion β
		LS ₁	LS ₂	LS ₃	LS ₄	
Two-storey MRF RC	Settlements- middle column	0.034	0.124	0.210	0.307	0.54
	Lateral spreading- middle column and h=v	0.038	0.147	0.263	0.448	0.50
	Lateral spreading- middle column and h=2v	0.045	0.163	0.283	0.467	0.50
Four-storey MRF RC	Settlements- middle column	0.027	0.098	0.176	0.305	0.50
	Lateral spreading- middle column and h=v	0.028	0.127	0.238	0.420	0.50
	Lateral spreading- middle column and h=2v	0.032	0.146	0.270	0.465	0.50
Nine-storey MRF RC	Settlements- middle column	0.022	0.083	0.156	0.270	0.50
	Lateral spreading- middle column and h=v	0.019	0.114	0.229	0.419	0.50
	Lateral spreading- middle column and h=2v	0.017	0.079	0.182	0.488	0.50
Warehouse	Lateral spreading and h=v	0.125	0.620	1.346	2.634	0.40
	Lateral spreading and h=2v	0.107	0.522	1.081	1.954	0.41

Furthermore, it has been shown that for the lateral spreading case, the two- and four-storey RC MRFs, the nine-storey RC MRF for the collapse damage state as well as the steel light frame warehouse are more vulnerable when the horizontal component is equal to the vertical one whereas the nine-storey RC frame building presents higher vulnerability in the case where the horizontal component is equal to twice the vertical one for the slight, moderate and extensive damage states. This could be attributed to the fact that for the high-rise RC frame building subjected to lateral spreading with the horizontal component being equal to twice the vertical one, in contrast to the other cases, the maximum structural local response (in terms of material strain) is observed at different elements as the displacement load increases. More specifically, at lower levels of differential displacement the most affected element is a first floor beam while for increasing displacement level (higher than 0.30m) the maximum deformation is expected for a second floor beam.

Figure 5.7. Fragility curves for the (a) two-storey, (b) four-storey, (c) nine-storey RC frame buildings and (d) the warehouse subjected to differential displacements due to liquefaction

For the cases where at least 50% of the RC columns in a storey reach their shear capacity, new fragility curves for the complete damage state due to shear are derived. Figure 5.8 presents the comparison between the new fragility curves for the complete damage state due to shear failure (SF) with the corresponding ones due to flexural failure (FF). It is shown that complete shear failure is anticipated only for the two-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings subjected to lateral spreading. For the four-storey building subjected to lateral spreading, even though some shear failures in the columns distributed at the different floors are observed, complete shear failure (as defined herein) does not occur. It is also noted that for the studied low-code high-rise RC frame building shear failure would be the prevailing damage mechanism of the structure while for the low-rise RC frame building the flexural failure is expected to come first. This could be probably due to the P-delta effects that may adversely affect the performance of the high-rise RC frame building at high deformation levels amplifying the seismic shear demand and therefore resulting to a more fragile (local) failure mechanism (e.g. [Fenwick et al. 1992](#)).

Figure 5.8. Fragility curves for the complete damage state due to flexural (FF) or shear (SF) failure for the two-storey (left) and nine-storey (right) buildings subjected to lateral spreading

It is also noted that low-code RC bare MRFs are modelled in this study while the effect of the presence of infill walls on the response and fragility of the buildings is not considered. However, preliminary results of low-code RC infilled frame buildings subjected to differential displacement have shown that the presence of the masonry infills might increase the structure's deformation demand and the expected shear failures leading to more vulnerable structures.

5.6 Vulnerability curves

Once the probabilities of exceeding the specified damage states are estimated, a damage (or vulnerability) index d_m is evaluated for each differential displacement (settlement or lateral spreading) according to the following expression:

$$d_{mj} = \sum_{i=1}^4 P_{ij} \cdot d_i \quad (5.3)$$

where d_{mj} is the damage index (taking values from 0: no damage to 1: complete damage) corresponding to liquefaction intensity level j , P_{ij} is the discrete damage probability for each damage state and d_i stands for the damage index at each of the considered damage states.

For the RC buildings, the central value of the damage index for each damage state (i.e. d_i) is assumed equal to 0.05, 0.20, 0.45 and 0.80 for the LS₁, LS₂, LS₃ and LS₄ respectively according to [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#). A vulnerability curve is then constructed for each structural typology which provides a unique damage or vulnerability index d_m for each level of differential displacement. Figure 5.9 illustrates the derived vulnerability curves for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code MRF RC buildings subjected to liquefaction-induced differential settlements and lateral spreading respectively, which include also the possibility of shear failure. It is noted that with the given curves, losses in the RC structural members of the buildings are accounted for.

Figure 5.9. Vulnerability curves for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings subjected to liquefaction-induced differential settlements (left) and lateral spreading (right)

For the steel light frame warehouse, the central value of the damage index for each damage state (i.e. d_i) is assumed equal to 0.10, 0.40, 0.75 and 1.00 for the LS₁, LS₂, LS₃ and LS₄ respectively according to [Blong \(2003\)](#). Figure 5.10 illustrates the derived

vulnerability curve for the steel light frame warehouse subjected to liquefaction-induced differential displacements.

Figure 5.10. Vulnerability curve for the steel light frame warehouse subjected to liquefaction-induced differential displacements

However, due to the fact that the cost of the RC and steel (including the infills) structural systems totals less than the cost of a (new) building (which also includes non-structural members), the computed damage indices could then be multiplied with an empirically derived reductive coefficient, i.e. 0.33 for low-rise and mid-rise RC buildings, 0.38 for high-rise RC buildings, and 0.5 for steel buildings, to derive the final global damage index. Thus, it is implicitly shown that the total cost of non-structural damage, e.g. damage to ceilings, mechanical and electrical equipment that is an integral part of the structure, piping and elevators, partitions, exterior walls, ornamentation, glass (NIBS 2004), may be higher compared to the cost of repairs required to the structural system itself. If an average replacement cost is assumed for the considered building typologies then the final global damage index multiplied with these values returns the total cost of repairs in each building due to structural and non-structural damage.

5.7 Comparison with literature

The developed fragility curves for the studied low-code RC frame buildings are compared with some representative analytical fragility curves presented in Bird et al. (2005). More specifically, Figure 5.11 presents indicative comparisons between the herein curves derived for the two-storey low-code RC MRF building subjected to differential settlements and the corresponding ones taken from Bird et al. (2005) for damage states LS₁, LS₂ and LS₃ which are featuring the same damage state definition as in this study. Despite the large uncertainties involved in the problem, a good agreement

is observed for LS₃ while for LS₁ and LS₂ the analytical curves generally present much lower damage probability compared to the numerically derived curves of this study. Among others, a key reason for the above differences could be the following: in Bird et al. (2005) the maximum differential displacement is assumed to be applied at an edge column while in this study fragility curves are derived for the most unfavorable cases where the maximum differential displacement is applied at a middle column.

Figure 5.11. Comparison of the proposed fragility curves for the two-storey MRF RC building subjected to differential settlements with the corresponding analytical ones of Bird et al. (2005)

Moreover, in the following, some comparisons with field observations where widespread liquefaction occurred may further increase the validity of the proposed fragility curves. In particular, after the Christchurch, New Zealand 2010 and 2011 earthquakes, a six-story building founded on isolated spread footings with tie beams and perimeter grade beam, illustrated in Figure 5.12, was subjected to an overall differential settlement of 25.0 cm and it was considered uneconomical to repair after the 22 February 2011 earthquake (Bray and Dashti 2014). This observation is in accordance to the proposed fragility curves for the mid-rise MRF building, which suggest a median differential settlement of approximately 30.0 cm for the complete damage state.

It should be noted that the structure's fragility might potentially be overestimated as the proposed fragility curves are derived for the worst case scenarios (i.e. the ones where the maximum differential displacement is applied at a middle column) and the distribution feature of the maximum differential displacement is not considered. However, although the maximum differential settlement for the six-story building shown

in Figure 5.12 occurred at the edge, the predicted median differential settlement using the proposed fragility curves for the complete damage state is slightly higher compared to the one actually observed. Thus, in this specific case the proposed curves may slightly underestimate the results.

Figure 5.12. Liquefaction-induced differential settlement of a building on shallow foundations (after Bray and Dashti 2014)

In addition, the proposed fragility curves for the steel light frame warehouse are finally compared with the results of geotechnical field investigations for the Port International de Port-au-Prince following the 2010 Haiti earthquake which caused catastrophic ground failures in calcareous-sand artificial fills at the seaport, including liquefaction, lateral spreads and differential settlements. In particular, the port steel-frame warehouse founded on strip footings with width approximately equal to 37.0 m suffered significant damage but no collapse. According to a detailed survey, the maximum differential settlement in an internal bay of the warehouse was equal to 57.3cm while the differential lateral displacement equal to 94.9 cm (Green et al. 2011). These findings are in good agreement with the proposed fragility curves for the warehouse, which suggest extensive damage be expected for a differential displacement vector equal to 110.0 cm.

5.8 Concluding remarks

Within the framework of this study, a numerical methodology is presented for the vulnerability assessment of low-code RC MRF buildings of various heights and a typical steel-frame warehouse with a shallow foundation system, all representative of typical

buildings in South Europe, subjected to liquefaction-induced differential displacements. Parametric nonlinear static time-history analyses have been performed for each building typology. Different differential displacement profiles were assumed including settlements and lateral spreading with the maximum differential displacement imposed quasi-statically at a middle or edge column at the foundation level. Two different damage mechanisms have been considered, namely a flexural damage of the building members and a shear failure of the columns. Probabilistic fragility curves for different structural damage states and damage indices as a function of the differential displacement are developed. The proposed curves could be used within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the vulnerability and risk of typical low-code RC buildings and steel light frame warehouses in Greece and in Southern Europe in general exposed to liquefaction-induced differential displacements.

It has been shown that low-code RC buildings on isolated footings subjected to settlements are expected to suffer larger damages compared to the ones where the maximum differential displacement has also a horizontal component (lateral spreading). In addition, the building height is also an important parameter that may significantly affect the structural performance. In general, the high-rise low-code RC MRF buildings are more vulnerable compared to the low- and mid-rise ones, especially for the lateral spreading cases. It is also observed that the warehouse is by far less vulnerable than the RC frame structures. Finally, it is seen that shear failure would be the dominant damage mechanism only for the considered low-code high-rise MRF building subjected to lateral spreading.

Comparisons made of the herein derived fragility curves with the available ones from the literature ([Bird et al. 2005](#)) as well as with field observations ([Bray and Dashti 2014](#); [Green et al. 2011](#)) are generally satisfactory considering the important uncertainties involved.

Future research should be oriented towards the development of a probabilistic framework for the evaluation of the risk to buildings subjected to liquefaction-induced differential displacements, which will also take into account the uncertainties in the computation of the differential displacements. Another important issue that could be addressed in a future study would be the consideration of the combined vulnerability and risk to buildings due to ground shaking and liquefaction following for example the methodology presented in [Fotopoulou and Pitilakis \(2017\)](#) for other similar combined hazards (i.e. ground shaking and landslide). Finally, given the significance of this study's findings, future work should also address fragility analysis taking into account varying strength and stiffness characteristics of the studied structures within the given building

classes (to assess analytically the variability in the capacity ([Iervolino et al. 2004](#)), additional structural configurations as well as site and SSI effects.

Chapter 6

Vulnerability assessment of RC buildings subjected to ground shaking & liquefaction

6.1 Introduction

Usually severe damage caused to coastal buildings founded in loose saturated alluvial deposits is commonly not related to the ground shaking itself but to the induced phenomena principally associated with liquefaction effects (e.g. [Werner 1998](#)). The recent strong seismic events have demonstrated that most damage to coastal buildings is often associated with significant deformation of a soft or liquefiable soil deposit. Although progress has been made on the influence of ground shaking and soil liquefaction on the structural response of buildings (e.g. [Kappos et al. 2006](#); [Fotopoulou et al. 2018](#)), studies coupling both phenomena are very limited. In addition, Soil-Structure Interaction (SSI), may also play a significant role on the seismic performance of coastal buildings, modifying their dynamic characteristics, as well as the seismic response at foundation level. According to [PIANC \(2001\)](#), most damage to coastal structures is the result of SSI; hence, design and analysis procedures should include both foundation geotechnical conditions and structural conditions of coastal structures.

Traditionally, the seismic behaviour of buildings is estimated assuming fixed-base conditions, which may be a reasonable hypothesis only for structures founded on rock or very stiff soil. Nevertheless, the seismic response of a structure resting on deformable soil may differ significantly compared to the fixed-base assumption ([Mylonakis and Gazetas 2000](#)). The incorporation of SSI phenomena in the analysis has been generally believed to be beneficial, as SSI effects generally tend to reduce force demands on the structure. However, in nonlinear soil-structure systems additional translation and rotation effects may be produced during strong shaking increasing the displacement demands of the structure ([Kramer 1996](#); [Karapetrou et al. 2015](#)). The problem is expected to be even more complicated when soil liquefaction phenomena are present. However, numerical modelling techniques for estimating the influence of both soil liquefaction and

SSI effects on the structural response of buildings, has not received much attention and hence requires further investigation.

In the present chapter an analytical methodology for the vulnerability and risk assessment of buildings resting on liquefiable soils subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction is proposed, based on a fully coupled numerical approach taking into account the soil-structure interaction (SSI). Typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights (low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise) with shallow flexible foundations are considered at level ground and slope conditions. Vulnerability is expressed in terms of lognormally distributed fragility (or vulnerability) curves, as a function of rock outcropping peak ground acceleration (PGA_{rock}) or peak ground velocity (PGV_{rock}), and in terms of coupled fragility surfaces as function of both peak ground acceleration at free-field (PGA_{ff}) surface and maximum permanent ground displacement (PGD) vector at surface bellow the structure or both peak ground velocity (PGV) and maximum PGD vector at surface bellow the structure. Moreover, predictive relationships are established through regression analysis between the maximum differential permanent displacements (settlement or vector) at the foundation level due to soil liquefaction and the maximum PGD vector at surface bellow the structure, for buildings resting on liquefiable soils at level ground or slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction. The important issue of the interaction of ground shaking and ground failure (i.e. soil liquefaction) for individual buildings is investigated. In particular, the direct one-step approach where the soil and the structure are modelled and analysed as a single system, which accounts simultaneously for inertial and kinematic interaction schemes, is implemented considering soil nonlinearity introduced by soil liquefaction. Three typical soil profiles susceptible to liquefaction are investigated. To estimate the fragility function parameters, two-dimensional incremental dynamic analysis (IDA) of the nonlinear SSI systems is conducted. In addition, a second set of IDA is performed considering slope with a 5% grade to further examine the contribution of liquefaction-induced lateral spreading. The liquefiable soil response and subsequently the SSI models considering liquefaction potential (used in the framework of this study) are validated through important observations that are also identified in the literature. Finally, in order to verify the reliability of the proposed fragility curves and surfaces for the typical low-code RC frame buildings resting on liquefiable soils subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, they are compared with some representative analytical fragility curves and field data from the literature.

6.2 Literature review on the SSI and liquefaction

6.2.1 Physical principles of SSI

SSI is the mutual interaction and modification of the response of both the structure and the adjacent soil, as the term pronounces. It is a complicated phenomenon which lies at the intersection of various civil engineering fields, such as soil and structural mechanics, soil and structural dynamics, earthquake engineering and others. It was only since 1970 that SSI field gained the interest of scientific community, with [Richart et al. \(1970\)](#) first conducting a study on vibrations of soils and foundations, while several other studies on SSI followed.

It is widely recognised that the dynamic response of a structure supported on soft soil may be different from the response of a similarly excited, identical structure supported on stiff soil. There are two principal effects of the SSI on the structural response ([Veletsos and Meek 1974](#)):

- The flexibly supported superstructure has more degrees of freedom and, thus, different dynamic characteristics than the fixed-base superstructure.
- A significant part of the vibration energy of the flexibly supported superstructure may be dissipated by radiation of waves back into the soil, or by hysteretic material damping in the soil.

The seismic ground motion at free-field is affected by the earthquake source, the travel path and the local site effects, while structural response to free-field motion is further influenced by SSI effects. Two mechanisms of SSI take place between the structure, foundation, and soil ([Stewart et al. 1999](#)):

- Inertial Interaction: Inertia developed in the structure due to its own vibrations gives rise to base shear and moment, which in turn cause foundation displacements relative to the free-field. The flexibility of the foundation support as well as the damping associated with foundation-soil interaction can be described by frequency dependent foundation impedance functions.
- Kinematic Interaction: The presence of stiff foundation elements on or in soil cause foundation motions to deviate from free-field motions as a result of ground motion incoherence, wave inclination, or foundation embedment. These kinematic effects can be described by a frequency dependent transfer function relating the free-field motion to the motion that would occur on the base slab if the slab and structure were massless.

The last decades, numerous studies have highlighted the effects of SSI on elastic and inelastic structural response (e.g. [Ciampoli and Pinto 1995](#); [Gazetas and Mylonakis 2001](#);

Aviles and Perez-Rocha 2003; Moghaddasi et al. 2011; etc.), but there are only few studies investigating SSI and site effects on structures under nonlinear soil behaviour (e.g. Ptilakis D. et al. 2013; Ptilakis K. et al. 2014c; Karapetrou et al. 2015). In general, SSI tends to increase the natural vibration period of the structure, due to the additional foundation compliance. This period lengthening is traditionally assumed to be beneficial for the seismic response of the system. However, it is often shown that, in certain seismic and soil environments, period lengthening of a moderately flexible structure due to SSI may have a detrimental effect on the imposed seismic demand, depending mostly on the design response spectrum at the site (Mylonakis and Gazetas 2000).

Furthermore, the SSI effects on the soil response may be also pronounced. The soil response in the vicinity of the structure foundation is generally different from the free-field response (which is the response of the soil obtained in the absence of the structure). Therefore, the seismic input motion induced in the foundation of the structure is no longer the free-field response commonly used in the dynamic analyses of fixed-base structures, but is affected from the properties of the foundation soil and the dynamic characteristics of the superstructure.

6.2.2 Numerical modelling of SSI

In seismic performance assessment, it is a common practice to assume that structures are fixed to their base ignoring the presence of the soil beneath their foundation (Clough 1955), i.e. rigidly connected to the foundation soil. This assumption of a fixed-base structure may be a realistic hypothesis only when the structure is founded on relatively solid rock or very stiff soil. Nevertheless, the seismic response of a structure resting on deformable soil may significantly differ compared to the fixed-base assumption (Clough 1955; Mylonakis and Gazetas 2000). Especially in the case of soft soil formations and high-rise structures, SSI effects are generally more pronounced, modifying considerably the free-field input motion as well as the dynamic characteristics of the building and finally its response (Stewart et al. 1999).

SSI response in numerical modelling is usually achieved by considering inertial and kinematic interaction schemes that result to an elongation of the fundamental period of the SSI system and an increase of system damping due to the energy dissipation at the soil-foundation level compared to the fixed-base case (Veletsos and Meek 1974). In fact, kinematic interaction is the inability of the foundation to conform to the deformations of the free-field ground due to the actual stiffness of the foundation elements and the soil (Kramer 1996). On the other hand, the inertial interaction causes further deformation in the soil due to the inertial forces and moments induced by the superstructure to the soil. The general complexity of the SSI problem stems from the fact that the response of the

whole SSI system depends on two separate but strongly coupled components, the superstructure and the soil.

There are two main approaches that are commonly used for the analysis of the SSI phenomenon: the "direct approach", in which the soil and structure are modelled and analysed as a single system (Lysmer et al. 1975), and the "substructure approach" (Wolf 1985), in which SSI is analysed as two separate systems, usually the soil-foundation and the foundation-structure, each one solved separately, where the coupling of the interacting subdomains is achieved using impedance functions at the interface of the soil with the foundation (e.g. Gazetas 1991). The direct approach allows analysing the SSI system in its integrity, modelling the nonlinear behaviour of the structure and the soil through finite element formulations and evaluating simultaneously the response in the soil and in the structure. However, the increased computational cost compared to the substructure approach restricts its extensive application in the usual engineering practice. The substructure approach proves to be very efficient, as it decomposes the complete SSI system into different subdomains and evaluates the response of each subdomain separately with the best-suited numerical tool and the total system response is retrieved with linear superposition at the end. Finally, in the last two decades, hybrid methods that combine the advantages of the direct and substructure approaches have been developed, based mainly on the substructure method, where the superstructure is modelled by the standard finite element method.

6.2.3 Influence of SSI and liquefaction on the response and the vulnerability of buildings

Liquefaction constitutes a major source of damage to buildings during earthquakes, thus within a performance-based earthquake engineering (PBEE) framework, there is an urgent need to evaluate the liquefaction hazard and its consequences. Soil liquefaction can lead to excessive settlement, lateral displacement, tilt, and loss of bearing capacity of many buildings on shallow foundations, as observed during previous earthquakes, all of which can cause damage to structures. Especially liquefaction-induced building displacements are the main reason for buildings failures on liquefiable sites.

In the earthquake engineering practice, several methodologies are proposed in order to estimate the structural damage induced by soil liquefaction. In these methodologies the assessment of liquefaction potential and liquefaction-induced settlements is performed using literature relationships. In the simplified liquefaction assessment procedures, each layer is studied alone and a factor of safety against liquefaction triggering, maximum shear and volumetric strains are assessed separately for each layer, ignoring potential interactions between the different layers in the dynamic

response or pore water pressure redistribution and water flow. Thus, key mechanisms of system-response of liquefying deposits that potentially contribute to the severity of liquefaction apparition are not accounted for. [Cubrinovski et al. \(2017\)](#) demonstrated the need to account for the system response of liquefiable deposits in the assessment of liquefaction and associated damage. In addition, the procedures available for evaluating liquefaction potential (e.g. [Seed and Idriss 1971](#); [Youd et al. 2001](#); [Seed et al. 2003](#); [Idriss and Boulanger 2008](#); etc.) are based on free-field site conditions, ignoring the influence of the superstructure and SSI on the liquefaction hazard, the extent of excess pore pressure generation, the resulting changes in the amplitude and frequency content of the ground motion ([Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi 2008](#); [Dashti 2009](#)) as well as the resulting settlements, which are important in the vicinity of the structure. Moreover, the existing methods for assessing liquefaction-induced settlements (e.g. [Tokimatsu and Seed 1987](#); [Ishihara and Yoshimine 1992](#)) are primarily semi-empirical simplified procedures that also assume free-field conditions. In these procedures, soil response is assumed to be fully-undrained during seismic loading, while free-field settlements are calculated based on post-liquefaction volumetric strains alone. The partial drainage that occurs simultaneously with excess pore pressure generation during strong seismic shaking and the important deviatoric strain mechanisms are ignored.

However, centrifuge and numerical modelling studies (i.e. [Dashti et al. 2010](#); [Karimi and Dashti 2016](#)) found that SSI-induced deviatoric building ratcheting and localised volumetric strains during partially drained cyclic loading, that are controlled by three-dimensional (3D) transient hydraulic gradients, are often the dominant mechanisms of liquefaction-induced settlement of shallow-founded buildings, while the contribution of volumetric strains due to reconsolidation of the liquefied layer is relatively minor. When the 3D transient hydraulic gradients are at their peak and the soil approaches a state near liquefaction, the rate of flow is particularly high during shaking ([Dashti et al. 2010](#); [Shahir et al. 2012](#); [Karimi and Dashti 2015](#)). Moreover, it has been observed that the extent of excess pore pressure generation depends on the level of shear strains imposed on the soil ([Dobry et al. 1982](#)), while the level of induced shear strains depends on the soil properties, e.g. geometry and soil stiffness, the rock input motion characteristics, e.g. amplitude, frequency content and duration, as well as the superstructure properties, e.g. geometry, modal frequencies, and contact pressure ([Dashti and Karimi 2017](#)). Therefore, excess pore pressure generation and subsequently the seismic response of a SSI system strongly depends on the dynamic characteristics of the ground motion, the structure, as well as the structure's interaction with the underlying soil.

The last decades, several researchers conducted studies on the evaluation of SSI effects commonly using equivalent-linear, viscoelastic soil models. In the case where an elastic soil behaviour is assumed, the surface motion is amplified proportionally to the input motion. However, the soil response is highly nonlinear, especially when it undergoes significant strength loss and softening, e.g. the case of soil liquefaction. Thus, a better understanding of the SSI effects, in cases where the underlying soil is susceptible to liquefaction is required for earthquake-resistant structural design.

The soil response of saturated soils under strong seismic loading is governed by rather complex mechanical processes which may basically be attributed to hysteretic behaviour. Hysteretic behaviour consists of a decrease in the shear modulus associated with an increase in energy dissipation (damping), and volumetric-distortional coupling, which is related to plastic irreversible strain that takes place at high shear loading and induces either volumetric strains under drained conditions or pore pressure changes under undrained conditions (Tropeano et al. 2019), e.g. liquefaction in loose cohesionless soils. Regarding the pore pressure variation, two different approaches can be adopted in the response analysis: a “decoupled approach”, where the amount of excess pore water pressure is computed adopting semi-empirical relationships and starting from the result of a seismic response analysis of total stress; and a “coupled approach” that allows computing the time history of excess pore water pressure and carrying out non-linear dynamic analyses of effective stress by using either a simplified or an advanced soil constitutive model. Within an effective stress site response framework, two further distinct approaches can be adopted to predict earthquake-induced pore pressures: a “loosely coupled approach” that predicts pore pressures by adopting relationships used in combination with constitutive models that address total stress (e.g. pore pressure prediction based on accumulated strains or stresses) and a “fully coupled approach” that uses a plasticity-based constitutive model to predict both the stress-strain and the pore pressure response of the soil.

More recently, some advances have been made on the assessment of seismic liquefaction potential considering SSI effects. In particular, Noorzad et al. (2009) evaluated the effect of structures on the wave-induced liquefaction potential of seabed sand deposits. Oka et al. (2012) proposed a methodology to incorporate static shear stresses within the framework of the simplified procedure in order to take into account the effect of heavy structures on the liquefaction potential of the foundation soils. Cetin et al. (2012) developed an alternative simplified procedure for 3D dynamic response assessment of SSI systems, based on results from 3D finite difference-based total stress analyses for generic soil, structure and earthquake combinations, which can produce unbiased estimates of the representative and maximum soil-structure-earthquake-

induced cyclic stress ratio values. Meanwhile, [Wang et al. \(2015\)](#) evaluated the liquefaction potential of a liquefiable foundation overlying a sluice dam, based on the stress-based approach which compares the earthquake-induced cyclic stresses (CSR) with the cyclic resistance ratio (CRR) of the soil and seismic response analysis of a 3D FEM model including the dam and foundation. They considered both the static and dynamic interaction effects between the dam and foundation in the calculated CSR of the foundation.

In addition, in the literature a few methods have been developed for the evaluation of the liquefaction-induced settlement of shallow foundations using numerical modelling. For example, [Bouckovalas et al. \(1991\)](#) developed simplified analytical methods for predicting liquefaction-induced settlements based on the effective stress analysis. On the contrary, assuming that residual deformation occurs in the liquefied ground due to a reduction of shear modulus, [Yasuda et al. \(2001\)](#) calculated the ground deformation using total stress analysis with the initial shear modulus and reduced shear modulus due to liquefaction. However, these simplified methods ignore the true dynamic effects and the nonlinear soil behaviour. For an accurate assessment of the liquefaction-induced settlement of shallow-founded buildings, modelling of the processes of liquefaction and subsequent consolidation considering SSI effects is required. In order to simulate more realistically and in an integrated manner the seismic response of shallow-founded structures on liquefiable soil, nonlinear, fully coupled, dynamic numerical simulations of the SSI system considering effective stress analysis are often warranted. These simulations are able to provide insight into the soil's nonlinear response, its interaction with the superstructure, and the building's settlement, tilt, period lengthening and drift.

Among numerical studies on the influence of soil liquefaction and SSI on the structure response, [Popescu and Prevost \(1993\)](#); [Pietruszczak and Oulapour \(1999\)](#); [Koutsourelakis et al. \(2002\)](#); [Popescu \(2002\)](#); [Chakraborty et al. \(2004\)](#); [Elgamal et al. \(2005\)](#); [Popescu et al. \(2006\)](#); [Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi \(2008\)](#); [Andrianopoulos et al. \(2010\)](#); [Shahir and Pak \(2010\)](#) and [Karamitros et al. \(2013\)](#) conducted (2D) two-dimensional (plane strain) and 3D, fully coupled, nonlinear, finite element and finite-difference analysis to study the dynamic interaction between a homogeneous liquefying soil layer and a structure resting on the ground surface. In these analyses, the superstructure was modelled either as a surface load, rigid structure, or as a single degree of freedom (SDOF) system on top of a rigid shallow foundation.

Indicatively, it is mentioned that [Koutsourelakis et al. \(2002\)](#) dealt with the non-linear stochastic dynamic analysis of a SDOF structure based on a rigid, shallow foundation and located on top of a saturated sand layer (SSI system). They considered the stochastic spatial variability of soil properties and the randomness of the seismic excitation in order

to estimate the statistics of the response, measured in terms of uniform foundation settlement and tilting. They finally estimated the risk of damage to the SSI system due to liquefaction by establishing fragility curves, which are of paramount importance for risk assessment and management studies of such systems. [Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi \(2008\)](#) dealt with the influence of soil non-linearity, introduced by soil liquefaction and the SSI phenomena on both structural drift and settlement of a given structure. They considered several SDOF structures of different mechanical properties (i.e. mass and frequency) and input motion characteristics (i.e. amplitude, frequency content, Arias intensity), shallow-founded to reveal, with great simplicity, the beneficial or unfavourable effects of the SSI phenomenon. They carried out 2D coupled finite element effective stress analysis with GEFDYN computational tools ([Aubry and Modaressi 1996](#)) using the elastoplastic multi-mechanism Hujeux model ([Hujeux 1985](#)), which uses a Coulomb type failure criterion and the critical state concept, to represent the soil behaviour in a large range of deformations. [Karamitros et al. \(2013\)](#) demonstrated the beneficial role of a clay crust separating the foundation from the liquefied ground and provided insight into the complex soil-structure-pore-fluid interaction mechanisms which control the foundation's response, by performing 2D fully coupled nonlinear effective stress finite-difference analyses of a shallow strip foundation over a non-liquefiable clay.

Furthermore, [Elgamal et al. \(2005\)](#) implemented a 3D fully coupled numerical model, where the foundation was modelled as a surface load, using the soil stress-strain constitutive model of [Yang et al. \(2003\)](#) which is based on the original multi-surface-plasticity theory for frictional cohesionless soils ([Prevost 1985](#)), in order to investigate the liquefaction-induced settlement of footings. In addition, [Shahir and Pak \(2010\)](#) studied the dynamic response of shallow foundations on liquefied soils conducting a 3D fully coupled dynamic analysis, using the critical state two-surface plasticity model developed by [Dafalias and Manzari \(2004\)](#), which is based on the bounding surface plasticity theory ([Dafalias 1986](#)) within the critical state soil mechanics framework ([Schofield and Wroth 1968](#)).

Most of the previous numerical studies on soil liquefaction and its effects on structures (e.g. [Elgamal et al. 2005](#); [Popescu et al. 2006](#); [Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi 2008](#)) are case-specific and primarily aim to verify the accuracy of the various numerical techniques in comparison with experimental data, not covering a range of soil, structural, and ground motion properties. An exception is the early numerical study of [Naesgaard et al. \(1998\)](#), although less advanced compared with current practices, it was parametric and resulted to simple analytical expressions for the assessment of seismic foundation settlements of light buildings. Another study conducted

to reveal the simultaneous influence of non-linear SSI and soil liquefaction on the structural response considering both the “substructure approach” and the “direct approach” is that of [Barrios and Chouw \(2015\)](#). In particular, they used a two-step approach that considered a 1D soil column, in which the acceleration obtained at the surface was applied to an SDOF structure with fixed base assumption, as well as one-step approach that considered a 2D soil-foundation-structure model. After studying SDOF structures with different fundamental frequencies to represent a wide range of structures, they concluded that structures with a low natural frequency seem to be more affected by liquefaction.

The whole liquefaction process, including the onset of liquefaction, the process of generation, diffusion and release of excess pore water pressure, and even the development of liquefaction-induced displacements can be simulated with complicated codes of fully coupled dynamic consolidation involving comprehensive constitutive models. It should also be noted that the accuracy of numerical simulation depends on the material constitutive model. Over the years, a plethora of numerical simulation platforms, e.g. OpenSEES ([Mazzoni et al. 2009](#)), FLAC ([Itasca 2016](#)), PLAXIS ([Brinkgreve et al. 2017](#)), etc., have been developed for advanced geotechnical engineering simulations involving liquefaction, most of which treat the saturated soil as two-phase media in which the differential equations governing the motion of soil and pore water flow are formulated by using Biot's theory or mixture theory. Moreover, some exciting progress has been achieved in the realm of constitutive modelling of the cyclic loading of non-cohesive soils, with emphasis on cyclic mobility and flow liquefaction, that may be divided into different categories depending on their fundamental characteristics, such as multi-surface plasticity models (e.g. [Prevost 1978](#); [Cubrinovski and Ishihara 1998](#); [Yang et al. 2003](#); [Yang et al. 2008](#)), two-surface plasticity models (e.g. [Poorooshasb and Pietruszczak 1986](#); [Manzari and Dafalias 1997](#); [Gajo and Wood 1999](#); [Papadimitriou et al. 2001](#); [Papadimitriou and Bouckovalas 2002](#); [Loukidis and Salgado 2009](#)), bounding surface plasticity models (e.g. [Dafalias 1986](#); [Wang et al. 1990](#); [Li et al. 1999](#); [Li 2002](#); [Andrianopoulos et al. 2010](#)) and generalised plasticity models (e.g. [Pastor et al. 1990](#); [Iai et al. 1992](#); [Ling and Liu 2003](#); [Ling and Yang 2006](#)). It is mentioned that in the multi-surface plasticity concept, the complex aspects of soil behaviour are described by nested yield surfaces and as the loading occurs the stress state moves along nested yield surfaces and plastic strains are generated, while in the bounding surface plasticity concept, the magnitude of plastic strain is function of a given stress state and stress state on the bounding surface ([Zahmatkesh and Choobbasti 2017](#)). Each constitutive model has certain advantages and limitations. A short description of some of the most

widely used constitutive models implemented in advanced computer codes is following below.

The Simple ANisotropic SAND (SANISAND) plasticity model (Dafalias and Manzari 2004) is a simple plasticity sand model accounting for fabric change effects that is based on the sand constitutive model proposed by Manzari and Dafalias (1997). The main advantages of the SANISAND constitutive model are that it is relatively simple of formulations and has a unique set of input parameters for a wide range of initial stress and void ratio. It has been successfully used for simulating the behaviour of granular soils subjected to monotonic and cyclic loading (e.g. Jeremic et al. 2008), while its parameters have been calibrated for different types of sand, such as Toyoura sand (Dafalias and Manzari 2004), Sacramento sand (Taiebat et al. 2010), Nevada sand (Shahir et al. 2012), and Babolsar coastal sand (Zahmatkesh and Choobbasti 2017).

The UBCSAND plasticity model (Puebla et al. 1997; Byrne et al. 2004; Beaty and Byrne 2011) is a fully nonlinear, effective stress constitutive model, commonly used in practice in advanced stress-deformation analyses of geotechnical structures, that directly estimates the soil skeleton response to general increments of loading. The model is based on classic plasticity theory and the characteristic sand behaviour observed in laboratory tests under monotonic and cyclic loading conditions. The model has been successfully used for capturing reasonably well the undrained responses of a clean sand specimen in triaxial compression, extension, and simple shear tests (Puebla et al. 1997), as well as the characteristic drained response of clean sand in cyclic simple shear tests (Byrne et al. 2004). The predictive capabilities of 2D, fully coupled, numerical simulations using the fully nonlinear, effective stress soil constitutive model UBCSAND implemented in the finite-difference Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua (FLAC) platform (Itasca 2016) have been also validated by Dashti and Bray (2013) using the results from the Dashti et al. (2010) centrifuge experiments of shallow-founded structures on liquefiable sand.

The PM4Sand plasticity model (Boulanger and Ziotopoulou 2012) is another sand constitutive model widely used for geotechnical earthquake engineering applications, which follows the basic framework of the stress-ratio controlled, critical state compatible, bounding surface plasticity model for sand initially proposed by Manzari and Dafalias (1997) and later modified by Dafalias and Manzari (2004). Further modifications developed by Boulanger (2010) and Boulanger and Ziotopoulou (2012) finally improved its ability to estimate the stress-strain behaviour that is important to predict liquefaction-induced ground deformations during earthquakes. The PM4Sand model can be used with the commercial finite-difference software FLAC (Itasca 2016). Indicatively, it is mentioned that the PM4Sand plasticity model was used to model all soil layers by

Ziotopoulou and Montgomery (2017) in order to evaluate the relative importance of post-liquefaction reconsolidation settlements on shallow foundations. They used 2D fully coupled dynamic analyses to simulate the response of shallow foundations on liquefiable soil deposits. They found that liquefaction and subsequent reconsolidation can lead to settlement, ground cracking and loss of bearing capacity all of which can cause damage to structures.

Finally, the pressure depend multi-yield 02 (PDMY02) plasticity-based soil constitutive model (Elgamal et al. 2002; Yang et al. 2003; 2008) which is incorporated into the finite element Open Source Earthquake Engineering Simulator (OpenSees) platform (Mazzoni et al. 2009), is a model which directly takes into account excess pore pressure redistribution and SSI in evaluating the liquefaction hazard and effects on structures. Yang and Elgamal (2003) attempted to calibrate the PDMY02 soil constitutive model to a database of field and laboratory data and have established some typical values for various sand densities (Mazzoni et al. 2009). In addition, Karimi and Dashti (2016), conducted a more comprehensive comparison of numerical simulation results with recordings from centrifuge experiments performed by Dashti et al. (2010) for a range of structures, soil layering, and ground motions, in terms of acceleration, settlement, tilt, flexible-base fundamental period, as well as the different components of transient inter-storey drift (total, rocking, and flexural) in both time and frequency domains. In particular, they implemented in OpenSees, 3D, solid-fluid, fully coupled, nonlinear, dynamic finite element simulations of shallow-founded (SDOF) structures resting on liquefiable soils, using the PDMY02 soil constitutive model, which provides a tool to capture liquefaction during seismic loading and provided insights into the model's capabilities and limitations in predicting the key engineering demand parameters that control building performance and damage potential for a range of conditions. The fundamental period, foundation contact pressure, building height/width ($H=B$) aspect ratio, and foundation contact area varied among three SDOF structures studied experimentally and numerically. The relative density and drainage capacity of the liquefiable layer also varied, allowing an evaluation of their effects on the response of different structures. Subsequently, Dashti and Karimi (2017) using the results of the numerical parametric study, validated against centrifuge results, identified improved IMs for predicting the generation of excess pore pressure and thus the liquefaction potential in saturated sandy soils not just in the far-field, but also in the vicinity of structures.

Although the predictive capabilities of the above models have often been evaluated by several researchers individually, a systematic comparison of their capabilities and limitations in capturing the seismic site response and SSI on layered liquefiable soil deposits is also beneficial, not only to advance the accuracy of the numerical models but

also to gain insight into the different numerical models and platforms. Towards this direction, the study of [Ramirez et al. \(2018\)](#) quantifies and compares the accuracy of two numerical platforms (i.e. OpenSees and FLAC) and two constitutive models (i.e. PDMY02 and SANISAND) in simultaneously capturing the seismic response of a layered saturated level liquefiable soil deposit in terms of volumetric settlements, accelerations, and excess pore pressures. A similar study is underway by researchers following the LEAP (Liquefaction Experiments and Analysis Projects) international collaborative project, which primarily aims to develop a protocol for verification, calibration, and validation of numerical simulations used for analysis of liquefaction problems ([Manzari et al. 2014](#); [Kutter et al. 2015](#)).

The described numerical modelling techniques for estimating liquefaction-induced damages using the “coupled approach”, where the damages due to combined ground shaking and soil liquefaction are estimated in a single step, have already been applied for bridge systems (e.g. [Bowers 2007](#); [Kwon et al. 2009](#); [Elgamal 2010](#); [Aygün et al. 2011](#); [Brandenberg et al. 2011a](#); [Wang et al. 2014](#)), quay walls ([Ichii 2003](#); [2004](#)) and other simplified soil-structure systems (e.g. [Koutsourelakis et al. 2002](#); [Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi 2008](#); etc.). Indicatively, [Elgamal \(2010\)](#) highlighted the influence of seismically-induced ground deformation on the overall structural response of a large bridge, conducting 3D simulation of combined ground foundation-structural system with OpenSeesPL software. [Wang et al. \(2014\)](#) investigated effects of SSI and liquefaction on the fragility of both an unretrofitted and an isolated coupled bridge-soil-foundation (CBSF) system, concluding that the failure probability of the isolated system is less than that of the non-isolated one for both stiff soils and soft soils, whereas SSI tends to simultaneously decrease isolation effectiveness; and that liquefaction provides an effective natural isolation by reducing the curvature demands on the columns, although it increases the isolation bearing displacement and pile curvature. Therefore, SSI should be considered in the design of isolated bridges, as appropriate isolation in conjunction with the CBSF system could still offer a viable retrofit option by replacing the vulnerable steel bearings and reducing critical component demands, such as columns, even if liquefaction occurs. [Chen et al. \(2018\)](#) also used the OpenSees platform to conduct Plane strain analysis, where the liquefiable soil was modelled using the unified plasticity model for large post-liquefaction shear deformation of sand (CycLiqCPSP) developed by [Wang R. et al. \(2014\)](#) and [Wang R. \(2016\)](#). Moreover, it should be noted that these numerical modelling techniques have also been applied for liquefaction mitigation. In particular, [Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi \(2013\)](#) assessed numerically the efficiency of the soil densification using preloading techniques on the improvement of liquefiable sandy profiles to shaking. However, the application of

these advanced modelling methods to typical building structures has not received much attention and hence requires further investigation, probably due to the fact that the combined soil-structure models require large amounts of computational power.

In general, the seismic assessment of building performance and the consideration of impacts from soil liquefaction has often been studied completely separately. However, it should be noted that [Bird and Bommer \(2004\)](#) reported several cases where a combination of shaking and ground failure damage could be observed. In addition, recent works dealing with the assessment of structural damage induced by earthquake-induced liquefaction, point out the necessity to incorporate liquefaction phenomena into a loss estimation model ([Juang et al. 2005](#); [Bird et al. 2006](#)). An important issue for the incorporation of earthquake-induced liquefaction into earthquake loss estimations is how to combine liquefaction-induced damage with damage caused by ground shaking. [Bird et al. \(2006\)](#) also discuss the issues with combining ground shaking damage and soil liquefaction damage, and proposed a methodological framework for estimating losses from combined damage, by first assessing structural performance to ground shaking and then assessing liquefaction demands using the residual capacity of the building and combining damage using a utility function based on the time of liquefaction.

More recently, extensive research on earthquake-induced liquefaction disasters has been conducted within a European research project titled LIQUEFACT ("Assessment and mitigation of liquefaction potential across Europe: a holistic approach to protect structures / infrastructures for improved resilience to earthquake-induced liquefaction disasters"). In the framework of this project, only a few papers have already been published. In particular, [Borozan et al. \(2017\)](#), in an attempt to understand the effect of the presence of the structure on the settlements due to earthquake-induced liquefaction, concluded that the static safety factor of the foundation appears to be an indicator that should be considered for the development of simplified models to estimate building settlements due to liquefaction. [Chiaradonna et al. \(2018\)](#), after conducting dynamic analyses that reproduce the observed liquefaction triggering caused by the 2012 M6.1 Emilia earthquake and predict the seismic soil response at a selected site of Pieve di Cento in Italy, assessed the effectiveness of several mitigation measures against liquefaction at this test site. Moreover, [Gómez-Martínez et al. \(2018\)](#) proposed a simplified methodology for the preliminary estimation of the relevance of the differential settlements due to liquefaction and their corresponding elastic flexural demand on members accounting for SSI. This is a rather simple approach relying on the structure-to-soil stiffness ratio and the soil degradation extent under footings. In addition, [Millen et al. \(2018\)](#) attempted to develop a simplified cost-effective procedure to include both liquefaction-related damage and ground shaking damage for use in preliminary building

assessment. In this procedure, the effects of liquefaction were quantified through modifications to the soil-foundation-structure system, the site response, the inclusion of differential settlements.

Although some advances have been made on the effect of overlying structures on the evaluation of liquefaction potential and on the assessment of liquefaction displacements as well as on the separate estimation of building performance due to ground shaking or soil liquefaction displacements, to estimate seismic structural damages and losses of buildings resting on liquefiable soils still remains a controversial and difficult issue. Taking into account the general lack of methodologies to account for the combined effects of ground shaking and soil liquefaction on structural damages considering SSI, an analytical fully coupled analytical vulnerability assessment methodology resulting to the derivation of fragility functions for buildings on flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils is proposed herein.

In particular, the direct one-step approach where the soil and the structure are modelled and analysed as a single system is implemented considering soil nonlinearity introduced by soil liquefaction. Two-dimensional effective stress response analysis of the nonlinear SSI systems is conducted, using the finite element code OpenSees. For the soil nine-node quadrilateral plane-strain elements with both displacement and pore pressure degrees of freedom, which enable the soil model to track changes in pore pressure and effective stress during the earthquake excitation, are implemented. These elements are capable to simulate dynamic response of solid-fluid fully coupled material, based on Biot's theory of porous medium. For the structure nonlinear beam-column elements are used. Two-dimensional IDA analysis of the nonlinear SSI systems is conducted so as the fragility function parameters are estimated. In addition, the contribution of liquefaction-induced lateral spreading is further examined by performing a second set of IDA considering slope with a 5% grade. Finally, it is noted that although no direct comparisons are made with centrifuge studies, observed trends are assessed and discussed, and the proposed fragility curves and surfaces are compared with analytical fragility curves and field data from the literature in order to verify their reliability.

6.3 Description of the methodological framework

The schematic flowchart of the proposed methodological framework for the vulnerability and risk assessment of buildings resting on liquefiable soils subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction taking into account SSI is illustrated in Figure 6.1. It involves a comprehensive set of nonlinear numerical computations and adequate statistical analysis. The conceptual features of the proposed methodology are outlined in the following paragraphs.

Figure 6.1. Flowchart of the proposed methodology for the vulnerability and risk assessment of buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

In the proposed methodology, in terms of numerical simulation, the direct one-step coupled analysis is conducted, where the soil and the structure are modelled and analysed as a single system, which accounts simultaneously for inertial and kinematic interaction schemes and considers soil nonlinearity introduced by soil liquefaction. Typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights (low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise) with flexible foundation system and three typical soil profiles susceptible to liquefaction with level ground conditions and slope conditions (5% grade) are considered for the analysis. The numerical simulation of the structural capacity is based on the structural detailing, the material properties and the plasticity modelling, while SSI effects are incorporated in the assessment methodology performed. The complex issue of the interaction of ground shaking and ground failure (i.e. soil liquefaction) for individual buildings is investigated and taken into account in the evaluation of the building's vulnerability. The earthquake demand is determined based on the selection of real earthquake records that cover a wide range of seismic input motions in terms of amplitude, frequency content and

significant duration. Each seismic input motion is applied to the base of the soil model (bedrock). Two-dimensional Incremental Dynamic Analyses (IDA) are conducted to assess the seismic performance of the SSI systems and the building's response in terms of maximum inter-storey drift (maxISD), i.e. the EDP, is estimated.

Subsequently, appropriate damage limit states are defined in terms of maxISD. Four damage states are defined associated with slight, moderate, extensive and complete structural damage of the buildings. The vulnerability is assessed through probabilistic fragility curves and fragility surfaces, which describe the probability of exceeding each limit state, considering various sources of uncertainty. In the probabilistic approach proposed within the framework of this thesis, several uncertainties are involved with respect to the structural capacity (which reflects the variability of the structural properties and the fact that the modelling procedures are not perfect), the seismic demand (which is associated with the randomness in the ground motions and the record-to-record variability) and the definition of the damage states (which are attributed to the fact that the thresholds of the damage indices or parameters used to define the damage states are generally not known).

A key point in the fragility assessment is the selection of the intensity measure (IM) that adequately correlates with damage. It is noted that when the rock outcropping peak ground acceleration (PGA_{rock}), which characterises the earthquake ground motion peak amplitude (amplitude/intensity), or peak ground velocity (PGV_{rock}) which characterises the intensity and frequency content of the earthquake motion, is used as an IM, the local soil conditions, surface geology, soil and topographic amplification are directly included in the fragility analysis. On the other hand, permanent ground displacement (PGD) at surface that is obtained from the response of the liquefiable soil profile to ground shaking is better correlated to structural deformation and damage. In addition, maximum differential permanent displacements at the foundation level could also be used as measure of the liquefaction intensity (see also Chapter 5). However, their accurate estimation in the field generally involves a higher degree of uncertainty. Thus, their use is justified for site-specific applications on critical buildings where adequate data from field measurements and/or detailed numerical analysis are available.

Based on the above, fragility curves are generated in terms of either the PGA_{rock} or the PGV_{rock} . Moreover, except for conventional fragility curves, it was deemed appropriate to develop fragility surfaces, which are a function of more than one IM, for use within seismic risk assessment of buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction. In section 6.9, some of the most pronounced advantages of fragility surfaces against curves are presented. Thus, the pair of the PGA_{ff} at free-field surface and the maximum permanent ground displacement (PGD) vector that occurs at surface

at the foundation level of the structure as well as the pair of the PGV and the maximum PGD vector that occur at surface below the structure are selected as the most adequate pairs of IMs for the derivation of fragility surfaces, as they provide useful and important information for an integrated vulnerability assessment.

For the development of fragility curves, an appropriate relationship between the numerically calculated maxISD (i.e. the EDP) and the PGA_{rock} or the PGV_{rock} (i.e. the IM) is established through nonlinear regression analysis. Lognormally distributed fragility curves are finally derived in terms of either the PGA_{rock} or the PGV_{rock} for the different damage limit states for the various building typologies considered, based on the statistical exploitation of the results of the IDA.

For the development of fragility surfaces, a linear regression which can be considered as an extension of scalar fragility fitting, is adopted to correlate the computed maxISD (EDP) with the two considered IMs for the estimation of fragility surfaces for the different damage limit states for the various building typologies considered. In particular, first a relationship between the two considered IMs is obtained by a linear regression fit of the logarithms of the IM_1 - IM_2 IDA data pairs. Moreover, a linear regression fit of the logarithms of the IM_1 -maxISD data pairs which minimizes the regression residuals is adopted in all analysis cases. Subsequently, another linear regression analysis of the residuals of the previous regression on IM_1 (PGA_{ff} or PGV) and the logarithms of the corresponding IM_2 (PGD) is also conducted for each structural model.

Once the fragility curves of the considered building typologies subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction are available, a vulnerability curve or surface can be constructed, which provides a unique damage or vulnerability index d_m for each level of seismic intensity. The damage index is a convenient measure to quantify the structural losses and finally to assess the risk at building or community level when properly aggregated. It may be quantified in cost terms as the ratio of cost of repair to cost of replacement taking values from 0: no damage (cost of repair equals 0) to 1: complete damage (cost of repair equals the cost of replacement).

6.4 Numerical modelling

6.4.1 Selection of the structural building typologies and liquefiable soil profiles

To illustrate the proposed methodology for the vulnerability assessment of buildings subjected to combined ground shaking & liquefaction, the three typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights (Kappos et al. 2006), presented in the previous chapters, are selected as reference structures. As noted in previous chapters, they were

designed according to the 1959 Greek seismic code ('Royal Decree' of 1959) corresponding to low level of seismic design. This means that issues such as the ductility, the capacity and the dynamic features of the structures were completely ignored in their design. The first building is a two-storey three-bay frame structure representative of low-rise (1-3 stories) MRF RC buildings. The second one is a four-storey three-bay frame structure that represents mid-rise (4-7 stories) MRF RC buildings, while the third one is a nine-storey three-bay frame structure that is considered typical of high-rise (8+ stories) MRF RC buildings. In all cases the height of the 1st storey is 4.5m and that of the upper storeys is 3.0m. Table 4.4 summarizes the main characteristics of the building typologies studied in this chapter, namely the mass, fundamental period, compressive concrete strength f_c and yield strength of steel reinforcement f_y , while Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3a illustrate the reinforcement layout and the floor plan respectively of the studied low-code RC MRF building typologies (Kappos et al. 2006).

Regarding the soil, three liquefiable soil profiles, representative of the port area of Thessaloniki, simplified regarding their total depth, denoted as A, B, and C (Figure 6.2), with fundamental periods T_0 equal to 0.88 sec, 0.73 sec and 0.64 sec respectively, have been defined based on the available geotechnical information of the port area and the available SPT and laboratory data (Anastasiadis et al. 2001; Pitilakis et al. 2018) to compute the ground response. Further information regarding the available geotechnical and geophysical data in the area of Thessaloniki port as well as the geological background information of the broader area is provided in the next chapter. Figure 6.2 presents the variation of the shear wave velocities V_s with depth together with a general geotechnical characterization according to USCS classification for the three soil profiles.

Figure 6.2. Schematic representation of the V_s profiles for sites A (left), B (middle) and C (right) together with a general geotechnical characterization according to USCS classification

The liquefaction potential of the subsoil layers of the whole soil profiles was quantitatively evaluated by following the guidelines of EC8 and is more analytically presented in Annex A. Among the three representative soil profiles, liquefaction effects are found to be more pronounced in profile A. For soil profile A the liquefiable soil formations were found at depths $z=-9\div 11\text{m}$, $z=-14\div 20\text{m}$ and $z=-26.5\div 36\text{m}$, for soil profile B at depths $z=-3\div 14\text{m}$, while for soil profile C at depths $z=-4\div 20\text{m}$, which are basically silty/clayey sands and non-plastic silts with low values of NSPT. Thus, knowing that the liquefaction susceptibility in the port area is rather high, these soil profiles refer to ground type S2 according to EC8 classification.

6.4.2 Structural finite element modelling in OpenSees

The two-dimensional numerical simulation of the selected building typologies is built using the open-source computational platform OpenSees ([Mazzoni et al. 2009](#)). The Open System for Earthquake Engineering Simulation (OpenSees) is an open-source finite element framework developed at PEER (Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Centre). It is a comprehensive and continually developing software, designed around an object-oriented architecture, which is used for simulation of the seismic response of structural and geotechnical systems subjected to static and seismic loadings. An extensive library of material models is provided, supporting also a wide range of solution procedures and computation models.

Inelastic force-based formulations are implemented for the two-dimensional with three degrees of freedom nonlinear beam-column frame element modelling. The nonlinear beam-column frame elements are subjected to both axial compression and bending, considering five Gauss-Lobatto ([Neuenhofer and Filippou 1997](#)) integration points along each member's length. The applied formulations allow both geometric nonlinearities (P-delta and large displacements/rotation effects) and material inelasticity to be captured.

Distributed material inelasticity along the element is applied based on the fibre approach to represent the cross-sectional behaviour ([Spacone et al. 1996](#)). Each fibre is associated with a uniaxial stress-strain relationship; the sectional stress-strain state of the beam-column elements is obtained through the integration of the nonlinear uniaxial stress-strain response of the individual fibres in which the section is subdivided.

In the present analysis, for the concrete the uniaxial "Concrete01" material is used to construct a uniaxial Kent-Scott-Park ([Scott et al. 1982](#)) concrete material object with degraded linear unloading/reloading stiffness according to the work of Karsan-Jirsa ([Karsan and Jirsa 1969](#)) and zero tensile strength. Different material parameters are adopted for the confined (core) and the unconfined (cover) concrete. For the steel

reinforcement, the uniaxial "Steel01" material is used to construct a uniaxial bilinear steel material object with kinematic hardening described by a non-linear evolution equation. Figure 6.3 illustrates the material objects adopted in OpenSees used for the representation of the uniaxial stress-strain relationships for the concrete (cover and core) and for the steel reinforcement.

Figure 6.3. Material objects adopted in OpenSees for the representation of the uniaxial stress-strain relationships for the concrete cover and core (left) and for the steel reinforcement (right)

For the definition of the concrete material objects, the following parameters are involved: the concrete compressive strength at 28 days (f_{pc}), the concrete strain at maximum strength (e_{psc0}), the concrete crushing strength (f_{pcu}) and the concrete strain at crushing strength, e_{psU} . Thus, for the concrete material adopted for the studied building typologies in the analysis, the concrete compressive strength and the concrete strain at maximum strength are set equal to $f_{pc} = 14.0$ MPa and $e_{psc0} = 0.002$ respectively, while the concrete crushing strength and the corresponding concrete strain are taken equal to $f_{pcu} = 2.8$ MPa and $e_{psU} = 0.0098$ respectively. The confinement factor (i.e. the ratio of confined to unconfined concrete strength) is taken equal to 1.0 (i.e. no confinement is considered), as the buildings are designed with low seismic design code level.

For the definition of the steel reinforcement material objects, the main parameters that are required are the yield strength (F_y), the initial elastic tangent (E_0) and the strain-hardening ratio (b), which is the ratio between post-yield tangent and initial elastic tangent. In this analysis, the yield strength, the initial elastic tangent modulus of steel and the strain-hardening ratio are taken equal to $F_y = 400.0$ MPa, $E_0 = 200.0$ GPa and $b=0.005$ respectively.

Except for hysteretic damping, which is implicitly taken into account within the nonlinear fibre model formulation of the inelastic frame elements, tangent stiffness-based Rayleigh proportional damping is assigned, with a damping ratio of 3.0%, in order to

account for the non-hysteretic viscous type of damping that is mobilised during the dynamic response of the analysed systems (e.g. internal friction). In this case the stiffness coefficients are recomputed each time the stiffness changes and the damping matrix is reformed on this basis, assuming that the damping ratios in the specified modes do not change, regardless of modal frequency (Charney 2008). It is noted that Priestley and Grant (2005) showed that tangent stiffness proportional viscous damping is more appropriate than a constant damping for modelling elastic viscous damping in inelastic time-history analyses, resulting to a more realistic computation of the elastic damping forces and more reliable estimates of the displacement responses.

6.4.3 Soil-structure interaction (SSI) modelling

The direct one-step approach, which accounts simultaneously for inertial and kinematic interaction schemes, is applied for the consideration of SSI. The two-dimensional (2D) dynamic analysis of the considered SSI models are conducted with OpenSees finite element platform (Mazzoni et al. 2009). Figure 6.4 represents the two-dimensional (2D) coupled finite element (FE) soil-structure models for the three representative low-code RC frame buildings of different heights (low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise) resting on liquefiable soil, which are subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, developed in OpenSees and adopted within the framework of this thesis.

6.4.3.1 Description of the model

In order to identify the appropriate dimensions of the grid for each considered soil profile, a sensitivity analysis is conducted so as to assure free-field and “quasi transparent” conditions at the boundaries. The obtained free-field (FF) response of the sites was validated conducting also 1D site response analysis in OpenSees (Mazzoni et al. 2009) and Cyclic 1D (Elgamal et al. 2015), where the response was found the same. Therefore, the grids adopted for the different soil profiles A, B and C have total lengths three times their depth to avoid spurious wave reflections at the vertical boundaries. Their dimensions are defined equal to 60.0m x 180.0m, 50.0m x 150.0m and 46.0m x 138.0m, respectively. Dense discretization is achieved using quadrilateral elements of 0.5m x 2.0m (height x length), considering that the maximum frequency of interest is set to 10.0Hz. This mesh allows an adequate number of elements to fit within the shortest wavelength of the propagating shear wave.

Full bond is assumed between the structure’s foundation and the soil nodes. The connection of the soil with the structure is achieved by applying common nodes and appropriate constrains (to ensure equal displacement) for both the soil and the structure’s foundation. Shallow, relatively flexible foundations are considered, modelled

as elastic beam-column elements of infinite rigidity, which allow columns moving differentially and hence permitting the computation of structural deformation demand using a numerical approach. It is furthermore assumed that no interface has been considered between the structure and the foundation and that failure will take place on the building's structural elements, while the structural integrity of the foundation itself will not be affected by the liquefaction induced deformation.

Figure 6.4. Finite element SSI models for the (a) two-storey, (b) four-storey and (c) nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings resting on liquefiable soil

Each soil profile consists of several layers of cohesive and cohesionless soil material. The depth of the groundwater table of each soil profile is shown in Figure 6.2. In particular, the groundwater table is located at a depth of 1.5m, 2.0m and 1.5m for soil profiles A, B and C, respectively. Saturated unit weights are used for the soil below this level and effective stress analysis is considered using nine-node quadrilateral elements with both displacement and pore pressure degrees of freedom, which enable the model to track changes in pore pressure and effective stress during the earthquake excitation. In particular, such elements are able to simulate fluid-solid coupling during the earthquake excitation, based on Biot's theory of porous medium (Biot 1962). Figure 6.5 illustrates a single nine-node element to demonstrate the layout of the nodes and the order of element connectivity. In particular, the corner nodes of a nine-node element have three degrees of freedom, two translational and one pore pressure, while the interior nodes have only two translational degrees of freedom. It is noted that the pore pressure nodes above the groundwater table are fixed in the pore pressure degree of freedom (representing an open drainage condition).

Figure 6.5. Nine-node quadrilateral element adopted in OpenSees

Each soil profile is underlain by an elastic half-space which represents the finite rigidity of the underlying bedrock. A Lysmer-Kuhlemeyer dashpot (Lysmer and Kuhlemeyer 1969) is incorporated at the base of each soil profile, in order to account for the finite rigidity of the underlying bedrock, using a bedrock shear wave velocity of 627.0m/s, 750.0m/s and 750.0m/s for the soil profiles A, B and C respectively and a mass density of 2.2Mg/m³. The Lysmer-Kuhlemeyer dashpot is assigned based on the viscous uniaxial material model and the "zeroLength" element formulation at the same location, to connect the two previously defined dashpot nodes. In particular, the single "zeroLength" element is used to define the Lysmer-Kuhlemeyer dashpot. One end of the dashpot element is fixed against all displacements, while the other is given "equalDOF" with the soil node in the lower left hand corner of the soil model, which is the master

node for the horizontal "equalDOF" assigned to the nodes at the base of the mesh. The viscous uniaxial material is used to define the constitutive behaviour of the Lysmer-Kuhlemeyer dashpot in the horizontal direction. This material model requires a single input, the dashpot coefficient (c), which is defined according to Joyner and Chen (1975) as the product of the mass density and shear wave velocity of the underlying bedrock including also the base area of the soil profile. The dashpot coefficient is scaled by the area of the base of the soil model to ensure that equivalent loading is applied. To model the underlying elastic half-space necessitates that the nodes at the base of the soil model be left free to displace in the horizontal direction, be all given the same horizontal displacements and finally be fixed against vertical translation only.

Since elastoplastic soil behaviour is considered in these models, inherent hysteretic damping occurs. However, a small amount of mass and stiffness proportional Rayleigh damping is employed to account for energy dissipation during seismic loading, so there is still some damping at low strain values. The level of Rayleigh damping is controlled by the damping ratio (assigned equal to $\xi = 2.0\%$ for the soil material) and the angular frequencies of two modes of vibration. This damping form facilitates the dynamic analysis, as the damping matrix is built as a linear combination of the mass and stiffness matrices:

$$[C] = a[M] + b[K] \quad (6.1)$$

where a is the mass proportional damping constant and b is the stiffness proportional damping constant. The selection of the lower and upper angular frequency ω_1 and ω_2 respectively is made in order the resulting damping curve to simulate an almost constant damping at the frequency range of interest. The frequency range of interest is defined based on the predominant frequencies of the soil deposit, f_1 and $f_2 = 5 \times f_1$ Hz (Kwok et al. 2007). This range includes the model's natural frequencies and the predominant frequencies of the input motions. Assuming constant frequency for both modes of vibration, the damping parameters are finally given by the following equations:

$$\alpha = 2 \times \xi \times \left(\frac{\omega_1 \times \omega_2}{\omega_1 + \omega_2} \right), \quad \beta = 2 \times \xi \times \left(\frac{1}{\omega_1 + \omega_2} \right) \quad (6.2)$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 are the natural (angular) frequencies of the modes of vibration.

Periodic boundary conditions are used to ensure that free-field conditions exist at the horizontal boundaries of the soil model. In particular, the displacement degrees of freedom for the nodes on either side of the soil model are tied together imposing the same translational displacements in x and z directions. This is achieved through the use of the "equalDOF" command in OpenSees. It is noted that the pore pressure degrees of freedom for these (corner) nodes are not linked using the "equalDOF" command. Each soil profile is excited at the base by a horizontal force time history which is proportional

to the known velocity time history of the ground motion (Joyner and Chen 1975; Lysmer 1978). The vertical component of ground motion is not considered. It is noted that due to the consideration of an elastic halfspace it was possible to directly apply the outcropping rock motion at the base of the soil model (Kwok et al. 2007).

It should also be noted that a script was developed during the implementation of this thesis to create the soil models in OpenSees. It has been set up in a manner such that only the definition of the geometry of the soil profile and groundwater table is needed and subsequently the nodes as well as the appropriate boundary conditions are generated automatically based on the input geometry information. The input file has also been set up such that different element sizes can be used within each soil layer. This script could be used for the quick formation of a two-dimensional soil profile of any geometry.

6.4.3.2 Soil constitutive model

A two-phase (solid-fluid) fully coupled (u-P) FE formulation, where the displacement of the soil skeleton (u) and the pore pressure (p) are computed simultaneously and interactively at each time step, is employed. The u-P formulation is capable of simulating permanent shear-strain accumulation in clean medium-dense cohesionless soils during liquefaction and dilation due to increased cyclic shear stiffness and strength. The soil constitutive model (Figure 6.6 and Figure 6.7) implemented in OpenSees is based on the framework of multi-yield-surface (nested-surface) plasticity (Iwan 1967; Prevost 1985), with modifications by Yang (2000), where p' is the effective confining pressure, τ is the octahedral shear stress, and γ is the octahedral shear strain.

Figure 6.6. Hyperbolic backbone curve for soil nonlinear shear stress-strain response and piecewise linear representation in multi-surface plasticity (Prevost 1985; Parra 1996 and Yang et al. 2003)

The hardening law (which describes changes in the size and shape of the yield surface as plastic deformation occurs), the yield function (which describes the limiting stress conditions for which elastic behaviour is observed) and the flow rule (which relates increments of plastic strain to increments of stress) constitute the major components of the plasticity model. During the application of gravity load, the material behaviour is linear elastic. In the subsequent dynamic loading phase, the stress-strain response is turned to elastic-plastic following the multi-surface plasticity concept.

Figure 6.7. Schematic of constitutive model response showing octahedral shear stress τ , effective confinement p' , and shear strain γ relationship (Yang et al. 2003)

There are two types of hardening, the isotropic hardening, which occurs when the yield surface changes size but maintains the same centre, and the kinematic hardening, which occurs when the yield surface moves around the stress space without any change in size. To generate soil hysteretic response under cyclic loading a purely deviatoric kinematic hardening rule (Prevost 1985) is employed. This kinematic rule dictates that all yield surfaces may translate in stress space within the failure envelope (Parra 1996; Yang 2000) and be consistent with the Masing unloading/reloading criteria (Masing

1926). Within the multi-surface plasticity framework, the yield surfaces define regions of constant plastic shear modulus in the stress space, which can be determined by using a piecewise linear approximation of a hyperbolic backbone curve. As illustrated in Figure 6.6 each linear segment represents the domain of a yield surface f_m with shear modulus H_m for $m=1,2,\dots,NYS$, where NYS denotes the total number of yield surfaces (Stewart et al. 2008). The outermost yield surface f_{NYS} , which corresponds to the peak shear strength T_{max} , represents the failure surface and corresponds to zero shear modulus $H_{NYS}=0$.

For the cohesionless soil layers, an elastic-plastic material for simulating the essential response characteristics of pressure sensitive soil materials under general loading conditions, namely "PressureDependMultiYield02" (PDMY02), is used in Opensees, where the yield function is assumed to follow the Drucker-Prager shape (Figure 6.8) and the yield surface is described in effective stress space as a function of friction angle and cohesion (as defined in the Mohr-Coulomb failure criteria). Plasticity is formulated based on the multi-surface concept, with a non-associative flow rule (Parra 1996) that handles the soil contractive/dilatative behaviour during shear loading to achieve appropriate interaction between shear and volumetric responses.

Figure 6.8. Conical Drucker-Prager multi-yield surfaces in principal stress space and deviatoric plane for sand (Prevost 1985; Parra 1996; Yang 2000)

For the cohesive soil layers, which undergo fast undrained loading during earthquakes, an elastic-plastic material in which plasticity exhibits only in the deviatoric stress-strain response, namely "PressureIndependMultiYield" (PIMY), is used. The volumetric stress-strain response is linear-elastic and is independent of the deviatoric response. This material is implemented to simulate monotonic or cyclic response of materials whose shear behaviour is insensitive to the confinement change. The yield function is assumed to follow the Von Mises shape (Figure 6.9) and the yield surface is a function solely of undrained shear strength. Plasticity is formulated based on the multi-

surface concept, with an associative flow rule in which the incremental plastic strain vector is normal to the yield surface.

Figure 6.9. Cylindrical Von Mises multi-yield surfaces for clay (Prevost 1985; Parra 1996; Yang 2000 and Stewart et al. 2008)

A series of material properties are required to capture the constitutive behaviour of each soil layer and the underlying elastic bedrock. The main soil properties are the mass density (

Table 6.1, Table 6.2 and Table 6.3), the shear wave velocity (Figure 6.2) and Poisson's ratio (taken equal to 0.35). From these, the shear and bulk moduli are computed. In particular, the shear modulus is calculated according to the following expression:

$$G = \rho \cdot V_S^2 \quad (6.3)$$

while the bulk modulus is calculated as:

$$B = 2G \cdot \left(\frac{1 + \nu}{3 \cdot (1 - 2 \cdot \nu)} \right) \quad (6.4)$$

Each soil layer is given a separate set of properties, selected based on a combination of recommended values from the constitutive model developer (Yang et al. 2008).

Table **6.1**, Table 6.2 and Table 6.3 summarize the parameters of the soil material properties adopted for soil profile A, B and C, respectively, while Table 6.4, Table 6.5 and Table 6.6 present the liquefaction parameters adopted for PDMY02 soil layers of soil profile A, B and C, respectively.

Table 6.1. Soil properties adopted for soil profile A

Soil layer	Model	Layer Thickness (m)	Mass density (ton/m ³)	G (kPa)	B (kPa)	Friction angle	Cohesion (kPa)	Peak shear strain (%)	Ref. press. (kPa)	Pressure depend. coeff.
18	PDMY02	1.0	1.835	1.54e ⁵	4.63e ⁵	39	-	0.1	100	0.5
17	PDMY02	1.0	2.013	1.16e ⁵	3.48e ⁵	35	-	0.1	100	0.5
16	PDMY02	2.0	1.666	8.36e ⁴	2.51e ⁵	32	-	0.1	100	0.5
15	PDMY02	1.0	1.666	7.42e ⁴	2.23e ⁵	32	-	0.1	100	0.5
14	PDMY02	1.0	1.666	6.53e ⁴	1.96e ⁵	32	-	0.1	100	0.5
13	PDMY02	3.0	1.666	2.44e ⁴	7.32e ⁴	32	-	0.1	100	0.5
12	PDMY02	2.0	2.013	2.66e ⁴	7.99e ⁴	33.5	-	0.1	100	0.5
11	PIMY	1.0	2.095	2.92e ⁴	8.75e ⁴	22.75	23	0.1	100	0.0
10	PIMY	2.0	2.095	4.97e ⁴	1.49e ⁵	22.75	23	0.1	100	0.0
9	PDMY02	6.0	2.120	1.59e ⁵	4.77e ⁵	35	-	0.1	100	0.5
8	PIMY	6.0	2.059	1.66e ⁵	4.97e ⁵	30	15	0.1	100	0.0
7	PDMY02	5.0	2.120	2.98e ⁵	8.94e ⁵	36.5	-	0.1	100	0.5
6	PDMY02	5.0	2.120	4.56e ⁵	1.37e ⁶	36.5	-	0.1	100	0.5
5	PIMY	6.0	2.020	6.29e ⁵	1.89e ⁶	25	30	0.1	100	0.0
4	PIMY	2.0	2.120	2.44e ⁵	7.31e ⁵	38	15	0.1	100	0.0
3	PIMY	6.0	2.112	1.52e ⁵	4.56e ⁵	25	30	0.1	100	0.0
2	PIMY	5.0	2.036	3.75e ⁵	1.12e ⁶	27	60	0.1	100	0.0
1	PIMY	5.0	2.162	6.14e ⁵	1.84e ⁶	10	85	0.1	100	0.0

Table 6.2. Soil properties adopted for soil profile B

Soil layer	Model	Layer Thickness (m)	Mass density (ton/m ³)	G (kPa)	B (kPa)	Friction angle	Cohesion (kPa)	Peak shear strain (%)	Ref. press. (kPa)	Pressure depend. coeff.
8	PDMY02	2.0	1.835	9.29e ⁴	2.79e ⁵	39	-	0.1	100	0.5
7	PDMY02	6.0	1.886	6.11e ⁴	1.83e ⁵	32	-	0.1	100	0.5
6	PDMY02	6.0	2.039	8.16e ⁴	2.45e ⁵	33.5	-	0.1	100	0.5
5	PIMY	6.0	2.039	1.27e ⁵	3.82e ⁵	25	23	0.1	100	0.0
4	PIMY	8.0	2.039	2.50e ⁵	7.49e ⁵	25	23	0.1	100	0.0
3	PIMY	8.0	2.141	3.43e ⁵	1.03e ⁶	25	25	0.1	100	0.0
2	PIMY	12.0	2.141	3.43e ⁵	1.03e ⁶	25	40	0.1	100	0.0
1	PIMY	2.0	2.141	5.35e ⁵	1.61e ⁶	20	50	0.1	100	0.0

Table 6.3. Soil properties adopted for soil profile C

Soil layer	Model	Layer Thickness (m)	Mass density (ton/m ³)	G (kPa)	B (kPa)	Friction angle	Cohesion (kPa)	Peak shear strain (%)	Ref. press. (kPa)	Pressure depend. coeff.
6	PDMY02	2.0	1.835	9.29e ⁴	2.79e ⁵	39	-	0.1	100	0.5
5	PDMY02	2.0	2.039	1.03e ⁵	3.10e ⁵	35	-	0.1	100	0.5
4	PDMY02	10.0	1.886	7.54e ⁴	2.26e ⁵	32	-	0.1	100	0.5
3	PDMY02	6.0	2.141	1.34e ⁵	4.01e ⁵	33.5	-	0.1	100	0.5
2	PIMY	10.0	2.141	1.93e ⁵	5.78e ⁵	25	25	0.1	100	0.0
1	PIMY	16.0	2.141	5.35e ⁵	1.61e ⁶	25	40	0.1	100	0.0

Table 6.4. Liquefaction parameters adopted for PDMY02 soil layers of soil profile A

Soil layer	Phase transformation angle (PTAng)	Contraction and dilation model parameters				number of yield surfaces	Initial void ratio e	Critical-state parameters		
		c1	c3	d1	d3			cs1	cs2	cs3
18	26	0.013	0	0.3	0	20	0.77	0.9	0.02	0.7
17	26	0.028	0.05	0.1	0.05	20	0.65	0.9	0.02	0.7
16	26	0.067	0.23	0.06	0.27	20	0.85	0.9	0.02	0.7
15	26	0.067	0.23	0.06	0.27	20	0.85	0.9	0.02	0.7
14	26	0.067	0.23	0.06	0.27	20	0.85	0.9	0.02	0.7
13	26	0.067	0.23	0.06	0.27	20	0.85	0.9	0.02	0.7
12	26	0.045	0.15	0.06	0.15	20	0.65	0.9	0.02	0.7
9	26	0.028	0.05	0.1	0.05	20	0.55	0.9	0.02	0.7
7	26	0.013	0	0.3	0	20	0.70	0.9	0.02	0.7
6	26	0.013	0	0.3	0	20	0.70	0.9	0.02	0.7

Table 6.5. Liquefaction parameters adopted for PDMY02 soil layers of soil profile B

Soil layer	Phase transformation angle (PTAng)	Contraction and dilation model parameters				number of yield surfaces	Initial void ratio e	Critical-state parameters		
		c1	c3	d1	d3			cs1	cs2	cs3
8	PDMY02	0.013	0	0.3	0	20	0.77	0.9	0.02	0.7
7	PDMY02	0.067	0.23	0.06	0.27	20	0.70	0.9	0.02	0.7
6	PDMY02	0.045	0.15	0.06	0.15	20	0.65	0.9	0.02	0.7

Table 6.6. Liquefaction parameters adopted for PDMY02 soil layers of soil profile C

Soil layer	Phase transformation angle (PTAng)	Contraction and dilation model parameters				number of yield surfaces	Initial void ratio e	Critical-state parameters		
		c1	c3	d1	d3			cs1	cs2	cs3
6	PDMY02	0.013	0	0.3	0	20	0.75	0.9	0.02	0.7
5	PDMY02	0.028	0.05	0.1	0.05	20	0.65	0.9	0.02	0.7
4	PDMY02	0.067	0.23	0.06	0.27	20	0.70	0.9	0.02	0.7
3	PDMY02	0.045	0.15	0.06	0.15	20	0.60	0.9	0.02	0.7

Moreover, included with the material definitions for each soil layer, some additional parameters are used for the definition of the nine-node quadrilateral elements. These include the element thickness, the horizontal and vertical body forces on the element, the undrained bulk modulus, and the horizontal and vertical permeability coefficients. In this model, a unit thickness is used for all soil layers, as two-dimensional analyses are conducted. Regarding the body forces, they are not defined as the unit weight of the soil in each layer (as should be done in the case that four node quad elements are used), instead they are set to have magnitudes equal to the components of gravity only. For the analysis of level ground using SI units, the vertical body force is -9.81 and the horizontal body force is zero. For the second set of analysis, considering slope with a 5% grade, the infinite slope conditions are modelled by using horizontal and vertical gravity components computed from the angle of the sloping ground as the body forces acting on the elements. The undrained bulk modulus is defined as the bulk modulus of the fluid ($2.2e^6$ kPa for water) divided by the porosity of the soil layer, while for the layer above the groundwater table, a small value ($5e^{-6}$ kPa) is used. In addition, as the fluid is water, the fluid mass density for each layer is set to 1.0 Mg/m^3 .

Regarding the soil permeability coefficients, they play a key role in the process of numerical simulation of the liquefaction phenomenon, as liquefaction causes a considerable increase in soil permeability, due to the creation of easier paths for water flow. In this model, the permeabilities for all of the soil elements are initially set to 1.0 m/s to ensure that hydrostatic conditions exist after the application of gravity in the model. If the permeability of a particular soil layer is too low, it may take many gravity analysis steps in order to reach hydrostatic pressure conditions. Prior to the application of the ground motion, the permeabilities of each soil layer are updated, using the "updateParameter" command in OpenSees, to their respective assigned values so pore pressure generation during the horizontal excitation is captured appropriately. Parameter tags are defined for each permeability parameter (horizontal and vertical) for each soil element, which are subsequently used to update the corresponding parameters. It should

be noted that the input file developed during the implementation of this thesis to create the soil models in OpenSees has also been set up to automatically generate the parameter tags and update the permeability parameters.

6.4.4 Gravity and dynamic loading

The analysis is performed into two consequent steps, a gravity application step followed by a dynamic excitation step. Gravity application to the model ensures that the model has been generated properly and that the distributions of pore pressure and effective stresses in the model are appropriate for the site conditions prior to the application of a ground motion. Separate recorders are set up to distinct the gravity analysis information from any post-gravity results. Nodal displacements, accelerations, and pore pressures are recorded along with the elemental stresses and strains at the four corner and the one interior in the centre of the nine Gauss points.

The gravity analysis is conducted in two parts to ensure that hydrostatic pore pressure conditions are achieved. In the first part, the soil elements are considered to be linear elastic. This is accomplished by setting the material stage equal to zero for each material object using the `"updateMaterialStage"` command in OpenSees. In the second part of the gravity analysis elastoplastic constitutive behaviour of the soil elements is considered by updating the material stage to one for each material object. The elastic portion of the gravity analysis is run as a transient analysis with very large time steps. In particular, gravity is applied for 10 steps with a time step of 500. Then, the plastic portion of the gravity analysis is run using smaller time steps to achieve convergence.

Subsequently, the seismic excitation is applied as a force time history to the base of the soil model, at the node which shares equal degrees-of-freedom with the Lysmer-Kuhlemeyer (1969) dashpot, using the method of Joyner and Chen (1975). This force time history is obtained by multiplying the velocity time history of the recorded ground motion by the mass density and shear wave velocity of the underlying bedrock layer including also the area of the base of the soil model (dashpot coefficient). This technique, as noted previously, considers the finite rigidity of the underlying bedrock layer by allowing energy to be radiated back into the underlying material. The force time history is applied to the model as a `"Path TimeSeries"` object using a `"Plain load pattern"` object in OpenSees. The actual force applied to the node in each time step is the product of the load factor indicated in the pattern object, the additional load factor included in the timeSeries object, and the value found in the velocity time history of the recorded ground motion at that time step. For improved success in completing the analysis in a timely manner, a convergence loop is also included in the input file. In the case that

convergence is not reached, the time step is reduced in half and the analysis continues. The loop is set such that this process can occur twice before the analysis is deemed over.

For the implementation of the dynamic analysis, the penalty constraints is used as it works better than the transformation constraints. In addition, the Krylov-Newton algorithm is used, as the dynamic analysis seemed to run more smoothly opposed to when using the standard Newton algorithm. The dynamic analysis is again run as a transient analysis, conducted with the Newmark integrator using the gamma and beta coefficients defined equal to 0.5 and 0.25, respectively, to ensure there is no numerical damping in the analysis.

6.5 Seismic input motion

A representative set of fifteen real ground motion records (Table 6.7) is selected from the European Strong-Motion Database (<http://www.isesd.hi.is/>) in order to perform nonlinear incremental dynamic analysis and provide the necessary response statistics for the fragility analysis. They are all referring to rock type or stiff soils (ground types A and B according to EC8) with moment magnitude (M_w) and epicentral distance (R) that range between $5.5 < M_w < 6.5$ and $0.0 < R < 45.0 \text{ km}$ respectively. The primary selection criterion is the average acceleration spectra of the set to be of minimal "epsilon" (Baker and Cornell 2005) at the period range of $0.00 < T < 2.00 \text{ sec}$ with respect to the corresponding 5% damped median plus 0.5 standard deviations spectrum defined based on the ground motion prediction equation (GMPE) proposed by Akkar and Bommer (2010). Epsilon (defined as a measure of the difference between the spectral acceleration of a record and the mean of a GMPE at the given period) is computed by subtracting the mean predicted logarithmic spectral acceleration that corresponds to the fundamental structural period $\ln S_a(T_1)$ from the record's $\ln S_a(T_1)$ and dividing it by the logarithmic standard deviation, as estimated by the GMPE (Baker and Cornell 2005). It is also noted that epsilon is defined with respect to the unscaled record and do not change in value when the record is scaled, as it is an indicator of the "shape" of the response spectrum and the shape of the spectrum does not change with scaling (Baker and Cornell 2005). So as to achieve minimal "epsilon", the set mean spectrum is constrained to match the mean S_a prediction with a tolerance dependent on corresponding variance of S_a . The optimization procedure is performed using REXEL software (Iervolino et al. 2010), a freely available software (http://www.reluis.it/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=118&Itemid=105&lang=en), that allows obtaining combinations of accelerograms, which on average are compatible to the reference spectrum, either user-defined or automatically generated according to EC8 (CEN 2004a) or the Italian seismic code (NTC 2008).

Table 6.7. List of earthquake records used for the dynamic analyses

Earthquake Name	Date	M_w	Fault Mechanism	Epicentral Distance [km]	PGA [m/s^2]	EC8 Site class	Waveform ID
<i>Umbria Marche (aftershock)</i>	10/6/1997	5.5	normal	5	1.838	A	651
<i>Valnerina</i>	9/19/1979	5.8	normal	5	1.510	A	242
<i>SE of Tirana</i>	1/9/1988	5.9	thrust	7	4.037	A	3802
<i>Lazio Abruzzo (aftershock)</i>	5/11/1984	5.5	normal	15	1.411	A	990
<i>Valnerina</i>	9/19/1979	5.8	normal	5	2.012	A	242
<i>Kozani</i>	5/13/1995	6.5	normal	17	2.039	A	6115
<i>Friuli (aftershock)</i>	9/15/1976	6	thrust	12	1.339	A	149
<i>Umbria Marche</i>	9/26/1997	5.7	normal	23	1.645	A	763
<i>Friuli (aftershock)</i>	9/15/1976	6	thrust	14	2.586	B	134
<i>Patras</i>	7/14/1993	5.6	strike slip	9	3.337	B	1932
<i>Kalamata</i>	9/13/1986	5.9	normal	11	2.670	B	414
<i>Umbria Marche 2</i>	9/26/1997	6	normal	11	5.138	B	594
<i>Montenegro (aftershock)</i>	5/24/1979	6.2	thrust	17	1.708	B	229
<i>Kefallinia island</i>	1/23/1992	5.6	thrust	14	2.223	B	6040
<i>Ano Liosia</i>	9/7/1999	6	normal	14	2.159	B	1714

The selected records cover a wide range of seismic input motions in terms of amplitude, frequency content and significant duration. Figure 6.10 depicts the mean elastic response spectrum of the records in comparison with the corresponding median plus 0.5 standard deviations Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum. As shown in the figure, a good match between the two spectra is achieved.

Figure 6.10. Average elastic response spectrum of the input motions in comparison with the corresponding median plus 0.5 standard deviations Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum

6.6 Incremental dynamic analysis (IDA)

6.6.1 Performing IDA

The incremental dynamic analysis (IDA) is used to estimate more thoroughly the seismic performance and finally to assess the seismic vulnerability of these SSI systems considering liquefaction under seismic loads. IDA is a parametric analysis method, that has recently emerged in several different forms, which involves performing a series of nonlinear dynamic analyses under a multiply scaled suite of ground motion records, whose intensities should be ideally selected to cover the entire range of response, from elasticity to global dynamic instability (Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2002). Subsequently, IDA curves, which provide a relationship between a damage measure quantity (i.e. EDP) and a scalable intensity measure (IM) of the applied scaled accelerograms, are generated by interpolating the resulting EDP-IM discrete points. To express the scaling level an initial, temporary choice of IM is needed. Scaling can be re-expressed in any other scalable IM (Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2002) after the runs are performed. Within the framework of this thesis, the IM is initially described by the peak ground acceleration (PGA) on rock outcropping conditions. This IM is considered more appropriate due to its simplicity.

In addition, it is widely recognised that scaling procedure and the gained scaling factors can cause some bias in nonlinear structural response that increases with the degree of scaling (Luco and Bazzurro 2007). However, due to the lack of recorded ground motions covering a wide range of intensities, scaling real records was preferred than synthetic ground motions. Hence, IDA for the nine SSI models (combinations of the three buildings and the three soil profiles) is conducted by applying the 15 progressively scaled records, considering a first elastic run at 0.05g and an initial step of 0.1g, increased by a constant step of 0.1g, up to 1.0g which is considered an extreme value of PGA to take place at bedrock. According to Luco and Bazzurro (2007), in the engineering seismology community, acceptable ground motion scaling limits vary widely from one to ten or more. From Table 6.7 it is obvious that the scaling factors used in IDA analysis are within these values. In addition, a second set of IDA for the nine SSI models is performed considering slope with a 5% grade to further examine the contribution of liquefaction-induced lateral spreading. A sequence of at least twelve runs is performed on each record, leading to a total of 3240 dynamic analyses. It should be noted that the main shortcoming of this approach is the high computational cost that becomes more significant for highly non-linear problems. The damage measure (DM) is expressed in terms of maximum inter-story drift (maxISD), which is known to relate well to dynamic instability and structural damage of RC frame buildings.

6.6.2 Indicative free-field (FF) site response analysis results

In this section, indicative results of the IDA performed are presented in order to highlight important observations for the response of the soil. Firstly, it is noted that layers of potential liquefaction are identified by the loss of effective confining stress (equal to zero) which is also verified by the corresponding stress-strain loops. A general useful observation is that liquefaction is not observed when the SSI model is subjected to any record scaled to a PGA level equal to 0.05g. Liquefaction is usually apparent when the SSI model is subjected to a PGA_{rock} level equal to or higher than 0.1g. Indicatively, Figure 6.11 (top) illustrates the computed variation of effective confinement with depth and stress-strain hysteretic loops at specific depth (i.e. at 7.0m below surface) for one of the above input motions for soil profile B at free-field, while Figure 6.11 (bottom) depicts the computed variation of effective confinement with depth and stress-strain hysteretic loops at 7.0m below surface for soil profile B at free-field for the same input motion scaled to a PGA equal to 0.05g.

Figure 6.11. Variation of the effective confinement with depth and stress-strain hysteretic loops at 7.0m depth at soil profile B free-field for the ID 229 input motion (top) and for the ID 229 input motion scaled to a PGA equal to 0.05g (bottom)

Generally, it is confirmed that the liquefaction model employed in OpenSees is able to accommodate yielding and build-up of excess pore pressure which may result in loss of effective confining stress and shear strength, degradation of shear stiffness and permanent ground deformations due to lateral spreading at high strain levels. Indicatively, in order to identify the depth and thickness of the zones where liquefaction takes place as well as to better understand the parameters that influence them, for soil profile C (with fundamental period, T_o , equal to 0.64 sec), four of the earthquake records presented in section 6.5, namely Montenegro (aftershock), Kefallinia island, Ano Liosia and Kalamata (with waveform IDs 229, 6040, 1714, and 414 respectively) with mean periods, T_m , equal to 0.26sec, 0.30sec, 0.43sec and 0.53sec respectively, are used for comparisons. Firstly, it is interesting to compare the variation of the effective confinement with depth (Figure 6.12) as well as the induced excess pore pressure excess distribution with depth at the end of the seismic analyses for different input acceleration levels, i.e. PGA_{rock} (Figure 6.13).

Figure 6.12. Variation of the effective confinement with depth at soil profile C free-field for the four seismic input motions scaled to different PGA_{rock} values

According to Figure 6.11 and Figure 6.12, it is observed that the liquefaction phenomena occurs for PGA_{rock} values equal to or higher than 0.1 g. Moreover, it is seen that as the intensity of the seismic input motion (PGA_{rock}) increases, liquefaction apparition extents in deeper layers. These conclusions agree with those found by Koutsourelakis et al. (2002), Popescu (2002) and Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi (2008).

Figure 6.13. Variation of the excess pore pressure with depth at soil profile C free-field for the four seismic input motions scaled to different PGA_{rock} values

As far as it concerns the induced maximum shear strains in the soil profile, Figure 6.14 depicts the evolution of maximum cyclic shear strain with depth at soil profile C free-field for the four seismic input motions scaled to different PGA_{rock} values. It is noted that the onset of liquefaction coincides with the apparition of large shear strain levels, which correspond to higher levels of soil stiffness degradation, i.e. $G/G_{max} \approx 0$ (G - γ - D curves). As far as it concerns the peak ground acceleration obtained at the free-field surface, a modification of the frequency content in the seismic ground motion at surface relative to bedrock due to soil liquefaction is also observed. Indicatively, Figure 6.15 shows a comparison between bedrock and free-field surface normalised acceleration response spectra for Kefallinia island seismic ground motion at soil profile C. A reduction

of short period spectral accelerations can be seen, probably due to the increase of pore pressure, while for periods larger than about 0.40s, free-field surface spectral accelerations are greater than the bedrock accelerations. This difference is more obvious when the bedrock acceleration increases and soil liquefaction occurs, as the soil softening is higher. Similar observations have also been reported by Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi (2008).

Figure 6.14. Evolution of maximum cyclic shear strain with depth at soil profile C free-field for the four seismic input motions scaled to different PGA_{rock} values

Figure 6.15. Comparison between bedrock and surface normalised acceleration response spectra for Kefallinia island seismic ground motion

Moreover, the modification of characteristics of seismic ground motion (i.e. acceleration time history and frequency content) due to apparition of soil liquefaction is studied. Figure 6.16 and Figure 6.17 illustrate the variation of $PGA_{surf,ff}$ as a function of the PGA_{rock} at level ground and slope conditions respectively. It is observed that an amplification of $PGA_{surf,ff}$ relative to PGA_{rock} appears for a PGA_{rock} value less than 0.2g, while higher PGA_{rock} values result in attenuation of the seismic motion observed at the free-field ground surface and subsequently reduction of the $PGA_{surf,ff}$ principally due to the nonlinear behaviour of the soil profile introduced by the apparition of soil liquefaction. This trend is in accordance with the observations of the study conducted from [Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi \(2008\)](#). In addition, it is observed that this trend also holds true considering slope conditions (Figure 6.17), as the $PGA_{surf,ff}$ - PGA_{rock} relationship for level ground conditions is similar to that for slope conditions.

Figure 6.16. Relationship between $PGA_{surf,ff}$ at surface and PGA_{rock} at bedrock obtained from all the IDA analyses at level ground conditions

Figure 6.17. Relationship between $PGA_{surf,ff}$ at surface and PGA_{rock} at bedrock obtained from all the IDA analyses at slope conditions

Furthermore, it was deemed appropriate to also present the variation of $PGV_{surf,ff}$ as a function of the PGV_{rock} at level ground and slope conditions in Figure 6.18 and Figure 6.19 respectively. An almost linear positive correlation is observed for a PGV_{rock} value less than 15.0cm/sec, while higher PGV_{rock} values result either in attenuation or amplification of the $PGV_{surf,ff}$ depending on the record. In general, it is also observed that PGV_{rock} values higher than almost 40.0cm/sec principally result in attenuation of the $PGV_{surf,ff}$ due to the nonlinear behaviour of the soil profile introduced by soil liquefaction as well as failure of the soil-structure system. This trend also holds true considering slope conditions (Figure 6.19).

Figure 6.18. Relationship between $PGV_{surf,ff}$ at surface and PGV_{rock} at bedrock obtained from all the IDA analyses at level ground conditions

Figure 6.19. Relationship between $PGV_{surf,ff}$ at surface and PGV_{rock} at bedrock obtained from all the IDA analyses at slope conditions

It should be noted that this subsection with the important observations that are also identified in the literature is a declarative way of validating the liquefiable soil response and subsequently the SSI models considering liquefaction potential used in the framework of this thesis in order to propose coupled fragility curves and surfaces for the vulnerability assessment of typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction taking into account SSI.

6.6.3 IDA results

6.6.3.1 Level ground conditions

By interpolating the derived pairs of PGA_{rock} and $maxISD$ for each individual record 15 continuous IDA curves for each SSI model are derived, as shown in Figure 6.20, Figure 6.21 and Figure 6.22. As an IDA is record and structural model specific, when a model is subjected to different ground motions, it will often produce quite dissimilar responses that are difficult to be predicted a priori (Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2002). Indeed, the derived IDA curves display a wide range of behaviour, showing large record-to-record variability, as becomes obvious in Figure 6.20, Figure 6.21 and Figure 6.22.

Therefore, it is essential to summarize such data and quantify the randomness introduced by the records. There are several methods to summarize the IDA curves, but the cross-sectional fractiles are arguably the most flexible and robust with respect to the infinite DMs introduced by the flatlines (Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2002).

Firstly, stripes of DM-values at arbitrary levels of the IM are generated; each stripe contains fifteen DM-values, one for each record, that may be finite or even infinite when a record has already reached its flatline at a lower IM-level. By summarizing the DM-values for each stripe into their 16%, 50%, and 84% percentiles, fractile values of DM given IM are estimated that are in turn interpolated for each fractile to generate the 16%, 50%, and 84% fractile IDA curves.

Figures 6.18 to 6.20 present except from the graphs of the derived IDA curves for each record in terms of PGA at rock and the corresponding summarised across all records IDA curves at 16, 50 and 84% fractiles for the different examined SSI models.

Figure 6.20. IDA curves for the two-storey RC frame building resting on soil profiles A, B and C

Figure 6.21. IDA curves for the four-storey RC frame building resting on soil profiles A, B and C

Figure 6.22. IDA curves for the nine-storey RC frame building resting on soil profiles A, B and C

As it can be seen, in many cases the IDA curves of individual time-histories are observed to display a twisting pattern that corresponds to successive segments of “softening” and “hardening”, regions where the local slope or stiffness decreases and increases respectively with higher IM. More specifically, the excessive “hardening” leads a system that showed high response at a given intensity level, to exhibit the same or even lower response when subjected to higher seismic intensities. This could be attributed to the fact that as the seismic input motion is scaled up, the structure may yield in an early cycle thus altering its properties and becoming less responsive in later stronger cycles. In engineering terms this means that the structure may experience acceleration or deceleration of the EDP accumulation rate, thus locally pulling the IDA curve to relatively lower EDPs resulting to a non-monotonic function of the IM (Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2002).

It should also be noted that analyses using records scaled to a PGA_{rock} value higher than 1.0g were not conducted, as a PGA_{rock} value equal to 1.0g is considered an extreme value of PGA to take place at bedrock. In addition, considering that PGA_{rock} values higher than 0.2g are found to result in attenuation of the seismic ground motion at surface and thus reduction of the PGA_{surf} due to the apparition of soil liquefaction, there were records that even scaled to a PGA_{rock} value equal to 1.0g did not lead to structure failure. Therefore, the derived IDA curves did not become flat up to the maximum PGA scaling of 1.0g that is applied on the bedrock and subsequently most of the 16% and 50% fractile IDA curves did not reach their flatline.

6.6.3.2 Slope conditions (5% grade)

To better examine the contribution of liquefaction-induced lateral spreading, a second set of IDA for the nine SSI models is performed considering slope with a 5% grade. By interpolating the derived pairs of PGA_{rock} and maxISD for each individual record, 15 continuous IDA curves for each SSI model are again derived, as shown in Figure 6.23, Figure 6.24 and Figure 6.25.

It is seen that in this case of slope conditions most of the IDA curves reach their flatline, as lateral spreading occurs. It is noted that lateral spreading involves large lateral ground movement as well as substantial differential displacements in the direction of spreading, resulting in large extensional deformation and ground fissuring (Cubrinovski et al. 2012) and subsequently more structural damages.

Figure 6.23. IDA curves for the two-storey RC frame building resting on soil profiles A, B and C considering slope with grade equal to 5%

Figure 6.24. IDA curves for the four-storey RC frame building resting on soil profiles A, B and C considering slope with grade equal to 5%

Figure 6.25. IDA curves for the nine-storey RC frame building resting on soil profiles A, B and C considering slope with grade equal to 5%

6.7 Development of predictive relationships between differential displacements and PGD using IDA results

In this section, predictive relationships between the maximum differential permanent ground displacements (settlement or vector) and the maximum permanent ground displacements (PGD) vector at surface bellow buildings with shallow flexible foundations due to ground shaking and liquefaction are established through regression analysis.

More specifically, the response of building footings on the ground, in terms of differential permanent displacements (settlement or vector) among the building footings and PGD vector of each building footing, is obtained from the nonlinear IDA conducted. Subsequently, the maximum from these differential displacements and PGD vector values are selected. The logarithms of the obtained maximum differential displacement (settlement or vector) and maximum PGD vector data pairs are used for the regression analysis. In general, it is observed that the ground conditions affect the relationship between differential displacements and PGD vector. Thus, different relationships are established for buildings at level ground and at slope conditions.

In particular, a polynomial regression fit of the logarithms of the maximum differential displacement vector - maximum PGD vector and maximum differential settlement - maximum PGD vector data pairs which minimizes the regression residuals is adopted for buildings with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at level ground conditions, as shown in Figure 6.26 and Figure 6.27 respectively. On the other hand, for buildings with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at slope conditions, a linear regression fit of the logarithms of the maximum differential displacement vector - maximum PGD vector and maximum differential settlement - maximum PGD vector data pairs which minimizes the regression residuals is found to better predict their relationship, as presented in Figure 6.28 and Figure 6.29 respectively.

6.7.1 Level ground conditions

Figure 6.26. Relationship between the maximum differential displacement vector and maximum PGD vector (in m) for buildings with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at level ground conditions

Figure 6.27. Relationship between the maximum differential settlement and maximum PGD vector (in m) for buildings with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at level ground conditions

6.7.2 Slope conditions (5% grade)

Figure 6.28. Relationship between the maximum differential displacement vector and maximum PGD vector (in m) for buildings with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at slope conditions

Figure 6.29. Relationship between the maximum differential settlement and maximum PGD vector (in m) for buildings with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at slope conditions

6.8 Definition of damage limit states

The selection of well-defined and realistic damage states is a key issue in the fragility assessment, since these values have a direct effect on the evaluation of the fragility curve/surface parameters. Usually, the damage states are defined on the IDA curves derived for the fixed-base building subjected to ground shaking, with the complete/collapse damage state placed at a point where the IDA curve is leaning towards the flatline, but at low enough values of maxISD so that the structural model remains trustworthy (Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2004). It is noted that the above presented IDA curves derived for the SSI systems cannot be used for this reason as they do not capture absolutely the structural damage; especially the high-rise buildings, which even they are susceptible to liquefaction, their structural system may not sustain any damage, but basically sink or tilting.

Petridis and Ptilakis (2018), who studied the same buildings at fixed-base conditions, reported that the limit states in terms of maxISD proposed by Ghobarah (2004) for nonductile RC MRFs are appropriate for the two-storey and four-storey low-code RC frame buildings (based on the derived 50th percentile IDA curves for the fixed-base models), while they are too conservative for the nine-storey RC frame building which reaches the flatline at higher maxISD values. Moreover, Ptilakis et al. (2014d), who also studied extensively the four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings at fixed-base conditions, proposed for collapse damage state a maxISD value equal to 0.013 and 0.0225 respectively.

Therefore, taking into consideration the above, for the purpose of the present study four limit states are defined in terms of maxISD, representing the exceedance of slight, moderate, extensive and complete damage of the RC frame buildings. The limit state values finally adopted for the low-code RC frame buildings are presented in Table 6.8, while the qualitative description of each damage state is given in Table 6.9.

Table 6.8. Limit state values in terms of maxISD adopted for the various height nonductile RC frame buildings

Limit states	Nonductile RC MRF		
	Low-rise	Mid-rise	High-rise
Limit state 1	0.002	0.002	0.002
Limit state 2	0.005	0.005	0.005
Limit state 3	0.008	0.008	0.010
Limit state 4	0.010	0.013	0.0225

Table 6.9. Structural damage state description for RC MRF buildings (NIBS 2004)

Limit state	Structural damage	Description
LS1	Slight	Flexural or shear type hairline cracks in some beams and columns near joints or within joints
LS2	Moderate	Most beams and columns exhibit hairline cracks. In ductile frames some of the frame elements have reached yield capacity indicated by larger flexural cracks and some concrete spalling. Nonductile frames may exhibit larger shear cracks and spalling
LS3	Extensive	Some of the frame elements have reached their ultimate capacity indicated in ductile frames by large flexural cracks, spalled concrete and buckled main reinforcement; nonductile frame elements may have suffered shear failures or bond failures at reinforcement splices, or broken ties or buckled main reinforcement in columns which may result in partial collapse.
LS4	Complete	Structure is collapsed or in imminent danger of collapse due to brittle failure of nonductile frame elements or loss of frame stability.

6.9 Fragility assessment

Currently, seismic risk is usually evaluated using methods based on fragility curves representing the ground motion by a single IM parameter, e.g. PGA, in order to relate the level of ground shaking to the expected structural damage. Aleatory and epistemic uncertainties are introduced, due to the fact that the effect of an earthquake on the response of the structure cannot fully be represented, especially when liquefaction phenomenon is also involved. Furthermore, it is shown that an increase from one to two ground motion IMs leads to a significant reduction in the scatter in the fragility analysis, allowing the uncertainty related to the effect of the second ground-motion IM to be accounted for within seismic risk assessment of buildings (Seyedi et al. 2010; Gehl et al. 2013). For this reason, except for conventional fragility curves, it was deemed appropriate to attempt the development of fragility functions, which are a function of more than one IM (fragility surfaces), for use within seismic risk evaluation of buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction. The investigation of alternative IMs is facilitated by defining their efficiency and sufficiency, as already mentioned in section 3.4.2.2. The efficiency and sufficiency of an IM are both criteria that can be quantified via regression analysis with DM results from nonlinear dynamic analysis of a structure (Luco and Cornell 2007). It is noted that herein only the efficiency criterion has been considered for the selection of the IMs that better correlate with structural damage.

6.9.1 Development of conventional fragility curves

A conventional seismic fragility curve represents a graphical relationship of the probability of exceeding a predefined level of damage under a seismic excitation of a given intensity. Shinozuka et al. (2000) have proven the lognormality of fragility curves

and thus a log-normal distribution of IM conditional on a given level of EDP can be fitted to the numerical data (Baker 2007). Hence, the results of the nonlinear IDA (PGA_{rock}-maxISD and PGV_{rock}-maxISD pairs) are used to derive the fragility curves expressed as two-parameter lognormal distribution functions according to equation 6.5:

$$P[DS_i/IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM) - \ln(\overline{IM}_i)}{\beta}\right) \quad (6.5)$$

where, Φ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function, IM is the intensity measure of the earthquake expressed both in terms of rock outcropping peak ground acceleration PGA_{rock} (in units of g) or peak ground velocity PGV_{rock} (in units of cm/s), \overline{IM}_i and β are the median values of PGA_{rock} (in units of g) or PGV_{rock} (in units of cm/s) at which the building reaches each damage limit state, i , and log-standard deviations respectively of the building fragilities for each damage state i and DS _{i} is the damage state. Thus, for the development of the seismic fragility curves according to Equation 6.5, two parameters, namely \overline{IM} and β , need to be defined. The median values of PGA_{rock} and PGV_{rock} corresponding to the prescribed damage limit states are determined based on a regression analysis of the nonlinear IDA results (PGA_{rock}-maxISD and PGV_{rock}-maxISD pairs) for each structural model. In particular, a linear regression fit of the logarithms of the PGA_{rock}-maxISD and PGV_{rock}-maxISD data pairs which minimizes the regression residuals is adopted in all analysis cases. Indicatively, Figure 6.30 and Figure 6.31 illustrate example plots (in log-log scale) of damage evolution in terms of maxISD as a function of PGV_{rock} (in m/sec) for the two-storey and nine-storey RC frame building respectively at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction. The corresponding limit values of maxISD defined for each damage state are also shown.

Figure 6.30. PGV_{rock} (in m/s) – maxISD relationship for the two-storey RC frame building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.31. PGV_{rock} (in m/s) – $maxISD$ relationship for the nine-storey RC frame building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

The various uncertainties are taken into account through the log-standard deviation parameter β , which describes the total dispersion related to each fragility curve and is defined according to Section 5.5.2 of Chapter 5 (equation 5.2). In the following subsections the derived sets of fragility curves in terms of the single IM parameter PGA_{rock} or PGV_{rock} for the considered RC frame building typologies subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction for the different ground conditions are presented.

6.9.1.1 Level ground conditions

When considering level ground conditions, the computed sets of fragility curves for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction along with their lognormally distributed fragility parameters (median m and log-standard deviation β) in terms of PGA_{rock} and PGV_{rock} are depicted in Figure 6.32 and Figure 6.33 respectively.

As it can be seen, for the studied typical low-code RC frame buildings the total height of the building may considerably influence its vulnerability to the earthquake-induced ground shaking and liquefaction. In particular, it is seen that the low-rise building suffers more structural damages compared to the mid- and high-rise ones. This may be attributed to the fact that as the height of the building increases, the building tends to behave as a rigid body and thus, even susceptible to liquefaction, its structural system may not sustain any damage, but only sink or tilting. This trend is also due to the increased confinement (induced by weight increase) and subsequent increase in resistance against strength loss, which reduces slightly the contribution of shear strains under the building foundation. It is noted that at many liquefied sites after the 1999 Adapazari earthquake, larger settlements and tilting were observed for taller and heavier

buildings (Borozan et al 2017). It was also noticed that deformations were generally larger for buildings with higher aspect ratio (height over width).

Moreover, the fact that the low-rise buildings are more vulnerable compared to the mid- and high-rise ones may also be due to that no large differential displacements appear to the foundation level of the building and that the major influence on the building performance is attributed to the ground motion characteristics, also supported by Millen et al (2018). It is noted that the low-rise MRF RC frame buildings are more vulnerable to ground shaking than high-rise ones (Kappos et al. 2003). This is also in accordance with field observations; e.g. in the 1990 Luzon (Philippines) Earthquakes most of the damaged buildings on liquefied sites were two to four stories and shallow-founded (Tokimatsu et al. 1994). To further enhance the above statements, it is also noted that Gómez-Martínez et al. (2018) also reported that the relevance of differential settlements in seismic situation appears to be minor.

Additionally, another important observation is that the high-rise building does not sustain extensive and complete structural damages (even if they are subjected to records with a PGA_{rock} value equal to 1.0g). As it can be seen in Figure 6.31 for the nine-storey RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, the corresponding limit values of maxISD defined for extensive and complete damage state are not reached and thus fragility curves for these limit states are not proposed. This is in accordance with the observations of Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi (2008).

More specifically, they reported that when liquefaction phenomena are present in the soil foundation, the structural damage in structures with significant SSI effects may be reduced due to the local effects, while the structure can be considered as a rigid block and subsequently moves without significant internal deformation, and differential movements. This observation in addition to the study by Karapetrou et al. (2015), who reported that the effect of SSI is observed to be significant for the structural behaviour of typical high-rise RC frame buildings designed according to low seismic code provisions, enhance the reliability of the above observation. It is noted that Stewart et al. (1999) also claimed that especially in the case of soft soil formations and high-rise structures, SSI effects are generally more pronounced. On the other hand, for structures without SSI, Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi (2008) reported that the response of the structure is principally in flexion mode, thus the structure can present structural damage (i.e. damage in the structural elements due to the large induced deformations) related to the liquefaction phenomena.

Figure 6.32. Fragility curves in terms of PGA at bedrock for the different RC frame building typologies at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.33. Fragility curves in terms of PGV at bedrock for the different RC frame building typologies at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

6.9.1.2 Slope conditions (5% grade)

For slope conditions with a grade equal to 5%, Figure 6.34 presents an example plot (in log-log scale) of the damage evolution in terms of maxISD as a function of PGV_{rock} for the four-storey RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction as well as the maxISD limit values for each damage state. The developed sets of fragility curves for the considered low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction along with their lognormally distributed fragility parameters (median m and log-standard deviation β) in terms of PGA_{rock} and PGV_{rock} are depicted in Figure 6.35 and Figure 6.36 respectively.

Figure 6.34. PGA_{rock} – maxISD relationship for the four-storey RC frame building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

A general observation for the studied typical low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions is that, as should be expected, they are found more vulnerable compared to the corresponding ones at level ground conditions probably due to the occurrence of lateral spreading. This is also in accordance with field observations (Cubrinovski et al. 2012), as lateral spreading involves large lateral ground movement as well as substantial differential displacements in the direction of spreading, resulting in large extensional deformation and subsequently more structural damages.

Figure 6.35. Fragility curves in terms of PGA at bedrock for the different RC frame building typologies at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.36. Fragility curves in terms of PGV at bedrock for the different RC frame building typologies at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

6.9.1.3 Comparisons of the strain-based developed and literature fragility curves

In this section, an attempt is made to develop fragility curves due to combined ground shaking and liquefaction in terms of differential settlement and differential lateral deformation using maximum values of material strain as the EDP. They are compared with the corresponding *strain-based* ones of Chapter 5 as well as of Bird et al. (2005). It should be noted that the fragility curves in this section were developed only for comparison reasons in order to enhance the reliability of the proposed methodology. In particular, the results of the conducted nonlinear IDA (i.e. maximum differential displacement – maximum material strain and maximum differential lateral deformation – maximum material strain pairs) are used to derive the fragility curves expressed as two-parameter lognormal distribution functions according to equation 5.1. It has been observed that for all analysis cases, steel strain (ϵ_s) gives more critical results compared to the concrete strain (ϵ_c). Hence, hereafter, the EDP is defined in terms of steel bar strain.

The comparisons are conducted only for the first two limit states, namely LS1 (defined as steel bar yielding) and LS2 (defined as post-yield limit state) described in chapter 6, which were initially proposed by Crowley et al. (2004) as shown in Table 3.3; and subsequently by Bird et al. (2005) for buildings on flexible foundations exposed to liquefaction-induced ground deformations which undergo structural deformations (Table 3.4). These limit states seem to be captured by the IDA results as shown in Figure 6.37 and Figure 6.38. It should be noted that maxISD is a better and most commonly used EDP for the derivation of fragility functions for RC buildings subjected to ground shaking, as it correlates to its damage description via a substantial amount of experimental data (Rossetto and Elnashai 2003), while maximum material strain needs caution as it may overlook global response. For this reason, the proposed curves in terms of PGA_{rock} and PGV_{rock} are derived using IM-maxISD pair data.

Subsequently, the developed fragility curves for the studied low-code RC frame buildings are compared with some representative analytical fragility curves presented in chapter 5 and Bird et al. (2005). More specifically, Figure 6.39 presents indicative comparisons between the herein curves derived for the two-storey low-code RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction and the corresponding ones taken from Chapter 5 for damage states LS1 and LS2 which are featuring the same damage state definition as in this study. It is observed that as expected the fragility curves of Chapter 5 for LS1 and LS2 generally present much lower damage probability compared to the numerically derived curves of this study. This is reasonable as in the former case the building is subjected only to differential displacements while in the latter

one the building is subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction and more damages are expected.

Figure 6.37. Differential settlement- steel strain relationship for the two-storey RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.38. Differential lateral deformation- steel strain relationship for the two-storey RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.39. Comparison of the proposed fragility curves in terms of differential settlement for the two-storey RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction with the corresponding analytical ones of Chapter 5

In addition, Figure 6.40 presents indicative comparisons between the herein curves derived for the two-storey low-code RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction and the corresponding ones taken from Bird et al. (2005) for damage states LS1 and LS2 which are also featuring the same damage state definition as in this study.

Figure 6.40. Comparison of the proposed fragility curves in terms of differential lateral deformation for the two-storey RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction with the corresponding analytical ones of Bird et al. (2005)

Despite the large uncertainties involved in the problem, a good agreement is observed for LS2 median. The basic difference among them is the higher slope of the [Bird et al. \(2005\)](#) curve (representing the higher standard deviation). In this case probably the effect of differential displacement on the building is more intense compared to the effect of ground shaking and for this reason the LS2 medians of this study and [Bird et al. \(2005\)](#) are almost the same. For LS1 the analytical curve also presents much lower damage probability compared to the numerically derived curves of this study. This is also reasonable as in [Bird et al. \(2005\)](#) the building is subjected only to liquefaction-induced differential displacements ignoring possible damage due to ground shaking, while in this study fragility curves are derived for the building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction where more damages are expected, as already mentioned.

In general, it is seen that when the low-code low-rise RC frame building on isolated footings is subjected to differential settlements (Figure 6.39) it is more vulnerable compared to when subjected to differential lateral deformation (Figure 6.40). This is in accordance with the findings of Chapter 5, where it was shown that low-code RC buildings on isolated footings subjected to differential settlements are expected to suffer larger damages compared to the ones where the maximum differential displacement has also a horizontal component (lateral spreading).

6.9.2 Development of fragility surfaces

In current practice, fragility curves are developed using a single IM to relate the level of shaking to the expected structural damage, which is not able to represent all characteristics of a ground motion. [Baker and Cornell \(2005\)](#) showed that considering two IMs instead of one may improve the collapse probability calculation for a multi-degree-of-freedom structure. In addition, [Gehl et al. \(2013\)](#) demonstrated through various statistical techniques the fact that the use of more than one IM leads to a better prediction of the damage state of a building than just a single IM, which is the current practice. Recently, some efforts have been made to model the effect of several IMs on structural damage. More specifically, [Seyedi et al. \(2010\)](#) proposed a methodology for building seismic fragility functions for various damage states explicitly involving more than one IM (deriving in that way fragility surfaces instead of simple fragility curves) based on the damage calculation through nonlinear numerical analysis of multi-degree-of-freedom systems. [Koutsourelakis \(2010\)](#) introduced a Bayesian framework to derive vector-valued fragility functions from the limited data available. In addition, [Gehl et al. 2013](#) presented a method for the development of vector-valued fragility functions, which are a function of more than one IM for use within seismic risk evaluation of buildings. More recently, [Malaga-Chuquitaype and Bougatsas \(2017\)](#) provided a detailed

quantification of the benefits of employing a vector-valued analysis over a scalar formulation when evaluating maxISD in buildings.

In this subsection, bivariate fragility functions for RC frame buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction are derived and represented in the form of fragility surfaces as functions of both peak ground acceleration at free-field (PGA_{ff}) surface (IM_1), which is easily estimated through site response analysis or measured in the field, and maximum permanent ground displacement (PGD) vector that occurs at surface at the foundation level of the structure (IM_2), which is considered by [Brandenberg et al. \(2011b\)](#) the most important and useful IM to characterize liquefaction-induced lateral spreading. In addition, fragility surfaces as functions of both peak ground velocity (PGV) and maximum PGD vector at surface below the structure (IM_1 and IM_2 respectively) are also derived, as PGV and PGD are better correlated with structural damage. The following procedure, inspired by [Baker and Cornel \(2005\)](#) and [Malaga-Chuquitaype and Bougatsas \(2017\)](#), has been followed to construct the fragility surfaces.

In particular, linear regression which can be considered as an extension of scalar fragility fitting ([Baker 2007](#)), is adopted to correlate the computed maxISD (EDP) with the two considered IMs for the estimation of fragility surfaces. The cumulative probability of exceeding a limit state conditioned on the two IMs (vector $[IM_1 \ IM_2]$), i.e. PGA_{ff} and PGD or PGV and PGD, is given by the following equation 6.6:

$$P\{DS_i/IM\} = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM_1) - (b_0 + b_1 \times \ln(\overline{IM}_2))}{\beta}\right) \quad (6.6)$$

where, Φ is the (bivariate) normal cumulative density function of the distribution, b_0 and b_1 are regression coefficients, \overline{IM}_2 and β are the median values of IM_2 and log-standard deviations respectively of the building fragilities for each damage state i and DS_i is the damage state.

The relationship between the two considered IMs is obtained by a linear regression fit of the logarithms of the IM_1 - IM_2 IDA data pairs and is given by the following equation 6.7:

$$\ln(IM_1) = b_0 + b_1 \times \ln(IM_2) \quad (6.7)$$

A graphical example of the regression analysis on the logarithms of the PGD (IM_2) relative to the logarithms of the PGV (IM_1) at surface data obtained for the two-storey RC frame building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction is illustrated in Figure 6.41.

Figure 6.41. Regression analysis on the logarithms of the PGD relative to the logarithms of the PGV data obtained for the two-storey RC frame building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

For the development of the seismic fragility surfaces according to Equation 6.6, the \overline{IM}_1 and \overline{IM}_2 (the median values of the two IMs at which the building reaches each damage limit state) as well as β , need to be defined. For this reason, a similar procedure with the one followed in the previous section to estimate the median of the scalar IM in order to develop conventional fragility curves is followed. In particular, except from IM_1 , IM_2 is also incorporated in prediction of the response in terms of maxISD (EDP).

First, a linear regression fit of the logarithms of the IM_1 -maxISD data pairs which minimizes the regression residuals is adopted in all analysis cases. A graphical example of the regression analysis on the logarithms of the maxISD relative to the logarithms of the PGV (IM_1) data obtained for the two-storey RC frame building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction is shown in Figure 6.42.

Subsequently, another regression analysis of the residuals of the previous regression on IM_1 and the logarithms of IM_2 is also conducted for each structural model. It is observed that there tends to be a linear dependence between the residuals of the regression on IM_1 (PGA_{ff} or PGV) and the logarithms of the corresponding IM_2 (PGD). Thus, the functional form used for the regression on a vector of IMs is described as:

$$\ln(EDP) = a \ln(IM_1) + b \ln(IM_2) + c + \varepsilon \cdot \sigma \quad (6.8)$$

where EDP is the maximum inter-storey drift (maxISD), IM_1 and IM_2 are the PGA_{ff} or PGV and the maximum PGD vector, respectively (all derived from the analysis due to combined ground shaking and liquefaction), a , b , and c are regression coefficients, ε is the standard normal variant with zero mean and unit standard deviation and the

dispersion sigma (σ) represents the conditional standard deviation of the regression (in natural log units) and is a metric of the efficiency of the IMs with respect to the EDP (maxISD).

In addition, the coefficient of determination R^2 is included as a goodness of fit measure to identify the correlation between the residuals and the second IM. It is noted that problems may arise when implementing linear regression with vectors incorporating strongly correlated IMs (Malaga-Chuquitaype and Bougatsas (2017)). Thus, R^2 values approaching zero indicate uncorrelated IMs.

Figure 6.42. Regression analysis on the logarithms of the maxISD relative to the logarithms of the PGV data obtained for the two-storey RC frame building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Therefore, the median values of the two IMs corresponding to the prescribed damage limit states are determined based on this regression analysis of the residuals of the regression on IM_1 and the logarithms of the corresponding IM_2 data for each structural model combined with equation 6.7. A graphical example of the regression analysis on the residuals|PGV relative to the logarithms of the PGD (IM_2) data obtained for the two-storey RC frame building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction is depicted in Figure 6.43.

Figure 6.43. Regression analysis on the residuals|PGV relative to the logarithms of the PGD data obtained for the two-storey RC frame building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

The various uncertainties are taken into account through the log-standard deviation parameter β , which describes the total dispersion related to each fragility surface and is defined according to Section 5.5.2 of Chapter 5 (equation 5.2). In the following subsections the derived fragility surfaces in terms of both PGA_{ff} and maximum PGD vector at surface below the structure as well as both PGV and maximum PGD vector at surface below the structure for the considered RC frame building typologies subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction for the different ground conditions are presented.

6.9.2.1 Level ground conditions

When considering level ground conditions, the computed fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD vector that occurs at surface at the foundation level of the structure obtained by means of linear regression for the different damage states for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction are depicted in Figure 6.44, Figure 6.45 and Figure 6.46 respectively, while Table 6.10 summarises the corresponding fragility parameters, namely median m and log-standard deviation β , in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD.

It is noted that for the nine-storey RC frame building subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, the corresponding limit values of maxISD defined for extensive and complete damage state using PGA_{ff} as IM_1 are not reached and thus fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for these limit states are not proposed (Figure 6.46).

Table 6.10. Parameters of the proposed fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for the typical low-code RC frame buildings at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Building typology	Median PGA_{ff} (g)				Median PGD (m)				Dispersion β
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	
2- storey MRF RC	0.05	0.13	0.20	0.26	0.004	0.029	0.082	0.134	0.79
4- storey MRF RC	0.05	0.15	0.26	0.44	0.005	0.048	0.158	0.541	0.85
9- storey MRF RC	0.09	0.22	-	-	0.021	0.117	-	-	0.67

Figure 6.44. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for slight (LS1), moderate (LS2), extensive (LS3) and complete (LS4) limit states for the two-storey MRF RC building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.45. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for slight (LS1), moderate (LS2), extensive (LS3) and complete (LS4) limit states for the four-storey MRF RC building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.46. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for slight (LS1) and moderate (LS2) limit states for the nine-storey MRF RC building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Similarly, the computed fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD obtained by means of linear regression for the different damage states for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction are depicted in Figure 6.47, Figure 6.48 and

Figure 6.49 - Figure 6.50 respectively, while Table 6.11 summarises the corresponding fragility parameters.

Table 6.11. Parameters of the proposed fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for the typical low-code RC frame buildings at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Building typology	Median PGV (m/sec)				Median PGD (m)				Dispersion β
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	
2- storey MRF RC	0.06	0.13	0.20	0.25	0.010	0.036	0.068	0.091	0.57
4- storey MRF RC	0.07	0.16	0.24	0.38	0.013	0.050	0.100	0.204	0.63
9- storey MRF RC	0.09	0.21	0.43	-	0.029	0.098	0.249	-	0.53

Figure 6.47. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for slight (LS1), moderate (LS2), extensive (LS3) and complete (LS4) limit states for the two-storey MRF RC building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

When PGV is used as IM_1 (that better correlates with structural damage), it is noted that only the corresponding limit value of maxISD defined for complete damage state is

not reached and thus the fragility surface in terms of PGV and PGD for complete damage state is not proposed (Figure 6.49 and Figure 6.50).

Figure 6.48. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for slight (LS1), moderate (LS2), extensive (LS3) and complete (LS4) limit states for the four-storey MRF RC building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.49. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for slight (LS1) and moderate (LS2) limit states for the nine-storey MRF RC building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.50. Fragility surface in terms of PGV and PGD for extensive (LS3) limit state for the nine-storey MRF RC building at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

As it can be seen in general, a similar trend with the scalar-based fragility curves is also observed in the developed vector-valued fragility surfaces for the typical low-code RC frame buildings at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction. In particular, the total height of the building considerably influences its vulnerability to the earthquake-induced ground shaking and liquefaction, with the low-rise building suffering more structural damages compared to the mid- and high-rise ones.

6.9.2.2 Slope conditions (5% grade)

When considering slope conditions with a grade equal to 5%, the developed fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD vector that occurs at surface at the foundation level of the structure obtained by means of linear regression for the different damage states for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction are depicted in Figure 6.51, Figure 6.52 and Figure 6.53 - Figure 6.54 respectively, while Table 6.12 summarises the corresponding fragility parameters, i.e. medians and log-standard deviation beta.

Table 6.12. Parameters of the proposed fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for the typical low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Building typology	Median PGA_{ff} (g)				Median PGD (m)				Dispersion β
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	
2- storey MRF RC	0.05	0.14	0.24	0.31	0.005	0.115	0.594	1.292	0.76
4- storey MRF RC	0.06	0.16	0.26	0.44	0.008	0.167	0.801	4.046	0.82
9- storey MRF RC	0.09	0.23	0.49	-	0.032	0.518	4.236	-	0.73

Figure 6.51. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for slight (LS1), moderate (LS2), extensive (LS3) and complete (LS4) limit states for the two-storey MRF RC building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Similarly, the computed fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD obtained by means of linear regression for the different damage states for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions (with a grade equal to 5%) subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction are depicted in Figure 6.55 - Figure 6.56, Figure 6.57 and Figure 6.58 respectively, while Table 6.13 summarises the corresponding fragility parameters.

As it can be seen, a similar trend with the scalar-based fragility curves is also identified in the developed vector-valued fragility surfaces for the studied typical low-code RC frame buildings. In particular, the studied typical low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions are found more vulnerable compared to the corresponding ones at level ground conditions probably due to the occurrence of lateral spreading. Moreover, it is seen that the high-rise building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction does not sustain complete structural damages (even if they are subjected to records with a PGA_{rock} value equal to 1.0g) an observation that is also confirmed from the scalar-based fragility curves. This response confirms once again field observations reporting that high-rise buildings erected on relatively shallow foundation

behave as rigid block and are prone to tilt excessively or topple (Bray and Dashti 2014) when subjected to ground shaking and liquefaction, without sustaining significant internal deformation and differential movements, which are the main reasons for presenting structural damage (i.e. damage in the structural elements due to the large induced deformations).

Figure 6.52. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for slight (LS1), moderate (LS2), extensive (LS3) and complete (LS4) limit states for the four-storey MRF RC building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.53. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for slight (LS1) and moderate (LS2) limit states for the nine-storey MRF RC building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.54. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD for extensive (LS3) limit state for the nine-storey MRF RC building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Table 6.13. Parameters of the proposed fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for the typical low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Building typology	Median PGV (m/sec)				Median PGD (m)				Dispersion β
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	
2- storey MRF RC	0.08	0.17	0.24	0.28	0.013	0.118	0.367	0.627	0.60
4- storey MRF RC	0.10	0.18	0.25	0.34	0.019	0.152	0.441	1.328	0.64
9- storey MRF RC	0.12	0.23	0.37	-	0.049	0.332	1.404	-	0.55

Figure 6.55. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for slight (LS1) and moderate (LS2) limit states for the two-storey MRF RC building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.56. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for extensive (LS3) and complete (LS4) limit states for the two-storey MRF RC building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.57. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for slight (LS1), moderate (LS2), extensive (LS3) and complete (LS4) limit states for the four-storey MRF RC building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.58. Fragility surfaces in terms of PGV and PGD for slight (LS1), moderate (LS2) and extensive (LS3) limit states for the nine-storey MRF RC building at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

For the fragility surfaces proposed as function of PGV and PGD at surface below the structure, it is suggested that PGV and PGD at free-field surface values can also be used, as they refer to buildings with flexible shallow foundations (pad footings). To enhance this proposition, kinematic interaction is proved to be negligible. In particular, kinematic interaction results from the presence of stiff foundation elements on or in soil, which causes motions at the foundation to deviate from free-field motions (NIST 2012).

The dimensionless frequency for footings (a_0) affects the kinematic transfer function (the ratio of the foundation input motion to the free-field ground motion). The a_0 is given by the following equation:

$$a_0 = \frac{\omega B}{V_s} \tag{6.9}$$

where ω is the undamped natural vibration frequency (in rad/sec), B is the foundation half-width (in m) and V_s is the shear wave velocity in a homogeneous isotropic half-space.

According to NIST (2012), for a_0 values near zero, the foundation input motion, in terms of acceleration (m/sec^2), velocity (m/sec) or displacement (m), is equal to the

free-field ground motion. As presented in Table 6.14, for the studied soil-structure cases (buildings with shallow pad footings), the obtained a_0 values are almost zero.

Table 6.14. Calculation of the dimensionless frequency for footings (a_0) for the studied SSI cases according to NIST (2012)

RC frame building height	a_0		
	Soil Profile A	Soil Profile B	Soil Profile C
Two-storey	0.09	0.07	0.07
Four-storey	0.07	0.05	0.05
Nine-storey	0.04	0.04	0.03

Therefore, the proposed fragility surfaces can be applied using also the PGV and PGD at free-field surface. It is noted that the use of the proposed fragility surfaces is justified for site-specific applications on critical buildings where adequate data from field measurements are available and/or detailed 1D numerical site-response analysis are conducted.

6.10 Vulnerability assessment

Once the probabilities of exceeding the specified damage states are estimated, a damage (or vulnerability) index d_m is evaluated for each level of seismic intensity according to the following expression:

$$d_{mj} = \sum_{i=1}^4 P_{ij} \cdot d_i \quad (6.10)$$

where d_{mj} is the damage index (taking values from 0: no damage to 1: complete damage) corresponding to seismic intensity level j , P_{ij} is the discrete damage probability for each damage state and d_i stands for the damage index at each of the considered damage states.

For the RC buildings, the central value of the damage index for each damage state is assumed equal to 0.05, 0.20, 0.45 and 0.80 for the LS_1 , LS_2 , LS_3 and LS_4 respectively according to Kappos et al. (2006). A vulnerability curve or surface is then constructed for each building typology which provides a unique damage or vulnerability index d_m for each level of seismic intensity. Indicatively, Figure 6.59 and Figure 6.60 illustrate the derived vulnerability curves in terms of PGA_{rock} and in terms of PGV_{rock} for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings at level ground and slope conditions respectively, subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction. It is noted that with

the given curves, losses in the RC structural members of the buildings are accounted for. It is seen once again that the total height of the building considerably influences its losses to the earthquake-induced ground shaking and liquefaction, with the low-rise building suffering more losses compared to the mid- and high-rise ones.

In general it is seen that even when subjected to PGA_{rock} values higher than 0.5g which are considered extreme values, the studied low-code RC frame buildings present low damage index values. This is principally due to the nonlinear behaviour of the soil profile introduced by the apparition of soil liquefaction, which results in attenuation of the seismic motion observed at the free-field ground surface. It is noted that the corresponding $PGA_{ff,surf}$ values of the median PGA_{rock} values proposed in section 6.9.1 for ground shaking and liquefaction are close to the proposed ones by Kappos et al. (2003) for ground shaking.

Moreover, it should once again be noted that the PGA_{rock} is found to be poor IM, as the increase of it does not necessarily lead to collapse of the soil-structure system. On the contrary, PGV_{rock} values higher than almost 40.0cm/sec principally result in failure of the soil-structure system (which is also obvious from the large damage index). Thus, it was deemed appropriate to also provide the vulnerability curves in terms of PGV_{rock} as this IM better correlates with structural damage.

Figure 6.59. Vulnerability curves in terms of PGA_{rock} and in terms of PGV_{rock} for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings at level ground conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

Figure 6.60. Vulnerability curves in terms of PGA_{rock} and in terms of PGV_{rock} for the two-storey, four-storey and nine-storey low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction

However, due to the fact that the cost of the RC structural system totals less than the cost of a (new) building (which also includes non-structural members), the computed damage indices could then be multiplied with an empirically derived reductive coefficient to derive the final global damage index. For instance, according to [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#) for the low, mid and high-rise residential RC frame buildings this coefficient varies from 0.33 to 0.38 (values that have been calibrated against cost of damage data from Greece). Thus, it is implicitly shown that the total cost of non-structural damage, e.g. damage to ceilings, mechanical and electrical equipment that is an integral part of the structure, piping and elevators, partitions, exterior walls, ornamentation, glass ([NIBS 2004](#)), may be higher compared to the cost of repairs required to the RC structural system itself. If an average replacement cost is assumed for the considered low-code RC buildings then the final global damage index multiplied with these values returns the total cost of repairs in each building due to structural and non-structural damage.

6.11 Comparison with literature

In the following, some comparisons are made of the above findings with field observations for buildings on areas where widespread liquefaction occurred to further increase the validity of the proposed fragility functions and relationships.

In particular, after the 22 February 2011 ($M_w = 6.2$) Christchurch, New Zealand earthquake, a six-storey RC frame building founded on isolated spread footings with tie beams and perimeter grade beam, located within the Central Business District (CBD) of Christchurch, illustrated in Figure 6.61, was subjected to an overall differential settlement of 25.0 cm. Ground shaking was recorded at four strong motion stations within the CBD. The geometric mean horizontal peak ground accelerations (PGA) recorded at the station CCCC, which is the closest to this building, was equal to 0.42g,

while the median PGA recorded from the four stations was equal to 0.44g (Bray et al. 2014). This building was considered uneconomical to repair after the 22 February 2011 earthquake (Bray and Dashti 2014). This observation is in accordance to the proposed fragility surfaces for the mid-rise frame building, which suggest a median PGA_{ff} equal to 0.44g for the complete damage state. Moreover, by using the relationship proposed in Figure 6.27, for a PGD value equal to 0.49cm (which is the corresponding to PGA_{ff} of 0.42g), a differential settlement equal to 24.5cm is estimated. Therefore, a really good agreement between the findings of this thesis and the above field reconnaissance data is observed.

Figure 6.61. RC frame building on shallow foundation undergoing significant liquefaction-induced differential settlement after being subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction (after Bray and Dashti 2014)

Unfortunately, no other building, similar to the studied building typologies, reporting such information on PGA and displacements was found in the available literature. However, some other reported field observations are following. More specifically, Cubrinovski et al. (2011) reported that a three-story building on shallow foundations (no information about its material and type of shallow foundation) in the CBD, uniformly displaced laterally approximately 15.0cm toward the area of significant liquefaction near the front of the building. It is noted that in the CBD, horizontal PGAs of between 0.37g and 0.52g were recorded (Bradley and Cubrinovski 2011). It is also reminded that for the mid-rise RC frame buildings for the extensive damage state (LS3) a median PGA_{ff} equal to 0.26g and a median PGD equal to 15.8cm is proposed, while for the complete damage state (LS4) a median PGA_{ff} and a median PGD equal to 0.44g and 54.1cm, respectively. Moreover, Bray et al. (2014) reported that a four-story RC framed structure (approved in 1972) that consisted of shallow RC strip footings interconnected with square RC tie

beams was damaged significantly after the Christchurch earthquake, with evidence of damage to the structural columns at the ground level.

Furthermore, [Cubrinovski et al. \(2012\)](#) generally reported that within the CBD, the maximum permanent spreading displacements were predominantly between 10.0cm and 30.0cm, except at three locations where the displacements reached 50.0-70.0cm, while at regions with extensive lateral spreading (probably due to slope conditions) they reported maximum (relative) magnitudes of permanent lateral ground displacements due to spreading of liquefied soils of the order 2.0-3.5m. These PGD values are in accordance with the maximum PGD values obtained within this study from the IDA analysis. In particular, for complete damage at level ground conditions a median PGD value equal to 54.1cm is proposed, while at slope conditions a median PGD value about 4.0m. Considering the important uncertainties involved, the above comparisons made of the herein findings with field observations are generally satisfactory.

6.12 Concluding remarks

Within the framework of this study, an analytical methodology is proposed for the vulnerability and risk assessment of typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights (low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise) with shallow flexible foundations resting on liquefiable soils at level ground and slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction based on a fully coupled numerical approach taking into account the SSI. The important issue of the interaction of ground shaking and soil liquefaction for individual shallow-founded buildings was investigated. In particular, the direct one-step approach where the soil and the structure are modelled and analysed as a single system, which accounts simultaneously for inertial and kinematic interaction schemes, was implemented considering soil nonlinearity introduced by soil liquefaction. Three typical soil profiles susceptible to liquefaction were investigated. To estimate the fragility function parameters, two-dimensional incremental dynamic analysis (IDA) of the nonlinear SSI systems was conducted. In addition, a second set of IDA was performed considering slope with a 5% grade to further examine the contribution of liquefaction-induced lateral spreading. The liquefiable soil response and subsequently the SSI models were validated through observed trends that are also identified in the literature.

Vulnerability is expressed in terms of lognormally distributed fragility curves, as a function of PGA_{rock} or PGV_{rock} , in terms of vulnerability curves as a function of PGA_{rock} or PGV_{rock} to assess the expected direct losses in normalised cost terms as well as coupled fragility surfaces as functions of both PGA_{ff} and maximum PGD vector at surface or both PGV and maximum PGD vector at surface. The proposed curves and surfaces can be used within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the vulnerability and risk of

typical low-code RC frame buildings in Greece and in Southern Europe in general exposed to combined ground shaking and liquefaction. Moreover, predictive relationships between the maximum differential permanent ground displacements (settlement or vector) and the maximum permanent ground displacements (PGD) vector at surface below buildings with shallow flexible foundations due to ground shaking and liquefaction were established through regression analysis.

In general, it has been shown that the total height of the building may considerably influence its vulnerability to the earthquake-induced ground shaking and liquefaction. More specifically, the low-code low-rise RC frame building suffers more structural damages compared to the mid- and high-rise ones. This may be attributed to the fact that as the height of the building increases, the building tends to behave as a rigid body and is prone to tilt excessively or topple, without sustaining extensive structural damages. Moreover, it is observed that the typical low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions are found more vulnerable compared to the corresponding ones at level ground conditions probably due to the occurrence of lateral spreading. This is also in accordance with field observations (Cubrinovski et al. 2012), as lateral spreading involves large lateral ground movement as well as substantial differential displacements in the direction of spreading, resulting in large extensional deformation and subsequently more structural damages.

Comparisons made of the herein proposed fragility curves/surfaces for the typical low-code RC frame buildings resting on liquefiable soils subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction with the available ones from the literature (Bird et al. 2005) as well as with field observations (Bray and Dashti 2014; Bray et al. 2014; Cubrinovski et al. 2012; Cubrinovski et al. 2011) are generally satisfactory considering the important uncertainties involved.

Future research should be oriented towards the development of a probabilistic framework for the evaluation of the risk to buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, which also take into account the possibility of soil liquefaction apparition according to the estimated factor of safety against liquefaction. Another important issue that could be addressed in a future study would be the consideration of varying strength and stiffness characteristics of the studied structures within the given building classes (to assess analytically the variability in the capacity (Iervolino et al. 2004), additional structural configurations as well as other parameters involved, which have not been considered in this analysis, like aging effects on the material properties. In addition, given the significance of this study's findings, future work should also address fragility analysis taking into account infill walls and their contribution to the response to both ground shaking and soil liquefaction, as well as other structural systems and

foundation systems, such as steel light frame warehouses, unreinforced masonry buildings which tend to have shallow relatively flexible foundations and RC frame buildings with piled foundations or basements. Finally, comparison of the results with experimental studies would further enforce the validity of the proposed fragility curves and surfaces.

Chapter 7

Risk assessment of Thessaloniki port buildings due to ground shaking & liquefaction

7.1 Introduction

A scenario-based risk assessment analysis due to the combined effect of ground shaking and liquefaction for the buildings of Thessaloniki port, one of the largest Greek seaports, is the main aim of this chapter. An effort is made to identify as accurately as possible the site specific response and subsequently estimate the risk and increase port's resilience as well as verify the reliability and applicability of the proposed methodological frameworks and the respective fragility curves and surfaces presented in Chapters 5 and 6 respectively. The risk assessment is performed taking into account the potential physical damages and corresponding losses of the port buildings for two different considered seismic scenarios based on nonlinear site-response analyses for representative soil profiles susceptible to liquefaction.

In particular, two different seismic scenarios are considered: the design seismic scenario and the extreme event seismic scenario which includes also the potential of liquefaction corresponding to a return period of 475 years and 4975 years respectively. For each seismic scenario, a representative target spectrum for bedrock conditions ($V_s=700-800$ m/s) is defined. For the 475 years scenario a set of fifteen accelerograms is selected that on average fit the target spectrum, while for the extreme scenario, ten synthetic accelerograms are computed to fit the target spectrum. Three representative soil profiles are considered for the site response analyses distributed along the area of the port. The soil profiles have been defined based on previous studies ([Anastasiadis et al. 2001](#)), including in situ geophysical and laboratory tests as well as new array measurements of microtremors. Nonlinear (NL) site response analyses including also the potential for liquefaction are carried out for the three soil profiles using as input motions at the seismic bedrock the ones estimated for the 475 years and 4975 years seismic

scenarios. The uncertainty in the V_s profiles represented by the scatter of the field measurements is evaluated in the simulations, considering a standard deviation of the natural logarithm of the V_s equal to 0.2 in the base-case geotechnical models. The variation of horizontal and vertical permanent ground displacement (PGD), maximum shear strain, maximum shear stress, effective confinement and excess pore water pressure with depth are also computed for each analysis case.

Regarding the potential damages and losses to port buildings, for the steel light frame warehouses they are assessed using appropriate fragility models for ground shaking from the literature and the fragility curves developed in Chapter 5 for liquefaction, while for the RC buildings they are evaluated for the combined effect of ground shaking and liquefaction using the fragility surfaces developed in Chapter 6. A structural damage index weighted with respect to the built area is evaluated to quantify the economic losses as the ratio of the cost of repair to the cost of replacement.

7.2 Background of Thessaloniki port

7.2.1 Thessaloniki port buildings

An important seaport represents a remarkable factor of development of a region or even a nation. The interruption of functionality of port structures can have severe direct and indirect effects on the economy and on the social and environmental growth of the broader area of interest, in our case the city of Thessaloniki, or even broader, Greece as a whole. The Port of Thessaloniki is one of the largest transit-trade ports in Greece and the Aegean Sea basin. As a free port, it also functions as a major gateway for the Balkan hinterland and South-East Europe. Its strategic geographical position increases its importance for the trade and the economy of the region, as it is a crucial point for supply chains, import-export trade and transportation.

According to information provided by the Port authorities, critical buildings of Thessaloniki port (as well as its vicinity) mainly consist of low- and pre- code RC buildings constructed before and after the introduction of the 1959 Greek seismic code ('Royal Decree' of 1959) respectively, and steel light frame warehouses (Figure 7.1). These buildings compared to other inland buildings designed according to current modern codes (high-code) would present a worse seismic behaviour, as issues such as the ductility and capacity as well as the dynamic features of the structures were ignored in their design.

In total, 69 building and storage facilities are considered in this case study, 52 of which are RC buildings of different heights including principally low or no-code MRF systems, while the rest 17 are basically steel light frame warehouses with one or two

floors. It should be noted that within the area of Thessaloniki Port there are also 16 buildings, i.e. eight RC dual buildings and eight unreinforced masonry (URM) buildings that were ignored herein. The vulnerability of these building typologies due to liquefaction were not studied within the framework of this thesis, thus it was considered out of the scope of this application to use literature fragility curves for their risk estimation.

Figure 7.1. Geographical representation of Thessaloniki port buildings considered in the study

7.2.2 Geotechnical, geological, geophysical data of Thessaloniki port

In this section the available geotechnical and geophysical data in the area of Thessaloniki port as well as the geological background information of the broader area are summarised.

7.2.2.1 Geological background information of the broader area

The city of Thessaloniki is located on the Axios-Vardar zone, which is adjacent to the Servomacedonian massif, one of the most seismo-tectonically active regions in Europe (Papazachos et al. 1997). Thessaloniki with its suburbs extends towards the E-NE direction in the Thermaikos Gulf coastal zone and has an interesting topography, starting from sea level and reaching an altitude of 100.0 to 150.0 m with smooth ascents. The entire urban area is situated on three main large-scale geology structures, oriented in the NW-SE direction. The first formation includes the metamorphic substratum consisting of gneiss, epigneiss, and green schists which are surficial near the city at the N-NE border of the urban area. These crystalline rocks constitute the bedrock basement beneath the city reaching a depth of 150.0-300.0 m near the coastline in the W-WS direction. The

second formation comprises alluvial deposits mainly of the Neogene period. In this geological structure the red silty clay series are dominant, covering the bedrock basement beneath the city. Finally, recent deposits of Holocene clay-sands-pebbles compose the third surficial formation. The soil conditions in the broader area of the port are characterised by soft soil formations at relatively high depth reaching close to the sea 150.0m to 180.0m. The rock substratum is even deeper. In several locations the surface formations composed of loose silty sand are susceptible to liquefaction. However during the last strong earthquake in Thessaloniki (M=6.4, R=25.0km) no evidence of liquefaction has been observed. Thessaloniki disposes one very complete geotechnical map with all relevant information to perform any kind of site response analysis (Anastasiadis et al. 2001). The Port area is a part of this general geotechnical map.

7.2.2.2 Geotechnical and geophysical data in the Port area

Soft alluvial deposits composed mainly of sandy clays and silts, sometimes susceptible to liquefaction, characterize the Thessaloniki Port subsoil conditions. A comprehensive set of in-situ geotechnical tests (e.g. drillings, sampling, SPT and CPT tests), detailed laboratory tests and measurements, as well as geophysical surveys (cross-hole, down-hole, array microtremor measurements) at the port broader area provide all necessary information to perform all kind of site-specific ground response analyses (Anastasiadis et al. 2001; Apostolidis et al. 2004). Complementary geophysical tests including array microtremor measurements have been recently conducted at four different sites inside the port (Pitilakis et al. 2016) using the SPatial Autocorrelation Coefficient–SPAC method (Aki 1957). All available data (Figure 7.2) are properly archived. Table 7.1 to Table 7.3 present the total number of field geotechnical and geophysical surveys and geotechnical boreholes, while Table 7.4 gives the parameters of the SPAC measurements conducted in the port of Thessaloniki.

Table 7.1. Geophysical data close to Thessaloniki port (*1: Raptakis and Makra 2010; *2: ITSAK's Equipment and Instrumentation Upgrade project, 2002-2006)

Map location	Type	Id	Depth (m)	Boreholes	Bottom layer V_s (m/s)	Bottom layer V_p (m/s)	Year
Over Pier 6 (Thermaikos football field)	Cross-hole *1	CH-1	40.0	No	400	-	1993
Pier 3-4 (near the church)	Down-hole *2	DH-1	80.30	Yes	710	2462	2008

Table 7.2. Microtremor array measurements at port area (Apostolidis et al. 2004)

Map location	Array Id	Depth (m)	Bedrock Vs (m/s)	Circle radius (m)	Analysis Method	Year
Pier 1-2	A-1	180	700	10, 50	SPAC	2001
Over Pier 6 (Customs Office)	A-2	160	600	15	SPAC	2001

Table 7.3. Boreholes at the broader Thessaloniki Port area (Anastasiadis et al. 2001)

Piers	Number of Boreholes	Boreholes Id	Depth (m)	SPT Data	CPT Data	Lab data	USCS Classification	Year
1	4	B-1÷B-2	13.0÷20.0	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	1996
		B-3	22.0	No	Yes			1996
		B-69	26.0	Yes	No			1999
1-2	3	B-68	28.5	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	1999
		B-70÷B71	30.0÷40.0	No	Yes	No	No	
2	4	B-4÷B-7	21.0÷32.0	No	No	No	Yes	1962
4	8	B-8÷B15	17.0÷22.7	No	No	No	Yes	1940
4-5	8	B-22÷B29	30.5÷31.5	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	1962
5	6	B-16÷B-18	19.0÷21.5	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	1962
		B-30÷B-32						
5-6	3	B-19÷B21	18.0÷20.5	Yes	No	No	Yes	1965
6	35	B-33÷B67	24.0÷36.0	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	1964
								1970
								1972

Figure 7.2. Location of geotechnical tests and geophysical field measurements in Thessaloniki’s port area

Table 7.4. Microtremor array measurements in Thessaloniki port (Pitilakis et al. 2016)

Map location	Array ID	Circle radius (m)	Analysis Method	Year
Pier 1-2 (close to passenger station)	M-1	10, 27	SPAC	2015
Pier 2-3 (church)	M-2	10, 20, 50	SPAC	2015
Pier 6	M-3	10, 20	SPAC	2015
Close to pier 6	M-4	10, 20, 50	SPAC	2015

Three representative soil profiles distributed along the area of the port denoted as A, B, and C (Figure 7.3) have been defined based on the available data for the site response analyses (section 7.4). Their fundamental periods T_0 are equal to 1.58 sec, 1.60 sec and 1.24 sec respectively. Figure 7.3 presents the variation of the shear wave velocities V_s with depth for the three soil profiles.

Figure 7.3. Shear wave velocities (V_s) profiles for sites A, B and C

Soil profile A is located close to the site of the Down-hole test (CH-1) (ITSAK Equipment and Instrumentation Upgrade project, 2002-2006) and the existing 1D cross section with code name CS-4, where in situ and laboratory geotechnical surveys were also made available. Soil profiles B and C are located close to the existing 1D cross sections with code names CS-7 and CS-1 respectively. Profiles A, B and C are also close to the sites where array measurements of microtremors with code names M-2, M-1 and M-3 respectively were performed (Figure 7.2). The average geophysical and geotechnical characteristics of the finally adopted soil profiles are presented in Annex A.

All soil profiles refer to ground type C according to EC8 classification with an average depth varying from 142.0m (Soil Profile C) to 180.0m (Soil profile B). Knowing, however, that the liquefaction susceptibility in the port area is rather high, they could be also classified as ground type S according to EC8. The evaluation of liquefaction for the selected soil profiles is presented in section 7.4.1.

7.3 Seismic hazard scenarios for the Port of Thessaloniki

Two different seismic scenarios are defined in this study, the standard seismic design scenario and an extreme scenario corresponding to return periods of $T_m=475$ years and $T_m=4975$ years, respectively. To perform the site response analyses a target spectrum for seismic bedrock conditions ($V_s=700-800$ m/s) and a suite of acceleration time histories are needed.

For the 475 years scenario, the target spectrum is defined based on the disaggregation of the probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (SRM-LIFE 2003-2007; Papaioannou 2004). This study, conducted few years ago in the frame of the microzonation study of Thessaloniki, has shown that the most significant contribution to seismic hazard for Thessaloniki port is associated with the Anthemountas fault system (i.e. a normal fault) regardless of the return period. In particular, for the 475 years scenario, the maximum annual exceedance probability for a certain PGA value with a moment magnitude M_w of 5.7 and an epicentral distance R_{epi} of 14.6 km was provided. For the 4975 years scenario, an extreme rupture scenario breaking along the whole Anthemountas fault zone with a characteristic magnitude M_w of 7.0, close to the maximum magnitude of the seismic source, was assumed. Input data regarding the Anthemountas fault were taken from the Greek Database of Seismogenic Sources GreDaSS (Caputo et al. 2012). The R_{jb} distance (i.e. the closest distance to the surface projection of the rupture zone) and the rupture distance R_{rup} (i.e. the closest distance to rupture zone) are estimated as 5.0 km and 10.0 km for the 475 years scenario while they are both taken as 5.0 km for the 4975 years scenario.

In addition to magnitude and distance, both hazard scenarios include an error term ϵ (which measures the number of standard deviations of logarithmic residuals σ to be accounted for in a GMPE) that is responsible for an appreciable proportion of spectral ordinates. The contribution from ϵ grows with the return period (Bommer and Acevedo 2004). Thus, the median spectral values plus 0.5 and 1 standard deviation are considered for the 475 years and the 4975 years scenarios respectively. This is also in line with the earthquake scenarios selected in Akkar et al. (2014) to generically represent the moderate seismicity (median + 0.5 σ for a M_w 6 event) and high seismicity (median + 1 σ for a M_w 7 event) regions in Europe. The median spectra plus the corresponding

standard deviations defined based on the ground motion prediction equation (GMPE) proposed by Akkar and Bommer (2010) are selected as the target spectra for the 475 years and the 4975 years respectively, since they describe better both hazard scenarios in Thessaloniki port area (Pitilakis et al. 2016).

A set of fifteen accelerograms are selected from the European Strong-Motion Database (Table 7.5) for the 475 years scenario. They are all referring to rock type or stiff soils (ground types A and B according to EC8) with moment magnitude (M_w) and epicentral distance R that range between $5.5 < M_w < 6.5$ and $0 < R < 45 \text{ km}$ respectively. The primary selection criterion is the average acceleration spectra of the set to be of minimal "epsilon" (Baker and Cornell 2005) at the period range of $0.00 < T < 2.00 \text{ sec}$ with respect to the corresponding 5% damped median plus 0.5 standard deviations Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum. The optimization procedure is performed using REXEL software (Iervolino et al. 2010) that allows obtaining combinations of accelerograms, which on average are compatible to the reference spectrum. Figure 7.4 depicts the mean elastic response spectrum of the records in comparison with the corresponding median plus 0.5 standard deviations Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum for the 475 years scenario. As shown in the figure, a good match between the two spectra is achieved.

Table 7.5. List of earthquake records used for the dynamic analyses for the 475 years scenario

Earthquake Name	Date	M_w	Fault Mechanism	Epicentral Distance [km]	PGA [m/s^2]	EC8 Site class	Waveform ID
<i>Umbria Marche (aftershock)</i>	10/6/1997	5.5	normal	5	1.838	A	651
<i>Valnerina</i>	9/19/1979	5.8	normal	5	1.510	A	242
<i>SE of Tirana</i>	1/9/1988	5.9	thrust	7	4.037	A	3802
<i>Lazio Abruzzo (aftershock)</i>	5/11/1984	5.5	normal	15	1.411	A	990
<i>Valnerina</i>	9/19/1979	5.8	normal	5	2.012	A	242
<i>Kozani</i>	5/13/1995	6.5	normal	17	2.039	A	6115
<i>Friuli (aftershock)</i>	9/15/1976	6	thrust	12	1.339	A	149
<i>Umbria Marche</i>	9/26/1997	5.7	normal	23	1.645	A	763
<i>Friuli (aftershock)</i>	9/15/1976	6	thrust	14	2.586	B	134
<i>Patras</i>	7/14/1993	5.6	strike slip	9	3.337	B	1932
<i>Kalamata</i>	9/13/1986	5.9	normal	11	2.670	B	414
<i>Umbria Marche 2</i>	9/26/1997	6	normal	11	5.138	B	594
<i>Montenegro (aftershock)</i>	5/24/1979	6.2	thrust	17	1.708	B	229
<i>Kefallinia island</i>	1/23/1992	5.6	thrust	14	2.223	B	6040
<i>Ano Liosia</i>	9/7/1999	6	normal	14	2.159	B	1714

Figure 7.4. Average elastic response spectrum of the input motions in comparison with the corresponding median plus 0.5 standard deviations Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum for the 475 years scenario

For the 4975 years scenario the selection of real records to fit the median plus one standard deviation Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum that corresponds to the extreme event was not possible as records were not available. Thus, synthetic accelerograms to fit the median plus one standard deviation Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum are computed with SeismoMatch code starting from a set of recorded waveforms. SeismoMatch is an application capable of adjusting earthquake accelerograms to match a specific target response spectrum, using the wavelets algorithm proposed by Abrahamson (1992) and Hancock et al. (2006). This procedure is supported recently by Grant and Diaferia (2012) who have shown that spectrum matching does not seem to lead to significant bias in structural analysis results. The matching period range was adjusted as $0.05 < T < 2.00$ sec and the required tolerance was set equal to 0.3. Table 7.6 presents the characteristics of the ten real records used to derive the synthetic motions obtained from SHARE database (www.share-eu.org). These are referring to rock and stiff soils (ground types A and B according to EC8) with $M_w > 6.5$, $0 < R < 60$ km and $PGA > 0.4g$. Finally, Figure 7.5 presents the target spectrum, i.e. median plus one standard deviation Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum for the 4975 years scenario, and the corresponding matched spectra for the considered records.

Table 7.6. List of earthquake records used for the dynamic analyses for the 4975 years scenario

Earthquake Name	Date	M_w	Fault Mechanism	Epicentral Distance [km]	PGA [m/s^2]	EC8 Site class	Waveform ID
<i>Cape Mendocino</i>	25/04/1992	7.01	Reverse	4.51	6.499	B	NGA_828
<i>Northridge-01</i>	17/01/1994	6.69	Reverse	8.48	9.161	B	NGA_1004
<i>Loma Prieta</i>	18/10/1989	6.93	Reverse-Oblique	7.17	6.315	B	NGA_753
<i>Tabas</i>	16/09/1978	7.35	Oblique	57.00	10.174	B	ESMD_60
<i>Chi-Chi, Taiwan</i>	20/09/1999	7.62	Reverse-Oblique	32.67	8.059	B	NGA_1197
<i>Duzce, Turkey</i>	36505	7.10	Strike-Slip	27.17	8.715	B	T-NSMP_1596
<i>South Iceland</i>	17/06/2000	6.57	Strike-Slip	15.00	5.536	A	ESMD_381
<i>Kobe, Japan</i>	16/01/1995	6.90	Strike-Slip	8.70	4.997	B	NGA_1111
<i>Manjil, Iran</i>	20/06/1990	7.37	Strike-Slip	40.43	5.048	B	NGA_1633
<i>Hyogo - Ken Nanbu</i>	16/01/1995	6.90	Strike-Slip	16.60	8.206	-	C&F_956

Figure 7.5. Target median plus one standard deviation Akkar and Bommer (2010) spectrum for the 4975 years scenario and matched spectra for the considered earthquake records

7.4 Site response analyses for the selected seismic scenarios

Detailed one-dimensional (1D) nonlinear (NL) site response analyses including also the potential for liquefaction are carried out for the three soil profiles A, B, and C (Figure 7.3 and Annex A) using as input motions at the seismic bedrock the ones estimated for the 475 years and 4975 years seismic scenarios. The numerical code Cyclic1D (Elgamal et al. 2015) is used for the site response analyses computations. All models assume vertical propagating SH waves from the bedrock to the surface.

To investigate the impact of the uncertainty in the shear wave velocity (V_s) profiles, the analyses are performed for the geotechnical models for the three sites, considering except for the basic V_s model, upper-range and lower-range models utilizing a logarithmic standard deviation for the V_s profile equal to 0.2. In particular, three runs are performed for each soil profile and input motion considering the base-case model and the base-case ± 1 logarithmic standard deviation models (i.e. 45 analyses for the 475 years scenario and 30 analyses for the 4975 years scenario). In Annex B the variation of PGA, horizontal and vertical PGD, maximum shear strain, effective confinement and excess pore water pressure with depth are presented for each analysis.

7.4.1 Assessment of liquefaction potential

For the evaluation of the liquefaction potential, a thorough understanding of the site conditions, soil stratigraphy, material properties and their variability as well as the spatial extent of potentially liquefiable layers need to be developed. Investigations required for this purpose should as a minimum include the execution of either in situ Standard Penetration Tests (SPT) or Cone Penetration Tests (CPT) to characterize the soil conditions. Thus, before the onset of the detailed liquefaction assessment using Cyclic1D, a preliminary evaluation of the liquefaction potential to identify the layers susceptible to liquefy, that is more analytically presented in Annex A, is performed according to EC8, NCEER 1997, [Robertson and Wride \(1998\)](#) and [Seed et al. \(2003\)](#).

By taking into account the guidelines of EC8 (see Chapter 2) as well as the available geotechnical information of the port (Figure 7.2) the liquefaction potential of the subsoil layers at soil profiles A and C where SPT and laboratory data were made available (Table 7.3) has been quantitatively evaluated. For soil profile A, the liquefiable soil formations were found at depths $z=-9.0\div 11.0\text{m}$, $z=-14.0\div 20.0\text{m}$ and $z=-26.5\div 36.0\text{m}$, while for soil profile C at depths $z=-4.0\div 20.0\text{m}$, which are basically silty/clayey sands and non-plastic silts with low values of N_{SPT} .

According to the guidelines of [Robertson and Wride \(1998\)](#) and NCEER 97 (see Chapter 2), liquefaction potential was evaluated in the position of boreholes B-3, B-70 and B-71 where CPT data were available (see Table 7.3). All these boreholes are located close to the selected soil profile C. Liquefiable layers are found at several depths ($z=-4.4\div 6.8\text{m}$, $z=-7.6\div 7.8\text{m}$, $z=-9.2\text{m}$, $z=-16.6\text{m}$, $z=-17.2\div 17.4\text{m}$ and $z=-20.0\text{m}$) but not greater than twenty meters from the ground surface.

In order to evaluate the potential of liquefaction of the very loose fine-grained soil layers found in soil profile A, the liquefaction susceptibility criteria proposed by [Seed et al. \(2003\)](#) were applied for the fine-grained soil layers of profile A. Potentially liquefiable soil formations are found at depths $z=-4.0\div 5.0\text{m}$ and $z=-6.0\div 9.0\text{m}$.

Based on the preliminary evaluation of the liquefaction potential and the available in situ and laboratory data, Cyclic1D is used to perform the NL site-response analyses including liquefaction for the considered soil profiles and seismic scenarios. The finite element formulation implemented in Cyclic1D is based on a fully coupled solid-fluid approach (known as u-p formulation) (e.g. Chan 1988). The liquefaction model employed (Parra 1996; Yang 2000) was developed within the framework of multi-yield-surface plasticity (e.g. Prevost 1985). The liquefiable soil formations considered were found at depths $z=-2.0\div 11.0\text{m}$, $z=-15.0\div 20.0\text{m}$ and $z=-27.0\div 36.0\text{m}$ for soil profile A, at depths $z=-3.0\div 14.0\text{m}$ for soil profile B and at depths $z=-5.0\div 20.0\text{m}$ for soil profile C. The granular soils (e.g. sands, gravels, non-plastic silts) that are not susceptible to significant pore pressure build-up are simulated using an elastic-plastic material in which a confinement-dependent shear response is considered. For the clay/rock materials an elastic-plastic material is considered where shear behaviour is insensitive to the confinement change.

7.4.2 Indicative site response analysis results for the selected seismic scenarios

The results of the NL site response analysis (fully presented in Annex B) indicate that liquefaction is evident for all soil profiles and scenarios. However, for the extreme scenario, the liquefiable layers are larger and extended to greater depths (up to 35.0m, e.g. see Figure 7.6 left). Among the three representative soil profiles, liquefaction effects are shown to be more pronounced in profile A. Large variability in the computed permanent displacements is shown for the different seismic input motions (e.g. see Figure 7.6 right). Generally, low-frequency input motions increase the accumulation of lateral deformations and settlements. The computed maximum horizontal displacement values (resulting from lateral spreading) when considering the basic geotechnical models are 4.5 cm and 18.6 cm for the 475 and 4975 years seismic scenarios respectively, while the corresponding values for the vertical displacements (that refer to settlements resulting from the reconsolidation of the liquefied or partially liquefied soil) are 4.8 cm and 11.0 cm.

Figure 7.6. Variation of effective confinement (left) and settlement with depth (right) for soil profile A for the 475 years scenario (top) and the 4975 years scenario (bottom)

7.5 Scenario-based seismic risk assessment of Thessaloniki port buildings due to ground shaking & liquefaction

The scenario-based risk assessment of Thessaloniki port buildings due to ground shaking and liquefaction is performed taking into account the potential physical damages and corresponding losses of the different building typologies of the port (i.e. low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses). The low-code RC frame buildings are examined using the fragility surfaces developed in Chapter 6 due to the combined effect of ground shaking and liquefaction, while the vulnerability for the steel light frame warehouses is assessed using appropriate fragility models for ground shaking from the literature and the fragility curves developed in Chapter 5 due to liquefaction-induced differential displacements.

The risk assessment is performed for the 475 and 4975 years scenarios based on the NL site-response analyses. The results from response analyses of soil profiles A, B or C are considered in the risk assessment analysis, depending on the proximity of each component to the location of the three soil profiles. In particular, for the low-code RC frame buildings, the numerically calculated PGA values at the ground surface as well as the PGD (vector of the horizontal and vertical displacements) values at the ground

surface from the total analysis cases for each soil profile (i.e. 45 analyses for the 475 years scenario and 30 analyses for the 4975 years scenario) are considered to directly evaluate their vulnerability due to ground shaking and liquefaction, using the proposed fragility surfaces in terms of PGA_{ff} and PGD.

For the steel light frame warehouses, first their potential damages due to ground shaking are estimated using the fragility functions for ground shaking proposed by HAZUS (NIBS 2004) in terms of PGA considering again the calculated PGA values at the ground surface from the total analysis cases. Afterwards, considering the numerically calculated PGD (vector of the horizontal and vertical displacements) values at the ground surface from the total analysis cases for each soil profile and the proposed relationship (Figure 6.26) between the maximum differential displacement vector and PGD, the maximum differential displacements vector are estimated for each analysis. Thus, the potential damages to steel light frame warehouses are also evaluated using the proposed fragility curves due to liquefaction-induced differential displacements (vector). Finally, the combined damages for the steel light frame warehouses are estimated by combining the damage state probabilities due to the liquefaction (P_L) and ground shaking (P_{GS}), based on the assumption that damage due to ground shaking is independent and not affect the damage due to liquefaction (NIBS 2004). Thus, the combined probability (P_{COMBi}) of exceeding a given damage limit state i is given by the following equation:

$$P_{COMBi}[LS \geq LS_i] = P_L[LS \geq LS_i] + P_{GS}[LS \geq LS_i] - P_L[LS \geq LS_i] \times P_{GS}[LS \geq LS_i] \quad (7.1)$$

where LS_i is the damage limit state i .

Once the probabilities of exceeding the specified DS are estimated, a median ± 1 standard deviation damage index d_m is evaluated, to quantify the structural losses as the ratio of cost of repair to cost of replacement taking values from 0: no damage (cost of repair equals 0) to 1: complete damage (cost of repair equals the cost of replacement). It can be mathematically expressed as follows:

$$d_{mj} = \sum_{i=1}^4 P_{ij} \cdot d_i \quad (7.2)$$

where d_{mj} is the damage index (taking values from 0: no damage to 1: complete damage) corresponding to seismic intensity level j , P_{ij} are the discrete damage probabilities for each damage state and d_i stands for the damage index at each of the considered damage states.

The last term (i.e. d_i) in the equation was taken from the study of Kappos et al. (2006) for the RC buildings (equal to 0.05, 0.20, 0.45 and 0.80 for the LS1, LS2, LS3 and LS4 respectively) and from HAZUS (NIBS 2004) for the steel light frame warehouses (equal to 0.08, 0.275, 0.6 and 0.90 for the LS1, LS2, LS3 and LS4 respectively). Due to the fact that the cost of the RC and steel (including the infills) structural systems totals less than

the cost of a (new) building, which also includes non-structural members, the damage indices are multiplied with a reductive coefficient, i.e. 0.33 for low-rise and mid-rise RC frame buildings or 0.38 for RC buildings with more than 5 storeys, and 0.5 for steel buildings, to derive the final damage index. A weighted loss index (WLI) is finally calculated for the buildings to weight the damage index with respect to the built area. The spatial distribution of the estimated losses for buildings for the design and the extreme scenarios are illustrated in Figure 7.7 and Figure 7.8 respectively.

Figure 7.7. Spatial distribution of the losses of Thessaloniki port's buildings for the 475 years scenario

Figure 7.8. Spatial distribution of the losses of Thessaloniki port's buildings for the 4975 years scenario

The spatial distribution of the estimated losses for port buildings (Figure 7.7 and Figure 7.8) indicates that a non-negligible percentage of them are expected to suffer significant losses (higher than moderate). The median values of this percentage range from 4% for the design scenario (475 years scenario) to 20% for the extreme scenario (4975 years scenario). This is expectable as all buildings were constructed with low or no seismic code provisions. Among the considered building typologies, the RC structures appear to present less losses compared to the steel systems.

7.6 Conclusions

A scenario-based risk assessment analysis was performed for the critical buildings of the Port of Thessaloniki exposed to the earthquake-induced hazards, i.e. ground shaking and liquefaction. The vulnerability assessment for the low-code RC frame buildings was performed using the fragility surfaces developed in Chapter 6 due to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, while for the steel light frame warehouses was assessed using appropriate fragility models for ground shaking from the literature and the fragility curves developed in Chapter 5 due to liquefaction-induced differential displacements. The seismic risk of Thessaloniki port buildings was then assessed for two different seismic hazard scenarios, the design seismic scenario and an extreme seismic scenario corresponding to a return period of 475 years and 4975 years respectively. NL site-specific response analyses including also the potential for liquefaction were conducted for three representative soil profiles using as input motions at the seismic bedrock the ones estimated for the two seismic scenarios. It has been shown that the RC structures appear to present less losses compared to the steel systems.

In this chapter the applicability of the proposed methodological frameworks and the respective fragility curves and surfaces presented in Chapters 5 and 6 was presented. It has been shown that they can be adapted within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the vulnerability and subsequently the risk of buildings exposed to earthquake-induced ground shaking and liquefaction. Stakeholders can use them to evaluate efficiently the risk to their own structures and take appropriate decisions to reduce their risk and increase their resilience. Finally, it should be noted that in areas with high liquefaction potential where no site response analysis can be conducted due to the lack of geotechnical data, the fragility curves for the low-code RC frame buildings due to combined ground shaking and liquefaction in terms of rock outcropping peak ground acceleration or peak ground velocity, proposed in chapter 6, can also be used to directly evaluate the vulnerability of these building typologies. Future work should also address fragility analysis (following the methodology in chapter 6) taking into account other structural systems, such as steel light frame warehouses and URM buildings.

Chapter 8

Conclusions and Perspectives

8.1 Summary of findings and contributions

Earthquake-induced hazards, such as ground shaking, liquefaction and tsunami, are often catastrophic and attract global attention, as they are able to cause tremendous direct and indirect losses in terms of fatalities and infrastructure (**Chapter 2**). Moving toward a safer and more resilient society requires efficient risk assessment tools that could be utilised by emergency planners, lifeline operators and stakeholders to establish integrated risk mitigation strategies on a regional or site-specific scale. Thus, the quantification of both hazard and vulnerability of the elements at risk is required (**Chapter 3**). Over the years several hazard assessment studies have been conducted, while the last two decades vulnerability assessment has also emerged as an important research field. However, most of the existing studies provide fragility curves due to ground shaking and do not focus on assessing physical vulnerability of buildings and infrastructures due to other earthquake-induced hazards (i.e. tsunami and liquefaction). Only recently some vulnerability assessment methodologies due to other earthquake-induced hazards have been developed but they are principally based on empirical data and/or expert judgment, as field reconnaissance of the damage caused by earthquake-induced hazards has been standard practice for many years. In this context, their general application is restricted as they are highly specific to a particular seismo-tectonic, geomorphological and built environment.

Stemming from the general lack of methodological frameworks to assess building vulnerability to the earthquake-induced ground shaking, liquefaction and tsunami, one of the most significant contributions of the present research was the proposition and quantification of analytical methodologies to estimate the physical vulnerability and subsequently the risk of specific building typologies subjected to tsunami forces (**Chapter 4**), liquefaction-induced differential permanent displacements (**Chapter 5**) as well as combined ground shaking and liquefaction taking into account SSI (**Chapter 6**). Vulnerability was defined through probabilistic fragility and vulnerability curves or

fragility surfaces (when it is deemed appropriate) which allow for direct implementation within a probabilistic risk assessment framework.

Inspired from the methods used for the development of seismic fragility curves for ordinary buildings, in **Chapter 4** an analytical methodology was proposed to derive tsunami fragility and vulnerability curves for buildings subjected to tsunami forces. Typical buildings representative of typologies found in ordinary port areas in South Europe like the port of Thessaloniki, namely low-code RC buildings and steel light frame warehouses subjected to tsunami forces were considered. Regarding the studied RC buildings, they were classified according to their structural system (i.e. MRF, dual), their height (i.e. low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise), as well as the seismic design level (i.e. the 1959 Greek seismic code corresponding to low level of seismic design). Moreover in order to investigate the impact of masonry infills on the response of RC buildings due to tsunami forces, these typologies were also analysed considering regularly contributed infills along the height of the structures. Fixed-base conditions were assumed for all models in the analysis, while far-source generated tsunami was considered assuming that the structure did not sustain any initial damage prior to the tsunami due to ground shaking. Each structure was subjected to buoyant, hydrostatic and hydrodynamic forces combined with forces due to debris, all of which constitute tsunami forces, determined based on FEMA P646 recommendations and proper engineering judgment. The tsunami forces were then directly applied as input time-variant static loads to the nonlinear structural models for gradually increasing inundation depths and the structure's response in terms of material strain for the different statically applied tsunami loads was estimated. To minimize the uncertainties related to the definition of damage limit states, tsunami nonlinear static time-history analyses were performed, and appropriate tsunami capacity curves were derived for the considered structures. Structural limit states were defined on tsunami capacity curves in terms of threshold values of material strain to account for the flexural structural failure. Except for flexural failure, failure due to shear (the attainment of shear capacity in a structural member) was also considered and the structure's demand in terms of shear forces was estimated. Various sources of uncertainty with respect to the structural capacity and the demand defined in terms of material strain and shear forces were considered. Vulnerability was then assessed through probabilistic tsunami fragility curves, which describe the probability of exceeding each limit state, and tsunami vulnerability curves, which provide a unique damage index for each level of tsunami inundation depth to assess the expected direct losses in normalised cost terms, as a function of tsunami inundation depth.

It was shown that the high-rise RC buildings present lower vulnerability to tsunami compared to the low-rise ones, which is in accordance with empirical observations. In

addition, the low-rise and mid-rise infilled models were found more vulnerable compared to the bare frames. This trend also holds true for the high-rise MRF for the exceedance of none to slight and moderate damage. In contrast, when extensive or complete damage of the high-rise MRF structures is anticipated, the bare frame is expected to suffer larger damages compared to the infilled one. Moreover, the low-rise dual models were found more vulnerable compared to the MRFs, which is related to the concentration of large tsunami forces to shear walls. Regarding the fragility curves for the warehouse they were generally similar to the ones of the low-rise and mid-rise MRF RC buildings, and the difference between the damage states was not so large indicating that once yielding occurs, the structure very rapidly attains the post-yield limit states. It was also shown that the shear failure is the prevailing failure mechanism for all low-code MRF RC buildings with bare frames, regardless of their height as well as for the infilled high-rise MRF and low-rise dual models. The consideration of masonry infills may have a significant impact on the response and finally on the failure mechanism of the structures (i.e. flexural or shear). Comparisons made between the numerical tsunami fragility curves and the few available empirical ones for RC and steel structures were generally satisfactory considering the important uncertainties and scatter of the empirical data.

The proposed tsunami fragility curves for the low-code RC buildings could be applicable to typical RC buildings designed according to the pre-1980 codes in Greece and Southern Europe, considered as “low-code” structures, as the building typologies used in this study are commonly found in these countries (Kappos et al. 2003). Moreover, the suggested curves for the representative warehouse could be applicable to typical port steel light frame warehouses worldwide, as this is a common typology in ports around the world (NIBS 2004; Green et al. 2011). Knowing the expected tsunami height from an appropriate tsunami hazard analysis and the characteristics of the exposed structures (geometrical features, material strength etc.), stakeholders could select and make use of the appropriate set of tsunami fragility curves within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the physical vulnerability and subsequently evaluate the risk to their own structures, and take appropriate measures to reduce their risk.

Except from tsunami hazard, soil liquefaction hazard has also been widely recognised as being one of the principal earthquake hazards resulting to significant economic and societal losses. However, research in the vulnerability assessment and quantitative evaluation of the expected physical damages and losses to building structures is rather limited. In **Chapter 5** an analytical methodology for the vulnerability and risk assessment of buildings with shallow flexible foundation system subjected to liquefaction-induced differential permanent ground displacements (settlements and lateral

movements) was proposed based on the uncoupled numerical approach. It is noted that the differential ground displacements become the major cause of damage to buildings (Bird et al. 2005; 2006), as the absolute (uniform) displacements on their own are often insufficient to describe the main damage patterns of the structures. Typical low-code RC frame buildings and steel light frame warehouses were considered. It was assumed that failure takes place on the building's structural elements and the load bearing capacity of the foundation is adequately designed to resist the liquefaction induced deformation, while possible initial damage to the building's structural members (e.g. in terms of stiffness and strength degradation) due to ground shaking was ignored. A series of nonlinear static time-history analyses of each building typology was carried out considering different gradually increasing differential displacement patterns applied as quasi-static loads directly at its supports (footings). In particular, either only the vertical component of the differential displacement (i.e. to represent settlements in level ground) or the horizontal differential displacement with a vertical component (i.e. to represent lateral spreading in gently sloping ground) were considered. Different damage mechanisms were examined including a flexural damage of the building members and a shear failure of the columns. Appropriate damage limit states were defined in terms of threshold values of material strain to account for the flexural structural failure based on the existing literature (Crowley et al. 2004; Bird et al. 2005; 2006; Fotopoulou and Pitilakis 2017) and expert judgement. Vulnerability was assessed through probabilistic fragility curves, which describe the probability of exceeding each limit state, and vulnerability curves, as a function of liquefaction-induced differential displacement (settlement or vector). Various sources of uncertainty associated with the structural building capacity, the definition of damage limit states and the deformation demand were explicitly considered in the fragility analysis. The reliability of the proposed fragility curves was verified through their comparison with corresponding analytical fragility curves from the literature and field reconnaissance data from past events which caused extensive liquefaction and differential displacements.

It was shown that low-code RC buildings on isolated footings subjected to settlements are expected to suffer larger damages compared to the ones where the maximum differential displacement has also a horizontal component (lateral spreading). In addition, the building height is also an important parameter that may significantly affect the structural performance. In general, the high-rise low-code MRF RC buildings were more vulnerable compared to the low- and mid-rise ones, especially for the lateral spreading cases. It was also observed that the warehouse is by far less vulnerable than the MRF RC buildings. Finally, it was seen that shear failure would be the dominant damage

mechanism only for the considered low-code high-rise MRF building subjected to lateral spreading.

At a subsequent step, in **Chapter 6** the complex issue of combined damages due to ground shaking and soil liquefaction to individual buildings was studied. An analytical methodology was proposed for the vulnerability and risk assessment of buildings with shallow flexible foundation system resting on liquefiable soils (at level ground and slope conditions) subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, based on a fully coupled numerical approach taking into account SSI. In particular, the direct one-step approach, which accounts simultaneously for inertial and kinematic interaction schemes, where the soil and the structure are modelled and analysed as a single system was implemented considering soil nonlinearity introduced by soil liquefaction. Typical low-code RC frame buildings of various heights (low-rise, mid-rise and high-rise) with flexible foundation system and three typical soil profiles susceptible to liquefaction at level ground conditions and slope conditions (5% grade) were considered for the analysis. Inelastic force-based formulations were implemented for the two-dimensional with three degrees of freedom nonlinear beam-column frame element modelling, while elastoplastic behaviour was considered for the soil. A fully coupled (u-P) formulation, capable of simulating permanent shear-strain accumulation in clean medium-dense cohesionless soils during liquefaction and dilation due to increased cyclic shear stiffness and strength, was employed. The soil constitutive behaviour was based on the framework of multi-surface (nested-surface) plasticity. Full bond between the structure's foundation and the soil nodes was assumed. The earthquake demand was determined based on the selection of real earthquake records that cover a wide range of seismic input motions in terms of amplitude, frequency content and significant duration. Each seismic input motion was applied to the base of the soil model (bedrock). Two-dimensional incremental dynamic analysis (IDA) of the nonlinear SSI systems was conducted for the estimation of the buildings response and the fragility function parameters. Furthermore, a second set of incremental dynamic analyses was performed considering slope with a 5% grade to better examine the contribution of liquefaction-induced lateral spreading. Overall, a total of 3240 nonlinear dynamic analyses were performed. It was also noted that the main shortcoming of this approach is the high computational cost that becomes more significant for highly non-linear problems. Appropriate damage limit states were defined in terms of maxISD to account for the flexural structural failure according to numerical analysis, the available literature (Ghobarah 2004; Petridis and Pitilakis 2018; Pitilakis et al. 2014d) and proper engineering judgement. In the fragility analysis several uncertainties were involved with respect to the structural capacity, the seismic demand and the definition of the damage limit states.

Vulnerability was finally assessed through probabilistic fragility (or vulnerability) curves as a function of PGA_{rock} or PGV_{rock} and coupled fragility surfaces as function of both PGA_{ff} and maximum PGD vector at surface or both PGV and maximum PGD vector at surface. It is noted that the use of the former fragility functions is suggested when the local soil conditions, surface geology, soil and topographic amplification are not known, as they are directly included in the fragility analysis, while the use of the latter ones is justified for site-specific applications on critical buildings where adequate data from field measurements and/or detailed numerical analysis are available. In order to enhance the reliability and robustness of the proposed fragility curves and surfaces, they were compared with corresponding literature curves as well as field observations from past earthquakes which caused extensive liquefaction and lateral spreading. The comparisons made were generally satisfactory considering the important uncertainties involved. A major contribution of the present research was also the proposition of predictive relationships between the maximum differential permanent ground displacements (settlement or vector) and the maximum permanent ground displacements (PGD) vector at surface bellow buildings with shallow flexible foundations resting on soils at level ground or slope conditions subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction.

In general, it was shown that the total height of the building may considerably influence its vulnerability to the earthquake-induced ground shaking and liquefaction. More specifically, the low-code low-rise RC frame building suffers more structural damages compared to the mid- and high-rise ones. This may be attributed to the fact that as the height of the building increases, the building tends to behave as a rigid body and is prone to tilt excessively or topple, without sustaining extensive structural damages. This trend is also due to the increased confinement (induced by weight increase) and subsequent increase in resistance against strength loss, which reduces slightly the contribution of shear strains under the building foundation. It is noted that at many liquefied sites after the 1999 Adapazari earthquake, larger settlements and tilting were observed for taller and heavier buildings (Borozan et al 2017). The fact that the low-rise buildings are more vulnerable compared to the mid- and high-rise ones may also be due to that no large differential displacements appear to the foundation level of the building and that the major influence on the building performance is attributed to the ground motion characteristics, also supported by Millen et al (2018). It is noted that the low-rise MRF RC frame buildings are more vulnerable to ground shaking than high-rise ones (Kappos et al. 2003). This is also in accordance with field observations; e.g. in the 1990 Luzon (Philippines) Earthquakes most of the damaged buildings on liquefied sites were two to four stories and shallow-founded (Tokimatsu et al. 1994).

Moreover, it was observed that the typical low-code RC frame buildings at slope conditions were found more vulnerable compared to the corresponding ones at level ground conditions, which is expected due to the occurrence of lateral spreading. This is also in accordance with field observations, as lateral spreading involves large lateral ground movement as well as substantial differential displacements in the direction of spreading, resulting in large extensional deformation and subsequently more structural damages.

Finally, in an effort to identify as accurately as possible the site specific response and subsequently estimate the risk and increase the resilience of the buildings of Thessaloniki port, one of the largest Greek seaports, a scenario-based risk assessment analysis due to the combined effect of ground shaking and liquefaction was conducted. Through this application the applicability of the proposed methodological frameworks and the respective fragility curves and surfaces presented in **Chapter 5** and **Chapter 6** respectively was verified. The seismic risk of Thessaloniki port buildings was performed taking into account the potential physical damages and corresponding losses of the port buildings assessed for two different seismic hazard scenarios, the design seismic scenario and an extreme seismic scenario corresponding to a return period of 475 years and 4975 years respectively. Nonlinear site-specific response analyses including also the potential for liquefaction were conducted for three representative soil profiles using as input motions at the seismic bedrock the ones estimated for the two seismic scenarios. It was shown that the RC structures of Thessaloniki Port present lower losses compared to the steel systems.

In general, it was shown that the proposed fragility models can be adapted within a probabilistic risk assessment framework to assess the vulnerability and subsequently the risk of typical low-code RC buildings and steel light frame warehouses in Greece and in Southern Europe exposed to earthquake-induced ground shaking and liquefaction. Stakeholders could use them to evaluate efficiently the risk to their own structures and take appropriate measures to reduce their risk and increase their resilience. It was also noted that in areas with high liquefaction potential where no site response analysis could be conducted due to the lack of geotechnical data, the fragility curves for the low-code RC frame buildings due to combined ground shaking and liquefaction in terms of PGA_{rock} or PGV_{rock} , proposed in **Chapter 6**, could also be used to directly evaluate the vulnerability of these building typologies.

8.2 Limitations and recommendations for future research

The research conducted in the present thesis has certain limitations and should be extended through additional work in the following areas:

- In the proposed tsunami vulnerability assessment methodology, tsunami loading is determined based on FEMA P646 recommendations and proper engineering judgment. Future work should address tsunami vulnerability assessment taking into account time series of tsunami forces (as a function of inundation depth and flow velocity) or different combination of tsunami forces as well as other parameters involved, which have not been considered in this analysis, like scouring effects, SSI and the potential structural damages caused from prior ground shaking.
- The methodology proposed for the vulnerability assessment of buildings subjected to liquefaction-induced differential displacements, should be extended to take into account the uncertainties in the computation of the differential displacements. It should also be extended to account for potential structural damages induced by prior ground shaking, by still using the uncoupled approach which is far simpler than the fully coupled approach. This could be achieved by using degraded material properties (e.g. reduced Young modulus and concrete and steel compressive strength).
- Future research should also be oriented towards the development of a probabilistic framework for the evaluation of the risk to buildings subjected to combined ground shaking and liquefaction, which also take into account the possibility of soil liquefaction apparition according to the estimated factor of safety against liquefaction.
- It is also suggested to increase the applicability band of the proposed methodological frameworks through the development of supplementary fragility models for other structural typologies (e.g. URM), foundation systems (e.g. piled foundations) and soil conditions. In addition, significant effort should be devoted in fragility analysis taking into account infill walls and their contribution to the building response to both ground shaking and soil liquefaction, as was conducted for the derivation of tsunami fragility curves.
- Future research should also aim at the validation of the proposed fragility models with experimental tests, while large scale laboratory tests in prototype building structures would certainly enhance their reliability and robustness.
- Another important issue that could be addressed in a future study would be the consideration of varying strength and stiffness characteristics of the studied structures within the given building classes (to assess analytically the variability in the capacity ([Iervolino et al. 2004](#)), additional structural configurations as well as other parameters involved, which have not been considered in this thesis, like aging effects on the material properties.
- Investigation of foundation failure during tsunami flow or the effect of soil liquefaction could also be included in future research.

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Annex A

Representative soil profiles of the Port of Thessaloniki

A.1 Geotechnical characteristics of the defined soil profiles of Thessaloniki Port

Table A.1. Geotechnical characteristics of soil profile A

Depth (m)	USCS	V_s (m/sec)	c (kN/m ²)	ϕ (°)	γ_m (kN/m ³)
1.0	SM	300	5	37	18.00
H ₂ O↓ 1.5	SM	270	5	37	18.00
2.0	SM	240	5	32	19.75
4.0	CH/CL	224	10	26	16.34
5.0	CH/CL	211	10	26	16.34
6.0	CH/CL	198	10	26	16.34
9.0	CH/CL	121	10	26	16.34
11.0	SM	115	1	32	19.75
12.0	CL	118	20	23	20.55
14.0	CL	154	20	23	20.55
20.0	SC	274	5	31	20.80
24.0	CL	274	15	30	20.27
26.5	CL	299	15	30	20.09
31.0	SC	375	15	33	20.80
32.0	SC	404	15	30	20.80
36.0	SC	479	15	30	20.80
42.0	CL	558	30	25	19.82
44.0	SC	339	15	36	20.80
45.0	CL	300	26	25	20.81
46.0	CL	260	30	25	20.81
48.0	CL	244	30	25	20.68

50.0	CL	281	30	25	20.68
53.0	CL	453	60	27	19.97
55.5	CL	400	60	27	19.97
56.0	SC	396	-	-	21.21
60.0	SC	447	-	-	21.21
62.0	SW-SM	546	-	-	21.21
64.0	-	682	-	-	21.21
66.0	ML	577	-	-	21.21
68.0	CL	602	-	-	20.67
70.0	CL	562	-	-	20.67
72.0	CL	600	-	-	20.67
73.0	CL	655	-	-	21.16
74.0	CL	710	-	-	21.16
76.0	CL	744	-	-	21.16
78.0	CL	633	-	-	20.98
80.0	CL	627	-	-	20.98
170.0	CL	627			21.00

Table A.2. Geotechnical characteristics of soil profile B

	Depth (m)	USCS	V_s (m/sec)	c (kN/m ²)	Φ (°)	γ_m (kN/m ³)
H ₂ O↓	2.0	SC-CL 60% & SM,GM, GP	225	5	37	18.00
	8.0	ML,SM,ML-OL, SM-ML, SC-SM	180	10	26	18.50
	14.0	CL,SC, SC(SM), CL-ML, CH(MH)	200	20	23	20.00
	20.5	CL,SC, SC(SM), CL-ML, CH(MH)	250	20	23	20.00
	28.0	CL,SC, SC(SM), CL-ML, CH(MH)	350	20	30	20.00
	36.0	CL,SC: 80% SC(SM)	400	30	25	21.00
	48.0	CL: 90% SC(GC)	400	30	25	21.00
	68.0	CL: 90% SC(GC)	450	60	27	21.00
	88.0	CL: 90% SC(GC)	500	60	27	21.00
	108.0	CL: 90% SC(GC)	550	60	27	21.00
	128.0	CL: 90% SC(GC)	600	60	27	21.00
	152.0	CL: 90% SC(GC)	650	60	27	21.00
	176.0	CL: 90% SC(GC)	700	60	27	21.00
	180.0	CL: 90% SC(GC)	750	60	27	21.00

Table A.3. Geotechnical characteristics of soil profile C

	Depth (m)	USCS	V_s (m/sec)	c (kN/m ²)	ϕ (°)	γ_m (kN/m ³)
H ₂ O↓	1.5	SC-CL 60% & SM,GM, GP	225	5	37	18.00
	5.5	SC-CL 60% & SM,GM, GP	225	5	33	20.00
	14.5	ML,SM,ML-OL, SM-ML, SC-SM	200	10	26	18.50
	20.5	CL,SC: 80% SC(SM)	250	20	23	21.00
	30.5	CL,SC: 80% SC(SM)	300	20	30	21.00
	38.5	CL: 90% SC(GC)	500	30	25	21.00
	46.5	CL: 90% SC(GC)	500	30	25	21.00
	66.5	CL: 90% SC(GC)	550	60	27	21.00
	86.5	CL: 90% SC(GC)	600	60	27	21.00
	110.5	CL: 90% SC(GC)	650	60	27	21.00
	138.5	CL: 90% SC(GC)	700	60	27	21.00
	142.5	CL: 90% SC(GC)	750	60	27	21.00

A.2 Liquefaction potential for the defined soil profiles of Thessaloniki Port

In this section, the preliminary evaluation of the liquefaction potential, following the guidelines of EC8, [Robertson and Wride \(1998\)](#) and NCEER 1997 as well as Seed et al. (2003), for the considered soil profiles is presented. Among the three representative soil profiles, liquefaction effects are found to be more pronounced in profile A.

More specifically, following the guidelines of EC8, for the soil profile A the liquefiable soil formations are found at depths $z=-9\div 11\text{m}$, $z=-14\div 20\text{m}$ and $z=-26.5\div 36\text{m}$, for the soil profile B at depths $z=-3\div 14\text{m}$, while for the soil profile C at depths $z=-4\div 20\text{m}$, which are basically silty/clayey sands and non-plastic silts with low values of N_{SPT} . Thus, these soil profiles are categorised to ground type S2 according to EC8 classification. Indicatively, Table A.4 presents the evaluation of "liquefiable" soil layers according to EC8 using SPT data from borehole B-68 (see Table 7.3), located close to the soil profile C, while Table A.5 shows the assessment of liquefaction potential following EC8 guidelines using the data from down-hole DH-1, located close to the soil profile A.

Table A.4. Assessment of "liquefiable" soil layers according to EC8 using SPT of borehole B-68 (soil profile C)

Depth (m)	USCS	γ_m (kN/m ³)	N_{SPT} (m/sec)	Ολική τάση σ_v (kPa)	Ενεργός τάση σ'_v (kPa)	α (g)
4.00	GM-GC	18	9	100.80	59.80	0.52
7.20	ML	17	6	170.40	89.40	0.52
12.00	CL	21	14	274.20	139.20	0.52
18.00	SC	21.5	15	369.45	189.45	0.52

Table A.4. Assessment of "liquefiable" soil layers according to EC8 using SPT of borehole B-68 (soil profile C) continued

Depth (m)	CSR	C_N	C_E	$N_{1,60}$	FC (%)	$CRR_{7,5}$	$CM_{7,0}$	$CRR_{7,0}$	$FS_{7,0}$	Potentially liquefiable
4.00	0.57	1.29	0.90	10	35	0.2	1.30	0.26	0.45	YES
7.20	0.65	1.06	0.90	6	35	0.17	1.30	0.22	0.34	YES
12.00	0.67	0.85	0.90	11	35	0.22	1.30	0.29	0.43	YES
18.00	0.66	0.73	0.90	10	35	0.18	2.30	0.41	0.62	YES

In addition, according to the guidelines of [Robertson and Wride \(1998\)](#) and NCEER 1997, liquefaction potential is evaluated in the position of boreholes B-3, B-70 and B-71, located close to the soil profile C, where CPT data were available (see Table 7.3). Indicatively, the assessment of liquefaction potential using CPT of borehole B-71 is presented in Table A.6. Liquefiable layers for the soil profile C are found at several depths ($z=-4.4\div 6.8\text{m}$, $z=-7.6\div 7.8\text{m}$, $z=-9.2\text{m}$, $z=-16.6\text{m}$, $z=-17.2\div 17.4\text{m}$ and $z=-20.0\text{m}$) but not greater than twenty meters from the ground surface.

Finally, in order to evaluate the potential of liquefaction of the very loose fine-grained soil layers found in soil profile A, the liquefaction susceptibility criteria proposed by [Seed et al. \(2003\)](#) were applied for the fine-grained soil layers of profile A. Thus, potentially liquefiable soil formations for the soil profile A are also found at depths $z=-4.0\div 5.0\text{m}$ and $z=-6.0\div 9.0\text{m}$.

Table A.5. Assessment of liquefaction potential according to EC8 using DH-1 data (soil profile A)

	Depth (m)	USCS	γ_m (kN/m ³)	N_{SPT} (m/sec)	V_s (m/sec)	Ολική τάση σ_v (kPa)	Ενεργός τάση σ'_v (kPa)	α (g)
H ₂ O↓	1.0	SM	18.00	-	300	9.00	9.00	0.34
	1.5	SM	18.00	-	270	22.50	22.50	0.34
	2.0	SM	19.75	11	240	31.94	29.44	0.34
	4.0	CH/CL	16.34	2	224	53.22	38.22	0.34
	5.0	CH/CL	16.34	3	211	77.73	47.73	0.34
	6.0	CH/CL	16.34	3	198	94.07	54.07	0.34
	9.0	CH/CL	16.34	4	121	126.75	66.75	0.34
	11.0	SM	19.75	8	115	171.01	86.01	0.34
	12.0	CL	20.55	9	118	201.03	101.03	0.34
	14.0	CL	20.55	14	154	231.86	116.86	0.34
	20.0	SC	20.80	17	274	346.01	176.01	0.34
	24.0	CL	20.27	17	274	417.75	212.75	0.34
	26.5	CL	20.09	24	299	483.40	245.90	0.34
	31.0	SC	20.80	23	375	555.31	282.81	0.34
	32.0	SC	20.80	-	404	612.51	312.51	0.34
	36.0	SC	20.80	12	479	664.51	339.51	0.34
	42.0	CL	19.82	33	558	765.57	390.57	0.34
	44.0	SC	20.80	19	339	845.83	430.83	0.34
	45.0	CL	20.81	25	300	877.04	447.04	0.34
	46.0	CL	20.81	25	260	897.85	457.85	0.34
	48.0	CL	20.68	25	244	928.93	473.93	0.34
	50.0	CL	20.68	25	281	970.29	495.29	0.34
	53.0	CL	19.97	25	453	1020.93	520.93	0.34
	55.5	CL	19.97	30	400	1075.84	548.34	0.34
	56.0	SC	21.21	-	396	1106.11	563.61	0.34
	60.0	SC	21.21	ΑΡΝΗΣΗ	447	1153.83	588.83	0.34
	62.0	SW-SM	21.21	12	546	1217.46	622.46	0.34
	64.0	-	21.21	-	682	1259.88	644.88	0.34
	66.0	ML	21.21	35	577	1302.30	667.30	0.34
	68.0	CL	20.67	ΑΡΝΗΣΗ	602	1344.18	689.18	0.34
70.0	CL	20.67	-	562	1385.52	710.52	0.34	
72.0	CL	20.67	-	600	1426.86	731.86	0.34	

Table A.5. Assessment of liquefaction potential according to EC8 using DH-1 data (soil profile A) continued

Depth (m)	CSR	C _N	C _E	N _{1,60}	FC (%)	CRR _{7,5}	CM _{7,0}	CRR _{7,0}	FS _{7,0}	Potentially liquefiable
1.0	0.22	3.33	0.90	-	-	-	1.30	-		
1.5	0.22	2.11	0.90	-	-	-	1.30	-		
2.0	0.24	1.84	0.90	18	24	0.30	1.30	0.39	1.61	NO
4.0	0.31	1.62	0.90	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.0	0.36	1.45	0.90	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.0	0.39	1.36	0.90	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.0	0.42	1.22	0.90	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.0	0.44	1.08	0.90	8	45	0.20	1.30	0.26	0.58	YES
12.0	0.45	0.99	0.90	8	64	-	1.30	-	-	-
14.0	0.44	0.93	0.90	12	-	-	1.30	-	-	-
20.0	0.44	0.75	0.90	14	36	0.26	1.30	0.34	0.77	YES
24.0	0.44	0.69	0.90	10	56	-	1.30	-	-	-
26.5	0.44	0.64	0.90	14	74	-	1.30	-	-	-
31.0	0.44	0.59	0.90	12	38	0.28	1.30	0.36	0.83	YES
32.0	0.44	0.57	0.90	4	23	0.12	1.30	0.16	0.36	YES
36.0	0.44	0.54	0.90	6	39	0.18	1.30	0.23	0.53	YES
42.0	0.44	0.51	0.90	15	82	-	1.30	-	-	-
44.0	0.44	0.48	0.90	8	40	0.21	1.30	0.27	0.62	YES
45.0	0.44	0.47	0.90	11	70	-	1.30	-	-	-
46.0	0.44	0.47	0.90	11	52	-	1.30	-	-	-
48.0	0.44	0.46	0.90	-	67	-	1.30	-	-	-
50.0	0.44	0.45	0.90	10	62	-	1.30	-	-	-
53.0	0.44	0.44	0.90	10	86	-	1.30	-	-	-
55.5	0.44	0.43	0.90	12	64	-	1.30	-	-	-
56.0	0.44	0.42	0.90	-	-	-	1.30	-	-	-
60.0	0.44	0.41	0.90	-	-	-	1.30	-	-	-
62.0	0.44	0.40	0.90	4	-	-	1.30	-	-	-
64.0	0.44	0.39	0.90	-	-	-	1.30	-	-	-
66.0	0.44	0.39	0.90	12	-	-	1.30	-	-	-
68.0	0.44	0.38	0.90	-	-	-		-		
70.0	0.44	0.38	0.90	-	-	-		-		
72.0	0.44	0.37	0.90	-	-	-		-		

Table A.6. Assessment of liquefaction potential according to [Robertson and Wride \(1998\)](#) using CPT of borehole B-71 (soil profile C)

Depth (m)	q_c (MPa)	f_s (MPa)	FR (%)	γ (kN/m ³)	σ_{v0} (kPa)	σ'_{v0} (kPa)	Q	F	I_{c-1}	q_{c1NA}	I_{c-2}	q_{c1NB}	I_{c-3}	I_c FINAL
4.2	1.2	53.33	4.44	20.00	81.20	54.71	20.40	4.77	2.88	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	2.88
4.4	2	33.33	1.67	20.00	85.20	56.75	33.70	1.74	2.43	26.50	2.51	QC1NA	IC-2	2.51
6.8	5	60.00	1.20	18.50	131.10	79.11	61.50	1.23	2.13	56.20	2.16	QC1NA	IC-2	2.16
7.0	1.8	40.00	2.22	18.50	134.80	80.85	20.60	2.40	2.69	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	2.69
7.4	0.6	13.33	2.22	18.50	142.20	84.32	5.40	2.91	3.21	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	3.21
7.6	3	80.00	2.67	18.50	145.90	86.06	33.20	2.80	2.57	32.30	2.57	QC1NA	IC-2	2.57
7.8	5.2	60.00	1.15	18.50	149.60	87.80	57.50	1.19	2.15	55.50	2.16	QC1NA	IC-2	2.16
8.0	0.8	73.33	9.17	18.50	153.30	89.54	7.20	11.34	3.46	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	3.46
9.0	0.5	26.67	5.33	18.50	171.80	98.23	3.30	8.13	3.64	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	3.64
9.2	6	80.00	1.33	18.50	175.50	99.96	58.30	1.37	2.18	60.00	2.17	QC1NA	IC-2	2.17
9.4	1.4	80.00	5.71	18.50	179.20	101.70	12.00	6.55	3.14	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	3.14
16.4	3	93.33	3.11	21.00	313.70	167.53	16.03	3.47	2.87	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	2.87
16.6	4.6	93.33	2.03	21.00	317.90	169.77	25.22	2.18	2.59	35.30	2.47	QC1NA	IC-2	2.47
16.8	3	66.67	2.22	21.00	322.10	172.01	15.57	2.49	2.79	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	2.79
17	1.6	53.33	3.33	21.00	326.30	174.25	7.31	4.19	3.19	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	3.19
17.2	4.8	60.00	1.25	21.00	330.50	176.48	25.33	1.34	2.47	36.13	2.34	QC1NA	IC-2	2.34
17.4	6	80.00	1.33	21.00	334.70	178.72	31.70	1.41	2.40	44.88	2.28	QC1NA	IC-2	2.28
17.6	3.5	66.67	1.90	21.00	338.90	180.96	17.47	2.11	2.71	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	2.71
19.0	0.4	13.33	3.33	21.00	368.30	196.63	0.16	42.05	5.12	Q	IC-1	Q	IC-1	5.12
20.0	5.8	20.00	0.34	21.00	389.30	207.82	26.04	0.37	2.20	40.23	2.02	QC1NA	IC-2	2.02

Table A.6. Assessment of liquefaction potential according to [Robertson and Wride \(1998\)](#) using CPT of borehole B-71 (soil profile C) continued

Depth (m)	K_c	K_c FINAL	K_c Descr	q_{c1N} CS	$CRR_{7.5}$	FC	T_{max} (kPa)	T_{ave} (kPa)	CSR	$FS_{7.5}$	$MSF_{7.0}$	$FS_{7.0}$	Pot. Liquef.
4.2	5.46	5.46	NLIQ	111.61	0.21	50.46	43.22	28.09	0.51	0.41	1.19	0.49	NO
4.4	2.84	2.84		75.39	0.12	31.31	46.35	30.13	0.53	0.23	1.19	0.27	YES
6.8	1.58	1.58		88.82	0.15	17.76	66.71	43.36	0.55	0.27	1.19	0.32	YES
7.0	3.89	3.89	NLIQ	80.14	0.13	39.68	69.28	45.03	0.56	0.23	1.19	0.27	NO
7.4	9.42	9.42	NLIQ	51.14	0.09	73.95	71.86	46.71	0.55	0.17	1.19	0.20	NO
7.6	3.17	3.17		102.49	0.18	34.09	74.43	48.38	0.56	0.32	1.19	0.38	YES
7.8	1.57	1.57		87.06	0.14	17.60	76.96	50.02	0.57	0.25	1.19	0.30	YES
8.0	13.42	13.42	NLIQ	96.93	0.17	95.44	76.96	50.02	0.56	0.30	1.19	0.35	NO
9.0	16.70	16.70	NLIQ	55.81	0.10	100.00	86.24	56.05	0.57	0.17	1.19	0.20	NO
9.2	1.59	1.59		95.70	0.16	17.98	86.24	56.05	0.56	0.29	1.19	0.34	YES
9.4	8.44	8.44	NLIQ	101.37	0.18	68.45	88.41	57.47	0.57	0.31	1.19	0.37	NO
16.4	5.40	5.40	NLIQ	86.59	0.14	50.08	123.90	80.54	0.48	0.29	1.19	0.35	NO
16.6	2.64	2.64		93.31	0.16	29.56	124.53	80.94	0.48	0.33	1.19	0.39	YES
16.8	4.72	4.72	NLIQ	73.54	0.12	45.58	125.15	81.34	0.47	0.25	1.19	0.30	NO
17	9.13	9.13	NLIQ	66.73	0.11	72.32	126.38	82.15	0.47	0.23	1.19	0.27	NO
17.2	2.08	2.08		75.22	0.12	24.01	127.01	82.56	0.47	0.26	1.19	0.30	YES
17.4	1.87	1.87		84.15	0.14	21.65	127.63	82.96	0.46	0.29	1.19	0.35	YES
17.6	4.07	4.07	NLIQ	71.16	0.11	41.02	128.81	83.73	0.46	0.25	1.19	0.29	NO
19.0	60.18	60.18	NLIQ	9.70	0.06	100.00	134.00	87.10	0.44	0.13	1.19	0.16	NO
20.0	1.33	1.00		40.23	0.08	13.63	137.92	89.65	0.43	0.19	1.19	0.23	YES

Table A.7. Assessment of liquefaction potential according to [Seed et al. \(2003\)](#) using DH-1 data (soil profile A)

Depth (m)	USCS	Όριο Atterberg			PI	Liquef. diagram Applicable	Wc>0,8LL	Potentially liquefiable Zone A	Wc>0,85LL	Potentially liquefiable Zone B
		W _p	W	W _L						
4.0	CH/CL	24	62	61	37	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO
5.0	CH/CL	20	37	39	19	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES
6.0	CH/CL	24	63	61	37	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO
9.0	CH/CL	17	46	37	20	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES

PL=W_p=όριο πλαστικότητας, LL=W_L=όριο υδαρότητας, PI=LL-PL= δείκτης πλαστικότητας

Thessaloniki Port site response analysis results

B.1 Site response analysis results for the three representative soil profiles of Thessaloniki Port for the two seismic hazard scenarios

Figure B.1 to Figure B.3 show respectively the computed variation of excess pore water pressure, effective confinement and maximum shear strain with depth for the three representative soil profiles and the selected input motions for the 475 years and 4975 years seismic scenarios when considering the base-case V_s -profile. The significant build-up of excess pore pressure shown in Figure B.1 (reaching up to 30.0-40.0 m) results in the loss of effective confining stress (Figure B.2) and increased cyclic shear strain accumulation (Figure B.3) identifying layers of potential liquefaction. In particular, it is shown that liquefaction is evident for the three soil profiles for both scenarios. However, for the 4975 years scenario the liquefiable layers are extended to deeper depths (up to 35.0m). Among the three representative soil profiles, liquefaction effects are shown to be more pronounced for profile A.

Figure B.4 and Figure B.5 show respectively the estimated maximum residual horizontal and vertical displacements profiles for the three representative sites for the two considered seismic scenarios. It is noted that the residual horizontal displacements result from the lateral spreading while the vertical ones refer to the settlements that results from the reconsolidation of the liquefied or partially liquefied soil. Large variability in the computed permanent displacements is shown for the different seismic input motions and scenarios. Generally low-frequency input motions increase the accumulation of lateral deformations and settlements. The computed maximum horizontal displacement values when considering the base-case V_s -profile are 4.5 cm and 18.6 cm for the 475 and 4975 years seismic scenarios respectively, while the corresponding values for the vertical displacements (settlements) are 4.8 cm and 11.0 cm.

Figure B.1. Variation of excess pore pressure with depth for the three soil profiles for the 475 years scenario (left) and the 4975 years scenario (right)

Figure B.2. Variation of effective confinement with depth for the three soil profiles for the 475 years scenario (left) and the 4975 years scenario (right)

Figure B.3. Variation of maximum shear strain with depth for the three soil profiles for the 475 years scenario (left) and the 4975 years scenario (right)

Figure B.4. Variation of maximum residual horizontal ground displacement with depth for the three soil profiles for the 475 years scenario (left) and the 4975 years scenario (right)

Figure B.5. Variation of maximum vertical ground displacement with depth for the three soil profiles for the 475 years scenario (left) and the 4975 years scenario (right)

In addition, Figure B.6 illustrates the PGA profile with depth for the three soil profiles for the 475 years and the 4975 years scenarios, while comparative graphs between the two hazard scenarios are shown in Figure B.7 in terms of median values and median \pm 1 standard deviation of the PGA profile with depth. The liquefaction model employed in Cyclic1D is able to accommodate yielding and build-up of excess pore pressure which

may result in loss of effective confining stress and shear strength, degradation of shear stiffness and permanent ground deformations due to lateral spreading at high strain levels. It is seen that near-surface yield and the subsequent liquefaction-induced permanent deformations attenuate high-frequency surface motions.

Figure B.6. Variation of PGA with depth for the three soil profiles for the 475 years scenario (left) and the 4975 years scenario (right)

Figure B.7. Variation of median PGA and median PGA ± 1 standard deviation with depth for the three soil profiles for the 475 years scenario (left) and the 4975 years scenario (right)

Εκτενής Περίληψη

I.1 Εισαγωγή

Οι φυσικοί κίνδυνοι που προκαλούνται από σεισμό, όπως σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση, ρευστοποίηση και τσουνάμι, αποτελούν μια κύρια μορφή απειλή για τον πληθυσμό και το δομημένο περιβάλλον. Τις τελευταίες δεκαετίες σοβαρές βλάβες παράκτιων κατασκευών έχουν παρατηρηθεί λόγω αυτών των φυσικών κινδύνων μετά από ισχυρούς σεισμούς, όπως για παράδειγμα στην Τουρκία (Kocaeli, 1999), στη Ν. Ζηλανδία (Christchurch, 2011), στον Ινδικό ωκεανό (Indian Ocean tsunami, 2004) και στην Ιαπωνία (Tohoku, 2011), οι οποίες οδήγησαν σε σημαντικές οικονομικές και κοινωνικές απώλειες. Υπάρχει επομένως ένα αυξανόμενο ενδιαφέρον από την επιστημονική κοινότητα των μηχανικών τόσο στο αντικείμενο της διακινδύνευσης όσο και της δομικής τρωτότητας λόγω αυτών των φυσικών κινδύνων που προκαλούνται από σεισμό, με στόχο την αποτελεσματική διαχείριση και μείωση της διακινδύνευσης που συνδέεται με αυτούς.

Η μετάβαση προς μια ασφαλέστερη και πιο ανθεκτική κοινωνία απαιτεί αποτελεσματικά εργαλεία εκτίμησης διακινδύνευσης τα οποία θα μπορούσαν να αξιοποιηθούν από τους υπεύθυνους σχεδιασμού έκτακτης ανάγκης, τους φορείς διάσωσης και τους εμπλεκόμενους φορείς για τη θέσπιση ολοκληρωμένων στρατηγικών μετριασμού των κινδύνων τόσο σε περιφερειακό επίπεδο όσο και σε τοπικό επίπεδο. Συνεπώς, απαιτείται ποσοτική αποτίμηση της επικινδυνότητας και της τρωτότητας των στοιχείων που βρίσκονται σε κίνδυνο. Με την πάροδο των ετών πραγματοποιήθηκαν αρκετές μελέτες εκτίμησης της επικινδυνότητας, ενώ τις τελευταίες δύο δεκαετίες η εκτίμηση της τρωτότητας έχει επίσης αναδειχθεί ως σημαντικός ερευνητικός τομέας. Ωστόσο, οι περισσότερες από τις υπάρχουσες μελέτες παρέχουν καμπύλες τρωτότητας λόγω της σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης και δεν επικεντρώνονται στην εκτίμηση της τρωτότητας των κτιρίων και των υποδομών λόγω άλλων φυσικών κινδύνων που προκαλούνται από σεισμούς (όπως τσουνάμι και ρευστοποίηση). Μόνο πρόσφατα έχουν αναπτυχθεί ορισμένες μεθοδολογίες εκτίμησης τρωτότητας λόγω άλλων σεισμικών κινδύνων, οι οποίες όμως βασίζονται κυρίως σε εμπειρικά δεδομένα ή / και στην έμπειρη κρίση ειδικών, καθώς

η συνήθης πρακτική εδώ και πολλά χρόνια είναι η επί τόπου αναγνώριση των βλαβών που προκλήθηκαν. Σε αυτό το πλαίσιο, η γενική τους εφαρμογή περιορίζεται καθώς είναι ιδιαίτερα εξειδικευμένες σε συγκεκριμένο σεισμο-τεκτονικό, γεωμορφολογικό και δομημένο περιβάλλον.

Λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τα παραπάνω, κύριος στόχος της διδακτορικής διατριβής αποτελεί η πρόταση και ποσοτικοποίηση αναλυτικών μεθοδολογιών για την αποτίμηση της τρωτότητας και διακινδύνευσης κτιρίων που υπόκειται είτε σε τσουνάμι, είτε σε διαφορικές μόνιμες μετακινήσεις που προκαλούνται από ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους, ή σε συνδυασμένη σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους λαμβάνοντας υπόψη την δυναμική αλληλεπίδραση εδάφους-κατασκευής (ΔΑΕΚ). Στο πλαίσιο της διατριβής προτείνονται καμπύλες ή επιφάνειες (όπου κρίνεται σκόπιμο) τρωτότητας για διάφορους τύπους κτιρίων, οι οποίες μπορούν να βρουν άμεση εφαρμογή σε ένα πιθανοτικό πλαίσιο εκτίμησης της διακινδύνευσης λόγω των παραπάνω φυσικών κινδύνων που προκαλούνται από σεισμό. Οι προτεινόμενες καμπύλες και επιφάνειες τρωτότητας επιβεβαιώνονται μέσω αντιπροσωπευτικών συγκρίσεων τους με σχετικές καμπύλες της βιβλιογραφίας και δεδομένα από βλάβες σε κτίρια λόγω αυτών των φυσικών κινδύνων.

I.2 Καμπύλες τρωτότητας κτιρίων Ο/Σ και μεταλλικών αποθηκών λόγω τσουνάμι

Στο πλαίσιο της διδακτορικής διατριβής, προτείνεται μια μεθοδολογία για την αποτίμηση της τρωτότητας κτιρίων που υπόκειται σε τσουνάμι, εμπνευσμένη από τις μεθόδους που χρησιμοποιούνται για την ανάπτυξη καμπυλών τρωτότητας λόγω σεισμού. Το Σχήμα I.1 απεικονίζει το γενικό πλαίσιο της προτεινόμενης μεθοδολογίας. Για την εφαρμογή της μεθοδολογίας επιλέχθηκαν τυπικά κτίρια αντιπροσωπευτικά των τυπολογιών που εντοπίζονται σε συνήθεις λιμενικές περιοχές της Νότιας Ευρώπης, όπως το λιμάνι της Θεσσαλονίκης, δηλαδή κτίρια οπλισμένου σκυροδέματος Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένων βάσει χαμηλού επιπέδου κανονισμού και μεταλλικές αποθήκες που υποβάλλονται σε δυνάμεις τσουνάμι. Η «ικανότητα» της κατασκευής ορίζεται από την τυπολογία του κτιρίου (γεωμετρία, δυσκαμψία), τις ιδιότητες των υλικών και την προσομοίωση της πλαστικότητας των μελών. Για την προσομοίωση της κατασκευής χρησιμοποιούνται κατάλληλα μη γραμμικά καταστατικά μοντέλα θεωρώντας συνθήκες πάκτωσης στο βράχο. Αξίζει να σημειωθεί ότι η συγκεκριμένη μεθοδολογία στηρίζεται στην υπόθεση ότι το επίκεντρο του σεισμού που προκαλεί το τσουνάμι βρίσκεται μακριά από την κατασκευή και ότι οι βλάβες στην κατασκευή είναι αποτέλεσμα μόνο των φορτίων τσουνάμι και όχι συνδυασμός αυτής με την σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση. Έτσι, η κατασκευή δεν υποβάλλεται σε κάποια αρχική απομείωση της αντοχής ή της δυσκαμψίας της λόγω της επίδρασης της σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης.

Σχήμα Ι.1. Διάγραμμα ροής της προτεινόμενης μεθοδολογίας για την εκτίμηση της τρωτότητας λόγω τσουνάμι

Τα φορτία λόγω τσουνάμι καθορίζονται με βάση τις συστάσεις της οδηγίας FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008) και την ορθή κρίση μηχανικού. Συγκεκριμένα, κάθε κτίριο υπόκειται σε δυνάμεις άνωσης (buoyant forces), υδροστατικές (hydrostatic forces) και υδροδυναμικές (hydrodynamic forces) δυνάμεις συνδυασμένες με δυνάμεις που οφείλονται σε συντρίμια (debris forces), τα οποία αποτελούν τα φορτία τσουνάμι. Οι συνδυασμοί των δυνάμεων λόγω τσουνάμι που θεωρούνται διαφέρουν για τις διάφορες τυπολογίες κτιρίων ενώ οι υπολογιζόμενες δυνάμεις λόγω τσουνάμι αυξάνουν με το ύψος τσουνάμι. Τα φορτία τσουνάμι στη συνέχεια εφαρμόζονται απευθείας ως στατικά φορτία χρονικά μεταβαλλόμενα στο μη γραμμικό προσομοίωμα της κατασκευής για σταδιακά αυξανόμενο ύψος τσουνάμι. Η ανάλυση που πραγματοποιείται είναι ψευδοστατική θεωρώντας ανελαστική τη συμπεριφορά των υλικών της κατασκευής υπό τη μορφή ινών (fibers). Για κάθε ανάλυση, εξάγεται τελικά η μέγιστη απόκριση της κατασκευής σε επίπεδο τοπικής παραμόρφωσης υλικού (που αποτελεί και την παράμετρο βλάβης).

Στη συνέχεια, τα δεδομένα της απόκρισης σε επίπεδο τοπικής παραμόρφωσης υλικού χρησιμοποιούνται για την ανάπτυξη των καμπυλών τρωτότητας λόγω τσουνάμι. Καθορίζονται οριακές στάθμες βλάβης καμπτικού τύπου σε όρους τοπικής παραμόρφωσης υλικού με βάση μη γραμμικές στατικές αναλύσεις, την τυπολογία και τα δομικά χαρακτηριστικά της κατασκευής, την έμπειρη κρίση των ειδικών και τη διαθέσιμη βιβλιογραφία (Crowley et al. 2004, Fotopoulou and Pitilakis 2013, Pitilakis 2015) ώστε να

είναι δυνατή η ανάπτυξη καμπυλών τρωτότητας για διαφορετικές στάθμες βλάβης. Συγκεκριμένα, προτείνονται τέσσερις οριακές στάθμες βλάβης για μικρές (LS1- Limit state 1), μέτριες (LS2- Limit state 2), εκτενείς (LS3- Limit state 3) βλάβες και ολική κατάρρευση (LS4- Limit state 4) με βάση οριακές τιμές παραμορφώσεων των υλικών. Εκτός από αστοχία καμπτικού τύπου, λαμβάνεται υπόψη και τυχόν αστοχία διατμητικού τύπου (απώλεια διατμητικής αντοχής ενός δομικού στοιχείου). Μια οριακή στάθμη βλάβης καθορίζεται σε αυτή την περίπτωση, η οποία περιγράφει την ολική κατάρρευση λόγω διατμητικής αστοχίας.

Η τρωτότητα εκφράζεται μέσω αθροιστικών λογαριθμοκανονικών συναρτήσεων τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) που περιγράφουν την πιθανότητα υπέρβασης της κάθε οριζόμενης στάθμης βλάβης συναρτήσει μιας ή περισσοτέρων παραμέτρων που χαρακτηρίζουν την ένταση του τσουνάμι. Αφού προταθούν οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας για τις υπό μελέτη τυπολογίες κτιρίων που υποβάλλονται σε φορτία τσουνάμι, μπορεί να κατασκευαστεί μια καμπύλη τρωτότητας σε όρους απωλειών (vulnerability curve) για κάθε τυπολογία κτιρίου η οποία παρέχει ένα μοναδικό δείκτη βλάβης ή τρωτότητας για κάθε επίπεδο ύψους τσουνάμι. Σημειώνεται ότι η κάθε προτεινόμενη καμπύλη τρωτότητας περιλαμβάνει επίσης την πιθανότητα διατμητικής αστοχίας. Ο δείκτης βλάβης αποτελεί ένα βολικό μέτρο ποσοτικοποίησης των δομικών απωλειών, καθώς μπορεί να ποσοτικοποιηθεί σε όρους κόστους, ως ο λόγος κόστους επισκευής προς κόστος αντικατάστασης, λαμβάνοντας τιμές από 0: καμία βλάβη (κόστος επισκευής ισούται με 0) έως 1: «οιονεί» κατάρρευση (το κόστος επισκευής ισούται με το κόστος αντικατάστασης).

Ένα βασικό σημείο στην παραγωγή καμπυλών τρωτότητας είναι η επιλογή του μέτρου έντασης που συσχετίζεται επαρκώς με τις βλάβες. Σύμφωνα με την FEMA P646 ([FEMA 2008](#)) οι αριθμητικές προβλέψεις των ταχυτήτων τσουνάμι είναι λιγότερο ακριβείς από τις προβλέψεις του ύψους τσουνάμι. Επιπλέον, είναι δύσκολο να προσδιοριστεί με επαρκή ακρίβεια και ανάλυση από δεδομένα πεδίου, γι' αυτό και οι περισσότερες εμπειρικές καμπύλες τρωτότητας στη βιβλιογραφία είναι σε όρους ύψους τσουνάμι. Με βάση τα παραπάνω, το ύψος τσουνάμι επιλέχθηκε ως το πλέον κατάλληλο μέτρο έντασης για τις προτεινόμενες καμπύλες τρωτότητας λόγω τσουνάμι.

1.2.1 Περιγραφή των υπό μελέτη κτιρίων

Τα λιμενικά κτίρια στην Ελλάδα αποτελούνται κυρίως από κτίρια Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένων βάσει χαμηλού επιπέδου κανονισμού («βασιλικό διάταγμα» του 1959) και μεταλλικές αποθήκες. Αυτά τα κτίρια σε σύγκριση με άλλα που σχεδιάστηκαν σύμφωνα με σύγχρονους κανονισμούς θα παρουσίαζαν μια χειρότερη σεισμική συμπεριφορά, καθώς θέματα όπως η πλαστιμότητα, η ικανότητα καθώς και τα δυναμικά χαρακτηριστικά των

κτιρίων αγνοήθηκαν στο σχεδιασμό τους. Η περιγραφή και η ταξινόμηση των διαφορετικών τυπολογιών κτιρίων έγινε βάσει του πλαισίου ταξινόμησης κατά SYNER-G, www.syner-g.eu (Crowley et al. 2011). Έτσι επιλέχθηκαν τρία αντιπροσωπευτικά κτίρια με πλαισιακό σύστημα, συγκεκριμένα ένα χαμηλό, ένα μέσου ύψους και ένα υψηλό κτίριο, καθώς και ένα κτίριο χαμηλό με τοιχωματικό σύστημα (Σχήμα I.2), όλα σχεδιασμένα με βάση τον Ελληνικό Αντισεισμικό Κανονισμό του 1959 (χαμηλό επίπεδο κανονισμού). Αυτές οι τυπολογίες κτιρίων μελετώνται λαμβάνοντας υπόψη διδιάστατα προσομοιώματα με «γυμνά» πλαισιακά ή τοιχωματικά συστήματα (χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις) καθώς και με τοιχοπληρώσεις με ομοιόμορφη καθ' ύψος κατανομή της τοιχοποιίας. Όσον αφορά τις αποθήκες, πρόκειται για μεγάλα κτίρια από χάλυβα (με ή χωρίς τοιχοποιία) που αντιπροσωπεύουν βασικά στοιχεία ενός λιμένα (NIBS 2004). Ο Πίνακας I. παρουσιάζει συγκεντρωτικά βασικά χαρακτηριστικά των φορέων σε όρους μάζας, αρχικής θεμελιώδους ιδιοπεριόδου T_1 , αντοχής σκυροδέματος f_c και χάλυβα f_y . Στο Σχήμα I.2 παρουσιάζονται τα γεωμετρικά χαρακτηριστικά καθώς και οι λεπτομέρειες όπλισης των υπό μελέτη πακτωμένων κατασκευών.

Πίνακας I.1. Κύρια χαρακτηριστικά των κτιριακών προσομοιωμάτων

Τυπολογία κτιρίου (Χαμηλό επίπεδο Κανονισμού)	Συνολική Μάζα (t)	Θεμελιώδης ιδιοπερίοδος T(sec)	f_c (Mpa)	f_y (Mpa)
Διώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	65.7	0.43	14.0	400.0
Διώροφο πλαισιακό τοιχοπληρωμένο Ο/Σ	114.9	0.18	14.0	400.0
Τετραώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	135.0	0.58	14.0	400.0
Τετραώροφο πλαισιακό τοιχοπληρωμένο Ο/Σ	233.1	0.31	14.0	400.0
Εννιαώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	334.0	0.89	14.0	400.0
Εννιαώροφο πλαισιακό τοιχοπληρωμένο Ο/Σ	550.7	0.55	14.0	400.0
Διώροφο τοιχωματικό Ο/Σ	131.8	0.12	14.0	400.0
Διώροφο τοιχωματικό τοιχοπληρωμένο Ο/Σ	137.6	0.11	14.0	400.0
Μεταλλική αποθήκη	5.1	0.30	-	235.0

Η αριθμητική προσομοίωση των φορέων έγινε στο πρόγραμμα πεπερασμένων στοιχείων Seismostruct v7.0 (Seismosoft 2015). Η ανελαστική προσομοίωση των δοκών και των υποστυλωμάτων έγινε χρησιμοποιώντας στοιχεία δοκού-υποστυλώματος με βάση τη μέθοδο των δυνάμεων. Η πλαστικότητα προσομοιώνεται ως κατανεμημένη σε όλο το μήκος των δομικών στοιχείων μέσω ινών που περιγράφουν τη συμπεριφορά των διατομών του κάθε μέλους βάσει μη-γραμμικών νόμων τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων. Για την προσομοίωση των ινών σκυροδέματος χρησιμοποιήθηκε το μονοαξονικό μη γραμμικό μοντέλο που προτάθηκε από τον Mander (1988), θεωρώντας μια σταθερή πίεση περίσφιξης για το περισφιγμένο σκυρόδεμα σε όλο το εύρος τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων. Για

την προσομοίωση του χάλυβα θεωρήθηκε διγραμμικός ελαστοπλαστικός νόμος με κινηματική κράτυνση. Η μάζα θεωρείται ομοιόμορφα κατανομημένη κατά μήκος των δομικών στοιχείων. Η προσομοίωση της τοιχοποιίας στο Seismostruct πραγματοποιείται βάσει του μοντέλου του διπλού θλιπτήρα που προτάθηκε από Crisafulli (1997).

Σχήμα 1.2. Σχηματική αναπαράσταση των γεωμετρικών (διατομές) και των κατασκευαστικών (λεπτομέρειες όπλισης) χαρακτηριστικών των υπό μελέτη κτιρίων

1.2.2 Φορτία λόγω τσουνάμι

Τα φορτία τσουνάμι που υπολογίζονται σύμφωνα με την FEMA P646 (FEMA 2008) επιβάλλονται ως στατικά φορτία χρονικά μεταβαλλόμενα στην κατασκευή στο σημείο εφαρμογής της συνισταμένης κάθε δύναμης ανάλογα με το ύψος τσουνάμι (h). Συγκεκριμένα, οι υδροδυναμικές δυνάμεις (F_d) και οι ωστικές δυνάμεις (F_s) εφαρμόζονται σε ύψος $h/2$ από τη βάση της κατασκευής, οι δυνάμεις πρόσκρουσης συντριμμίων (F_i) εφαρμόζονται σε ύψος h από τη βάση της κατασκευής ενώ οι υδροστατικές δυνάμεις (F_h) εφαρμόζονται σε ύψος $h/3$ από τη βάση της κατασκευής. Οι δυνάμεις άνωσης εφαρμόζονται στη βάση της κατασκευής. Οι δυνάμεις ανύψωσης σε ανώτερα πατώματα (F_u) εφαρμόζονται μόνο στις περιπτώσεις όπου το ύψος τσουνάμι υπερβαίνει το ύψος του πρώτου ορόφου. Ενδεικτικά στο Σχήμα 1.3 παρουσιάζονται οι συνδυασμοί των φορτίων τσουνάμι για το τετραώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ με και χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις.

Σχήμα 1.3. Φορτία τσουνάμι για το τετραώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ (α) χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις, όπου το ύψος τσουνάμι είναι μικρότερο από το ύψος του πρώτου ορόφου (β) χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις, όπου το ύψος τσουνάμι είναι μεγαλύτερο από το ύψος του πρώτου ορόφου (εφαρμόζονται δυνάμεις ανύψωσης) και (γ) με τοιχοπληρώσεις (όπου F_h , F_b , F_d , F_s , F_i and F_u είναι οι δυνάμεις υδροστατικές, άνωσης, υδροδυναμικές, ωστικές, πρόσκρουσης συντριμμίων και ανύψωσης σε ανώτερα πατώματα που προκαλούνται από τσουνάμι αντίστοιχα)

Στη συνέχεια διεξάγονται μη γραμμικές στατικές αναλύσεις ιστορίας, εφαρμόζοντας τα φορτία τσουνάμι απευθείας ως στατικά φορτία χρονικά μεταβαλλόμενα στο μη γραμμικό προσομοίωμα της κατασκευής για σταδιακά αυξανόμενο ύψος τσουνάμι. Για κάθε ανάλυση, εξάγεται η μέγιστη απόκριση της κατασκευής σε επίπεδο τοπικής παραμόρφωσης υλικού (χάλυβα ή σκυροδέματος).

1.2.3 Καμπύλες τρωτότητας λόγω τσουνάμι

Το επόμενο βήμα για την κατασκευή των καμπυλών τρωτότητας είναι ο ορισμός των οριακών σταθμών βλάβης. Προκειμένου να ελαχιστοποιηθούν οι αβεβαιότητες που σχετίζονται με την επιλογή των κατάλληλων οριακών σταθμών βλάβης, πραγματοποιούνται μη γραμμικές στατικές αναλύσεις για κάθε τυπολογία κτιρίου. Ο Πίνακας 1.2 παρουσιάζει τις οριακές στάθμες βλάβης που υιοθετήθηκαν τελικά. Ενδεικτικά στο Σχήμα 1.4 παρουσιάζεται ο ορισμός των σταθμών βλάβης επάνω στην καμπύλη αντίστασης λόγω τσουνάμι που έχει εξαχθεί για την περίπτωση του μέσου ύψους πλαισιακού κτιρίου Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένο με βάση χαμηλό αντισεισμικό κανονισμό. Σημειώνεται ότι η καμπύλη αντίστασης λόγω τσουνάμι για κάθε τυπολογία κτιρίου δεν εξάγεται από μία μόνο μη γραμμική στατική ανάλυση όπως για μια καμπύλη αντίστασης λόγω σεισμού αλλά από το σύνολο των μη γραμμικών στατικών αναλύσεων χρονοϊστορίας που έχουν διεξαχθεί για κάθε τυπολογία κτιρίου που υπόκειται σε σταδιακά αυξανόμενο ύψος τσουνάμι. Παρατηρείται ότι για όλες τις περιπτώσεις η παραμόρφωση του χάλυβα (ϵ_s) δίνει τα πιο κρίσιμα αποτελέσματα.

Πίνακας 1.2. Οριακές τιμές στάθμης βλάβης για κάθε τυπολογία κτιρίου που εξετάστηκε

Στάθμες βλάβης	Παραμόρφωση χάλυβα (ϵ_s)			
	Ο/Σ Πλαισιακό χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις	Ο/Σ Πλαισιακό με τοιχοπληρώσεις	Ο/Σ Τοιχωματικό με/χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις	Μεταλλική αποθήκη
LS1	0.002	0.0007	0.002	0.00112
LS2	0.0125	0.002	0.0125	0.0125
LS3	0.025	0.010	0.04	0.03
LS4	0.045	0.020	0.08	0.055

Σχήμα 1.4. Ορισμός οριακών τιμών στάθμης βλάβης στην καμπύλη αντίστασης λόγω τσουνάμι για το τετραώροφο πλαισιακό μη τοιχοπληρωμένο κτίριο Ο/Σ

Οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας περιγράφουν την πιθανότητα για δεδομένη ένταση (ύψος) τσουνάμι, η βλάβη μιας κατασκευής να είναι ίση ή μεγαλύτερη από ένα ορισμένο επίπεδο.

Τα αποτελέσματα των μη γραμμικών στατικών αναλύσεων (ύψος τσουνάμι-μέγιστη παραμόρφωση υλικού) χρησιμοποιούνται για την κατασκευή των καμπυλών τρωτότητας που περιγράφουν την κατανομή της πιθανότητας υπέρβασης της κάθε στάθμης βλάβης και εκφράζονται βάσει της ακόλουθης κανονικής λογαριθμικής κατανομής:

$$P[DS_i/IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM) - \ln(IM_i)}{\beta}\right) \quad (I.1)$$

όπου Φ : η τυπική κανονική αθροιστική συνάρτηση, DS : η στάθμη βλάβης, IM : το μέτρο έντασης που στην παρούσα μεθοδολογία εκφράζεται σε όρους ύψους τσουνάμι, IM και β : η διάμεσος (εκφρασμένη σε μέτρα, m) και η λογαριθμοκανονική τυπική απόκλιση των καμπυλών τρωτότητας αντίστοιχα. Οι τιμές των λογαριθμοκανονικών παραμέτρων (διάμεσος και διασπορά) των καμπυλών τρωτότητας που αντιστοιχούν στις καθορισμένες στάθμες βλάβης, υπολογίζονται με ανάλυση παλινδρόμησης των αποτελεσμάτων των μη γραμμικών στατικών αναλύσεων (ύψος τσουνάμι-μέγιστη παραμόρφωση χάλυβα). Στο Σχήμα I.5 παρουσιάζεται ενδεικτικά η σχέση ύψους τσουνάμι-μέγιστης παραμόρφωσης χάλυβα για την περίπτωση του μέσου ύψους πλαισιακού κτιρίου Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένο με χαμηλό επίπεδο κανονισμού. Στο σχήμα απεικονίζονται επίσης οι οριακές τιμές της παραμόρφωσης του χάλυβα του σπλισμού για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης. Τέλος, οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας συναρτήσει του ύψους τσουνάμι για τις διάφορες στάθμες βλάβης, παράγονται μετά από κατάλληλη μέθοδο στατιστικής επεξεργασίας της απόκρισης (σε επίπεδο τοπικών παραμορφώσεων), σε σχέση με την παράμετρο της έντασης του τσουνάμι (ύψος τσουνάμι) και τις οριζόμενες στάθμες βλάβης. Στην πιθανοτική προσέγγιση που προτείνεται, λαμβάνονται υπόψη διάφορες αβεβαιότητες που σχετίζονται με την ικανότητα της κατασκευής και την απαίτηση παραμόρφωσης. Στο Σχήμα I.6 και στο Σχήμα I.7 δίδονται οι προτεινόμενες καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω τσουνάμι για τις εξεταζόμενες τυπολογίες κτιρίων.

Σχήμα I.5. Σχέση ύψους τσουνάμι-μέγιστης παραμόρφωσης χάλυβα για το τετραώροφο πλαισιακό μη τοιχοπληρωμένο κτίριο

Σχήμα I.6. Καμπύλες πρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω τσουνάμι για τις διαφορετικές τυπολογίες κτιρίων Ο/Σ

Σχήμα I.7. Καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω τσουνάμι για την μεταλλική αποθήκη

Για τις περιπτώσεις όπου τουλάχιστον το 50% των υποσυλωμάτων σε έναν όροφο ξεπερνά την ικανότητα διάτμησης, προτείνονται νέες καμπύλες τρωτότητας για ολική κατάρρευση λόγω διατμητικής αστοχίας. Αποδεικνύεται ότι η διατμητική αστοχία αποτελεί τον κύριο μηχανισμό αστοχίας για τα πλαίσια κτίρια Ο/Σ χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις (Σχήμα I.8), το ψηλό πλαίσιακό καθώς και το χαμηλό τοιχωματικό κτίριο με τοιχοπληρώσεις.

Σχήμα I.8. Καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω τσουνάμι για τη στάθμη βλάβης ολική κατάρρευση λόγω καμπτικής ή διατμητικής αστοχίας

Τέλος, αφού εκτιμηθούν οι πιθανότητες υπέρβασης των καθορισμένων σταθμών βλάβης, ένας δείκτης βλάβης μπορεί να υπολογιστεί για κάθε ύψος τσουνάμι σύμφωνα με την ακόλουθη σχέση:

$$d_{mj} = \sum_{i=1}^4 P_{ij} \cdot d_i \quad (I.2)$$

όπου d_{mj} είναι ο δείκτης βλάβης (λαμβάνοντας τιμές από 0: καμία βλάβη έως 1: «οιονεί» κατάρρευση) που αντιστοιχεί σε επίπεδο ύψους τσουνάμι j , P_{ij} είναι η διακριτή πιθανότητα βλάβης για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης και d_i αντιπροσωπεύει τον δείκτη βλάβης σε κάθε μία από τις καθορισμένες στάθμες βλάβης. Σημειώνεται ότι για τα κτίρια Ο/Σ, η κεντρική τιμή του δείκτη βλάβης για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης (δηλαδή d_i) λαμβάνεται ίση με 0.05, 0.20, 0.45 και 0.80 για τις LS1, LS2, LS3 και LS4 αντίστοιχα σύμφωνα με την μελέτη των [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#), ενώ για τις μεταλλικές αποθήκες λαμβάνεται ίση με 0.10, 0.40, 0.75 και 1.00 για τις LS1, LS2, LS3 και LS4 αντίστοιχα σύμφωνα με την μελέτη των [Blong \(2003\)](#). Στο Σχήμα 1.9 παρουσιάζονται οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους απωλειών (vulnerability curves) λόγω τσουνάμι για τις διαφορετικές εξεταζόμενες τυπολογίες κτιρίων. Σημειώνεται ότι οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους απωλειών περιλαμβάνουν την πιθανότητα διατμητικής αστοχίας.

Σχήμα 1.9. Καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους απωλειών (vulnerability curves) λόγω τσουνάμι για τις διαφορετικές υπό μελέτη τυπολογίες κτιρίων

Αποδείχθηκε ότι τα ψηλά κτίρια Ο/Σ παρουσιάζουν μικρότερη τρωτότητα συγκριτικά με τα χαμηλά κτίρια, γεγονός που είναι σύμφωνο με παρατηρήσεις πεδίου ([Suppasri et al. 2013](#)). Επιπλέον, τα χαμηλά και μέσου ύψους κτίρια με τοιχοπληρώσεις βρέθηκαν πιο τρωτά σε σύγκριση με αυτά χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις. Αυτό ισχύει επίσης και για τα ψηλά κτίρια για την υπέρβαση της μικρής και μέτριας βλάβης. Αντιθέτως, όταν αναμένεται εκτενής βλάβη ή κατάρρευση, το ψηλά κτίρια χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις αναμένεται να αντέξουν μεγαλύτερες βλάβες σε σύγκριση με τα τοιχοπληρωμένα. Ακόμη, τα χαμηλά τοιχωματικά κτίρια είναι πιο τρωτά συγκριτικά με τα πλαίσια, γεγονός που σχετίζεται με τη συγκέντρωση μεγάλων δυνάμεων τσουνάμι στα τοιχώματα. Όσον αφορά τις καμπύλες τρωτότητας για την αποθήκη είναι γενικά παρόμοιες με αυτές για τα χαμηλά και μέσου ύψους πλαίσια κτίρια. Η διαφορά μεταξύ των καμπυλών τρωτότητας για τις διάφορες στάθμες βλάβης δεν είναι τόσο μεγάλη γεγονός που δείχνει ότι αφού συμβεί διαρροή, η αποθήκη πολύ γρήγορα ξεπερνά και τις επόμενες στάθμες βλάβης. Έχει επίσης αποδειχθεί ότι η διατμητική αστοχία αποτελεί τον κύριο μηχανισμό αστοχίας για τα πλαίσια κτίρια Ο/Σ χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις ανεξάρτητα από το ύψος τους καθώς και για τα τοιχοπληρωμένα ψηλά πλαίσια και τα χαμηλά τοιχωματικά κτίρια. Η θεώρηση των τοιχοπληρώσεων φαίνεται ότι έχει σημαντική επιρροή στην απόκριση και τον μηχανισμό αστοχίας (καμπτικός ή διατμητικός) των κτιρίων. Τέλος, πραγματοποιούνται συγκρίσεις μεταξύ των προτεινόμενων καμπυλών τρωτότητας και μερικών διαθέσιμων από την βιβλιογραφία για κτίρια Ο/Σ και μεταλλικές αποθήκες. Οι συγκρίσεις αυτές κρίνονται ικανοποιητικές δεδομένου των σημαντικών αβεβαιοτήτων και τη διασπορά των εμπειρικών δεδομένων.

Οι προτεινόμενες καμπύλες τρωτότητας λόγω τσουνάμι για τα κτίρια Ο/Σ θα μπορούσαν να εφαρμοστούν σε τυπικά κτίρια Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένα με κανονισμούς πριν το 1980 στην Ελλάδα και τη Νότια Ευρώπη, καθώς οι τυπολογίες κτιρίων που χρησιμοποιήθηκαν σε αυτή την μελέτη συναντώνται σε αυτές τις χώρες ([Kappos et al. 2003](#)). Επιπλέον, οι προτεινόμενες καμπύλες τρωτότητας λόγω τσουνάμι για τις μεταλλικές αποθήκες θα μπορούσαν να εφαρμοστούν σε τυπικές λιμενικές αποθήκες παγκοσμίως, καθώς πρόκειται για μια κοινή τυπολογία σε λιμένες ανά τον κόσμο ([NIBS 2004](#), [Green et al. 2011](#)). Γνωρίζοντας το αναμενόμενο ύψος τσουνάμι από μια ανάλυση επικινδυνότητας και τα χαρακτηριστικά των κτιρίων που εκτίθενται σε κίνδυνο (γεωμετρικά χαρακτηριστικά, αντοχή υλικών, κτλ.), οι ενδιαφερόμενοι φορείς θα μπορούσαν να επιλέξουν και να χρησιμοποιήσουν το κατάλληλο σύνολο καμπυλών τρωτότητας λόγω τσουνάμι σε ένα πιθανοτικό πλαίσιο εκτίμησης της διακινδύνευσης κτιρίων υπό της ευθύνη τους. Συγκεκριμένα, θα μπορούσε να εκτιμηθεί η φυσική τρωτότητα και στη συνέχεια η διακινδύνευση τους ώστε να ληφθούν οι κατάλληλες αποφάσεις για τη μείωση των απωλειών τους.

I.3 Αποτίμηση της τρωτότητας κτιρίων σε διαφορετικές μετακινήσεις λόγω ρευστοποίησης

Εκτός από τον κίνδυνο του τσουνάμι, ο κίνδυνος της ρευστοποίησης του εδάφους και των διαφορεικών μετακινήσεων που ενδέχεται να προκαλέσει στα κτίρια έχει αναγνωριστεί ευρέως ως ένας από βασικούς σεισμικούς κινδύνους οι οποίες μπορεί να οδηγήσουν σε σημαντικές οικονομικές και κοινωνικές απώλειες. Παρότι οι μέθοδοι ποσοτικής αποτίμησης των αναμενόμενων βλαβών και απωλειών είναι αρκετά διαδεδομένες για φυσικούς κινδύνους όπως οι σεισμοί, στην περίπτωση της ρευστοποίησης, οι μεθοδολογίες αποτίμησης της διακινδύνευσης δεν έχουν αναπτυχθεί παρά μόνο πολύ πρόσφατα και δεν έχουν εφαρμοστεί ενδελεχώς από την επιστημονική κοινότητα και τους αρμόδιους φορείς.

Στο πλαίσιο της διδακτορικής διατριβής, προτείνεται ακόμη μια μεθοδολογία για την αποτίμηση της τρωτότητας και διακινδύνευσης κτιρίων με εύκαμπτη θεμελίωση (μεμονωμένα πέδιλα) που υποβάλλονται σε διαφορεικές μόνιμες μετατοπίσεις εδάφους (καθιζήσεις και πλευρικές μετατοπίσεις) που προκαλούνται από ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους, η οποία βασίζεται στην αποσυζευγμένη αριθμητική προσέγγιση. Στην αποσυζευγμένη αριθμητική προσέγγιση το έδαφος και η κατασκευή μελετώνται ξεχωριστά και οι μετακινήσεις τους εδάφους επιβάλλονται σε ένα προσομοίωμα πεπερασμένων στοιχείων της κατασκευής (π.χ. [Brandenberg et al. 2011](#)). Σημειώνεται ότι οι διαφορεικές μετατοπίσεις εδάφους αποτελούν την σημαντικότερη αιτία βλάβης στα κτίρια ([Bird et al. 2005, 2006](#)). Το Σχήμα I.10 απεικονίζει το γενικό πλαίσιο της προτεινόμενης μεθοδολογίας. Για την εφαρμογή της μεθοδολογίας επιλέχθηκαν τυπικά πλαισιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένων βάσει χαμηλού επιπέδου κανονισμού και μεταλλικές αποθήκες (Σχήμα I.2). Η συγκεκριμένη μέθοδος στηρίζεται στην υπόθεση ότι αστοχία μπορεί να εμφανιστεί στα δομικά στοιχεία του κτιρίου και η φέρουσα ικανότητα της θεμελίωσης είναι επαρκώς σχεδιασμένη ώστε να αντέχει τις μετακινήσεις λόγω ρευστοποίησης, ενώ πιθανή αρχική βλάβη στα δομικά στοιχεία (π.χ. απομείωση της αντοχής ή της δυσκαμψίας) λόγω της σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης δε λαμβάνεται υπόψη.

Η «ικανότητα» της κατασκευής ορίζεται από την τυπολογία του κτιρίου (γεωμετρία, δυσκαμψία), τις ιδιότητες των υλικών και την προσομοίωση της πλαστικότητας των μελών. Για την προσομοίωση της κατασκευής χρησιμοποιούνται κατάλληλα μη γραμμικά καταστατικά μοντέλα θεωρώντας ανελαστική συμπεριφορά των υλικών της κατασκευής υπό τη μορφή ινών (fibers) και συνθήκες πάκτωσης στο βράχο. Η ανάλυση είναι ψευδοστατική και πραγματοποιείται στο πρόγραμμα πεπερασμένων στοιχείων Seismostruct v7.0 ([Seismosoft 2015](#)). Μηχανισμοί αστοχίας καμπτικού τύπου σε όλα τα δομικά στοιχεία και διατμητικού τύπου στα υποστυλώματα λαμβάνονται υπόψη.

Σχήμα Ι.10. Διάγραμμα ροής της προτεινόμενης μεθοδολογίας για την εκτίμηση της τρωτότητας και διακινδύνευσης κτιρίων που υπόκεινται σε διαφορικές μετακινήσεις λόγω ρευστοποίησης

Μια σειρά μη γραμμικών διδιάστατων στατικών αναλύσεων χρονοϊστορίας για κάθε τυπολογία κτιρίου πραγματοποιείται λαμβάνοντας υπόψη διαφορετικά σταδιακά αυξανόμενα προφίλ διαφορικής μετατόπισης που εφαρμόζονται ως «οιονεί» στατικά φορτία απευθείας στις στηρίξεις του (πέδιλα). Συγκεκριμένα, για κάθε κατασκευή πραγματοποιείται μια σειρά από περίπου 100 μη γραμμικές στατικές αναλύσεις για σταδιακά αυξανόμενο επίπεδο μετατόπισης (καλύπτοντας το εύρος από την ελαστικότητα μέχρι και την κατάρρευση της κατασκευής) που επιβάλλονται στο επίπεδο θεμελίωσης λαμβάνοντας υπόψη έξι διαφορετικά προφίλ διαφορικής μετατόπισης:

- i) Καθιζήσεις με τη μέγιστη μετατόπιση να εφαρμόζεται στο ακραίο υποστύλωμα
- ii) Καθιζήσεις με τη μέγιστη μετατόπιση να εφαρμόζεται στο μεσαίο υποστύλωμα
- iii) Πλευρική εξάπλωση με την οριζόντια (h) συνιστώσα της μετατόπισης να είναι ίση με την κατακόρυφη (v), $h=v$, και το μέγιστο διάνυσμα μετατόπισης να εφαρμόζεται στο ακραίο υποστύλωμα

- iv) Πλευρική εξάπλωση με την οριζόντια (h) συνιστώσα της μετατόπισης να είναι ίση με την κατακόρυφη (v), $h=v$, και το μέγιστο διάνυσμα μετατόπισης να εφαρμόζεται στο μεσαίο υποσύλωμα
- v) Πλευρική εξάπλωση με την οριζόντια (h) συνιστώσα της μετατόπισης να είναι ίση με το διπλάσιο της κατακόρυφης (v), $h=2v$, και το μέγιστο διάνυσμα μετατόπισης να εφαρμόζεται στο ακραίο υποσύλωμα
- vi) Πλευρική εξάπλωση με την οριζόντια (h) συνιστώσα της μετατόπισης να είναι ίση με το διπλάσιο της κατακόρυφης (v), $h=2v$, και το μέγιστο διάνυσμα μετατόπισης να εφαρμόζεται στο μεσαίο υποσύλωμα

Η προαναφερθείσα απαίτηση μετατόπισης θεωρείται ότι ακολουθεί τριγωνική κατανομή σε όλες τις περιπτώσεις. Το Figure 5.2 α) και β) παρουσιάζει ενδεικτικά τα επιβαλλόμενο προφίλ μετατόπισης i) και ii) αντίστοιχα για το διώροφο πλαίσιακό μη τοιχοπληρωμένο κτίριο Ο/Σ, ενώ το Figure 5.2 γ) και δ) δείχνει το προφίλ καθιζήσεων και διάνυσμα μετακινήσεων αντίστοιχα για την αποθήκη.

Σχήμα 1.11. Προφίλ διαφορικών καθιζήσεων με τη μέγιστη διαφορική μετακίνηση να εισάγεται στο α) ακραίο ή β) μεσαίο υποσύλωμα για το διώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ και προφίλ γ) διαφορικών καθιζήσεων ή δ) διανύσματος διαφορικών μετακινήσεων για την αποθήκη

Για κάθε ανάλυση, εξάγεται τελικά η μέγιστη απόκριση της κατασκευής σε επίπεδο τοπικής παραμόρφωσης υλικού και διατμητικών δυνάμεων (που αποτελούν και το δείκτη βλάβης). Παρατηρείται ότι για όλες τις περιπτώσεις η παραμόρφωση του χάλυβα (ϵ_s) δίνει

τα πιο κρίσιμα αποτελέσματα. Για την παραγωγή των καμπυλών τρωτότητας καθορίζονται τέσσερις οριακές στάθμες βλάβης καμπτικού τύπου σε όρους τοπικής παραμόρφωσης χάλυβα με βάση τη διαθέσιμη βιβλιογραφία (Crowley et al. 2004, Bird et al. 2005) για τα κτίρια σκυροδέματος και με βάση μη γραμμικές στατικές αναλύσεις και την έμπειρη κρίση για την μεταλλική αποθήκη (Karafagka et al. 2018a). Στο Σχήμα I.12 παρουσιάζεται ο ορισμός των σταθμών βλάβης επάνω στην καμπύλη αντίστασης λόγω ρευστοποίησης που έχει εξαχθεί για την μεταλλική αποθήκη. Επιπλέον, καθορίζεται και μια οριακή στάθμη βλάβης για τα κτίρια Ο/Σ η οποία περιγράφει την ολική κατάρρευση λόγω διατμητικής αστοχίας.

Σχήμα I.12. Ορισμός οριακών τιμών στάθμης βλάβης στην καμπύλη αντίστασης λόγω ρευστοποίησης για την μεταλλική αποθήκη που υπόκειται σε (αριστερά) διαφορικές καθιζήσεις και (δεξιά) διαφορικές μετατοπίσεις (οριζόντια και κατακόρυφη συνιστώσα)

Οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας περιγράφουν την πιθανότητα για δεδομένη ένταση διαφορικής καθίζησης ή διανύσματος μετατόπισης λόγω ρευστοποίησης, η βλάβη μιας κατασκευής να είναι ίση ή μεγαλύτερη από ένα ορισμένο επίπεδο. Τα αποτελέσματα των μη γραμμικών στατικών αναλύσεων (διαφορική μετατόπιση - μέγιστη παραμόρφωση υλικού) χρησιμοποιούνται για την κατασκευή των καμπυλών τρωτότητας που περιγράφουν την κατανομή της πιθανότητας υπέρβασης της κάθε στάθμης βλάβης και εκφράζονται βάσει της ακόλουθης κανονικής λογαριθμικής κατανομής:

$$P[DS_i/IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM) - \ln(\overline{IM}_i)}{\beta}\right) \quad (I.3)$$

όπου Φ : η τυπική κανονική αθροιστική συνάρτηση, DS : η στάθμη βλάβης, IM : το μέτρο έντασης που εκφράζεται σε όρους διαφορικής μετατόπισης λόγω ρευστοποίησης, \overline{IM}_i και β : η διάμεσος και η λογαριθμοκανονική τυπική απόκλιση των καμπυλών τρωτότητας αντίστοιχα. Οι τιμές των λογαριθμοκανονικών παραμέτρων (διάμεσος και διασπορά) των καμπυλών τρωτότητας που αντιστοιχούν στις καθορισμένες στάθμες βλάβης, υπολογίζονται με ανάλυση παλινδρόμησης των αποτελεσμάτων των μη γραμμικών

στατικών αναλύσεων (διαφορική μετατόπιση λόγω ρευστοποίησης - μέγιστη παραμόρφωση χάλυβα). Στο Σχήμα I.12 παρουσιάζονται τυπικά διαγράμματα εξέλιξης της βλάβης σε όρους μέγιστης παραμόρφωσης χάλυβα συναρτήσει της μέγιστης διαφορικής μετατόπισης (συνισταμένη) λόγω ρευστοποίησης για την περίπτωση του μέσου ύψους πλαισιακού μη τοιχοπληρωμένου κτιρίου Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένο με χαμηλό επίπεδο κανονισμού. Στο σχήμα απεικονίζονται επίσης οι οριακές τιμές της παραμόρφωσης του χάλυβα του οπλισμού για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης.

Σχήμα I.13. Σχέση διαφορικής μετακίνησης συνισταμένης-μέγιστης παραμόρφωσης χάλυβα για το τετραώροφο πλαισιακό μη τοιχοπληρωμένο κτίριο που υπόκειται σε διαφορικές καθιζήσεις με τη μέγιστη διαφορική μετακίνηση να εισάγεται στο μεσαίο υποστύλωμα

Τέλος, οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας συναρτήσει της διαφορικής καθίζησης ή της διαφορικής μετατόπισης (συνισταμένη) λόγω ρευστοποίησης για τις διάφορες στάθμες βλάβης, παράγονται μετά από κατάλληλη μέθοδο στατιστικής επεξεργασίας της απόκρισης (σε επίπεδο τοπικών παραμορφώσεων), σε σχέση με την παράμετρο της έντασης της ρευστοποίησης (διαφορική καθίζηση ή διαφορική μετατόπιση συνισταμένη) και τις οριζόμενες στάθμες βλάβης. Στην πιθανοτική προσέγγιση που προτείνεται, λαμβάνονται υπόψη διάφορες αβεβαιότητες που σχετίζονται με την ικανότητα της κατασκευής, τον ορισμό των σταθμών βλάβης και την απαίτηση παραμόρφωσης. Στο Figure 5.7 δίδονται οι προτεινόμενες καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω διαφορικών μετατοπίσεων λόγω ρευστοποίησης για τις εξεταζόμενες τυπολογίες κτιρίων.

Σχήμα I.14. Καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω διαφορικών μετατοπίσεων λόγω ρευστοποίησης για τις διαφορετικές τυπολογίες κτιρίων

Σημειώνεται ότι για τις περιπτώσεις όπου οι κατασκευές υποβάλλονται σε διαφορεική μετακίνηση (συνισταμένη) λόγω ρευστοποίησης με το μέγιστο διάνυσμα μετατόπισης να εφαρμόζεται στο μεσαίο υποστύλωμα, το ελάχιστο των δύο διάμεσων διαφορικών μετατοπίσεων που υπολογίζονται όταν η οριζόντια συνιστώσα της διαφορικής μετατόπισης είναι ίση ή διπλάσια της κατακόρυφης θεωρείται για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης. Έτσι, λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τη δυσκολία γνώσης της πραγματικής αναλογίας της οριζόντιας σε σχέση με την κατακόρυφη συνιστώσα της διαφορικής μετατόπισης και προς την πλευρά της ασφάλειας, ένα ανώτατο όριο σύνολο καμπυλών τρωτότητας αναπτύσσεται τελικά για κάθε κτίριο για την περίπτωση όπου το κτίριο υποβάλλεται σε διαφορεική μετακίνηση (συνισταμένη) λόγω ρευστοποίησης. Η αξιοπιστία των προτεινόμενων καμπυλών τρωτότητας επιβεβαιώνεται μέσω της σύγκρισης τους με σχετικές καμπύλες από τη βιβλιογραφία καθώς και με παρατηρήσεις πεδίου από σεισμικά γεγονότα που προκάλεσαν εκτεταμένη ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους και διαφορικές εδαφικές μετατοπίσεις.

Τέλος, αφού εκτιμηθούν οι πιθανότητες υπέρβασης των καθορισμένων σταθμών βλάβης, ένας δείκτης βλάβης μπορεί να υπολογιστεί για κάθε διαφορική μετατόπιση (καθίζηση ή συνισταμένη μετακίνηση) σύμφωνα με την ακόλουθη σχέση:

$$d_{mj} = \sum_{i=1}^4 P_{ij} \cdot d_i \quad (I.4)$$

όπου d_{mj} είναι ο δείκτης βλάβης (λαμβάνοντας τιμές από 0: καμία βλάβη έως 1: «οιονεί» κατάρρευση) που αντιστοιχεί σε επίπεδο διαφορικής μετατόπισης λόγω ρευστοποίησης j , P_{ij} είναι η διακριτή πιθανότητα βλάβης για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης και d_i αντιπροσωπεύει τον δείκτη βλάβης σε κάθε μία από τις καθορισμένες στάθμες βλάβης. Στο Figure 5.9 παρουσιάζονται οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους απωλειών (vulnerability curves) λόγω διαφορικών μετατοπίσεων λόγω ρευστοποίησης για τις διαφορετικές εξεταζόμενες τυπολογίες κτιρίων. Σημειώνεται ότι οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους απωλειών περιλαμβάνουν την πιθανότητα διατμητικής αστοχίας.

Αποδείχθηκε ότι τα μη τοιχοπληρωμένα πλαίσια κτίρια Ο/Σ με μεμονωμένα πέδιλα που υπόκεινται μόνο σε καθιζήσεις αναμένεται να υποστούν μεγαλύτερες βλάβες σε σύγκριση με το αν υπόκειται σε διαφορική συνισταμένη μετακίνηση (περιλαμβάνεται οριζόντια και κατακόρυφη συνιστώσα διαφορικής μετατόπισης) λόγω ρευστοποίησης. Επιπρόσθετα, το ύψος του κτιρίου αποτελεί μια σημαντική παράμετρο που μπορεί να επηρεάσει σημαντικά τη σεισμική απόκριση. Γενικά, τα ψηλά πλαίσια κτίρια Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένων βάσει χαμηλού επιπέδου κανονισμού είναι πιο τρωτά συγκριτικά με τα χαμηλά και μέσου ύψους, ειδικά για τις περιπτώσεις που υπόκειται σε διαφορική συνισταμένη μετακίνηση. Παρατηρείται επίσης ότι η μεταλλική αποθήκη είναι πολύ λιγότερο τρωτή από τα πλαίσια κτίρια Ο/Σ. Τέλος, διαπιστώθηκε ότι η διατμητική αστοχία αποτελεί τον κύριο μηχανισμό αστοχίας μόνο για την περίπτωση του ψηλού

πλαισιακού κτιρίου σχεδιασμένου βάσει χαμηλού επιπέδου κανονισμού που υπόκειται σε πλευρική εξάπλωση.

Σχήμα 1.15. Καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους απωλειών (vulnerability curves) λόγω διαφορικών μετατοπίσεων λόγω ρευστοποίησης για τις διαφορετικές τυπολογίες κτιρίων

1.4 Αποτίμηση της τρωτότητας κτιρίων Ο/Σ λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης

Πρόσφατοι καταστρεπτικοί σεισμοί κατέδειξαν ότι οι βλάβες σε κτίρια που βρίσκονται σε παράκτιες περιοχές οφείλονται εκτός από τη σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και στη ρευστοποίηση του υποκείμενου εδάφους (Werner 1998). Πρόσφατα παραδείγματα σοβαρών σεισμικών βλαβών λόγω ρευστοποίησης του εδάφους που οδήγησαν σε σημαντικές οικονομικές και κοινωνικές απώλειες, αποτελούν οι σεισμοί μεγέθους M_w 8.8 στην πόλη Maule στη Χιλή το 2010, M_w 7.4 στην επαρχία Kocaeli στην Τουρκία το 1999 και M_w 6.3 στην πόλη Christchurch (Νέα Ζηλανδία) το 2011. Παρόλο που έχει σημειωθεί πρόοδος όσον αφορά την επίδραση της σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης και της ρευστοποίησης του εδάφους στη σεισμική απόκριση των κτιρίων (Kappos et al. 2006, Fotopoulou et al. 2018), οι ερευνητικές προσπάθειες που λαμβάνουν υπόψη τη συνδυασμένη επιρροή και των δύο φαινομένων είναι πολύ περιορισμένες.

Η δυναμική αλληλεπίδραση εδάφους-κατασκευής (ΔΑΕΚ) μπορεί επίσης να επηρεάσει τη σεισμική απόκριση των παράκτιων κατασκευών, αλλάζοντας τα δυναμικά τους χαρακτηριστικά, καθώς και τη σεισμική απόκριση σε επίπεδο θεμελίωσης. Η ΔΑΕΚ αφορά στην αμοιβαία αλληλεπίδραση του εδάφους και της κατασκευής με αποτέλεσμα τη διαφοροποίηση της απόκρισης του συστήματος σε δυναμική φόρτιση. Υπάρχουν δύο βασικές προσεγγίσεις για την προσομοίωση του φαινομένου της ΔΑΕΚ: η «άμεση μέθοδος», όπου το έδαφος, η θεμελίωση και η κατασκευή προσομοιώνονται ως ένα ενιαίο σύστημα και η ανάλυση πραγματοποιείται σε ένα υπολογιστικό βήμα λαμβάνοντας με αυτό τον τρόπο υπόψη την αδρανειακή και την κινηματική αλληλεπίδραση, καθώς και η «προσέγγιση των αποσυζευγμένων συστημάτων» όπου τα διάφορα υποσυστήματα (έδαφος, θεμελίωση, ανωδομή) μελετώνται ξεχωριστά και η ενδοσιμότητα του εδάφους προσομοιώνεται μέσω κατάλληλων ελατηριακών σταθερών. Μέχρι σήμερα, οι τεχνικές αριθμητικής προσομοίωσης για την εκτίμηση της επιρροής τόσο της σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης όσο και της ρευστοποίησης του εδάφους, λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τις επιπτώσεις της ΔΑΕΚ στη σεισμική απόκριση των κτιρίων, δεν έχουν λάβει μεγάλη προσοχή και συνεπώς απαιτούν περαιτέρω διερεύνηση.

Στην παρούσα διατριβή προτείνεται μια αναλυτική μεθοδολογία εκτίμησης της τρωτότητας και διακινδύνευσης κτιρίων με εύκαμπτη θεμελίωση (μεμονωμένα πέδιλα) που εδράζονται σε ρευστοποιήσιμα εδάφη και υπόκεινται σε συνδυασμένη σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τη ΔΑΕΚ. Συγκεκριμένα, εφαρμόζεται η άμεση μέθοδος όπου η προσομοίωση και ανάλυση των υπό μελέτη συστημάτων (έδαφος και κατασκευή) πραγματοποιείται σε ένα υπολογιστικό βήμα (προσομοίωμα ΔΑΕΚ), ενώ λαμβάνεται ταυτόχρονα υπόψη η μη γραμμικότητα του εδάφους λόγω της ρευστοποίησης του υποκείμενου εδάφους. Το Σχήμα I.16 απεικονίζει το γενικό πλαίσιο της προτεινόμενης μεθοδολογίας, όπου η ρευστοποίηση και η ΔΑΕΚ ενσωματώνονται στη μεθοδολογία της αποτίμησης.

Η μεθοδολογία εφαρμόζεται σε τυπικά πλαίσιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ (Σχήμα I.2) σχεδιασμένα με χαμηλό επίπεδο αντισεισμικού κανονισμού (βασιλικό διάταγμα του 1959) διαφορετικού ύψους (χαμηλά, μεσαία και ψηλά) με εύκαμπτη θεμελίωση (μεμονωμένα πέδιλα) που εδράζονται σε ρευστοποιήσιμα εδάφη, σε επίπεδο έδαφος ή σε συνθήκες κλίσης (κλίση 5%), που υπόκεινται σε συνδυασμένη σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση. Θεωρήθηκαν τρία τυπικά προφίλ εδάφους με υψηλό δυναμικό ρευστοποίησης. Για την εκτίμηση των παραμέτρων των καμπυλών τρωτότητας, πραγματοποιούνται διδιάστατες μη γραμμικές βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικές δυναμικές αναλύσεις. Επιπλέον, πραγματοποιείται μια δεύτερη σειρά επαυξητικών δυναμικών αναλύσεων λαμβάνοντας υπόψη κλίση 5% ώστε να εξεταστεί καλύτερα η συμβολή της πλευρικής εξάπλωσης που προκαλείται λόγω ρευστοποίησης.

Σχήμα Ι.16. Διάγραμμα ροής της προτεινόμενης μεθοδολογίας για την εκτίμηση της τρωτότητας και διακινδύνευσης κτιρίων που υπόκεινται σε συνδυασμένη σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τη ΔΑΕΚ

Η «ικανότητα» του κτιρίου ορίζεται από την τυπολογία του (γεωμετρία, δυσκαμψία), τις ιδιότητες των υλικών και την προσομοίωση της πλαστικότητας των μελών. Η σεισμική απαίτηση ορίζεται βάσει καταγραφών από πραγματικούς σεισμούς που χρησιμοποιούνται ως κινήσεις εισαγωγής για τη διεξαγωγή των μη γραμμικών βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικών δυναμικών αναλύσεων με διαφορετικά χαρακτηριστικά ως προς το συχνοτικό περιεχόμενο και τη διάρκεια κίνησης. Η παράμετρος απόκρισης (βλάβης) η οποία μελετάται και βάσει της οποίας ορίζονται οι παράμετροι των καμπυλών τρωτότητας είναι το μέγιστο σχετικό βέλος ορόφου (maxISD). Ακόμη, καθορίζονται τέσσερις οριακές στάθμες βλάβης σε όρους μέγιστου σχετικού βέλους κάμψης με βάση τις αναλύσεις που διεξήχθησαν, τη διαθέσιμη βιβλιογραφία και την έμπειρη κρίση μηχανικού. Τα αποτελέσματα των μη γραμμικών βήμα προς βήμα δυναμικών αναλύσεων (ζεύγη μέτρου σεισμικής έντασης-maxISD) χρησιμοποιούνται για την κατασκευή των συναρτήσεων τρωτότητας.

Η τρωτότητα εκφράζεται μέσω αθροιστικών λογαριθμοκανονικών συζευγμένων καμπυλών τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) και σε όρους απωλειών (vulnerability curves) ως συνάρτηση της μέγιστης εδαφικής επιτάχυνσης ($PGA_{\beta\rho\acute{\alpha}\chi\omicron}$) ή της μέγιστης εδαφικής ταχύτητας ($PGV_{\beta\rho\acute{\alpha}\chi\omicron}$) σε συνθήκες βράχου, καθώς και σε όρους επιφανειών τρωτότητας (fragility surfaces) ως συνάρτηση τόσο της μέγιστης εδαφικής επιτάχυνσης ($PGA_{\#}$) ή ταχύτητας (PGV) στην επιφάνεια στο ελεύθερο πεδίο όσο και της μόνιμης εδαφικής μετατόπισης (PGD) στην επιφάνεια κάτω από την κατασκευή. Στην πιθανοτική προσέγγιση που προτείνεται, λαμβάνονται υπόψη διάφορες αβεβαιότητες που σχετίζονται με την ικανότητα της κατασκευής, τον ορισμό των σταθμών βλάβης και την απαίτηση παραμόρφωσης. Η τρωτότητα αποτελεί ένα σημαντικό εργαλείο στη συνέχεια για την εκτίμηση της διακινδύνευσης σε όρους οικονομικών απωλειών (ποσοστό του κόστους επισκευής σε σχέση με το κόστος αντικατάστασης) λόγω της συνδυασμένης επίδρασης των δύο φυσικών κινδύνων (σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση). Σημειώνεται ότι η απόκριση του ρευστοποιήσιμου εδάφους και στη συνέχεια τα μοντέλα ΔΑΕΚ επαληθεύονται μέσω των παρατηρούμενων τάσεων που επίσης εντοπίζονται στη βιβλιογραφία, ενώ οι προτεινόμενες καμπύλες και επιφάνειες τρωτότητας συγκρίνονται με ορισμένες αντίστοιχες αναλυτικές καθώς και δεδομένα πεδίου από τη βιβλιογραφία για την επαλήθευση της αξιοπιστίας τους.

I.4.1 Αριθμητικό προσομοίωμα

Η διδιάστατη αριθμητική προσομοίωση των υπό μελέτη συστημάτων εδάφους-κατασκευής πραγματοποιήθηκε με το πρόγραμμα πεπερασμένων στοιχείων OpenSees (Mazzoni et al. 2009). Για την προσομοίωση των κτιρίων, η ανελαστική συμπεριφορά δοκών και υποστυλωμάτων προσομοιώνεται χρησιμοποιώντας στοιχεία δοκού-υποστυλώματος με βάση τη μέθοδο των δυνάμεων. Η πλαστικότητα θεωρείται κατανομημένη σε όλο το μήκος των δομικών στοιχείων μέσω ινών που περιγράφουν τη συμπεριφορά των διατομών του κάθε μέλους και προσομοιώνεται μέσω μη-γραμμικών νόμων τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων. Για την περιγραφή της συμπεριφοράς του σκυροδέματος σε θλίψη χρησιμοποιείται το μοντέλο Kent-Scott-Park (Scott et al. 1982) με γραμμική μείωση της δυσκαμψίας υπό ανακυκλιζόμενη φόρτιση (Karsan and Jirsa 1969) και μηδενική εφελκυστική αντοχή ('Concrete01'), με διαφοροποίηση αντοχής και παραμορφωσιμότητας για το περισφιγμένο και το απερίσφιγτο σκυροδέμα. Για την προσομοίωση του χάλυβα θεωρείται διγραμμικός ελαστοπλαστικός νόμος με κινηματική κράτυνση ('Steel01'). Η μάζα θεωρείται ομοιόμορφα κατανομημένη κατά μήκος των δομικών στοιχείων.

Όσον αφορά το έδαφος, θεωρήθηκαν τρία εδαφικά προφίλ με υψηλό δυναμικό ρευστοποίησης (Σχήμα I.17), που χαρακτηρίζονται ως Α, Β και Γ, αντιπροσωπευτικά της

περιοχής του λιμανιού Θεσσαλονίκης (Anastasiadis et al. 2001, Pitilakis et al. 2018), κατηγορίας εδάφους S_2 σύμφωνα με τον Ευρωκώδικα 8 (EC8), απλοποιημένα ως προς το συνολικό τους βάθος, με θεμελιώδη ιδιοπερίοδο ίση με 0.88 sec, 0.73 sec, και 0.64 sec αντίστοιχα. Το δυναμικό ρευστοποίησης εκτιμήθηκε σύμφωνα με τον EC8 χρησιμοποιώντας τα διαθέσιμα γεωτεχνικά και εργαστηριακά δεδομένα της περιοχής του λιμανιού.

Σχήμα 1.17. Σχηματική αναπαράσταση των εδαφικών προφίλ Α (αριστερά), Β (μέση) και Γ (δεξιά) μαζί με γεωτεχνικό χαρακτηρισμό σύμφωνα με την ταξινόμηση USCS καθώς και των προφίλ διατμητικών ταχυτήτων V_s

Σημειώνεται ότι το μήκος των εδαφικών προφίλ Α, Β και Γ θεωρείται ίσο με το τριπλάσιο του ύψους τους (δηλαδή 60.0m x 180.0m, 50.0m x 150.0m και 46.0m x 138.0m αντίστοιχα), ώστε να εξασφαλιστούν στα άκρα συνθήκες ελευθέρου πεδίου. Για όλες τις περιπτώσεις υιοθετήθηκε πυκνή διακριτοποίηση βάσει της συχνότητας ενδιαφέροντος (10.0Hz) με τετράπλευρα στοιχεία 0.5m x 2.0m (ύψος x μήκος). Έγινε θεώρηση πλήρους σύνδεσης μεταξύ της θεμελίωσης της κατασκευής και των κόμβων του εδάφους. Η σύνδεση του εδάφους με την κατασκευή επιτυγχάνεται μέσω κοινών κόμβων όπου διασφαλίζεται κοινή μετατόπιση εδάφους και θεμελίωσης ανωδομής. Τα μεμονωμένα πέλδρα (εύκαμπτη θεμελίωση) προσομοιώνονται μέσω ελαστικών στοιχείων δοκού-υποστυλώματος, τα οποία επιτρέπουν τις διαφορικές μετακινήσεις των υποστυλωμάτων. Επιπλέον, σημειώνεται ότι δεν έχει ληφθεί υπόψη κάποια διεπιφάνεια μεταξύ της κατασκευής και της θεμελίωσης και ότι γίνεται η θεώρηση ότι η αστοχία μπορεί να εμφανιστεί μόνο στα δομικά στοιχεία της ανωδομής ενώ η δομική ακεραιότητα της θεμελίωσης (πέδλων) δε θα επηρεαστεί από την παραμόρφωση που προκαλείται λόγω της σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης και της ρευστοποίησης.

Κάθε εδαφικό προφίλ αποτελείται από διαφορετικές στρώσεις συνεκτικού και μη συνεκτικού εδάφους. Το βάθος του υδροφόρου ορίζοντα για κάθε εδαφικό προφίλ φαίνεται στο Σχήμα I.17. Διεξάγονται ανελαστικές δυναμικές αναλύσεις ενεργών τάσεων λαμβάνοντας υπόψη το κορεσμένο ειδικό βάρος για το έδαφος κάτω από αυτή τη στάθμη. Για την προσομοίωση του εδάφους χρησιμοποιούνται επιφανειακά εννιάκομβα στοιχεία επίπεδης παραμόρφωσης με βαθμούς ελευθερίας μετατόπισης και πίεσης του νερού των πόρων, με τα οποία λαμβάνονται υπόψη οι μεταβολές της πίεσης του νερού των πόρων και των ενεργών τάσεων κατά τη διάρκεια της σεισμικής διέγερσης. Επιπλέον, τα στοιχεία αυτά προσομοιώνουν τη σύζευξη ρευστού-στερεού, βάσει της θεωρίας Biot του πορώδους μέσου (Biot 1962). Η σεισμική εδαφική κίνηση, εισάγεται στο ελαστικό βραχώδες υπόβαθρο (Kwok et al. 2007), του οποίου η ταχύτητα διατμητικών κυμάτων (V_s) ισούται με 627m/s, 750m/s και 750m/s για τα εδαφικά προφίλ A, B και Γ αντίστοιχα, ενώ η πυκνότητά του είναι ίση με 2.2Mg/m^3 . Για την αποφυγή της ανάκλασης των σεισμικών κυμάτων στη βάση του κανάβου εφαρμόσθηκε κατάλληλος ιξώδης αποσβεστήρας για την προσομοίωση της απόσβεσης ακτινοβολίας. Για την προσομοίωση του βραχώδους υποβάθρου, αφήνεται ελεύθερη η μετατόπιση στην οριζόντια διεύθυνση των κόμβων στη βάση του κανάβου, ορίζεται κοινή μετατόπιση τους και απαγορεύεται η κατακόρυφη μετατόπιση τους. Στο Figure 6.4 απεικονίζονται τα προσομοιώματα πεπερασμένων στοιχείων των υπό μελέτη συστημάτων ΔΑΕΚ. Εφαρμόστηκε μια πλήρως συζευγμένη αριθμητική προσέγγιση πεπερασμένων στοιχείων, όπου η μετατόπιση του εδάφους (u) και η πίεση του νερού των πόρων (p) υπολογίζονται ταυτόχρονα σε κάθε χρονικό βήμα. Η προσέγγιση αυτή χρησιμοποιείται για την προσομοίωση της συγκέντρωσης μόνιμων τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων σε καθαρά μεσαίας πυκνότητας μη συνεκτικά εδάφη κατά τη διάρκεια της ρευστοποίησης λόγω της αυξημένης διατμητικής αντοχής και δυσκαμψίας υπό ανακυκλιζόμενη φόρτιση.

Κατά τη διάρκεια της στατικής ανάλυσης η συμπεριφορά του εδάφους λαμβάνεται γραμμική ελαστική, ενώ κατά τη δυναμική ανάλυση θεωρείται ελαστοπλαστική, όπου η σχέση τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων εκφράζεται μέσω ενός καταστατικού προσομοιώματος που συνδυάζει κινηματική κράτυνση με νόμο πλαστικής ροής και κριτήριο διαρροής ανάλογα αν πρόκειται για συνεκτικό ή μη συνεκτικό έδαφος και πολλαπλές επιφάνειες διαρροής (Prevost 1985). Έτσι λαμβάνεται υπόψη η διάχυση της υστερητικής ενέργειας καθώς και η δημιουργία πλαστικών παραμορφώσεων κατά τη διάρκεια της ισχυρής εδαφικής κίνησης. Η σκελετική μη γραμμική καμπύλη περιγράφεται βάσει του μοντέλου Masing (Masing 1926). Για την προσομοίωση μη συνεκτικών εδαφών στο OpenSees χρησιμοποιείται το ελαστοπλαστικό υλικό «PressureDependMultiYield02», όπου η σχέση τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων εκφράζεται μέσω ενός καταστατικού προσομοιώματος που συνδυάζει κινηματική κράτυνση με μη συσχετισμένο νόμο πλαστικής ροής (Parra 1996) με το

κριτήριο διαρροής Drucker-Prager και πολλαπλές επιφάνειες διαρροής. Για την προσομοίωση συνεκτικών εδαφών στο OpenSees χρησιμοποιείται το ελαστοπλαστικό υλικό «PressureIndependMultiYield», όπου η σχέση τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων εκφράζεται μέσω ενός καταστατικού προσομοιώματος που συνδυάζει κινηματική κράτυνση με συσχετισμένο νόμο πλαστικής ροής, με το κριτήριο διαρροής Von Mises και πολλαπλές επιφάνειες διαρροής.

Σχήμα I.18. Προσομοίωμα ΔΑΕΚ πεπερασμένων στοιχείων για το (α) διώροφο, (β) τετραώροφο και (γ) εννιαώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ που εδράζεται σε ρευστοποιήσιμο έδαφος

1.4.2 Σεισμικές διεγέρσεις εισαγωγής

Για την διεξαγωγή των μη γραμμικών βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικών δυναμικών αναλύσεων επιλέχθηκαν δεκαπέντε καταγραφές από πραγματικούς σεισμούς (Πίνακας 1.3) από την ευρωπαϊκή βάση δεδομένων ισχυρής εδαφικής κίνησης (<http://www.isesd.hi.is>). Οι καταγραφές που επιλέχθηκαν είναι σε επιφανειακή έξαρση βράχου ή σκληρού εδάφους και αντιστοιχούν σε κατηγορία εδάφους A και B σύμφωνα με τον Ευρωκώδικα 8 με μέγεθος (M_w) και επικεντρική απόσταση (R) που κυμαίνονται μεταξύ $5.5 < M_w < 6.5$ και $0 < R < 45 \text{ km}$ αντίστοιχα. Το βασικό κριτήριο επιλογής είναι το μέσο φάσμα επιταχύνσεων των καταγραφών για ένα εύρος περιόδων $0.00 < T < 2.00 \text{ sec}$ να προσεγγίζει κατά το δυνατόν το στοχευόμενο φάσμα αναφοράς, όπου οι φασματικές τιμές (διάμεσος +0.5 τυπική απόκλιση) εκτιμήθηκαν βάσει της σχέσης εκτίμησης της σεισμικής κίνησης κατά Akkar and Bommer (2010) χρησιμοποιώντας τις μέσες τιμές των M_w και R για τα ορισθέντα παραπάνω όρια. Η παραπάνω διαδικασία για την επιλογή των διεγέρσεων πραγματοποιήθηκε με τη βοήθεια του προγράμματος REXEL (Iervolino et al. 2010). Στο Figure 6.10 απεικονίζονται συγκριτικά το μέσο ελαστικό φάσμα των καταγραφών σε σχέση με το στοχευόμενο μέσο φάσμα αναφοράς όπου παρατηρείται πολύ καλή σύγκλιση.

Πίνακας 1.3. Σεισμικές διεγέρσεις για τη διεξαγωγή των δυναμικών αναλύσεων

Όνομα σεισμού	Ημερομηνία	M_w	Ρήγμα	Επικεντρική απόσταση [km]	PGA [m/s^2]	Κατηγορία εδάφους κατά EC8	ID
<i>Umbria Marche (aftershock)</i>	10/6/1997	5.5	κανονικό	5	1.838	A	651
<i>Valnerina</i>	9/19/1979	5.8	κανονικό	5	1.510	A	242
<i>SE of Tirana</i>	1/9/1988	5.9	επώθησης	7	4.037	A	3802
<i>Lazio Abruzzo (aftershock)</i>	5/11/1984	5.5	κανονικό	15	1.411	A	990
<i>Valnerina</i>	9/19/1979	5.8	κανονικό	5	2.012	A	242
<i>Kozani</i>	5/13/1995	6.5	κανονικό	17	2.039	A	6115
<i>Friuli (aftershock)</i>	9/15/1976	6.0	επώθησης	12	1.339	A	149
<i>Umbria Marche</i>	9/26/1997	5.7	κανονικό	23	1.645	A	763
<i>Friuli (aftershock)</i>	9/15/1976	6.0	επώθησης	14	2.586	B	134
<i>Patras</i>	7/14/1993	5.6	διεύθυνσης	9	3.337	B	1932
<i>Kalamata</i>	9/13/1986	5.9	κανονικό	11	2.670	B	414
<i>Umbria Marche 2</i>	9/26/1997	6.0	κανονικό	11	5.138	B	594
<i>Montenegro (aftershock)</i>	5/24/1979	6.2	επώθησης	17	1.708	B	229
<i>Kefallinia island</i>	1/23/1992	5.6	επώθησης	14	2.223	B	6040
<i>Ano Liosia</i>	9/7/1999	6.0	κανονικό	14	2.159	B	1714

Σχήμα 1.19. Σύγκριση μέσου ελαστικού φάσματος καταγραφών με το στοχευόμενο μέσο φάσμα αναφοράς των [Akkar and Bommer \(2010\)](#)

1.4.3 Μη γραμμικές βήμα προς βήμα δυναμικές αναλύσεις

Για την εκτίμηση της σεισμικής απόκρισης και στη συνέχεια τρωτότητας των υπό μελέτη κτιρίων συνεκτιμώντας τη ρευστοποίηση και τη ΔΑΕΚ διεξάγονται μη γραμμικές βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικές δυναμικές αναλύσεις. Τα υπό μελέτη εννιά συστήματα ΔΑΕΚ (συνδυασμοί των τριών κτιρίων και των τριών εδαφικών προφίλ) υποβάλλονται σε καταγραφές εδαφικής κίνησης, η καθεμία από τις οποίες κλιμακώνεται σε διάφορα επίπεδα έντασης καλύπτοντας το εύρος από την ελαστικότητα μέχρι και τη δυναμική αστάθεια της κατασκευής ([Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2002](#)). Παράγονται έτσι καμπύλες απόκρισης του κάθε συστήματος που εκφράζουν τη σχέση μεταξύ της παραμέτρου βλάβης και του επιπέδου έντασης. Στα πλαίσια της παρούσας μελέτης ως παράμετρος βλάβης επιλέχθηκε το μέγιστο σχετικό βέλος ορόφου ($\max\text{ISD}$) ενώ ως αρχικό μέτρο έντασης η μέγιστη εδαφική επιτάχυνση στον βράχο ($\text{PGA}_{\text{βράχο}}$).

Οι μη γραμμικές βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικές δυναμικές αναλύσεις διεξήχθησαν για όλα τα προσομοιώματα για τις δεκαπέντε προοδευτικά κλιμακούμενες σεισμικές διεγέρσεις. Η κλιμάκωση των καταγραφών έγινε θεωρώντας μια πρώτη ελαστική ανάλυση για 0.05g, αρχικό βήμα ίσο με 0.1g, επαυξητικό βήμα ίσο με 0.1g, έως 1.0g το οποίο θεωρείται μια ακραία τιμή PGA στον βράχο. Επιπλέον, πραγματοποιείται μια δεύτερη σειρά μη γραμμικών βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικών δυναμικών αναλύσεων για τα εννιά μοντέλα ΔΑΕΚ θεωρώντας κλίση στο έδαφος ίση με 5% ώστε να διερευνηθεί περεταίρω η συμβολή τη πλευρικής εξάπλωσης που προκαλείται από την ρευστοποίηση. Διεξάγονται δώδεκα αναλύσεις για κάθε καταγραφή, πραγματοποιώντας έτσι συνολικά 3240 μη γραμμικές δυναμικές αναλύσεις. Σημειώνεται ότι το κύριο μειονέκτημα αυτής της προσέγγισης είναι το υψηλό υπολογιστικό κόστος, το οποίο είναι σημαντικό για ιδιαίτερα μη γραμμικά προβλήματα.

I.4.3.1 Ενδεικτικά αποτελέσματα εδαφικής απόκρισης στο ελεύθερο πεδίο

Οι ρευστοποιημένες εδαφικές στρώσεις εντοπίζονται στα βάθη όπου μηδενίζεται η μέση ενεργός τάση (Σχήμα I.20 πάνω αριστερά) και είναι εμφανής και από τους βρόγχους υστέρησης τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων στα αντίστοιχα βάθη (Σχήμα I.20 πάνω δεξιά).

Σχήμα I.20. Μεταβολή της μέσης ενεργού τάσης με το βάθος (αριστερά) και βρόγχοι υστέρησης τάσεων-παραμορφώσεων σε βάθος 7.0 m (δεξιά) για το εδαφικό προφίλ B για τη σεισμική διέγερση με ID 229 (πάνω) και την ίδια σεισμική διέγερση σε κλίμακα PGA ίση με 0.3g (κάτω)

Γενικά, επιβεβαιώνεται ότι το πρόγραμμα πεπερασμένων στοιχείων OpenSees είναι κατάλληλο για την προσομοίωση εδαφών με υψηλό δυναμικό ρευστοποίησης, όπου λαμβάνονται υπόψη οι μεταβολές της πίεσης του νερού των πόρων και των ενεργών τάσεων κατά τη διάρκεια της σεισμικής διέγερσης. Ενδεικτικά, στο Σχήμα I.21 παρουσιάζεται η μεταβολή της μέσης ενεργού τάσης με το βάθος για το εδαφικό προφίλ Γ για τέσσερις σεισμικές διεγέρσεις κλιμακούμενες σε διαφορετικές PGA. Συγκεκριμένα παρουσιάζονται συγκρίσεις των σεισμικών διεγέρσεων Montenegro (aftershock), Kefallinia island, Ano Liosia και Kalamata (με κωδικούς 229, 6040, 1714, and 414 αντίστοιχα) με μέσες περιόδους T_m ίσες με 0.26sec, 0.30sec, 0.43sec και 0.53sec αντίστοιχα. Παρατηρείται ότι το φαινόμενο της ρευστοποίησης συμβαίνει για τιμή PGA στον βράχο ίση ή μεγαλύτερη από 0.1g. Επιπλέον, καθώς αυξάνεται η ένταση της σεισμικής εδαφικής

κίνησης η ρευστοποίηση εκτείνεται σε μεγαλύτερο βάθος. Αυτές οι παρατηρήσεις επιβεβαιώνονται και από τη διαθέσιμη βιβλιογραφία (Koutsourelakis et al. 2002, Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi 2008).

Σχήμα 1.21. Μεταβολή της μέσης ενεργού τάσης με το βάθος για το εδαφικό προφίλ Γ για τέσσερις σεισμικές διεγέρσεις κλιμακούμενες σε διαφορετικές PGA

Επιπλέον, μελετάται η τροποποίηση της σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης λόγω της ρευστοποίησης του εδάφους. Το Σχήμα 1.22 απεικονίζει τη σχέση της $PGA_{\text{επιφ}}$ στην επιφάνεια στο ελεύθερο πεδίο συναρτήσει της $PGA_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο που προκύπτει από τις δυναμικές αναλύσεις σε επίπεδο έδαφος και σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5%. Για τιμή $PGA_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο μικρότερη από 0.2g παρατηρείται ενίσχυση της τιμής PGA στην επιφάνεια σε σχέση με τον βράχο, ενώ για υψηλότερες τιμές εξασθένιση της σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και συνεπώς της $PGA_{\text{επιφ}}$ στην επιφάνεια. Η τάση αυτή είναι σύμφωνη και με τη διαθέσιμη βιβλιογραφία (Lopez-Caballero and Modaressi Farahmand-Razavi 2008). Ακόμη, θεωρήθηκε σκόπιμο να εξεταστεί και η μεταβολή της μέγιστης εδαφικής ταχύτητας $PGV_{\text{επιφ}}$ στην επιφάνεια στο ελεύθερο πεδίο σε σχέση με την $PGV_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο σε επίπεδο έδαφος και σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5%. Όπως φαίνεται στο Σχήμα 1.23, για τιμή $PGV_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο μικρότερη από 15.0cm/sec παρατηρείται μια θετική σχεδόν γραμμική συσχέτιση με την $PGV_{\text{επιφ}}$ στην επιφάνεια στο ελεύθερο πεδίο. Για υψηλότερες τιμές

$PGV_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο παρατηρείται είτε ενίσχυση ή εξασθένηση της $PGV_{\text{επιφ}}$ στην επιφάνεια ανάλογα με την καταγραφή. Παρατηρείται επίσης ότι για τιμή $PGV_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο μεγαλύτερη από περίπου 40.0cm/sec προκύπτει κυρίως εξασθένηση της $PGV_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο. Όμοιες τάσεις παρατηρούνται και σε έδαφος σε κλίση.

Σχήμα 1.22. Σχέση μεταξύ της $PGA_{\text{επιφ}}$ στην επιφάνεια στο ελεύθερο πεδίο και της $PGA_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο που προκύπτει από τις δυναμικές αναλύσεις σε επίπεδο έδαφος (αριστερά) και σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5% (δεξιά)

Σχήμα 1.23. Σχέση μεταξύ της $PGV_{\text{επιφ}}$ στην επιφάνεια στο ελεύθερο πεδίο και της $PGV_{\text{βράχο}}$ στον βράχο που προκύπτει από τις δυναμικές αναλύσεις σε επίπεδο έδαφος (αριστερά) και σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5% (δεξιά)

1.4.3.2 Καμπύλες απόκρισης μη γραμμικών βήμα προς βήμα δυναμικών αναλύσεων

Με βάση τα ζεύγη PGA και $\max ISD$ όπως προέκυψαν από κάθε δυναμική ανάλυση, κατασκευάστηκαν οι καμπύλες απόκρισης των βήμα προς βήμα δυναμικών αναλύσεων αυξανόμενης έντασης για τα υπό μελέτη κτίρια σε κάθε θεωρούμενο εδαφικό προφίλ. Στα σχήματα που ακολουθούν φαίνονται οι δεκαπέντε παραχθείσες καμπύλες απόκρισης και οι ποσοστιαίες καμπύλες 16%, 50% (διάμεσος) και 84% για τα υπό μελέτη κτίρια (χαμηλό,

μεσαίου ύψους και υψηλό) που εδράζονται στα εδαφικά προφίλ Α, Β και Γ σε επίπεδο έδαφος και σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5% (Σχήμα Ι.24, Σχήμα Ι.25 και Σχήμα Ι.26 αντίστοιχα).

Σχήμα Ι.24. Καμπύλες απόκρισης των βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικών δυναμικών αναλύσεων για το χαμηλό κτίριο που εδράζεται στα εδαφικά προφίλ Α, Β και Γ σε επίπεδο έδαφος (αριστερά) και σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5% (δεξιά)

Σχήμα Ι.25. Καμπύλες απόκρισης των βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικών δυναμικών αναλύσεων για το μεσαίου ύψους κτίριο που εδράζεται στα εδαφικά προφίλ Α, Β και Γ σε επίπεδο έδαφος (αριστερά) και σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5% (δεξιά)

Σχήμα Ι.26. Καμπύλες απόκρισης των βήμα προς βήμα επαυξητικών δυναμικών αναλύσεων για το υψηλό κτίριο που εδράζεται στα εδαφικά προφίλ Α, Β και Γ σε επίπεδο έδαφος (αριστερά) και σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5% (δεξιά)

Ι.4.4 Ανάπτυξη σχέσεων μεταξύ διαφορετικών μετακινήσεων και μόνιμων μετακινήσεων στην επιφάνεια

Σε αυτή την ενότητα, μέσω ανάλυσης παλινδρόμησης καθορίζονται σχέσεις μεταξύ των μέγιστων διαφορικών μόνιμων εδαφικών μετακινήσεων στο επίπεδο θεμελίωσης και της μόνιμης εδαφικής μετατόπισης στην επιφάνεια κάτω από την κατασκευή, για τις υπό μελέτη τυπολογίες κτιρίων που υπόκεινται σε συνδυασμένη σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση

και ρευστοποίηση, όταν εδράζονται σε επίπεδο έδαφος ή σε κεκλιμένο. Διαφορετικές τάσεις εντοπίζονται ανάλογα με το αν το κτίριο εδράζεται σε επίπεδο ή σε επικλινές έδαφος. Συγκεκριμένα, για κτίρια με εύκαμπτη θεμελίωση (μεμονωμένα πέλδιλα) σε επίπεδο έδαφος παρατηρείται πολυωνυμική τάση (Σχήμα I.27) μεταξύ των λογαρίθμων της μέγιστης διαφορικής μετακίνησης (συνισταμένης ή καθίζησης) και της μέγιστης εδαφικής μόνιμης συνισταμένης μετακίνησης (PGD), ενώ για κτίρια σε κεκλιμένο έδαφος (κλίση 5%) γραμμική τάση (Σχήμα I.28).

Σχήμα I.27. Σχέση μεταξύ της μέγιστης διαφορικής συνισταμένης μετακίνησης και της μόνιμης μετακίνησης PGD στην επιφάνεια σε επίπεδο έδαφος

Σχήμα I.28. Σχέση μεταξύ της μέγιστης διαφορικής συνισταμένης μετακίνησης και της μόνιμης μετακίνησης PGD στην επιφάνεια σε έδαφος σε κλίση 5%

I.4.5 Εκτίμηση τρωτότητας

Για την εκτίμηση της τρωτότητας καθορίζονται τέσσερις οριακές στάθμες βλάβης σε όρους μέγιστου σχετικού βέλους κάμψης με βάση τις αναλύσεις που διεξήχθησαν, τη διαθέσιμη βιβλιογραφία (Ghobarah 2004, Petridis and Pitilakis 2018, Pitilakis et al. 2014) και την έμπειρη κρίση μηχανικού. Ο Πίνακας I.4 παρουσιάζει τις οριακές στάθμες βλάβης που υιοθετήθηκαν.

Πίνακας I.4. Οριακές τιμές στάθμης βλάβης για κάθε τυπολογία κτιρίου που εξετάστηκε

Στάθμες βλάβης	Πλαισιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένων βάσει χαμηλού επιπέδου κανονισμού		
	Χαμηλά	Μέσου ύψους	Ψηλά
LS1	0.002	0.002	0.002
LS2	0.005	0.005	0.005
LS3	0.008	0.008	0.010
LS4	0.010	0.013	0.0225

Τα αποτελέσματα των μη γραμμικών βήμα προς βήμα δυναμικών αναλύσεων αυξανόμενης έντασης ($PGA_{\text{βράχο-maxISD}}$ ή $PGV_{\text{βράχο-maxISD}}$) χρησιμοποιούνται για την εκτίμηση των καμπυλών τρωτότητας που περιγράφουν την κατανομή της πιθανότητας υπέρβασης της κάθε στάθμης βλάβης και εκφράζονται βάσει της ακόλουθης κανονικής λογαριθμικής κατανομής:

$$P[DS_i/IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM) - \ln(\overline{IM}_i)}{\beta}\right) \quad (I.5)$$

όπου Φ : η τυπική κανονική αθροιστική συνάρτηση, DS : η στάθμη βλάβης, IM : το μέτρο έντασης που στην παρούσα μεθοδολογία εκφράζεται σε όρους μέγιστης εδαφικής επιτάχυνσης ή ταχύτητας στον βράχο, \overline{IM}_i και β : η διάμεσος και η λογαριθμοκανονική τυπική απόκλιση των καμπυλών τρωτότητας αντίστοιχα. Οι τιμές των λογαριθμοκανονικών παραμέτρων (διάμεσος και διασπορά) των καμπυλών τρωτότητας που αντιστοιχούν στις καθορισμένες στάθμες βλάβης, υπολογίζονται με ανάλυση παλινδρόμησης των αποτελεσμάτων των μη γραμμικών βήμα προς βήμα δυναμικών αναλύσεων αυξανόμενης έντασης ($PGA_{\text{βράχο-maxISD}}$ ή $PGV_{\text{βράχο-maxISD}}$). Στο Σχήμα I.29 παρουσιάζεται ενδεικτικά η σχέση $PGV_{\text{βράχο-μέγιστου}}$ σχετικού βέλους ορόφου (maxISD) για το χαμηλό πλαισιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σχεδιασμένο με χαμηλό επίπεδο κανονισμού. Στο σχήμα απεικονίζονται επίσης οι οριακές τιμές μέγιστου σχετικού βέλους ορόφου (maxISD) για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης.

Σχήμα I.29. Σχέση $PGV_{\text{βράχο-μέγιστου}}$ σχετικού βέλους ορόφου (maxISD) για το δώροφο πλαισιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ

Τέλος, οι καμπύλες τρωτότητας για τις διάφορες στάθμες βλάβης παράγονται μετά από κατάλληλη μέθοδο στατιστικής επεξεργασίας της απόκρισης (σε επίπεδο μέγιστου σχετικού βέλους ορόφου), σε σχέση με την παράμετρο της έντασης της σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης ($PGA_{\text{βράχο}}$ ή $PGV_{\text{βράχο}}$) και τις οριζόμενες στάθμες βλάβης. Στο Σχήμα I.30 και στο Σχήμα I.31 δίδονται οι προτεινόμενες καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης για τις εξεταζόμενες τυπολογίες κτιρίων σε επίπεδο και κεκλιμένο έδαφος αντίστοιχα.

Σχήμα I.30. Καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης για τις διαφορετικές τυπολογίες κτιρίων σε έδαφος επίπεδο

Σχήμα Ι.31. Καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility curves) λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης για τις διαφορετικές τυπολογίες κτιρίων σε έδαφος κεκλιμένο (κλίση 5%)

Λόγω της πολυπλοκότητας του προβλήματος και της έντονης μη γραμμικότητας λόγω ρευστοποίησης, εκτός από την πρόταση συμβατικών καμπυλών τρωτότητας, θεωρήθηκε σκόπιμο να προταθούν και επιφάνειες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility surfaces) συναρτήσε δύο μέτρων σεισμικής έντασης. Η χρήση δύο μέτρων σεισμικής έντασης αντί ενός μπορεί να βελτιώσει σημαντικά την εκτίμηση της πιθανότητας εμφάνισης ενός επιπέδου βλάβης (Baker and Cornell 2005, Gehl et al. 2013). Η ακόλουθη διαδικασία, εμπνευσμένη από τους Baker and Cornel (2005) και τους Malaga-Chuquitaype and Bougatsas (2017), χρησιμοποιήθηκε για την εκτίμηση των προτεινόμενων επιφανειών

τρωτότητας. Συγκεκριμένα, γραμμική παλινδρόμηση υιοθετείται για τη συσχέτιση της παραμέτρου βλάβης (μέγιστο σχετικό βέλος ορόφου-maxISD) και των δύο μέτρων σεισμικής έντασης. Η πιθανότητα υπέρβασης της κάθε στάθμης βλάβης συναρτηθεί των δύο μέτρων σεισμικής έντασης (IM_1 και IM_2) εκφράζεται βάσει της ακόλουθης σχέσης:

$$P[DS_i/IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM_1) - (b_0 + b_1 \times \ln(IM_2))}{\beta}\right) \quad (I.6)$$

όπου Φ : η διδιάστατη κανονική αθροιστική συνάρτηση κατανομής, b_0 και b_1 : συντελεστές παλινδρόμησης, $\overline{IM_2}$ και β : η διάμεσος του δεύτερου μέτρου σεισμικής έντασης και η λογαριθμοκανονική τυπική απόκλιση των επιφανειών τρωτότητας αντίστοιχα για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης i and DS_i : η στάθμη βλάβης.

Η σχέση μεταξύ των δύο μέτρων σεισμικής έντασης προκύπτει από γραμμική παλινδρόμηση των λογαρίθμων των ζευγών IM_1 και IM_2 σύμφωνα με την ακόλουθη εξίσωση:

$$\ln(IM_1) = b_0 + b_1 \times \ln(IM_2) \quad (I.7)$$

Στο Σχήμα I.32 παρουσιάζεται ένα γράφημα ανάλυσης παλινδρόμησης των λογαρίθμων των ζευγών PGV (IM_1) και PGD (IM_2) στην επιφάνεια για το δώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος που υπόκειται σε σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση.

Σχήμα I.32. Ανάλυση παλινδρόμησης των λογαρίθμων των ζευγών PGV και PGD για το δώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος που υπόκειται σε σεισμική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση

Για την ανάπτυξη των επιφανειών τρωτότητας σύμφωνα με την εξίσωση I.6, οι διάμεσοι των IM_1 και IM_2 καθώς και η λογαριθμοκανονική τυπική απόκλιση β πρέπει να υπολογισθεί. Για το λόγο αυτό, παρόμοια διαδικασία με αυτή που ακολουθήθηκε για την ανάπτυξη των καμπυλών τρωτότητας χρησιμοποιείται. Συγκεκριμένα, εκτός από το IM_1 , λαμβάνεται υπόψη και το IM_2 στην εκτίμηση της απόκρισης σε όρους μέγιστου σχετικού

βέλους ορόφου (maxISD). Καταρχήν σε όλες τις περιπτώσεις υιοθετείται γραμμική παλινδρόμηση των λογαρίθμων των ζευγών IM_1 -maxISD, που ελαχιστοποιεί τα υπολείμματα της παλινδρόμησης (regression residuals). Στο Σχήμα I.33 παρουσιάζεται ένα γράφημα ανάλυσης παλινδρόμησης των λογαρίθμων των ζευγών PGV (IM_1) και maxISD για το δώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος που υπόκειται σε σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση.

Σχήμα I.33. Ανάλυση παλινδρόμησης των λογαρίθμων των ζευγών PGV και maxISD για το δώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος που υπόκειται σε σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση

Στη συνέχεια, εκτελείται άλλη μία ανάλυση παλινδρόμησης των υπολειμμάτων (residuals) της προηγούμενης παλινδρόμησης βάσει του IM_1 και των λογαρίθμων του IM_2 , όπου παρατηρείται γραμμική τάση μεταξύ τους. Συνεπώς, η συσχέτιση της παραμέτρου βλάβης (EDP) με δύο μέτρα σεισμικής έντασης (IM_1 και IM_2) δίνεται από την εξίσωση:

$$\ln(EDP) = a \ln(IM_1) + b \ln(IM_2) + c + \varepsilon \cdot \sigma \quad (I.8)$$

όπου EDP: η παράμετρος βλάβης σε όρους μέγιστου σχετικού βέλους ορόφου (maxISD), IM_1 και IM_2 : είναι τα μέτρα σεισμικής έντασης σε όρους PGA_{ff} ή PGV και PGD στην επιφάνεια αντίστοιχα (οι τιμές των οποίων προκύπτουν από τα αποτελέσματα των μη γραμμικών βήμα προς βήμα δυναμικών αναλύσεων αυξανόμενης έντασης), a , b , και c : συντελεστές παλινδρόμησης, ε : η τυπική κανονική μεταβλητή με μηδενική μέση τιμή και τυπική απόκλιση ίση με μονάδα και η διασπορά σ (σ): η συνήθης τυπική απόκλιση της παλινδρόμησης (σε λογαριθμική κλίμακα) που αποτελεί και μέτρο της αποδοτικότητας (efficiency) των μέτρων σεισμικής έντασης σε σχέση με την παράμετρο βλάβης (maxISD).

Επιπλέον, ο συντελεστής προσδιορισμού, R^2 , συμπεριλαμβάνεται ως ένα ακόμη καλό μέτρο για την εκτίμηση του βαθμού εξάρτησης (συσχέτισης) του IM_1 από το IM_2 . Τιμές R^2

που πλησιάζουν το μηδέν δείχνουν ανεξάρτητα (ασυσχέτιστα) μέτρα σεισμικής έντασης. Σημειώνεται ότι προβλήματα μπορούν να προκύψουν όταν εκτελείται γραμμική ανάλυση παλινδρόμησης μεταξύ έντονα συσχετισμένων μέτρων σεισμικής έντασης (Malaga-Chuquitaype and Bougatsas 2017).

Επομένως, οι διάμεσοι των IM_1 και IM_2 για κάθε στάθμη βλάβης εκτιμώνται βάσει της ανάλυσης παλινδρόμησης μεταξύ των υπολειμμάτων (residuals) της παλινδρόμησης βάσει του IM_1 και των λογαρίθμων του IM_2 , σε συνδυασμό με την εξίσωση I.7. Στο Σχήμα I.34 παρουσιάζεται ένα γράφημα ανάλυσης παλινδρόμησης των υπολειμμάτων (residuals) της παλινδρόμησης βάσει της PGV (IM_1) και των λογαρίθμων της PGD (IM_2) για το διώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος που υπόκειται σε σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση.

Σχήμα I.34. Ανάλυση παλινδρόμησης των υπολειμμάτων (residuals) της παλινδρόμησης βάσει της PGV και των λογαρίθμων της PGD για το διώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος που υπόκειται σε σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση

Τέλος, ο Πίνακας I.5 και ο Πίνακας I.6 παρουσιάζουν συγκεντρωμένα τις παραμέτρους των επιφανειών τρωτότητας σε όρους PGA_{ff} -PGD και PGV-PGD αντίστοιχα για τις διάφορες στάθμες βλάβης των υπό μελέτη κτιρίων Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος που υπόκειται σε σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση. Ακόμη, ο Πίνακας I.7 και ο Πίνακας I.8 παρουσιάζουν συγκεντρωμένα τις παραμέτρους των επιφανειών τρωτότητας για τα υπό μελέτη κτίρια Ο/Σ σε κεκλιμένο έδαφος (κλίση 5%). Ενδεικτικά στο Σχήμα I.35 παρουσιάζονται οι επιφάνειες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility surfaces) συναρτήσεως των PGA_{ff} and PGD για τις τέσσερις στάθμες βλάβης (LS_1 , LS_2 , LS_3 και LS_4) για το διώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος που υπόκειται σε σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση.

Πίνακας I.5. Παράμετροι επιφανειών τρωτότητας λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης σε όρους PGA_{ff} και PGD για τα υπό μελέτη κτίρια Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος

Τυπολογία κτιρίου	Διάμεσος PGA_{ff} (g)				Διάμεσος PGD (m)				Διασπορά β
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	
Διώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.05	0.13	0.20	0.26	0.004	0.029	0.082	0.134	0.79
Τετραώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.05	0.15	0.26	0.44	0.005	0.048	0.158	0.541	0.85
Εννιαώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.09	0.22	-	-	0.021	0.117	-	-	0.67

Πίνακας I.6. Παράμετροι επιφανειών τρωτότητας λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης σε όρους PGV και PGD για τα υπό μελέτη κτίρια Ο/Σ σε επίπεδο έδαφος

Τυπολογία κτιρίου	Διάμεσος PGV (m/sec)				Διάμεσος PGD (m)				Διασπορά β
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	
Διώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.06	0.13	0.20	0.25	0.010	0.036	0.068	0.091	0.57
Τετραώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.07	0.16	0.24	0.38	0.013	0.050	0.100	0.204	0.63
Εννιαώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.09	0.21	0.43	-	0.029	0.098	0.249	-	0.53

Πίνακας I.7. Παράμετροι επιφανειών τρωτότητας λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης σε όρους PGA_{ff} και PGD για τα υπό μελέτη κτίρια Ο/Σ σε κεκλιμένο έδαφος

Τυπολογία κτιρίου	Διάμεσος PGA_{ff} (g)				Διάμεσος PGD (m)				Διασπορά β
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	
Διώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.05	0.14	0.24	0.31	0.005	0.115	0.594	1.292	0.76
Τετραώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.06	0.16	0.26	0.44	0.008	0.167	0.801	4.046	0.82
Εννιαώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.09	0.23	0.49	-	0.032	0.518	4.236	-	0.73

Πίνακας I.8. Παράμετροι επιφανειών τρωτότητας λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης σε όρους PGV και PGD για τα υπό μελέτη κτίρια Ο/Σ σε κεκλιμένο έδαφος

Τυπολογία κτιρίου	Διάμεσος PGV (m/sec)				Διάμεσος PGD (m)				Διασπορά β
	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	LS1	LS2	LS3	LS4	
Διώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.08	0.17	0.24	0.28	0.013	0.118	0.367	0.627	0.60
Τετραώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.10	0.18	0.25	0.34	0.019	0.152	0.441	1.328	0.64
Εννιαώροφο πλαισιακό Ο/Σ	0.12	0.23	0.37	-	0.049	0.332	1.404	-	0.55

Σχήμα 1.35. Επιφάνειες τρωτότητας σε όρους πιθανότητας υπέρβασης (fragility surfaces) λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης συναρτήσει των PGA_{ff} and PGD για τις τέσσερις στάθμες βλάβης (LS_1 , LS_2 , LS_3 και LS_4) για το δώροφο πλαίσιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ σε έδαφος επίπεδο

Αποδείχθηκε ότι το ύψος του κτιρίου αποτελεί μια σημαντική παράμετρο που μπορεί να επηρεάσει σημαντικά την τρωτότητα του έναντι σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης και ρευστοποίησης. Πιο συγκεκριμένα, τα χαμηλά πλαίσιακα κτίρια Ο/Σ που έχουν σχεδιασθεί και κατασκευαστεί βάσει χαμηλού επιπέδου κανονισμού είναι πιο τρωτά συγκριτικά με τα μέσου ύψους και ψηλά. Αυτό μπορεί να οφείλεται στο γεγονός ότι όσο το ύψος του κτιρίου αυξάνει, το κτίριο τείνει να συμπεριφέρεται ως άκαμπτο σώμα και τείνει να ανατραπεί. Ακόμη, η τάση αυτή οφείλεται και στην αύξηση των ενεργών τάσεων κάτω από την κατασκευή λόγω της αύξησης του βάρους της, με αποτέλεσμα την αύξηση της αντίστασης έναντι της απώλειας αντοχής, γεγονός που μειώνει ελαφρώς τις διατμητικές παραμορφώσεις κάτω από την κατασκευή. Σημειώνεται επίσης ότι σε περιοχές όπου υπήρχε εκτεταμένη ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους μετά από ένα σεισμό, βλάβες εντοπιζόταν σε χαμηλά και μέσου ύψους κτίρια, π.χ. μετά το σεισμό του 1990 στο νησί Luzon στις Φιλιππίνες (Tokimatsu et al. 1994). Επιπλέον, παρατηρείται ότι τα πλαίσιακα κτίρια Ο/Σ που έχουν σχεδιασθεί βάσει χαμηλού επιπέδου κανονισμού σε έδαφος με κλίση είναι πιθανόν να υποστούν περισσότερες βλάβες λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης συγκριτικά με αυτά σε έδαφος επίπεδο. Αυτό είναι επίσης σε συμφωνία με παρατηρήσεις στο πεδίο, καθώς σε συνθήκες κλίσης οι κατασκευές υποβάλλονται σε

πλευρική εξάπλωση λόγω ρευστοποίησης, η οποία συνεπάγεται μεγάλες πλευρικές εδαφικές μετακινήσεις καθώς και σημαντικές διαφορικές μετακινήσεις με αποτέλεσμα εκτεταμένες παραμορφώσεις των κτιρίων και συνεπώς περισσότερες βλάβες.

I.4.6 Αξιολόγηση των συναρτήσεων τρωτότητας

Στόχος αυτής της ενότητας είναι η επαλήθευση της αξιοπιστίας των προτεινόμενων καμπυλών και επιφανειών τρωτότητας. Για το σκοπό αυτό πραγματοποιήθηκαν συγκρίσεις αυτών με παρατηρήσεις στο πεδίο έπειτα από σεισμούς που προκάλεσαν εκτεταμένη ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους. Συγκεκριμένα, μετά το σεισμό της 22 Φεβρουαρίου 2011 στην πόλη Christchurch στη Νέα Ζηλανδία και λόγω εκτεταμένης ρευστοποίησης του εδάφους, ένα εξάωρο φλαισιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ με εύκαμπτη θεμελίωση που απεικονίζεται στο Σχήμα I.36 υποβλήθηκε σε διαφορική καθίζηση 25.0cm. Το κτίριο αυτό θεωρήθηκε μη οικονομικό να επισκευαστεί (Bray και Dashti 2014), κάτι το οποίο είναι σε συμφωνία με τις καμπύλες τρωτότητας που προτείνονται στην ενότητα I.3 για το μέσου ύψους φλαισιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ, όπου η διάμεσος σε όρους διαφορικής μετακίνησης για τη στάθμη βλάβης κατάρρευσης είναι ίση με 30.0cm. Ακόμη, σε έναν από τους σταθμούς στην περιοχή καταγράφηκε μέγιστη επιτάχυνση του εδάφους (PGA) ίση με 0.42g (Bray et al. 2014). Η παρατήρηση αυτή είναι επίσης σε συμφωνία με τις προτεινόμενες επιφάνειες τρωτότητας για το μέσου ύψους φλαισιακό κτίριο Ο/Σ όπου η διάμεσος σε όρους PGA_{ff} στην επιφάνεια στο ελεύθερο πεδίο για τη στάθμη βλάβης κατάρρευσης είναι ίση με 0.44g. Επιπλέον, χρησιμοποιώντας τη σχέση που προτείνεται στο Σχήμα I.27, για μια τιμή PGD ίση με 0.49cm (που αντιστοιχεί στην PGA_{ff} των 0.42g), υπολογίζεται διαφορική καθίζηση ίση με 24.5cm, πολύ κοντά στην τιμή των 25.0cm που καταγράφηκε. Συνεπώς, τα συμπεράσματα της παρούσας διατριβής είναι σε συμφωνία με τις παρατηρήσεις στο πεδίο.

Σχήμα I.36. Κτίριο Ο/Σ με εύκαμπτη θεμελίωση που υποβλήθηκε σε σημαντικές διαφορικές καθιζήσεις λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης και ρευστοποίησης (Bray and Dashti 2014)

I.5 Εκτίμηση της διακινδύνευσης των κτιρίων του λιμανιού της Θεσσαλονίκης λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης

Στόχος του κεφαλαίου αυτού είναι η επαλήθευση της αξιοπιστίας και της εφαρμοσιμότητας των προτεινόμενων συναρτήσεων τρωτότητας μέσω της εφαρμογής τους στην εκτίμηση της διακινδύνευσης λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης βάσει σεισμικών σεναρίων, των κτιρίων του λιμένα Θεσσαλονίκης, έναν από τους μεγαλύτερους λιμένες στην Ελλάδα. Δύο σεισμικά σενάρια καθορίζονται σε αυτή τη μελέτη, το σενάριο σχεδιασμού που αντιστοιχεί σε περίοδο επαναφοράς 475 χρόνων και ένα ακραίο που αντιστοιχεί σε περίοδο επαναφοράς 4975 χρόνων. Για κάθε σεισμικό σενάριο ορίζεται ένα φάσμα-στόχος για συνθήκες βράχου με βάση το οποίο επιλέγονται καταγραφές από πραγματικούς σεισμούς.

Η διακινδύνευση εκτιμάται λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τις πιθανές βλάβες και απώλειες των κτιρίων του λιμένα για τα δύο σεισμικά σενάρια πραγματοποιώντας μη γραμμικές δυναμικές αναλύσεις απόκρισης σε τυπικά εδαφικά προφίλ του λιμανιού με υψηλό δυναμικό ρευστοποίησης χρησιμοποιώντας τις επιλεγμένες καταγραφές. Ένας δομικός δείκτης βλάβης σταθμισμένος σε σχέση με τη δομημένη περιοχή εκτιμάται ώστε να εκτιμηθεί η διακινδύνευση σε όρους οικονομικών απωλειών (λόγος του κόστους επισκευής προς το κόστος αντικατάστασης). Η χωρική κατανομή των απωλειών των κτιρίων του λιμανιού Θεσσαλονίκης για το σενάριο των 475 (επάνω) και 4975 χρόνων (κάτω) παρουσιάζεται στο Σχήμα I.37. Αποδείχθηκε ότι τα κτίρια Ο/Σ του λιμανιού Θεσσαλονίκης αναμένεται να παρουσιάσουν λιγότερες απώλειες συγκριτικά με τις μεταλλικές αποθήκες.

Γενικά, φαίνεται ότι οι προτεινόμενες συναρτήσεις τρωτότητας μπορούν να βρουν άμεση εφαρμογή σε ένα πιθανοτικό πλαίσιο εκτίμησης της διακινδύνευσης λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής κίνησης και ρευστοποίησης τυπικών κτιρίων Ο/Σ και μεταλλικών πλαισιακών αποθηκών στην Ελλάδα και τη Νότια Ευρώπη, όπου συναντώνται αντίστοιχες τυπολογίες κτιρίων. Οι αρμόδιοι φορείς θα μπορούσαν να τις αξιοποιήσουν εκτιμώντας τη διακινδύνευση των κατασκευών που βρίσκονται υπό την ευθύνη τους με στόχο την ενίσχυση της ανθεκτικότητας τους. Σημειώνεται επίσης ότι για την εκτίμηση της τρωτότητας και διακινδύνευσης κτιρίων σε περιοχές με υψηλό δυναμικό ρευστοποίησης, όπου δεν μπορούν να διεξαχθούν μη γραμμικές δυναμικές αναλύσεις απόκρισης του εδάφους λόγω της έλλειψης γεωτεχνικών δεδομένων, θα μπορούσαν να χρησιμοποιηθούν οι προτεινόμενες καμπύλες τρωτότητας σε όρους $PGA_{\beta\rho\alpha\chi\omicron}$ ή $PGV_{\beta\rho\alpha\chi\omicron}$.

Σχήμα Ι.37. Χωρική κατανομή των απωλειών των κτιρίων του λιμανιού Θεσσαλονίκης για το σενάριο των 475 (επάνω) και 4975 χρόνων (κάτω)

I.6 Συμπεράσματα

Οι καταστρεπτικές συνέπειες των φυσικών κινδύνων που προκαλούνται από σεισμό, όπως σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση, ρευστοποίηση και τσουνάμι, καθιστούν επιτακτική την ανάγκη ανάπτυξης μεθοδολογιών για την αποτελεσματική αποτίμηση και στη συνέχεια μείωση της τρωτότητας και διακινδύνευσης έναντι αυτών. Ωστόσο, οι περισσότερες από τις υπάρχουσες μελέτες στη διαθέσιμη βιβλιογραφία παρέχουν καμπύλες τρωτότητας λόγω της σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης και δεν επικεντρώνονται στην εκτίμηση της τρωτότητας των κτιρίων λόγω άλλων φυσικών κινδύνων που προκαλούνται από σειμούς (όπως τσουνάμι και ρευστοποίηση). Στο πλαίσιο αυτό, το βασικότερο επίτευγμα της συγκεκριμένης διδακτορικής διατριβής αποτελεί η πρόταση και ποσοτικοποίηση αναλυτικών μεθοδολογιών για την αποτίμηση της τρωτότητας και διακινδύνευσης κτιρίων

που υπόκειται είτε σε τσουνάμι, είτε σε διαφορικές μόνιμες μετακινήσεις που προκαλούνται από ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους, ή σε συνδυασμένη σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση του εδάφους λαμβάνοντας υπόψη την δυναμική αλληλεπίδραση εδάφους-κατασκευής (ΔΑΕΚ). Στο πλαίσιο της διατριβής προτείνονται καμπύλες ή επιφάνειες (όπου κρίνεται σκόπιμο) τρωτότητας για συγκεκριμένες τυπολογίες κτιρίων, οι οποίες μπορούν να χρησιμοποιηθούν σε ένα πιθανοτικό πλαίσιο εκτίμησης της διακινδύνευσης λόγω των παραπάνω φυσικών κινδύνων που προκαλούνται από σεισμό. Η αξιοπιστία των προτεινόμενων μεθοδολογιών επαληθεύτηκε μέσω της σύγκρισης αντιπροσωπευτικών αναπτυσσόμενων καμπυλών με σχετικές καμπύλες της βιβλιογραφίας και δεδομένα από βλάβες σε κτίρια λόγω αυτών των φυσικών κινδύνων.

Συνοψίζοντας γενικά παρατηρείται ότι όταν τα κτίρια υπόκεινται σε τσουνάμι, τα ψηλά κτίρια Ο/Σ παρουσιάζουν μικρότερη τρωτότητα συγκριτικά με τα χαμηλά. Επιπλέον, τα χαμηλά τοιχωματικά κτίρια είναι πιο τρωτά συγκριτικά με τα πλαίσιακά, γεγονός που σχετίζεται με τη συγκέντρωση μεγάλων δυνάμεων τσουνάμι στα τοιχώματα. Έχει επίσης αποδειχθεί ότι η διατμητική αστοχία αποτελεί τον κύριο μηχανισμό αστοχίας για τα πλαίσιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ χωρίς τοιχοπληρώσεις ανεξάρτητα από το ύψος τους. Ακόμη, η θεώρηση των τοιχοπληρώσεων φαίνεται ότι έχει σημαντική επιρροή στην απόκριση και τον μηχανισμό αστοχίας (καμπτικός ή διατμητικός) των κτιρίων. Όσον αφορά την τρωτότητα λόγω τσουνάμι των μεταλλικών αποθηκών είναι γενικά παρόμοια με την τρωτότητα των χαμηλών και μέσου ύψους πλαίσιακών κτιρίων Ο/Σ. Όταν τα κτίρια υπόκεινται σε διαφορικές μετακινήσεις λόγω ρευστοποίησης παρατηρείται ότι τα ψηλά πλαίσιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ είναι πιο τρωτά συγκριτικά με τα χαμηλά και μέσου ύψους. Επίσης, τα πλαίσιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ με μεμονωμένα πέδιλα που υπόκεινται μόνο σε διαφορικές καθιζήσεις αναμένεται να υποστούν μεγαλύτερες βλάβες σε σύγκριση με το αν υπόκειται σε διαφορικές μετακινήσεις (όπου περιλαμβάνεται οριζόντια και κατακόρυφη συνιστώσα διαφορικής μετατόπισης). Επιπλέον, η διατμητική αστοχία αποτελεί τον κύριο μηχανισμό αστοχίας μόνο για την περίπτωση του ψηλού πλαίσιακού κτιρίου Ο/Σ που υπόκειται σε διαφορικές μετακινήσεις. Παρατηρείται ακόμη ότι η μεταλλική αποθήκη είναι πολύ λιγότερο τρωτή από τα πλαίσιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ. Όταν τα κτίρια υπόκεινται σε σεισμική εδαφική ταλάντωση και ρευστοποίηση, παρατηρείται ομοίως ότι το ύψος του κτιρίου αποτελεί μια σημαντική παράμετρο που μπορεί να επηρεάσει σημαντικά την τρωτότητα του, με τα χαμηλά πλαίσιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ πιο τρωτά συγκριτικά με τα μέσου ύψους και ψηλά. Επιπλέον, παρατηρείται ότι τα πλαίσιακά κτίρια Ο/Σ σε έδαφος επίπεδο αναμένεται να υποστούν λιγότερες βλάβες λόγω σεισμικής εδαφικής ταλάντωσης και ρευστοποίησης συγκριτικά με αυτά σε έδαφος με κλίση λόγω της πλευρικής εξάπλωσης, η οποία συνεπάγεται μεγάλες πλευρικές εδαφικές μετακινήσεις και σημαντικές διαφορικές

μετακινήσεις με αποτέλεσμα εκτεταμένες παραμορφώσεις των κτιρίων και συνεπώς περισσότερες βλάβες.

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